

D4.1. Landscape report on Open Access Diamond publishing in Africa, Europe and Latin America

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AI Usage Disclosure: This document was created with assistance from Artificial Intelligence tools for the following purposes: English writing improvement; translations; and images creation including word clouds. The content has been reviewed and edited by humans.

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Document overview

Project Acronym	ALMASI
Project Name	<u>A</u> ligning and <u>M</u> utualizing Nonprofit <u>O</u> A Publishing <u>S</u> ervices <u>I</u> nternationally
Project No.	101188192
Start Date	01/01/2025
End Date	31/12/2027
Contributing WP	WP4 Exploring and Supporting Sustainability through Policy and Funding
WP Leader	EIFL and SPARC Europe
Deliverable identifier	D4.1
Due Date	31/12/2025
Actual Delivery Date	22/12/2025
Nature	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Status	Under EC review

Version History

Version	Created/Modified	Comments
1	22/12/2025	none
2	26/01/2026	Corrections in authorship

Disclaimer

The project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON-WIDERA 2024-ERA-01

Disclaimer- ALMASI is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101188192.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission.

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ACRONYM GLOSSARY

ACRONYM	FULL FORM	COUNTRY (IF APPLIES)
AEUP	Association of European University Presses	
AGEN	Affirmative action on Gender Equality Network	Tanzania
AI	Artificial Intelligence	
AISA	Italian Association for the Advancement of Open Science	Italy
AJASSS	African Journal of Accounting and Social Sciences Studies	Tanzania
AJOL	African Journals Online	South Africa
ALMASI	Aligning and Mutualizing Nonprofit Open Access Publishing Services Internationally	
AMU	Adam Mickiewicz University	Poland
ANAQ-Sup	L'Autorité nationale d'Assurance Qualité de l'Enseignement supérieur, de la Recherche et de l'Innovation	Senegal
ANECA	Agencia Nacional de Evaluación de la Calidad y Acreditación	Spain
ANESRI	National Agenda for the Transformation of Higher Education, Research, and Innovation in Senegal	Senegal
ANID	Agencia Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo	Chile
ANII	Agencia Nacional de Investigación e Innovación de Uruguay	Uruguay
ANR	Agence Nationale de la Recherche	France
ANVUR	Agenzia Nazionale Di Valutazione Del Sistema Universitario E Della Ricerca	Italy
APC	Article Processing Charges	
APN-MCT	Administración Pública Nacional - Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación	Argentina
ARCIV	Doctoral School of Arts, Cultures and Civilizations, Université Cheikh Anta Diop de Dakar	Senegal
ASAA	African Studies Association for Africa	Ghana
ASJP	Algerian Scientific Journals Platform	Algeria
ASN	National Scientific Qualification	Italy
ASREN	Arab States Research and Education Network	Jordan
AURA	Asociación Uruguaya de Revistas Académicas	Uruguay
BMBF	Bundesministerium für Bildung und	Germany

	Forschung	
BMFTR	Bundesministerium für Forschung, Technologie und Raumfahrt	Germany
BOE	Boletín Oficial del Estado	Spain
BPC	Book Processing Charges	
BSO	Broad System of Ordering	
CAICYT	Centro Argentino de Información Científica y Tecnológica	Argentina
CAMES	African and Malagasy Council for Higher Education	Burkina Faso
CAMJOL	Central American Journals Online	
CAPEP	Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel	Brazil
CARLIGH	Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries	Ghana
CBUES	Consortio de Bibliotecas Universitarias de El Salvador	El Salvador
CC	Creative Commons Licence	
CC0	Creative Commons Zero (Public Domain Dedication)	
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution	
CC BY-SA	Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike	
CC BY-ND	Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivatives	
CC BY-NC	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial	
CC BY-NC-SA	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike	
CC BY-NC-ND	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives	
CC AA	Comunidades Autónomas	Spain
CCSD	Centre for Direct Scientific Communication	France
CDNU	University Digital Development Centres	
CEARL	Consortium of Ethiopian Academic and Research Libraries	Ethiopia
CERIST	Information Scientifique et Technique	Algeria
CITMA	Ministry of Science, Technology, and Environment	Cuba
CLACSO	Latin American Council of Social Sciences	
CLOCKSS	Controlled Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe	
CNDST-MESRI	National Centre for Scientific and Technical Documentation - Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research	Senegal
CNRS	National Center for Scientific Research	France

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CNRST	Centre National pour la Recherche Scientifique et Technique	Morocco
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment	
CODEPATA	Community Development Professional Association of Tanzania	Tanzania
CODESRIA	Council for the Development of Social Science Research in Africa	Senegal
CONACYT	Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología	Paraguay
CONAHCYT	Consejo Nacional de Humanidades, Ciencias y Tecnologías	Mexico
CONARE	Consejo Nacional de Rectores de Costa Rica	Costa Rica
CONCYTEC	National Council for Science, Technology, and Innovation, Peru	Peru
CONEAU	National Commission for University Evaluation and Accreditation, Argentina	Argentina
CONFOA	Lusophone Conference on Open Science	
CONICET	Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas	Argentina
CONICYT	Comisión Nacional de Investigación Científica y Tecnológica	Chile
COPIIM	Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs Project	(The) United Kingdom
COS	Chiefs of Open Science	
COSECSA	College of Surgeons of East, Central and Southern Africa	Tanzania
COSTECH	Tanzania Commission for Science and Technology	Tanzania
CRAFT-OA	Crafting the Future of Diamond Open Access	
CRAI	Centro de Recursos para el Aprendizaje y la Investigación	Spain
CRIS	Current Research Information System	
CROASC	Croatian Association for Scholarly Communication ZNAK	Croatia
CROSSDA	Croatian Social Science Data Archive	Croatia
CRUE	Conference of Rectors of Spanish Universities	Spain
CRUI	Conference of Italian University Rectors	Italy
CSIC	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
CSUC	Consortio de Universidades Catalanas	Spain
CSUCA	Consejo Superior Universitario Centroamericano	Central America and the Caribbean
CUECH	Consorcio Estatal de Universidades	Chile
CV	Curriculum Vitae	

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DABAR	Digitalni akademski arhivi i repozitoriji	Croatia
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub	
DFG	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft	Germany
DGRSDT	Direction Générale de la Recherche Scientifique et du Développement Technologique	Algeria
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication	
DOAB	Directory of Open Access Books	
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals	
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard	
DOI	Digital Object Identifier	
DORA	San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment	
DRP	Directorate of Research and Publications	
EAANS	East African Association of Neurological Surgeons	Kenya
EAJNS	East African Journal of Neurological Sciences	Kenya
EASTECO	East African Science & Technology Commission	Rwanda
EBAD-UCAD	Ecole de Bibliothécaires, Archivistes et Documentalistes de l'Université Cheikh Anta Diop	Senegal
ECAJS	East and Central African Journal of Surgery	Tanzania
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub	
EECTI	Estrategia Española de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación	Spain
EIFL	Electronic Information for Libraries	
EISMV	Ecole Inter-Etats des Sciences et Médecine Vétérinaires	Senegal
EJOL	Ethiopian Journals Online	Ethiopia
ENCA	Estrategia Nacional de Ciencia Abierta	Spain
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud	
EPFL	Swiss Federal Technology Institute of Lausanne	Switzerland
EPN	Escuela Politécnica Nacional	Ecuador
EPUB	Electronic Publication	
ERA	European Research Area	
EU	European Union	
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	
FCCN	Fundação para a Computação Científica	Portugal

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	Nacional	
FCT	Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia	Portugal
FECYT	Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología	Spain
FFOS	Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Osijek	Croatia
FLACSO	Facultad Latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales	
FNI	Fundo Nacional de Investigação	Mozambique
FNSO	Fonds National pour la Science Ouverte	France
FOLEC	Foro Latinoamericano sobre Evaluación Científica	
FRITT	Freedom to Research, Innovate, and Think	Norway
FUNDECIT	Foundation for Scientific and Technological Development	Angola
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation	
GIRCI	Groupe Interdisciplinaire de Recherche sur les Cultures et les Identités	Senegal
GLA	Ghana Library Association	Ghana
GLJ	Ghana Library Journal	Ghana
GTEC	Ghana Tertiary Education Commissions	Ghana
HAL	Hyper Articles en Ligne (open archive)	France
HCERES	Haut Conseil de l'évaluation de la Recherche et de l'enseignement Supérieur	France
HCTI	Humanidades, Ciencias, Tecnologías e Innovación	Mexico
HEET	Higher Education for Economic Transformation project	Tanzania
HORIZON-WIDERA	Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area (ERA)	
HRČAK	Central Portal That Brings Together Croatian Scientific And Professional Journals	Croatia
HSS	Humanities and Social Sciences	
HTML	HyperText Markup Language	
IAA	Institute of Accountancy Arusha	Tanzania
IFLA	International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions	
IMAF	Institute of African Worlds	France
IMIST	Information Scientifique et Technique	Morocco
INRAE	France's National Research Institute for Agriculture	France
INRIA	National Institute for Research in Digital Science and Technology	France
INSEE	National Institute of Statistics and	Senegal

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IPSP	Institutional Publishing Service Provider	
IRD	Institut de Recherche pour le Développement	France
ISCAT	Instituto Superior Politécnico da Catepa	Angola
ISPCAN	Instituto Superior Politécnico Dom Alexandre Cardeal do Nascimento	Angola
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number	
IUCEA	Inter-University Council of East Africa	Uganda
JATS	Journal Article Tag Suite	
JFINES	Journal of Food Innovation, Nutrition, and Environmental Sciences	Uganda
JGAT	The Journal of the Geographical Association of Tanzania	Tanzania
JIF	Journal Impact Factor	
JUST	Journal of Science and Technology	Ghana
KIU	Kampala International University	Uganda
KLISC	Kenya Library and Information Services Consortium	Kenya
KNUST	Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology	Ghana
LAI	Library Publishing Group of the Library Association of Ireland	Ireland
LARSIC	Laboratoire de Recherche en Sciences de l'Information et de la Communication	Senegal
LASDEL	Laboratoire d'Études et de Recherches sur les Dynamiques Sociales et le Développement Local	Niger
LASPAD	Laboratoire d'Analyse des Sociétés et Pouvoirs	Senegal
LATINDEX	Sistema Regional de Información en línea para Revistas Científicas en América Latina, el Caribe, España y Portugal	
LOSU	Ley Orgánica del Sistema Universitario	Spain
MESCyT	Ministerio de Educación Superior, Ciencia y Tecnología	Dominican Republic
MESCTI	Ministério do Ensino Superior, Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação de Angola	Angola
MESRI	Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur, de la Recherche et de l'Innovation	France, Senegal
MICITT	Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación, Tecnología y Telecomunicaciones	Costa Rica
MICIU	Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y	Spain

D4.1 Landscape Report on Open Access Diamond publishing in Africa, Europe and Latin America

	Universidades	
MINEDUCYT	Ministerio de Educación, Ciencia y Tecnología de El Salvador	El Salvador
MINESUP	Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur	Cameroon
MINRESI	Ministère de la Recherche Scientifique et de l'Innovation	Cameroon
MJTUM	Multidisciplinary Journal of Technical University of Mombasa	Kenya
MoRENNet	Mozambique Research and Education Network	Mozambique
MUR	Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca	Italy
MZOM	Ministarstvo Znanosti, Obrazovanja i Mladih	Croatia
NAWA	Narodowa Agencja Wymiany Akademickiej	Poland
NCBR	Narodowe Centrum Badań i Rozwoju	Poland
NCN	Narodowe Centrum Nauki	Poland
NOP-HS	Nordisk publiseringsnemnd for humanistiske og samfunnsvitenskapelige tidsskrifter	Norway
NORA	Norsk Åpent Forskningsarkiv	Norway
NORAD	The Norwegian Agency for Development Cooperation	Norway
NORF	National Open Research Forum	Ireland
NPOS	National Programme Open Science, The Netherlands	(The) Netherlands
NRP	Nationales Forschungsprogramm	Switzerland
NUPs	Netherlands University Presses	(The) Netherlands
NWO	Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek	(The) Netherlands
OA	Open Access	(The) United Kingdom
OACF	Open Access Community Framework (JISC)	(The) United Kingdom
OACIP	Open Access Community Investment Program (JISC)	(The) United Kingdom
OADJS	Open Access Diamond Journals Study	
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting	
OAPEN	Open Access Publishing in European Networks	(The) Netherlands
OASPA	Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association	
OBC	Open Book Collective	(The) United Kingdom
OIPA	Open Institutional Publishing Association	(The) United Kingdom

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OJC	Open Journals Collective	(The) United Kingdom
OJS	Open Journal Systems	Canada
OLH	Open Library of Humanities	(The) United Kingdom
OMP	Open Monograph Press	Canada
OPERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities	
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID	
ORE	Open Research Europe	
OS	Open Science	
OSNL	Open Science NL	(The) Netherlands
OUT	Open University of Tanzania	Tanzania
PAAA	Pan African Anthropological Association	
PALOMERA	Policy Alignment of Open access Monographs in the European Research Area	
PAN	Polish Academy of Sciences	Poland
PANINDEX	Indice de Revistas Científicas de Panamá (Panama Scientific Journals Index)	Panama
PDF	Portable Document Format	
PEI	Programa de Evaluación Institucional	Argentina
PEICTI	Plan Estatal de Investigación Científica y Técnica y de Innovación	Spain
PID	Persistent Identifier	
PIRESC	Confederación Universitaria Centroamericana	
PKP	Public Knowledge Project	Canada
PRSM	Portail des Revues Scientifiques Marocaines	Morocco
PUD	Presses Universitaires de Dakar	Senegal
RASPA	Revue Africaine de Santé et de Productions Animales	Senegal
RBGE	Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh	(The) United Kingdom
RCAAP	Repositórios Científicos de Acesso Aberto de Portugal	Portugal
RCN	Research Council of Norway	Norway
RECCA	Repositorio Concentrador de Ciencia Abierta	Mexico
RECERCAT	Dipòsit de la Recerca de Catalunya	Spain
RECOLECTA	Recolector de Ciencia Abierta	Spain
RECYT	Repositorio Español de Ciencia y Tecnología	Spain
REDICCES	Repositorio Digital de Ciencia y Cultura de El Salvador	El Salvador
REF	Research Excellence Framework	(The) United

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		Kingdom
REMERI	Red Mexicana de Repositorios Institucionales	Mexico
RENARE	Red Nacional de Repositorios Digitales de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación de Acceso Abierto	Peru
RENU	Research and Education Network for Uganda	Uganda
RERCIE	Red de Editores y Revistas Científicas Ecuatorianas	Ecuador
REUN	Red de Editoriales de Universidades Nacionales	Argentina
RFO	Research Funding Organisation	
RICE (D-RICE)	Directorate of Research, Innovation, Consultancy and Extension	
RJSAF	Réseau des Journalistes Scientifiques d'Afrique Francophone	Togo
ROR	Research Organization Registry	
RPO	Research Performing Organization	
RRS	Rights Retention Strategy	
SADC	Southern African Development Community	Botswana
SAGW	Swiss Academies for Humanities and Social Sciences	Switzerland
SciELO	Scientific Electronic Library Online	
SCOIR	Copyright and Related Rights (Research Outputs and Open Access) Bill 2024	
SCOSS	Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services	
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals	
SECIHTI	Secretaría de Ciencia, Humanidades, Tecnología e Innovación	Mexico
SECTI	Sistema Español de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación	Spain
SENACYT	Secretaría Nacional de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación	Panama
SENESCYT	Secretaría de Educación Superior, Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación	Ecuador
SEP	Strategy Evaluation Protocol	
SIBIUP	Sistema de Bibliotecas de la Universidad de Panamá	Panama
SIDIUN	Sistema Nacional de Docentes Investigadores Universitarios	Argentina
SIIDCA-CSUCA	Sistema Integrado de Información Documental Centroamericano	

D4.1 Landscape Report on Open Access Diamond publishing in Africa, Europe and Latin America

SINACTI	Sistema Nacional de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación	Peru
SMANLF	Société Médicale d'Afrique Noire de Langue Française	France
SNII	Sistema Nacional de Investigadores	Mexico
SNSF	Swiss National Science Foundation	Switzerland
SRANF	Société de Radiologie d'Afrique Noire Francophone	12 French-speaking countries in Sub-Saharan Africa
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities	
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics	
STI	Science, Technology and Innovation	
TCD	Trinity College Dublin	Ireland
TSV	Federation of Finnish Learned Societies	Finland
TUM	Technical University of Mombasa	Kenya
UAM	Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	Spain
UB	Universidad de Barcelona	Spain
UBA	Universidad de Buenos Aires	Argentina
UCAD	Cheikh Anta Diop University in Dakar	Senegal
UCE	Universidad Central del Ecuador	Ecuador
UCR	Universidad de Costa Rica	Costa Rica
UDFJC	Universidad Distrital Francisco José de Caldas	Colombia
UDG	University of Guadalajara	Mexico
UDSM	University of Dar es Salaam	Tanzania
UES	Universidad de El Salvador	El Salvador
UGB	Université Gaston Berger de Saint-Louis	Senegal
UGOE	University of Gottingen	Germany
UHR	Norwegian Rectors Conference, Universities Norway	Norway
UIR	International University of Rabat	Morocco
UKB	Dutch University Libraries and National Library consortium	(The) Netherlands
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation	(The) United Kingdom
ULM	University of Manouba	Tunisia
UNA	Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica	Costa Rica
UNAL	National University of Colombia	Colombia
UNAM	National Autonomous University of Mexico	Mexico
UNCHK	Cheikh Hamidou Kane Digital University	Senegal
UNCST	Uganda National Council for Science and Technology	Uganda
UNE	Union of Spanish University Publishers	Spain

D4.1 Landscape Report on Open Access Diamond publishing in Africa, Europe and Latin America

UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation	Costa Rica
UNL	Universities of the Netherlands	(The) Netherlands
UNLP	Universidad Nacional de La Plata	Argentina
UNMSM	Universidad Nacional Mayor de San Marcos	Peru
UÓR	Universidade Óscar Ribas	Angola
UPM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Spain
UPR	Universidad de Puerto Rico	Puerto Rico
UPU	Uganda Pentecostal University	Uganda
UPV	Universidad Politécnica de Valencia	Spain
URNM	Universidade Rainha Njinga a Mbande	Angola
USAC	Universidad de San Carlos de Guatemala	Guatemala
USAL	Universidad de Salamanca	Spain
UT	University of Tartu	Estonia
UTEC	Universidad Tecnológica de El Salvador	El Salvador
UTP	Universidad Tecnológica del Perú	Peru
UTPL	Universidad Politécnica Particular de Loja	Ecuador
UWP	University of Westminster Press	(The) United Kingdom
XML	Extensible Markup Language	
ZonMW	ZorgOnderzoek Nederland (ZON) + Medical Sciences (MW)	Netherlands

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The *Landscape Report on Diamond Open Access Publishing in Africa, Europe and Latin America* provides a comprehensive overview of the Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing ecosystem across 45 countries in Africa, Europe, and Latin America. This community-owned publishing model, characterised by the absence of publication fees for both authors and readers, represents one of the fundamental pillars for building an equitable, inclusive, and sustainable system for communicating research results.

The main objective of the report is to describe the systemic conditions and public policies that surround the development of the Diamond OA scholarly publishing model in each country, followed by an analysis of each of the three world regions. The country-level analysis includes a review of legal frameworks, specific policies, funding mechanisms, incentives and recognition systems, digital infrastructures and platforms, institutional support, human resources, the collaboration mechanisms between publishing services and editorial service providers, and editorial quality certification mechanisms. In addition, it includes a set of actions required to develop and strengthen national Diamond OA scholarly publishing systems.

The report highlights both the unique characteristics of each country and the diversity across regions, while also identifying shared patterns. First, it reveals significant variation in the existence, maturity, and scope of policies supporting Diamond OA publishing, alongside a general absence of structural funding. Second, it underscores the critical role of platforms, regional portals, and supporting digital infrastructures which, despite differing levels of maturity and robustness, function as key infrastructures for improving the quality and visibility of the Diamond OA model. Finally, the report shows that Diamond OA scholarly publishing suffers from a strong dependence on volunteer labour that is often unrecognised and unrewarded. Combined with the absence of academic incentives for publishing in or managing Diamond OA journals, this situation creates weaknesses in the continuity, quality, and scalability of the model in most of the analysed ecosystems.

Comparing the regions makes it possible to identify key structural differences. Africa shows significant transformative potential, constrained by structural and capacity limitations; Europe benefits from strong political and technical support, yet still lacks stable implementation mechanisms; and Latin America relies on the model's historical and cultural legitimacy, but faces the threat of commercialization as well as funding and sustainability challenges.

The report provides a set of recommendations addressed to policymakers, institutions, research funding agencies, non-profit editorial teams, and libraries. The key recommendations include: (1) the development of national policies and explicit regulatory frameworks to support the Diamond OA publishing model; (2) the establishment of national or regional funding streams specifically aimed at sustaining Diamond OA infrastructures and editorial work; (3) the professionalisation of editorial teams; (4) the design and implementation of incentives and reward and recognition systems for editing and publishing in Diamond OA venues; (5) the strengthening of shared digital platforms and services to reduce costs and increase efficiency; (6) the promotion of international alliances to enhance interoperability, quality, and the overall robustness of the Diamond OA model.

This report concludes that the future of Diamond OA does not depend solely on publishing initiatives, but on high-level policy decisions that recognize scholarly publishing as a global public good. Although the three world regions face common challenges, the policy responses required are profoundly context-specific and must be tailored to distinct historical, institutional, and socio-economic conditions in each region.

INTRODUCTION

The *Landscape Report on Diamond Open Access Publishing in Africa, Europe and Latin America* is the deliverable D4.1 of the EU funded ALMASI⁴ project (Aligning and Mutualizing Nonprofit Open Access Publishing Services Internationally)⁵. ALMASI project aims to provide the research community with a globally aligned, nonprofit, high-quality, and sustainable scholarly communication ecosystem, capable of implementing nonprofit OA publishing as a standard quality publication practice.

Nonprofit Open Access (OA) refers to Publishing activities that make available original scholarly outputs whose quality, editorial procedures, and content are controlled by (members of) an Institution without the aim to generate a profit and without applying APCs⁶.

Diamond Open Access (OA) refers to a model of open access publishing that publishes research outputs without charging obligatory fees to readers and authors, and irrespective of authors' affiliation or funding⁷. “Diamond OA journals represent community-driven, academic-led and -owned publishing initiatives. Serving a fine-grained variety of generally small-scale, multilingual, and multicultural scholarly communities, these journals and platforms embody the concept of bibliodiversity. For all these reasons, Diamond OA journals and platforms are equitable by nature and design”⁸. Its typical funding sources are research performing organizations (universities or research centres), scholarly societies, governments, consortia or cooperative funding models. In practice,

⁴ ALMASI is the word for ‘diamond’ in Swahili, the most widely spoken African language in Sub-Saharan Africa. Swahili *almasi* is a loanword from Arabic الماس *almas* ‘diamond’.

⁵ Funded under the call HORIZON-WIDERA-2024-ERA-01-08 — Global cooperation in not-for-profit OA publishing.

⁶ The term ‘nonprofit’ is preferred to ‘not-for-profit’ because only nonprofit organisations are required to benefit the public good, an explicit goal of OA scholarly communication. As part of the ALMASI project, this term refers particularly to Diamond OA (OA) publishing solutions led by scholarly organisations, institutions or scholars: Nonprofit publishing = non-APC AND (non-profit publisher OR research performing organizations). This definition does not include the hosting of content in repositories, educational materials, and archiving.

⁷ There are various borderline cases where one could argue that although no processing charges are levied, these do not fully operate in the spirit of diamond OA: 1. new journals for which publishers waive the fees in the beginning of their existence; 2. publications that are restricted to authors/grantees of the publishing institution, like ORE or the book programmes of some university presses; 3. publications using the S2O funding model; 4. publications that levy publication fees other than processing charges, such as page, colour, submission or licence fees. The definition proposed here, restricting to ‘obligatory fees’, includes open access for which voluntary fees are asked and accepted.

⁸ Ancion, Z., Borrell-Damián, L., Mounier, P., Rooryck, J., & Saenen, B. (2022). Action Plan for Diamond Open Access. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6282403>

Diamond OA is overwhelmingly operated by nonprofit or academic entities who have ownership of the content-related elements of scholarly communication.⁹

Diamond OA publishing as an object of study has been addressed in previous works. The *Open Access Diamond Journals Study* (OADJS) (Bosman, J. et al., 2021)¹⁰ explored “collaborative non-commercial OA publishing models for OA (a.k.a. Diamond OA)” and provided an analysis of the global landscape of Diamond OA journals and platforms. The most important finding of the study was that non-commercial OA worldwide can be characterised as a largely fragmented archipelago of 17.000 to 29.000 journals. One of the recommendations of OADJS was to align, coordinate, and improve the sustainability of nonprofit Diamond OA.

In Europe, the *Action Plan for Diamond Open Access* (Ancion Z. et.al., 2022)¹¹ and the European Council Conclusions on *High-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing* (2023)¹² created a high-level narrative for fostering open and equitable research ecosystems based on Diamond OA. Following this strategic framework, the EU funded project DIAMAS¹³ (2022-2025) mapped the current landscape of Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) in the European Research Area (ERA), created the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS)¹⁴ for IPSPs, and formulated community-led, actionable recommendations and strategies for institutional leaders, funders/sponsors/donors, and policymakers¹⁵. In parallel, the EU funded project CRAFT-OA¹⁶ (2023-2025) strengthened Diamond OA publishing by improving the technological bases of its platforms, software and infrastructure, thus making Diamond published research outputs more discoverable and impactful. Finally, the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH)¹⁷ was created as a common output of these two initiatives, to maintain these services beyond the duration of the projects.

⁹ For a definition of ‘content-related elements’, see Principle 2 in Rooryck, J. (2023). Principles of Diamond Open Access Publishing: a draft proposal. <https://thd.hypotheses.org/35>

¹⁰ Bosman, Jeroen, Frantsvåg, Jan Erik, Kramer, Bianca, Langlais, Pierre-Carl, & Proudman, Vanessa. (2021). OA Diamond Journals Study. Part 1: Findings. <https://zenodo.org/record/4558704#.YPmY1S1w1MJ>

¹¹ Ancion, Z., Borrell-Damián, L., Mounier, P., Rooryck, J., & Saenen, B. (2022). Action Plan for Diamond Open Access. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6282403>

¹² <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9616-2023-INIT/en/pdf>

¹³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058007/es>

¹⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/15227981>

¹⁵ Arasteh-Roodsary, S. L., Gaillard, V., Garbuglia, F., Mounier, P., Pölönen, J., Proudman, V., Rooryck, J., Saenen, B., & Stone, G. (2025). *Diamond Open Access Recommendations and Guidelines for Institutions, Funders, Sponsors, Donors, and Policymakers*. (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15518745>

¹⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094397/es>

¹⁷ <https://diamas.org/services>

In Latin America, there is a long tradition of scholar-led nonprofit OA initiatives such as SciELO¹⁸, Redalyc¹⁹, and Latindex²⁰, most of them directly promoting and sustaining Diamond OA in the region. The Latin American Survey on OA publishing (2020)²¹ was a first step for mapping the regional landscape. The report *Open Access Policies in Latin America, the Caribbean and the European Union – Progress towards a political dialogue* (Rico-Castro, P. y Bonora, L. 2023)²² was funded by the European Commission (EC) to gain a better understanding of the OA policies that have been developed in Latin America and in the EU, to analyse the common challenges and convergence paths for both regions to establish a policy dialogue, and to put forward specific recommendations for joint policy actions. The report applied a systematic approach to describe OA policies in 11 Latin America countries and in the European Union and formulated four priority objectives broken down into seven actions and 19 concrete measures, including support for Diamond OA publishing and the promotion of multilingualism in scholarly communication. In October 2023, the First Global Summit on Diamond OA took place in Toluca, Mexico²³. This in-person meeting marked a worldwide milestone, bringing together Diamond OA publishers alongside key institutions, government representatives, research funding and performing organizations, stakeholders, and experts from all continents, and resulting in the *Conclusions and way forward*²⁴ and the *Manifesto on Science as a Global Public Good: Non-Commercial Open Access*²⁵.

In Africa, Electronic Information for Libraries (EIFL), African Journals Online (AJOL) and the West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN), with support from Wellcome, launched the *Collaboration for Sustainable OA publishing in Africa project*²⁶ in 2023. This three-year initiative aims at strengthening the quality and sustainability of Diamond OA across Africa by identifying key challenges, reinforcing national and regional collaboration, and securing sustainable funding commitments from African governments and institutions through the integration of Diamond OA support into open science policies. In addition, the Second Global

¹⁸ <https://www.scielo.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.redalyc.org/>

²⁰ <https://latindex.org/latindex/>

²¹ <https://ameica.org/index.php/en/2020/06/23/survey-on-infrastructure-to-support-open-access-for-scientific-journals-in-latin-america/>

²² <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/8a4852c6-bca3-11ed-8912-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

²³ <https://globaldiamotoa.org/>

²⁴ <https://globaldiamotoa.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/202310-Global-Summit-Conclusions-Way-Forward.pdf>

²⁵ <https://globaldiamotoa.org/manifiesto/#/>

²⁶ <https://www.eifl.net/eifl-in-action/collaboration-sustainable-open-access-publishing-africa>

Summit on Diamond Open Access²⁷, held in December 2024 in Cape Town, South Africa, ensured the continuation and expansion of the debate beyond the previous Summit and reinforced the African community's engagement in high level debates and in shaping the narrative for Diamond OA public policies design. The Toluca-Cape Town Declaration emphasized scholarly knowledge as a public good, accessible to all communities, including readers and authors, without barriers and paywalls, and Diamond OA as community-owned, community-led, equitable, inclusive, non-commercial with social justice at the core. The implementation of Diamond OA needs to be supported by research assessment systems.

Building on the current momentum, the concrete objectives of the ALMASI project are as follows:

- (1) To gain a deeper understanding of the different nonprofit OA publishing solutions in Africa, Latin America and Europe, while building on knowledge gained in the above-mentioned projects.
- (2) To co-design and implement in a coordinated and aligned way non-technological good practices of service provision around DOAS to be compared across nonprofit OA publishing solutions in Africa, Latin America, and Europe to globally strengthen high-quality and trusted publishing services and outlets.
- (3) To improve the technical and scientific quality of publishing solutions and outlets so that they are trusted by researchers across countries and disciplines.
- (4) To stimulate the development of institutional and national policies that support non-profit OA publishing with funding. This includes establishing a single, interregional nonprofit publishing and Diamond OA policy and funder forum for policymakers in Africa, Europe and Latin America to co-develop context-appropriate policy recommendations.

The *Landscape Report on Open Access Diamond Publishing in Africa, Europe, and Latin America* has been produced under specific objective (1), and as part of ALMASI Work Package (WP) 4 “Exploring and Supporting Sustainability through Policy and Funding”.

The objective of the *Landscape Report* is to develop a comprehensive understanding of the policies, funding, and systemic conditions that enable Diamond OA publishing at regional, national, and international levels in these three regions. The report seeks to provide robust evidence, insights, and guidance to

²⁷ <https://doasummit.uct.ac.za/>

inform decision-making and support the strengthening of a more equitable publishing ecosystem.

The *Landscape Report*'s specific objectives are:

- (1) Mapping and analysing the current Diamond OA policy landscape across Africa, Europe and Latin America, identifying world-region, national and local variations.
- (2) Examining existing funding mechanisms and practices and sustainability strategies, including both public and private funding and support on various levels.
- (3) Documenting good practices and effective policy instruments that have successfully promoted and fostered Diamond OA publishing.
- (4) Identifying gaps and challenges that hinder the development and sustainability of nonprofit scholarly publishing.
- (5) Developing evidence-based recommendations to strengthen policy and funding frameworks supporting Diamond OA.

This report serves Open Access policymakers first and foremost, whether they are international, national, regional, or institutional. Diamond OA publishers can also look for inspiration and practical insights into how other initiatives organise their work and utilise available resources that can be adapted to strengthen their publishing practices. Second, institutional decision-makers will be interested to learn how they can optimise their existing resources and develop or refine institutional policies that foster a supportive environment for Diamond OA publishing. Finally, national policymakers who are seeking evidence-based guidance on effective measures to strengthen the Diamond OA landscape can find examples of how different policies and resource strategies have been successfully deployed in various contexts.

Ultimately, this report aims to contribute to the global dialogue on equitable, community-led publishing by identifying opportunities for collaboration, sustainability, and innovation within the Diamond OA framework. It builds upon and complements previous initiatives in the three world regions that have been mentioned above.

The *Landscape Report* is structured around three main chapters, each dedicated to one of the regions under study. It is complemented by an executive summary, an introduction, a methodology section, a comparative analysis, recommendations and concluding remarks. Each regional chapter combines an aggregated regional-level analysis with country-level case studies. The national case studies provide a detailed overview of different national contexts for Diamond OA publishing, along with recommendations on how it could be strengthened through policy and funding

actions. A homogeneous, descriptive, resource-based approach is used to present a common description framework of the Diamond OA landscape within each country. Across all regions, key contextual features are presented and analysed to identify significant trends and patterns in Diamond OA publishing.

In total, the report examines 45 countries across the three regions. In Africa, it includes 12 national case studies: Algeria, Angola, Cameroon, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Morocco, Mozambique, Senegal, Tanzania, Togo, and Uganda. In Europe, 15 countries are analysed: Croatia, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Serbia, Spain, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. In Latin America, the report covers 18 national case studies: Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Ecuador, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Puerto Rico, Venezuela, and Uruguay.

By providing a comparative and evidence-based analysis across three world regions, this *Landscape Report* supports informed policymaking and contributes to the development of coherent, equitable, and sustainable frameworks for Diamond Open Access worldwide.

METHODOLOGY

The *Landscape Report* has been written using a qualitative methodology in which a combination of desk research, focus groups and interviews have been applied. National case studies have been collectively written by all members of ALMASI WP4, in co-creation with national experts in Open Science and scholarly publishing around the world. In total, there are 27 authors, 134 contributors and 4 reviewers. The theoretical framework adopted has been the Neo Institutional Approach²⁸ of public policies analysis.

Selection of country cases

The countries were selected to represent geographic, linguistic, institutional, and socioeconomic diversity within the regions studied. The selection was mainly based on the existence (or potential existence) of Diamond OA ecosystems, representativeness in terms of policies, infrastructure, and governance models, and ultimately on the availability of information and local contacts. WP4 members were sub-divided into three sub-groups, one per region, that identified the countries to be included in the report and lead the data collection process.

For the African chapter, country selection was carried out by African Journals Online (AJOL), Electronic Information for Libraries (EIFL) and The Research Institute for Développement (IRD). These institutions were able to gather information on 12 African countries out of the 54 official countries in the continent. These countries represent 22% of geographical coverage and 41% share of total Africa GDP in 2025²⁹. This can be considered a major achievement given the massive geographical area and the political instability of the region.

For the European chapter, selection was undertaken by SPARC Europe, the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT), the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), EIFL, the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV), and the University of Göttingen (UGOE). These institutions were able to gather reliable information on 15 European countries, out of the approximately 50 official countries in the geographical continent. That represents 30% of geographical coverage, and around 80% of Europe's GDP in 2025³⁰.

²⁸ March, J. G. & J. P. Olsen 1984: "The New Institutionalism: Organizational Factors in Political Life". *American Political Science Review*, vol. 78 no. 3: 734 – 749.

²⁹ Source: International Monetary Fund.

³⁰ Source: International Monetary Fund and Eurostat.

For the Latin American chapter, selection was conducted by Redalyc and the Public Knowledge Project (PKP). These institutions were able to gather reliable information on 18 Latin American countries, including the Caribbean, out of the approximately 33 official countries in the geographical region. This coverage represents 60% of geographical coverage and 80% of the Latin American and Caribbean GDP in 2025³¹. These data give a clear idea of the ALMASI consortium's capacity to mobilize the Diamond OA community worldwide.

Data collection

The case studies' content is firmly based on evidence from desk research, dedicated focus groups, and interviews with key stakeholders from each selected country.

In the initial phase, country case studies were selected, and potential authors were identified from the ALMASI WP4 members and close collaborators, based on their professional expertise and access to relevant information. Not all country case studies were written by ALMASI consortium members; authorship and contributorship are clearly indicated in each country study.

Next, the analytical framework was thoroughly discussed among ALMASI WP4 members, leading to the development of a common descriptive outline for all case studies. This approach ensured both systematic coverage and comparability across countries and regions.

Once the framework was agreed upon, the country case studies were drafted. To ensure the validity of the analysis, each national study was enriched through fieldwork. National experts were identified in each country, and focus groups were organized to review and validate the content of the case studies, as well as to gather specific recommendations for advancing Diamond OA publishing. In cases where organizing focus groups was impractical due to logistical constraints or a lack of sufficient experts, structured interviews were conducted instead.

In total, 20 focus groups and 20 interviews were held between June and October 2025 with key stakeholders, primarily editors and librarians, but also decision makers, funding agencies, and researchers. A total of 134 participants engaged in these structured dialogues, discussing the accuracy and completeness of the information gathered. These interactions helped to enrich the documentary research with insights not publicly available, as well as expert recommendations from each country. This collaborative structure ensured both representativeness

³¹ Source: International Monetary Fund.

and contextual relevance, integrating local knowledge alongside a comparative perspective.

The focus groups and interviews were structured around a set of guiding questions (see Annex 1) aimed at assessing the reliability of the desk research work, complementing the country case studies with relevant non-public information and providing a set of expert-based recommendations on how to strengthen the Diamond OA model in their respective national contexts. During the sessions, participants were first invited to reflect on the accuracy and completeness of the country case studies and to identify any missing elements or additional information needed for a fuller picture. The discussion then explored existing policies, funding mechanisms, and initiatives that already support or could contribute to the growth of Diamond OA at national or institutional levels. A central part of the conversation examined the main obstacles to adopting or sustaining the Diamond OA model, either structural, economic, cultural, or technical, and the types of resources or solutions that could address them. Questions also probed institutional practices, including the extent of institutional support for Diamond OA journals, the units involved in publishing activities, coordination mechanisms, and practical steps required to enhance sustainability, as well as the potential role of the academic community.

Participants were further asked to reflect on strategic, policy, and funding actions needed to strengthen the Diamond OA model, including whether any existing strategies include dedicated funding. Financial aspects were explored in more depth through questions about the feasibility of reallocating APC-related spending toward Diamond OA initiatives, possible alternative funding models, and the role of different stakeholders, including institutions, agencies, and libraries, in pooling resources nationally or internationally.

Finally, the guiding questions addressed opportunities for shared infrastructures to advance Diamond OA, along with potential incentives for publishers, researchers, and universities to increase the adoption of the model, and ways such incentives could be implemented at institutional or national level.

Content of the Country Case Studies

Each chapter represents a country case study that has been consistently structured addressing the same set of issues, to enable a comparative analysis. Country case studies are structured in the following sections:

1. Landscape of Diamond Open Access and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing. This introductory section presents a short overview of Diamond OA publishing in the country, outlining the enabling national research policy environment, major national initiatives, and grassroots efforts that shape and facilitate Diamond OA publishing.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers. This section examines the policy, institutional, and systemic conditions that facilitate Diamond OA publishing. It includes:

- ✓ Policies at the national, institutional, or other relevant levels that explicitly promote or regulate Diamond OA publishing, together with their associated legal frameworks.
- ✓ An overview of available funding streams and sustainability strategies that support Diamond OA publishing.
- ✓ An analysis of incentive and reward systems for institutions and individuals involved in Diamond OA publishing.
- ✓ The infrastructures and platforms that underpin Diamond OA, including journal management systems, national publishing platforms, and repositories.
- ✓ Institutional roles and support mechanisms, as well as the human resources required to sustain Diamond OA publishing, such as editorial teams, technical staff, and other contributors.
- ✓ Forms of collaboration between publishers and service providers.
- ✓ Quality assurance instruments and mechanisms, including formal evaluation systems, national journal databases, and adherence to international publishing standards.

Finally, it is important to acknowledge the existence of cross-border effects in Diamond OA supply and demand, as well as in regulatory frameworks and infrastructures. These dynamics place limits on the extent to which insights can be derived from individual case studies and on how far observed differences can be attributed solely to national circumstances. Recognizing these limitations is therefore essential for the interpretation of the findings.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing. This section focuses on decision-maker good practices, policy recommendations and forward-looking strategies that are not yet in place and would be beneficial in the future. It highlights concrete resources and strategic measures that can be used to strengthen and expand the Diamond OA publishing landscape and provides recommendations for policy and funding actions.

Despite the common structure and analytical approach applied across all chapters, the country case studies vary considerably in style, length, and in the aspects that receive more extensive or more limited attention. These variations reflect the differing levels of maturity, capacity, and policy support within national Diamond OA publishing ecosystems and their enabling contexts. They also reflect and acknowledge the diversity of perspectives, expertise, and institutional backgrounds of the contributing authors.

Theoretical framework

The Political Sciences Neo-Institutional Approach³² studies how institutions, formal and informal rules, norms and structures shape political practice and policy outcomes, explaining how and why policies emerge and change, and emphasizes legitimacy, context and actor agency within structural constraints. Institutions are analysed as powerful structures that generate incentives, impose constraints, and shape the identities of political actors, rather than a simple set of rules. Moreover, institutional arrangements influence political behaviour, while sustained practices and political contestation can, over time, transform those institutions. Under this perspective, it is crucial to understand the context in which institutions operate and evolve. Within this framework, public organizations often prioritize legitimacy and aligning with societal norms and expectations over pure efficiency, a preference that significantly influences policy choices and institutional outcomes.

This report employs a resource-based analytical framework, adapted from the model developed by Subirats, Knoepfel, Larrue, and Varone (2008), which considers the following types of resources as essential for understanding public action and public policies: political support, funding streams, legal frameworks, enforcement mechanisms, infrastructure, human resources, consensus, organisational capacity, and information resources (see Image 1).

³² March, J. G. & J. P. Olsen 1984: “The New Institutionalism: Organizational Factors in Political Life”. *American Political Science Review*, vol. 78 no. 3: 734 – 749.

Image 1: Resources for public policies. Source: adaptation from Subirats, Joan; Peter Knoepfel, Corinne Larrue and Frédéric Varone (2008). *Análisis y gestión de políticas públicas*, Barcelona: Ariel.

In our analysis of Diamond OA ecosystems that are the result of public action, particular attention is paid to the national research policy environment, major national initiatives that facilitate Diamond OA publishing in the country, and to the nature and the extent of collaboration between publishers and service providers, including shared infrastructures and editorial services.

AFRICA

Image 2: Word cloud based on African country case studies content. Source: Own creation.

There are two distinct yet interconnected regions in Africa: North Africa, a region that encompasses the northern portion of the African continent, and Sub-Saharan Africa, which is the area and regions that lie south of the Sahara. Sub-Saharan Africa includes four geographical subregions of the member states of the African Union: Central Africa, East Africa, Southern Africa and West Africa.

Algeria and Morocco country case studies have been selected for North Africa; Cameroon for Central Africa; Ghana, Senegal, and Togo for West Africa; and Ethiopia, Kenya and Uganda - for East Africa; and Angola, Tanzania and Mozambique - for Southern Africa country case studies.

Across the 12 African country case studies, a number of converging strengths and persistent challenges emerge that collectively define the current landscape of academic publishing and the prospects for advancing non-profit and Diamond Open Access models on the continent.

The analysis shows that the most substantial strengths are located at the institutional level, where policies and dedicated funding streams provide a more stable foundation for Diamond OA publication activities. Many institutions allocate their own dedicated staff and, in some cases, with specific editorial incentives that try to embed publishing within academic career frameworks. Complementing these institutional assets, there is a significant and frequent reference to Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)³³ as the key aspirational database for Diamond OA journals. OJS is widely used as publishing software, which indicates progressive formalisation of journal workflows and adherence to international visibility and quality standards. African Journals Online (AJOL) plays a leading role in sustaining discoverability and providing shared infrastructure for the continent. This is combined with the existence of national publishing platforms, like the ASJP in Algeria, EJOL in Ethiopia, CNRST in Morocco and Le Grenier des savoirs in francophone Africa.

At the same time, the country case studies reveal several critical weaknesses that threaten the long-term sustainability and scalability of the system. Diamond OA journals across the region remain heavily dependent on a voluntary workforce, with editors often working for free or recognised working time. This is exacerbated by a systematic lack of stable funding and structural skill gaps, particularly in limited training on publishing workflows, digital tools, and editorial management. These elements hinder professionalisation of key actors, which is complemented by a lack of incentives and rewards for authors to publish in Diamond OA venues. Although

³³ <https://doaj.org/>

digital infrastructures have expanded, the adoption of persistent identifiers (PIDs) still remains low, limiting global interoperability and thus visibility of African published academic outputs. Overall, the comparative evidence points to a landscape where institutional commitment and in some cases national and continental infrastructures constitute the stronger enabling conditions, but where human resources, financial sustainability, and technical integration present substantial challenges.

Addressing these challenges will require a targeted funding stream for Diamond OA journals, a more systematic investment in skills and in dedicated staff as well as efforts to expand the use of PIDs and other global metadata standards. The widespread reliance on shared platforms such as AJOL demonstrates both the potential and the necessity of collaborative approaches. Strengthening these collective assets will be essential for consolidating a more robust, community-led and sustainable scholarly publishing ecosystem across Africa.

ALGERIA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Government agencies, such as the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, the Centre de Recherche sur l'Information Scientifique et Technique (CERIST) and the Direction Générale de la Recherche Scientifique et du Développement Technologique (DGRSDT) support Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing in the country. Openness is also embedded in national strategic documents. For example, *Stratégie nationale de la recherche scientifique et du développement technologique (2014-2024)* encouraged open sharing of research results and stressed the importance of OA, and *Stratégie nationale de l'innovation: Algérie horizon 2027* calls for open innovation and sustained investment in digital infrastructure.

DGRSDT identified and validated 903 Diamond OA journals. They mostly publish research conducted at universities in Arabic, Tamazigh, English, French, German, Spanish and other languages, covering a wide range of disciplines in both fundamental and applied research, including sciences, social sciences and humanities.

In 2015, Algeria launched an [Algerian Scientific Journals Platform \(ASJP\)](#), which currently includes 903 Diamond OA journals and 273,402 articles. The platform is hosted by CERIST, fully supports editorial and publication workflows in Arabic, French, English and Kabyle languages and is free to use for Algerian OA journals.

Algeria's Diamond OA potential is significant, especially for democratizing access to knowledge, but requires systemic investment in infrastructure, policies, and academic incentives to overcome sustainability challenges. Success hinges on

³⁴ Some text comes from Kuchma, I., & Ševkušić, M. (2024). Landscape of no-fee Open Access publishing in Africa. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12792474>

aligning this model with national innovation priorities and global Diamond OA frameworks.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

The national innovation strategy Algeria's Horizon 2027 has catalysed actionable steps toward an innovation-driven economy, with open innovation acting as a bridge for technology transfer. It outlines that while progress in institutional frameworks and pilot projects is evident, scaling impact requires sustained investment in digital infrastructure.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Most Diamond OA journals in Algeria rely on institutional subsidies, grants, or government support. Various sustainability strategies include:

- ✓ Subsidies and institutional funding: Crucial support from research organisations, universities and governments.
- ✓ Organisation of conferences.
- ✓ Free and open-source software and tools to facilitate journal management, free publishing platforms, efficient and automated publication processes.
- ✓ Collaborative training for journal editorial teams and reviewers.
- ✓ Promotion, awareness building and advocacy on the importance of Diamond OA journals.

Free publishing platforms such as ASJP and institutional platforms contribute to sustainability efforts.

Sustainability of Diamond OA journals faces several interconnected challenges rooted in economic, infrastructural, and cultural factors. Algeria's R&D budget remains limited (0.7% of GDP in 2024), with priority given to applied tech/energy over scholarly publishing.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

There are no incentives and rewards for Diamond OA publishing in Algeria, and researchers prioritise publishing in international (often subscription/APC-based) journals for career advancement, overlooking local Diamond OA venues.

Journal editors in Algeria do not have any incentives or rewards from their institutions for managing their Diamond OA journals.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

ASJP is funded from the public budget, by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, with a contribution from DGRSDT. Funding covers the costs of installations, maintenance, premises, human resources management, general IT services (e-mail, hardware, internet, etc.), specific IT services such as anti-virus and plagiarism software, and the salaries of permanent staff. Funding is currently very stable and will remain sustainable if public funding is provided.

ASJP IT engineers, technicians and developers receive performance bonuses; however, staff retention is an issue for ASJP. IT staff often get more attractive job offers in Europe and leave ASJP. Increased funding will help solve staff retention issues.

Institutional Roles and Support Mechanisms

Most Algerian universities and research centres provide Diamond OA journals with premises, specific IT services such as free hosting and permanent staff to manage journal updates. For example, Diamond OA journals with their own publishing platforms based on Open Journal Systems (OJS) are often hosted free of charge on the servers of universities and research institutes. They are easy to manage, as maintenance is carried out by the technical staff assigned to these journals or by volunteers. Journals that use OJS face fewer obstacles and challenges than other journals.

Dependence on institutional subsidies can undermine the sustainability of Algerian Diamond OA journals.

Workforce and Capacity Development

The staff of Diamond OA journals consists of volunteers (academics and researchers) and part-time or full-time employees of the managing institution. The paid staff receive salaries from the institutions that recruit them: universities, faculties, research institutes, research centres, and government bodies. They work as lecturers/researchers and do the related journal work during their free time off working hours. All Editors-in-Chief of Algerian OA journals are volunteers. However, some universities have a department responsible for publishing and scientific coordination, which manages their own journals. Instability of the editorial teams and boards, declining motivation among journal staff due to the lack of rewards and incentives and work overload are among the challenges faced by Algerian Diamond OA journals.

Collaboration between Publishers and Service Providers

There is significant collaboration between Diamond OA journals and service providers in Algeria through collaborative platforms (e.g. ASJP). Editorial boards and journal editorial teams organise joint workshops and training courses on OA publishing in collaboration with CERIST and DGRSDT for researchers, students, librarians and all members of the scientific community involved in the management of Algerian OA journals. Partnerships with Diamond OA journals in the Middle East and North Africa, as well as the European Research Area, would also be beneficial for Algerian Diamond OA journals.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Most Algerian OA journals that publish articles in French or English cannot afford professional language editing services. This has an impact on the quality of the articles published and requires financial and human resources.

Not all journals hosted on ASJP have persistent identifiers. CERIST is currently negotiating with Crossref to assign DOIs to articles published by journals hosted on this platform. However, the platform does not have a specific budget in foreign currencies (e.g. Euros, dollars) to cover recurring costs abroad. This creates significant operational hurdles, particularly for journals aiming to meet international standards. A lack of DOIs reduces journals' global visibility, citations and trust.

Few journals are indexed in international databases, and as a result, these journals have limited quality submissions from Algeria and abroad. There are 31 Algerian journals on the African Journals Online (AJOL) platform, of which 23 are Diamond OA journals. The Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) indexes 35 Algerian journals, and 32 of them are Diamond OA journals. In many cases, journal indexing services reject journals due to incomplete information on journal pages, such as the lack of information about the copyright policy and licences (Creative Commons licences are still not common among Algerian journals), and a lack of information about the editorial board. Irregularity and delays in journal publication, sometimes because of lengthy peer review processes, are also among the reasons for journal rejections by indexing services. Capacity building could help to mitigate these challenges and overcome shortcomings.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

One of the National Diamond OA Strategy's goals for Algeria is to integrate Diamond Publishing into the Horizon 2027 innovation programme, with dedicated funding from the National Fund for Innovation and Startups.

Funds that are allocated to pay Article Processing Charges to hybrid journals could be better invested in shared infrastructure and platforms that support Diamond OA journals.

Setting up a national fund for Diamond OA publishing would streamline the developments.

Collaboration with international funding bodies would also be beneficial to develop support strategies for Diamond OA journals.

ANGOLA

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Inocêncio; Munanga, Bettencourt; Roldán, Reynaldo; Sousa, João Baptista Machado; Tonet, Nvunda; Veloso, Helena.

1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Public institutions (universities and scholarly societies/associations) own and publish Diamond Open Access (OA) journals. According to focus group participants in the “OA for Angola Collaborative Project”³⁵, these journals contribute to the research progress and benefit the country by allowing for publication and access without economic constraints.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

There are currently no national policies that facilitate Diamond OA publishing in Angola. A multistakeholder team has been working on a national OA policy.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Most Diamond OA journals receive intermittent or no funding. There are no dedicated budget lines in university budgets for Diamond OA journals and journals are often personal and not institutional projects.

Some notable exceptions are Universidade Óscar Ribas (UÓR), which supports its *SAPIENTIAE* journal adhering to its commitment to academic excellence. Similarly, Universidade Rainha Njinga a Mbande (URNM) funds *Revista Angolana de Ciências*.

³⁵ OA for Angola Collaborative Project: <https://www.goap.info/oa-for-angola>

The *Academicus* journal owned and published by Academia de Investigação Científica also accepts donations in addition to institutional funding. Journal editorial teams submit applications to national and international calls for proposals aimed at promoting science, digital inclusion and internationalisation in order to obtain complementary funding.

The Foundation for Scientific and Technological Development (FUNDECIT) - a state institution responsible for managing the financial resources of the General State Budget earmarked for scientific research and development has been funding research projects at various higher education institutions. FUNDECIT might also fund institutions and/or publishers of Diamond OA journals in the future.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Angolan journals are still undervalued by local academics, who often see international publications as more prestigious. Incentivising researchers to publish in local Diamond OA journals could increase the adoption of Diamond OA publishing in Angola.

Incentives for the journal staff could be introduced in the form of a national award for Diamond OA publishing, salary bonuses or scholarships, or bonuses during researchers' performance evaluation, reduced workload for non-journal-related work, and mobility programmes for journal staff exchanges.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

A national repository and a publishing platform are being developed, which will improve the availability of research outputs and efficiency of Diamond OA publishing. The repository will harvest the metadata and the full-text content of Diamond OA journals, ensuring it is available in case journal websites are not accessible.

Institutional Roles and Support Mechanisms

UÓR includes the *SAPIENTIAE* journal's running costs in an annual institutional budget, with a dedicated budget line for the maintenance and operation of the journal, covering basic editorial, publishing platform, proofreading, layout, and dissemination costs.

URNM has a Publishing and Scientific Dissemination Department. The university provides funding for journals on a continuous basis and covers expenses as needed throughout the year. In the past two years (2023/2024), recurring expenses included payment for the plagiarism detection, hosting and domain name, DOIs, and external editorial consultancy service. This shows institutional commitment to

enhance *Revista Angolana de Ciências*, facilitate the development of science on the African continent and in Angola, and to strengthen the Diamond OA publishing model to safeguard regional academic and scientific production in OA.

Workforce and Capacity Development

There is a shortage of professionals specialized in scholarly publishing: editors, indexation technicians, and peer reviewers. Capacity building, staff exchange, and collaboration programmes could address this issue.

Collaboration between Publishers and Service Providers

Revista Angolana de Ciências collaborates with *Revista San Gregório* and two private higher education institutions in Malanje, namely ISCAT and ISPCAN, on seminars for editors, reviewers, and authors on best editorial practices and research integrity, as well as on engagement with the academic community through collaborative forums held nationally and internationally.

SAPIENTIAE Journal collaborates with Redalyc on the production of XML formats.

African Journals Online (AJOL) indexes four Diamond OA journals from Angola. The Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) also indexes four Angolan journals, and all of them are Diamond OA journals.

In Angola, there are currently no networks of scholarly journal editors. Some editors participate in the international network of Ibero-American editors Weeditors where they learn good editorial practices and support one another.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

The institutional culture for journal evaluation and monitoring is still lacking.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

A National OA Policy is being designed that will require OA to publicly funded research. Other policy and funding actions that will mainstream Diamond OA publishing are the following:

- ✓ Include Diamond OA publishing in National Strategies and Science, Technology, and Innovation policies, with clear targets and indicators; alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially SDG 9 (innovation) and SDG 4 (quality education). Promote Angolan Diamond OA journals as publication venues.
- ✓ Create a National Platform for Angolan Scientific Journals, hosted by a public university or MESCTI (Ministério do Ensino Superior, Ciências, Tecnologias e

Inovação). Joint platform governance and management by universities, research centres, university libraries, and MESCTI is expected. This platform will reduce individual journal costs, standardize editorial processes, increase visibility, and integration with international platforms.

- ✓ Establish an Angolan Editors Association/Consortium to share best practices and provide mutual technical support for using OJS (installation, updates, security, metadata, DOIs); ensure ongoing training in scholarly journals editing, indexation, open science, and digital tools, networking, institutional advocacy, and adoption of standards.
- ✓ Set up a national Fund for Scholarly Publishing to cover essential publishing costs: DOI, layout, web design, hosting, indexing, digital preservation, etc. This fund could be linked to MESCTI or a national funding agency (e.g., National Institute for Scientific Research). Funding criteria will include journal's transparency, merit-based editorial evaluation, commitment to OA policies and scientific integrity.
- ✓ Include clauses supporting Diamond OA publishing in research and university extension calls. Similarly, include clauses in grants and funding projects that support Diamond OA journals. Reallocate part of subscription spending on commercial journals to strengthen national scientific output.
- ✓ Introduce a dedicated budget line for scientific publishing in university budgets and competitive funding for journals that meet quality criteria.
- ✓ Encourage publication in Angolan journals as an institutional evaluation criterion, e.g. bonuses for scientific productivity linked to publications in local Diamond OA journals.
- ✓ Ensure institutional recognition of journals and editorial roles and their integration into academic careers: editorial roles (editor-in-chief, reviewer, associate editor) should count toward academic promotion. Formal recognition could include certificates, bonuses, and inclusion in performance reports.
- ✓ Set up a quality seal for Angolan journals with criteria adapted to local circumstances: Publication frequency, quality of peer review, complete metadata, the use of OJS and encourage continuous improvement and facilitate inclusion in AJOL, the Directory of Open Access journals and Latindex.

ANGOLA

- ✓ Create networks with Portuguese-speaking African Countries and Southern African Development Community countries for experience sharing and capacity building; enable technical interoperability between Diamond OA journals platforms in those countries.
- ✓ Introduce national editorial excellence awards to recognize Diamond OA journals and editorial teams for good practices.

CAMEROON

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Cameroonian researchers publish in a variety of formats, including monographs, collective works, institutional journals (from faculties, departments, laboratories, or research groups), journals belonging to learned societies or supported by individual initiatives, and "foreign" journals. National journals are published in print format, although a few already have an online presence and circulate in WhatsApp discussion groups in PDF format. Some assign DOIs to articles and are indexed primarily in directories such as DOAJ, AJOL, and Copernicus. Due to the lack of a policy supporting digital scientific publishing, most Cameroonian online journals operate using Article Processing Charges (APCs) and therefore cannot be considered Diamond journals.

Nationally, the number of Open Access journals has increased slightly, from 2 journals in 2015 to 8 journals in 2019. They can now be estimated at around twenty if we compile data from AJOL (8 journals), DOAJ (4 journals) and journals not yet indexed in these directories, but which have opened all of their publications to free consultation and downloading.

In this category, Diamond OA scientific journals are insignificant. Currently, and according to a small survey conducted on digital social networks for the purposes of this report, only three Cameroonian journals hosted in *Le Grenier des savoirs* publish according to this model and two hosted in AJOL. Specifically, these are:

- ✓ Adilaaku. *Droit, politique et société en Afrique* rattachée au Département des études politiques et juridiques du Centre national d'éducation (MINRESI);
- ✓ Jeynitaare. *Revue panafricaine de linguistique pour le développement* rattachée au laboratoire Langues, dynamiques et usages (Ladyrus) de l'Université de Ngaoundéré;

- ✓ Ngaban-Dibolel. *Revue africaine de responsabilité sociale et de management durable* créée par une chercheuse du Centre national d'éducation;
- ✓ *African Anthropologist* published biannually by the Pan African Anthropological Association (PAAA).
- ✓ *Journal africain d'imagerie médicale*, official journal of the *Société de Radiologie d'Afrique Noire Francophone (SRANF)*.

It should be noted, however, that many journals compensate for the evaluation work (around 15 euros per reviewer), which they finance by charging publication fees to authors. These fees remain very modest (between 30 and 40 euros). Although these journals do not pursue a profit-making objective, the application of these fees does not allow them to be associated with the Diamond OA ecosystem in the strict sense.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

Cameroon recognizes in its National Development Strategy 2020-2030 (NDS30) that scientific research and innovation will play an important role in achieving its development goals, even though it does not devote any specific chapters to them. However, it assigns the Ministry of Higher Education (MINESUP) and the Ministry of Scientific Research and Innovation (MINRESI) the responsibility for implementing this vision. According to the NDS30, they are responsible, among other things, for:

- ✓ strengthening human resources and research systems with a view to transforming the economy and encouraging innovation.
- ✓ developing research infrastructure in laboratories and research centres.
- ✓ promoting research in agriculture, health, energy, and information technology.

MINESUP's digital strategy, for example, consisted of building Digital Development Centres (CDNU) in the 11 state universities to interconnect them. This policy focuses on digital education and does not include digital research infrastructures (journal platforms, journal sites, data repositories, etc.), much less digital scientific publishing. The fact is that there is currently no national research policy that would provide an official framework for the deployment and development of open science. The SND30 does not mention the latter, nor scientific publishing, much less Diamond OA.

However, there is a report on the project to develop a Research Master Plan at the Directorate of University Research and Cooperation of the Ministry of Higher

Education. According to information received from a senior official of this ministry, a research law will soon be promulgated, the draft of which is almost complete. The National Quality Assurance Commission will in the future be responsible for evaluating scientific journals and research centres. The creation of a national journal portal is planned.

Unfortunately, this brief information does not indicate whether open science (and more specifically Diamond OA), scientific publishing, and digital research infrastructures will be considered in the preparation of this new research strategy.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

At the level of ministries responsible for research and in academic institutions and research centres, there are small grants that can partially cover the costs of field research, publication, or the organization of small scientific events. While institutional journals may occasionally receive support, the same cannot be said for Diamond OA journals.

The three Diamond journals from *Le Grenier des savoirs* mentioned above do not receive any institutional support for Diamond publishing. *Le Grenier des savoirs* provides them with free website hosting, free editorial and language editing services, free DOIs for their articles, free PDF production and archiving, and a minimal free social media outreach campaign upon issue release. Despite this support, journals struggle to properly conduct their publishing activities in a difficult context marked by the absence of an Open Access policy.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

No information available.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Unlike other African countries like Algeria or Morocco, which have a legislative framework and technical and digital infrastructure such as the Algerian Scientific Journals Platform (ASJP), Cameroon is lagging far behind, as the legislative body is still in draft form. It lacks a national platform that lists or hosts scientific journals in general. In this environment, it doesn't even occur to anyone to consider the role of Diamond OA journals in the development of local science. However, a well-designed local infrastructure could already bring visibility to this research and facilitate its management and dissemination across the continent and internationally.

Institutional Roles and Support Mechanisms

No information available.

Workforce and Capacity Development

In Cameroon, scientific journals in general, including Diamond OA journals, are primarily run by professors and researchers who work on a voluntary basis. No official text provides for a policy of incentivizing or recognizing their work. Their membership on an editorial board is just another line on their CV, even if it can be considered a form of support for research development. The motivation and stability of editorial boards are impacted by these discouraging factors.

The most striking example is the journal *Ngaban-Dibolel*, which was gradually abandoned by editorial board members after two issues. Researchers ultimately prefer to focus on their own careers and writing their articles instead of devoting time to a Diamond OA journal that does not earn them any money but also has difficulty getting its texts reviewed because reviewers increasingly demand to be paid for this task.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Le Grenier des savoirs regularly offers its editorial boards of Diamond OA journals free training on Open Access, managing an Open Access journal, and editorial practices in general. However, this initiative is very isolated due to the context mentioned above and the fact that journal project leaders and publication directors do not believe in the viability of the Diamond model. To change this perception, massive investment in training would be required to deconstruct this representation. But this approach can only be effective if the political level is already committed to the philosophy of open science and Diamond OA publishing.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

The work of the National Quality Assurance Commission is not yet evident in the Cameroonian scientific publishing community. Monographs, collective works, and indexed or unindexed journals are all possible publication venues that allow researchers to upgrade their ranking. Most Cameroonian journals, for example, are not indexed in the DOAJ. Diamond OA journals are no exception.

The reasons are diverse and can range from a lack of financial resources for infrastructure maintenance, linguistic revision, the purchase of persistent identifiers, the payment of human resources, etc., to a lack of awareness of the importance of indexing. For example, there is no national ISSN centre in Cameroon.

In the specific case of the *Grenier des savoirs* Diamond OA journals, the main problem is the instability of editorial boards and their difficulty in ensuring the intellectual survival of their journals in a competitive environment hostile to young journals and Diamond OA.

A note published on August 7, 2024, by *CAMES* reignited the debate on journal indexing and resurfaced the opposition between national and international journals, without anyone being able to rigorously define the criteria for internationalization. But most voices leaned toward the idea that these are journals indexed in major databases such as Scopus or Web of Science. This was nothing more or less than a call for scientific extroversion that will continue to weaken the local scientific publishing ecosystem if politicians and institutions do not address the issue. The debate on indexing ultimately revealed the enormous delay in humanities and social sciences journals, but above all a great lack of awareness among researchers and editorial boards of the issues surrounding open science and Diamond OA publishing.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Considering the above, the following recommendations can be made:

- ✓ The urgent development of a national research policy that includes open science as the main driver.
- ✓ The development of a national strategy to promote open science and the Diamond Model, specifying its funding method and the system for incentivizing and recognizing researchers' work.
- ✓ Mass awareness-raising among researchers and organizing training for universities, research centres and laboratories, and editorial teams on digital scientific publishing and responsible indexing that does not encourage extroversion.
- ✓ The creation of a technical office on open science, which will be equipped with the resources to conduct this awareness campaign and training, and to provide support to editorial boards.
- ✓ The creation of a national scientific journal portal to host and manage scientific journals in general and those that practice Diamond OA in particular.
- ✓ The establishment of partnerships with Cameroonian institutions and specialized organizations on issues related to open science and the visibility of science.

ETHIOPIA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

A national Open Access (OA) policy in Ethiopia requires OA to all publicly funded research outputs. Some institutions also introduced their OA and research data sharing policies.

Ethiopian Journals Online (EJOL)³⁷ is a national OA publishing portal built on OJS and managed by Addis Ababa University Libraries. It hosts over 20 Diamond OA journals.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

The Rights, Roles and Responsibilities section of the National OA Policy of Ethiopia for Higher Education, adopted by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education in 2019, requires that publicly funded research be published OA and includes a clause that Universities will implement and support OA publication platforms for online journals, which are created and managed by University departments or research centres.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Some Diamond OA journals receive recurrent funding from their institutions and associations and project funding from development funders (e.g. from NORAD in the framework of Institutional Collaboration Program between Mekelle and Hawassa Universities, Ethiopia and the Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Norway).

³⁶ Some text comes from Kuchma, I., & Ševkušić, M. (2024). Landscape of no-fee Open Access publishing in Africa. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12792474>

³⁷ Ethiopian Journals Online (EJOL): <https://ejol.aau.edu.et/>

Except for the salaries and incentives, no permanent or temporary funding is allocated for journals, which is a major challenge that affects the quality and publication frequency of journals.

Journals usually request a budget from their institutions on a case-by-case basis. Institutions previously provided some funding for printing, but due to inflation this is not always the case. Selling print versions and special issues are an alternative source of income for some journals.

Most institutions also provide infrastructure support such as hosting servers and dedicated office space for their Diamond OA journals.

Libraries usually provide professional support, managing OJS and facilitating capacity building training through a dedicated staff assignment.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Institutions usually provide some incentives for the journal staff. The editor-in-chief and associate editors receive small monthly payments, and the workload of the editor-in-chief is usually reduced (e.g. less teaching duties).

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

EJOL provides free hosting, help in setting up a journal online, training for editorial staff, backup, free Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), technical support and support on OA, copyright, digitisation, visibility and other related topics, and networking opportunities.

In addition to the national portal EJOL, there are also institutional OA journal portals at Diredawa University - Harla Journals hosting six journals, Jimma university portal with eight journals³⁸, Haramaya University with six journals³⁹, Hawassa University with ten journals⁴⁰, Mekelle University with 15 journals⁴¹, University of Gondar with six journals and Wollo university with five journals⁴².

Most platforms assign unique persistent identifiers in the form of DOI from DataCite and Crossref (sometimes via the African Journals Online (AJOL)).

AJOL indexes 46 Diamond OA journals from Ethiopia and the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) - 15 Diamond OA journals.

³⁸ Jimma university portal with eight journals: <https://journals.ju.edu.et>

³⁹ Haramaya University with six journals: <https://www.haramyajournals.org/>

⁴⁰ Hawassa University with ten journals: <https://journals.hu.edu.et/hu-journals/>

⁴¹ Mekelle University with 15 journals: <https://journal.mu.edu.et/>

⁴² Wollo university with five journals: <https://abjol.org.et/>

Institutional Roles and Support Mechanisms

Diamond OA journals host organizations provide facilities and premises, salaries of the staff, general IT services and publishing platforms/websites.

The technical infrastructure for journals is maintained and updated in-house by IT departments or institutional publishing departments, usually the library. Research offices are sometimes engaged as well. There is no dedicated unit to run OJS portals, but the staff employed by the institution share their time between the portal and other tasks. The portals do not have any allocated funding and therefore do not have dedicated staff. There are no incentives for working on the portals and this affects their quality and sustainability of the portals. Four institutional examples are described below.

Addis Ababa University provides a fixed annual budget for its journals that covers essential resources such as office facilities, internet access, and monthly salaries for some journal editors. Other editors, editorial board members, and peer reviewers are all affiliated researchers who contribute their expertise voluntarily, without financial compensation, as part of their professional engagement.

Jimma University covers the print cost and minor incentives for the editor-in-chief and managing editor. The sustainability of the Jimma University's Diamond OA journals is ensured through capacity-building, digital enhancement, and fostering a diverse and inclusive editorial environment. The elements of the sustainability plan include:

- ✓ Capacity-building and professional development: Continuous and need specific training for journal board members, editors, assistant editors, reviewers, and emerging female reviewers is crucial. These initiatives are integrated into the journals' ongoing operations, ensuring that new generations of professionals can uphold international academic publishing standards.
- ✓ Upgraded ICT technical service: A strong digital service is essential for the long-term sustainability of academic journals. Upgraded journals' websites and OJS efficiency streamline processes, reduce turnaround times, and make the submission, review, and reporting processes more user friendly.
- ✓ Gender inclusivity and early career researchers: Promoting gender inclusivity is a key aspect of ensuring the journals' sustainability. Targeted support for new female reviewers and editors helps diversify editorial boards and contribute to a more inclusive academic discourse. This is also addressed through including early career researchers. This inclusivity is institutionalized through mentorship

programs, ensuring diverse perspectives and enriching the content and scope of Diamond OA journals.

Mekelle University journal hosting platform is institutionally supported by the university's Library and Research Office, which have committed resources to technical maintenance, editorial support, and policy alignment.

University of Gondar provides the annual approved budget for its Diamond OA journals, which covers the monthly stipends of editors-in-chief and associate editors, technical infrastructure maintenance and web hosting, internet access and office facilities. The funds are intended to ensure the journals' operational sustainability, maintain editorial quality, and organize the peer review process throughout the year. In some cases, this funding is provided on an as-needed basis, drawn from the university's research and community service budget.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Almost all Diamond OA journals have a dedicated unit with staff employed to support publishing. They all have an editor-in-chief, a managing editor and associate editors. The editor-in-chief and associate editors are employed as faculty members and share their time between the institution and the journal. Managing editors, assistant editors, and secretaries, responsible for publishing operations, are recruited from the academic and administrative staff. Salaries for the staff working for the journal including the editor-in-chief, managing editor and associate editors, are covered by host institutions, but they are paid for their academic work and not for journal related work. Some institutions incentivize editors-in-chief and the managing editors, others - just provide small incentives to editors-in-chief and the associate editors. Assistant editors and secretaries mostly work without incentives except for a few journals. If Ethiopian journals could employ supporting staff the quality and rate of publishing would enhance.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Diamond OA journals have notable collaboration: they use shared hosting provided on the national level and within their institution. They also collaborate on capacity building workshops and other training events for editors, authors and reviewers.

Consortium of Ethiopian Academic and Research Libraries (CEARL) fosters collaborative efforts among Ethiopian academic and research libraries. Through CEARL, they exchange best practices, receive capacity building support, and align with national initiatives aimed at enhancing the management and sustainability of scholarly publishing and journal platforms in Ethiopia.

There are also collaborations among the journals, for example, *Ethiopian Medical Journal* owned and published by the Ethiopian Medical Association collaborates with the Centre for Innovative Drug Development and Therapeutic Trials for Africa, Armauer Hansen Research Institute and Ethiopian Public Health Institute.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

The Ministry of Education evaluates the quality of journals every three years and releases the lists of nationally accredited journals. Sometimes it also arranges generic training for journal editor-in-chiefs. In addition, some universities also have their own quality assurance strategy through their research office implementing criteria of evaluation and accrediting their institution journals, for example, Addis Ababa University.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Diamond OA journals in Ethiopia need funding and incentives to be able to have dedicated staff.

Journals can also be strengthened through capacity building on quality, including how to use the online publishing platforms.

The portals' funding needs are related to incentives for experts working on the portal: maintaining and updating the systems and experts to provide capacity building for editors, reviewers and authors.

Diamond OA journals in Ethiopia could be supported through funding, capacity building, and institutional departments support to strengthen their Diamond OA publishing and help sustain their journals. Libraries should also be strengthened in capacity to guide Diamond OA publishing. Support for the national platform EJOL and building the capacity of editors, reviewers and authors via training would also help. The above measures would help journals maintain quality and become sustainable. In addition, journals would greatly improve their response time and frequency of publication.

GHANA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Ghana has been making strides in Diamond OA publishing, and the Consortium of Academic and Research Libraries (CARLIGH) has been supporting Diamond OA publishing initiatives. All Diamond OA journals are owned and published by academic and research institutions.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

There are no National Policies and Legal Frameworks that facilitate Diamond OA publishing in Ghana.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Diamond OA journals are funded by their hosting institutions. Many Diamond OA journals are hosted by the university departments, which primarily provide funding Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

and staffing for journal-related work, with some consistent support from the primary institution.

Diamond OA journals face financial sustainability challenges and more reliable financial support from institutions is needed, enshrined in policy. Also, establishing partnerships with multiple organizations or entities willing to provide consistent financial backing will be helpful. Building and maintaining a supportive community around the journal is crucial for financial sustainability. Feedback and collaboration

⁴³ Some text is reused from Kuchma, I., & Ševkušić, M. (2024). Landscape of no-fee Open Access publishing in Africa. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12792474>

from the academic community, and their involvement in decision-making processes, would also help. Addressing these challenges requires a combination of financial planning, strategic partnerships, and community engagement.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

There are no formal incentives for journal staff. Some institutions take into consideration journal editing and publishing for evaluation and promotion, though it is not standardized or enshrined in policy. Promotion criteria don't foresee any additional points for the work done for journals.

Providing incentives for editorial team members, in the form of honoraria, professional development opportunities, or recognition, and by fostering a supportive and collaborative work environment would enhance team morale and retention.

High reviewer attrition rates are another challenge, and it is necessary to implement measures to recognize and reward reviewers for their contributions. Rewards and recognition could take the form of certificates, acknowledgments, or training opportunities and developing strategies to engage and retain reviewers, by providing clear guidelines, timely feedback, and opportunities for professional growth.

Currently, Ghanaian Universities, including the University of Ghana, have policies on promotion via metrics, which excludes publications in the local unindexed journals.^{44 45} As a result, Diamond OA journals struggle with visibility and attracting submissions, especially if researchers are unaware of their existence or they are not indexed in widely recognized databases.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Diamond OA journals collaborate with African Journals Online (AJOL) to achieve quality, visibility and sustainability. AJOL indexes 20 Diamond OA journals and Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) three Diamond OA journals from Ghana.

Some institutions face challenges in terms of technological infrastructure for hosting and maintaining online platforms for their Diamond OA journals. Two

⁴⁴ Guidelines for using the assessment by metrics options for promotion:

https://www.ug.edu.gh/hrodd/sites/hrodd/files/2024-06/GUIDELINES_FOR_USING_THE_ASSESSMENT_BY_METRICS_OPTION_FOR_PROMOTION-13-1-23_Final.pdf

⁴⁵ Oppong Bekoe, E., Kilbertson Zuttah, J., Mawuena A., A., Adjei- Mensah, T. D., & Mills, D. (2025). Challenges to Journal Editorial Work in West - Africa: Lessons from the University of Ghana. Ghana Library Journal, 30(1), 2-6. <https://doi.org/10.4314/glj.v30i1.2>

universities – University of Cape Coast⁴⁶ and University of Ghana⁴⁷ – maintain Open Journal System-based OA publishing platforms for their OA journals.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Two use cases below describe different types of institutional support from a university and professional non-profit organization.

The Journal of Science and Technology (JUST) receives institutional support from the Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST) to sustain its operations. The university provides dedicated office space, reliable IT infrastructure, and administrative staff, creating a stable work environment for the journal's editorial activities. Additionally, KNUST offers a consistent monthly financial contribution and allocates an annual budget to support the journal's activities. 2025 JUST budget lines include capital and operational expenditures, production costs and training costs. Senior academic staff from various faculties also serve as reviewers and editorial board members, enhancing the journal's credibility and peer review process. Overall, the institution's reputation and logistical backing are key pillars in JUST's sustainability strategy.

Similarly, Ghana Library Association (GLA) supports its *Ghana Library Journal (GLJ)* with an annual budget. The 2025 budget covers editorial management (Editor(s) honorarium or stipend, editorial assistant allowance and reviewer honoraria or tokens of appreciation), production costs (copyediting and proofreading, typesetting and formatting and graphic and image editing), technology and platform maintenance (journal website hosting and maintenance, content management system costs and DOI registration fees), marketing and promotion (journal branding and design, social media promotion, email campaigns and newsletters and advertisement placements), office supplies and software tools and some unforeseen operational costs as well. As a Diamond OA journal, GLJ relies on institutional support, volunteer contributions, and strategic partnerships to operate. By investing in strong governance, diversified resource mobilization, and continuous capacity development anchored by the GLA's support, GLJ is positioned to grow as a resilient, high-quality journal contributing to scholarly communication in Africa.

⁴⁶ University of Cape Coast: <https://journal.ucc.edu.gh/>

⁴⁷ University of Ghana: <https://journals.ug.edu.gh/>

Workforce and Capacity Development

Diamond OA journals are run by a lean staff, who are usually full-time staff at their universities, but often perform other functions there than journal management. Consequently, they offer their services to the journals on a voluntary basis and are not on any stipend or allowances.

Journal staff retention is another issue. For example, a significant majority of the University of Ghana editorial staff *“has fewer than five years of experience in working in the editorial role, which could be indicative of a high turnover rate of editorial staff”* and *“a considerable number of editorial staff were found to be non-permanent staff members.”*⁴⁸ Effective succession planning ensures continuity and sustainability of journal editing and publishing and the following measures could help achieve this: *“mentorship programs, structured integration of new editors, the need for documentation and knowledge transfer processes, and the establishment of succession planning committees.”*⁴⁹

There is a need for capacity building in terms of editorial skills, peer-review processes, and overall journal management to enhance the quality and professionalism of Diamond OA journals: *“Over 70% of the editorial staff reported they still manually processed their manuscripts. This highlights a considerable reliance on manual processes in the editorial management process suggesting potential areas for massive improvement, the need for editorial staff to adopt more advanced management tools and also increase proficiency in the use of the current online journal management system...The editorial staff bemoaned the lack of institutional support in terms of administration, financial, structural and editorial assistance. Key areas identified to help improve editorial work include the need for enhanced training in digital tools, manuscript editing, improved editorial management systems, and sustained professional development. Incentivizing journal editors and formalizing the engagement of editorial staff was also an issue.”*⁵⁰

⁴⁸ Oppong Bekoe, E., Kilbertson Zuttah, J., Mawuena A., A., Adjei- Mensah, T. D., & Mills, D. (2025). Challenges to Journal Editorial Work in West - Africa: Lessons from the University of Ghana. Ghana Library Journal, 30(1), 2-6. <https://doi.org/10.4314/glj.v30i1.2>

⁴⁹ Ibid

⁵⁰ Oppong Bekoe, E., Kilbertson Zuttah, J., Mawuena A., A., Adjei- Mensah, T. D., & Mills, D. (2025). Challenges to Journal Editorial Work in West - Africa: Lessons from the University of Ghana. Ghana Library Journal, 30(1), 2-6. <https://doi.org/10.4314/glj.v30i1.2>

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Collaboration with like-minded institutions and organizations can contribute significantly to the sustainability of Diamond OA journals.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

There are no Diamond OA journal specific quality assurance strategies in Ghana.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Improving the quality and sustainability of Diamond OA publishing in Ghana requires collaborative efforts at the journal, institutional, and national levels. National support and policies can create an environment conducive to high-quality Diamond OA publishing, while institutional and journal-level actions can contribute to the success of individual Diamond OA publishing initiatives.

Journal Level:

- ✓ Training for editors and reviewers should be provided to ensure consistency and quality and enhance the skills of editorial teams.
- ✓ Guidance and support for authors to build their confidence in Diamond OA journal publishing.
- ✓ Investing in robust and user-friendly online platforms for journal hosting and ensuring the security and sustainability of technical infrastructure.

Institutional Level:

- ✓ Fostering a culture of continuous learning in Diamond OA publishing: organizing workshops, webinars, and training sessions for researchers and journal editors.
- ✓ Allocating institutional funds to support Diamond OA publishing initiatives.
- ✓ Establishing grants or awards to encourage high-quality research and publications.
- ✓ Ensuring recognition and introducing incentives:
 - Acknowledging and rewarding quality publications through institutional awards or recognition.
 - Considering Diamond OA publishing in promotion and tenure criteria. Ghana Tertiary Education Commissions (GTEC) could enforce that in academic institutions.

- ✓ Providing infrastructure support: providing technical support for maintaining Diamond OA journal platforms and ensuring access to tools and software for editorial processes.

National Level:

GTEC could enforce the development and implementation of national policies that support Diamond OA publishing. Encourage institutions to adopt Diamond OA-friendly policies thereby introducing the following:

- ✓ Funding Initiatives:
 - Establishing national funding programmes to support Diamond OA journals.
 - Collaborating with international organizations to secure funding for local Diamond OA initiatives.
- ✓ Networking and Collaboration:
 - Facilitating collaboration between journals, institutions, and publishers.
 - Creation of a national network for sharing resources and best practices.
- ✓ Open Science Advocacy:
 - Promoting open science practices and advocating for the importance of Diamond OA publishing.
 - Engaging with policymakers (Ministry of Education, GTEC, Science and Technology Policy Research Institute – CSIR etc.) to incorporate Diamond OA publishing into research and education policies.
- ✓ Research Evaluation:
 - Encouraging the use of quality metrics and indicators that take into consideration the value of Diamond OA publications.
- ✓ Education and Awareness:
 - Conduct awareness campaigns to educate researchers, institutions, and policymakers about the benefits of Diamond OA publishing.
 - Provide resources on best practices in Diamond OA publishing.

KENYA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Various organizations in Kenya have developed and implemented institutional OA policies. These organizations own and publish OA journals and run repositories where research done by the members of the organizations, including students and faculty, is openly available. Through the Kenya Library and Information Services Consortium (KLISC) libraries are at the forefront of championing Diamond OA journal publishing and OA policies. Many universities have set up OJS-based portals for OA journal publishing. Decolonization of knowledge and creation of platforms for knowledge sharing are the main driving forces for institutional Diamond OA publishing.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

There are no National Policies and Legal Frameworks that facilitate Diamond OA publishing.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Diamond OA journals are mostly funded through periodically negotiated subsidies from the journals primary institution's base. These journals usually operate on a minimal budget. Some Diamond OA journals face a continuous decline in budgetary allocations, which affects their growth and development (for example, challenges with paying for platform hosting and domain name subscription fees after the host organizations withdrew their support).

⁵¹ Some text comes from Kuchma, I., & Ševkušić, M. (2024). Landscape of no-fee Open Access publishing in Africa. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12792474>

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Few organizations that own and publish Diamond OA journals provide incentives for the journal staff.

Current criteria for researchers' promotion include the number of publications and their strength, but don't provide any incentives for Diamond OA publishing.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

African Journals Online (AJOL) indexes 17 Kenyan Diamond OA journals and Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) 4.

Institutional Roles and Support Mechanisms

Many organizations provide in-kind support to their Diamond OA journals in addition to funding. All Diamond OA journals use their host organizations' facilities and premises, and most journals are supported with general IT services, including email, hardware, and the Internet. Some Diamond OA journals use service-specific IT services provided by their host organizations (e.g. OJS).

Three examples below describe how professional organizations and universities sustain their Diamond OA journals.

The East African Association of Neurological Surgeons (EAANS)

EAANS has an annual budget for its *East African Journal of Neurological Sciences* (EAJNS), which covers essential recurrent operating costs, including web hosting and domain renewal for the EAJNS online publishing platform, printing of hard copies of biannual journal issues, publication of the annual EAANS conference proceedings, basic administrative and logistical support, such as meeting coordination and minor communication costs.

EAANS also provides strategic direction, academic support, and access to a regional network of neurosurgeons and neuroscientists for EAJNS. EAANS promotes the journal during its annual conference and supports the peer-review process through its members.

Kenya Library and Information Services Consortium (KLISC)

KLISC provides a minimal budget allocation for its *Journal of Information Science & Knowledge Management*. The funding covers typesetting that involves formatting the text and graphics of the journal articles to ensure they meet publication standards (layout design, font selection, and ensuring visual consistency throughout the journal); editorial services (review and editing of submitted manuscripts including copy editing, proofreading, and sometimes substantive editing to ensure clarity, accuracy, and adherence to the journal's style guidelines); system maintenance, which includes maintaining the website, ensuring it is secure and accessible, and providing technical support for online submissions and access; marketing and promotion costs to increase its visibility and readership; and Crossref membership for the DOIs.

KLISC recognizes the importance of ensuring sustainable Diamond OA publishing in Kenya and encourages other journals to also embrace this model.

The Technical University of Mombasa (TUM)

TUM - a public university funded by the Kenyan government funds its *Multidisciplinary Journal of Technical University of Mombasa* (MJTUM) through an annual allocated budget to the Department of Partnership, Research and Innovation (PRI) and the University Library.

The library handles technical aspects of the journal publishing: installation and maintenance of the Journal Management System, ISSN registration and maintenance, DOI number subscription, metadata registration, copy editing, production, and publishing of the articles. The Chief Editor is responsible for the content of the journal, including managing peer review, and ensuring the quality of the articles published. The university is committed to sustaining MJTUM as its premier scholarly journal and maintaining its Diamond OA status, which is crucial for the dissemination of research output from Kenya and beyond.

Workforce and Capacity Development

In most Diamond OA journals the personnel work voluntarily, with no dedicated administrative or technical staff and these journals do not have a dedicated host department or unit within their parent organizations. In some cases, the institution employs the journal personnel, who share their time between journal publishing and their primary role at the parent organization. The absence of a permanent secretariat makes it difficult to manage the growing volume of submissions, maintain consistent communication with authors and reviewers, and ensure

editorial continuity. These limitations hinder Diamond OA journal's ability to scale operations or implement long-term quality assurance systems.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Diamond OA journals collaborate in many areas, including editorial services; training and support and/or advice on publishing policies and best practices; IT services (journal platforms, etc.); communication services (marketing/dissemination, social media, etc.); and production services (copy-editing, proofreading, typesetting, metadata, etc.).

For example, EAJNS actively collaborates with several organisations to support the quality and sustainability of their publishing operations. EAJNS is hosted on AJOL, which provides the journal with a stable digital publishing platform, visibility to a global readership, and technical support. AJOL's infrastructure enables EAJNS to maintain a professional online presence, index their content, and help adhere to international publishing standards. Many editorial board members and reviewers are affiliated with academic institutions (University of Nairobi, Moi University, Kenyatta University, Aga Khan University Hospital, among others) and their involvement ensures high-quality peer review, editorial integrity, and scholarly rigor. These institutions also promote the journal within their research and teaching communities. The University of Nairobi, through the Editor-in-Chief's faculty affiliation, also offers institutional backing.

KLISC collaborates with Strathmore University, which is hosting the journal platform temporarily. KLISC also supports OA journals with training on OJS and continues to be a valuable partner through benchmarking and knowledge exchange on international best practices in OA. Their leadership in promoting Diamond OA in Kenya inspired the journal's transition to a fee-free publishing model, and their support continues to enhance the journal's quality, visibility, and sustainability.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

There are no Diamond OA specific quality assurance strategies in Kenya.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

- ✓ Introduce a national OA policy and legal frameworks with Diamond OA publishing actions.
- ✓ Introduce sustainable funding mechanisms - national based grants through the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology to support Diamond OA publishing.

- ✓ Subsidize some costs for running Diamond OA journals - e.g. for office rental space, DOI costs.
- ✓ Provide support from professional bodies - scholarly societies within the region for Diamond OA journals.
- ✓ Strengthen institutional Diamond OA publishing policies.
- ✓ Incentivise journal editors and peer reviewers: consider journal editing and peer review activity as a way of building a scholarly profile and a community service; include editing and reviewing for local Diamond OA journals as additional criteria for assessment and promotion (with extra points); provide education and training to reviewers. Professional licensing bodies, e.g. the Medical Licensing Body, awarding Continuous Professional Development (CPD) points could also incentivise Diamond OA journal editors and reviewers. Consider issuing other types of certificates and recognition for editors and reviewers.
- ✓ Establish journal management offices/departments with funding towards supporting the basic costs of journals such as payments for editors, subscription for PIDs (e.g. Crossref or DataCite DOI), similarity checking tools (e.g. Ithenticate), annual server and web hosting costs and marketing.
- ✓ Set up shared OJS platforms and share expertise, e.g. in copyediting and publishing. Such a national infrastructure - e.g. through Kenyan libraries bodies, could help share costs for software, DOI registration, etc. Pool resources and partner in negotiating plagiarism detection software to achieve more affordable pricing.
- ✓ Ensure consistent and sustainable ways of capacity building, mentorship and training for editors and reviewers.
- ✓ Provide incentives to authors for publishing in Kenyan Diamond OA journals (e.g. extra points during promotion, researcher evaluation, etc.), etc. The Commission of University Education could introduce such a credit system. Similarly, Universities that publish Diamond OA journals could receive more funding/higher assessment scores.
- ✓ Set up public - private partnership where pharmaceutical companies and medical devices companies that have some R&D money in their budget allocate some portion of that money to support Diamond OA journals (instead of advertising arrangements that some medical journals have now).
- ✓ Involve philanthropies and NGOs into Diamond OA journals support.

MOROCCO

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Centre National pour la Recherche Scientifique et Technique (CNRST) through L'Institut Marocain de l'Information Scientifique et Technique (IMIST) maintains the Moroccan Scientific Journals Portal (PRSM)⁵³ with over 100 Diamond OA journals playing a key role in national research production. PRSM OA digital publishing platform could be used free of charge to manage the entire editorial process, including article submission, peer review, online publication and hosting or just for content indexing.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

There are no National Policies and Legal Frameworks that facilitate Diamond OA publishing in Morocco.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Diamond OA journals are funded from a variety of sources, including periodic institutional grants, time-limited external grants, donations and crowdfunding, partnerships and collaborations, and print sales. However, financial instability is common, and there is usually no approved annual budget for the journal. In addition, most Diamond OA journals do not have a sustainable development plan, which makes it difficult to guarantee long-term financial stability. Many journals find

⁵² Adapted from [Rachid Ayssi](#) and [Fadoua El Maguiri](#), Centre National pour la Recherche Scientifique et Technique (Morocco) in Kuchma, I., & Ševkušić, M. (2024). Landscape of no-fee Open Access publishing in Africa. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12792474>

⁵³ Moroccan Scientific Journals Portal (PRSM): <https://revues.imist.ma/>

it difficult to operate on a day-to-day basis, in particular to cover the costs of publishing and remunerating the staff involved.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Incentives for Diamond OA journal staff may vary, but generally speaking, academic recognition remains the main form of motivation.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

The majority of journals benefit from CNRST's PRSM, which offers technical support by providing a shared technical platform based on Open Journals System (OJS). The CNRST offers a range of services to journal publishers, including access to a common publication platform, anti-plagiarism software, implementation of DOIs, iThenticate, etc. and training sessions on various aspects of the editorial process and indexing. These training sessions offer publishers the opportunity to improve their skills and foster collaboration within the Moroccan scientific journal community.

While the submission and publication workflows are usually managed via the publishing platform, some journals still conduct peer review via email. The main reasons for this include:

- ✓ Resistance to change, where editorial teams prefer to maintain traditional methods rather than adopt new approaches.
- ✓ Insufficient human resources allocated for journal management, which often leads the publisher to take on several editorial roles.
- ✓ Lack of specialized training to use the journal management system effectively.
- ✓ Rotating editorial teams, requiring ongoing training to ensure effective journal management.
- ✓ Financial constraints, particularly regarding recruiting and maintaining the staff needed to manage the editorial process.

PRSN helps journals flip from print to Diamond OA and launch new Diamond OA journals. The shared service offering from PRSM enables a significant cost reduction for journals, while helping to ensure quality.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Diamond OA journals generally benefit from limited institutional support. Host institutions may provide in-kind support such as meeting facilities and basic IT services, but this largely depends on the resources available within each institution.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Most Diamond OA journals are run by individuals and operate without a dedicated publishing unit, using volunteer staff. For journals run by institutions, there is usually no dedicated unit either, but staff are employed by the institution and divide their time between publishing the journal and other tasks.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Collaborations between Diamond OA journals are very limited.

CNRST offers technical support, hosting, continuing education, and publishing services and tools.

Arab Research and Education Network (ASREN) ensures regional collaboration, visibility and interoperability.

Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) provides training and support in the professionalisation of Diamond OA journals and helps improve editorial services. 36 Diamond OA journals are indexed in DOAJ.

African Journals Online (AJOL) indexes two Moroccan Diamond OA journals.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

There are no quality assurance strategies specific to Diamond OA journals in Morocco.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

The main challenges to the financial sustainability of Moroccan journals include the lack of stable funding and dependence on short-term subsidies. Solutions could include diversifying funding sources, strengthen international collaborations and providing long-term funding and support to ensure financial stability.

Awareness-raising initiatives to promote the benefits of Diamond OA publishing would also contribute to the Moroccan Diamond OA journals sustainability.

In summary, to make Diamond OA journals more sustainable, it is essential to address both the financial and operational challenges they face. This requires the ongoing commitment of various stakeholders, including government institutions,

universities, research organizations and foundations, to support Diamond OA publishing initiatives and ensure their long-term viability in the Moroccan academic landscape and internationally.

Strengthening ministerial support by integrating the PRSM into national research priorities is also vital.

MOZAMBIQUE

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Diamond OA journals are owned and published by universities and research institutes such as Eduardo Mondlane University / Universidade Eduardo Mondlane, National Institute of Health / Instituto Nacional da Saúde, Catholic University of Mozambique / Universidade Católica de Moçambique, Higher Polytechnic Institute of Gaza / Instituto Superior Politécnico de Gaza, University of Lúrio / Universidade Lúrio, Pedagogical University of Maputo / Universidade Pedagógica de Maputo and University of Save / Universidade Save.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

There are no National Policies and Legal Frameworks that facilitate Diamond OA publishing in Mozambique.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Diamond OA journals in public institutions are funded from the public budget, while private institutions use funds from the institution's general revenues.

The funding, IT infrastructure, human resources management and other facilities for the Diamond OA journal are centrally provided by universities/research institutes and allocated to the editorial units. But there are many challenges to mobilizing funds, maintaining support services and infrastructures, such as higher

⁵⁴ Adapted from [Horacio Zimba](#), Eduardo Mondlane University (Mozambique) in Kuchma, I., & Ševkušić, M. (2024). Landscape of no-fee Open Access publishing in Africa. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12792474>

quality servers and a stable internet connection, IT specialists with knowledge and skills to configure and maintain submissions and scholarly publishing platforms.

In 2024, Universidade Eduardo Mondlane received funding from “Collaboration for sustainable OA publishing in Africa” project managed by EIFL, African Journals Online and West and Central African Research and Education Network, with funding from Wellcome. The grant helped to improve the publishing platform for Diamond OA journals and upgrade their infrastructure to guarantee smooth production and publication process; review journal policies and guidelines and enhance quality standards to fulfil indexing criteria.

Some specific activities, such as training for staff on academic writing and peer review, have been supported through projects funded by university partners. Although Fundo Nacional de Investigação (FNI, National Research Fund) provides support to research projects that include the publication and dissemination of information, Diamond OA journals have not been funded by the FNI yet.

In general, all public and private institutions publishing scholarly journals in Mozambique face many challenges in ensuring financial sustainability. They mostly depend on government resources, which have been reduced in recent years, as the publishing of scholarly journals does not seem to be a priority when allocating funds from the public budget. In most institutions, initiatives related to journal publishing are at an embryonic stage and they often depend on small projects funded by external partners. When these projects come to an end, funding for the journals established in this context also ceases, leading them to a crisis soon after the publication of the first issues.

For example, a new journal was launched through a project funded by external partners and was hosted in a cloud paid with the project funds. The funding is coming to an end and there are no funds to maintain the journal after the end of the project.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

There are no incentives for the editorial units of Diamond OA journals, except for monthly salaries provided by their institutions, which in many cases correspond to their main jobs and not exactly the function of editor and/or member of the scholarly journal's editorial team.

Efforts are made though to take into consideration some journal publishing activities in annual performance evaluations and professional career promotion of the employees.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Regional/national publishing/indexing platforms and other types of infrastructure don't support Diamond OA publishing in Mozambique yet.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Some universities have a dedicated unit responsible for scholarly publishing activities. A unit director also performs the functions of the editor-in-chief and coordinates tasks related to scholarly publishing with academic and research units: faculties, departments and research centres. In other institutions, the unit responsible for Research, Extension and Innovation coordinates scholarly publishing activities. In one institution the scholarly journal is under the responsibility of the Training and Communication unit. Institutions are willing to mobilize funding to support Diamond OA journals, but they face many challenges to ensure sustainable funding.

IT infrastructure, financial resources, human resources and support services are generally provided by the institutions that host Diamond OA journals. For example, the editorial unit can be in the central library and benefit from shared IT infrastructure services, including specific support services for installing, configuring and managing the OJS platform and other applications or IT services. A similar structure can be found at other institutions: resources are shared between the unit responsible for the journal and the IT department, where the IT department installs, configures and maintains the OJS platform. Another example of resource-sharing is the editorial team with staff from different departments: the library, IT, and communication services.

Four institutions have implemented the OJS platform to edit and publish Diamond OA journals. Although they have been using the OJS platform for some time, it is not yet used to its fullest. Namely, the OJS platform is used only for online publishing, while practically the entire process between submission and publication of accepted manuscripts is carried out outside of this. Submissions can be made either by email or via the platform, and the former option is used by Early Career Researches only, who recently graduated from master's or doctoral levels. The peer review process is conducted off platform.

Some institutions do not use OJS due to technical limitations and continue to publish journals in the PDF format, through links that are inserted on the institutions' websites, though they seem to have an IT infrastructure (servers, dedicated internet) capable of hosting the platform. These institutions lack support for the training of IT staff and editorial board members.

Workforce and Capacity Development

The dynamics of scholarly publishing in Mozambique often depends on the enthusiasm and commitment of individual professionals who take the role of the editor-in-chief. They make a tremendous effort to keep the journals running even when facing many structural difficulties.

In journals owned and published by public higher education and research institutions, the staff members performing editorial tasks are mostly employed by these institutions. In some cases, they are allocated to the unit responsible for publication management, while in others they carry out publication management activities on a voluntary basis, as they have other tasks that consume most of their working time.

For example, in one institution only the editor-in-chief is employed full-time at the unit, along with the administrative staff who do not perform any editorial functions. The remaining members of the editorial board are partially linked to the editorial unit, dedicating most of their time to other academic activities and research unrelated to editorial processes.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Diamond OA journal editors sometimes collaborate on training sessions for editors, reviewers and authors supported by partner-funded projects and these training activities are usually open to all those interested in the institution, as well as to other institutions as a way of maximizing gains in terms of sharing experiences in the Mozambican scholarly community.

Training opportunities for editors, reviewers and authors have been offered through initiatives such as Research4Life and other international organizations that work to mobilize resources and support for the development of platforms for accessing information resources and scientific publications. Similar workshops were organized in collaboration with partners from Brazil and Portugal through the Lusophone Open Science Conference (ConfOA).

Universidade Eduardo Mondlane and Universidade Católica de Moçambique participate in the No-Fee Open Access Publishing in Africa Community of Practice, which provides a good opportunity to share and learn many aspects of Diamond OA publishing, including efficient training for editorial teams, reviewers and authors, effective use of OJS, complying with journal indexing requirements and other good practices.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

There are no Diamond OA journals specific quality assurance strategies.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

The following policy and funding actions could maintain Diamond OA publishing:

- ✓ Diamond OA publishing policies.
- ✓ Training for editorial teams, reviewers and authors with an emphasis on Diamond OA publishing, including good practices, effective use of OJS platform and complying with journal indexing requirements.

To ensure the sustainability of Diamond OA journals, investment should be made in shared hosting and infrastructure for Diamond OA journal publishing. These services could be implemented and managed by the Mozambique Research and Education Network (MoRENet) that already offers shared connectivity and content storage infrastructure. Such infrastructure could also be used by institutions for scholarly journal publishing, and this would improve the sustainability of Diamond OA publishing in Mozambique.

Additionally, it would be necessary to invest in training a service management team, which would be responsible for replicating the training at the local (institutional) level. This will allow the creation of a collaboration network among institutions, ensuring the sustainability of Diamond OA journals.

SENEGAL

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

There are very few Diamond OA journals in Senegal and these journals, even with a solid institutional base, are mainly supported by committed individuals.

Diamond OA journals are owned, funded and published by scholarly societies, laboratories, research groups, Higher Education Institutions and foundations. For example, *Société Médicale d'Afrique Noire de Langue Française (SMANLF)* owns and publishes *Dakar Médical* journal; *Groupe Interdisciplinaire de Recherche sur les Cultures et les Identités (GIRCI) - Revue Les Cahiers du GIRCI*; the *DECRYPTA Laboratory of École doctorale Arts, Cultures, Civilisations (ARCIV) of the Doctoral School at Cheikh Anta Diop University in Dakar (UCAD) - Revue Africaine des Sciences de l'Antiquité SUNU XALAAAT* (a Wolof term meaning “our thought, our opinion, our reflection” on a given issue) and *UCAD Arts and Humanities Faculty - Les Annales de la Faculté des Lettres et Sciences Humaines*; *Ecole Inter-Etats des Sciences et Médecine Vétérinaires (EISMV) de Dakar - La Revue africaine de santé et de productions animales (RASPA)*; *Laboratoire d'Analyse des Sociétés et Pouvoirs / Afrique-diaspora (LASPAD-UGB) - Global Africa* with partners; *Laboratoire de Recherche en Sciences de l'Information et de la Communication (LARSIC) de l'Ecole de Bibliothécaires, Archivistes et Documentalistes (EBAD-UCAD) - La revue sénégalaise des sciences de l'information*; *La société africaine de chirurgie - Le Journal Africain de Chirurgie*; *ARCIV⁵⁵ - Revue d'études africaines*; *CERROMAN* laboratory endorsed by *ARCIV⁵⁶ UCAD - La revue semestrielle CERROMAN*; and *Fondation Senghor - Éthiopiennes*, founded by Léopold Sédar Senghor in 1975, one of the oldest journals in French-speaking Africa.

⁵⁵ Le Journal Africain de Chirurgie; ARCIV: <http://arciv.ucad.sn/>

⁵⁶ Ibid

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

*The Council for the Development of Social Science Research in Africa (CODESRIA) at its 2016 Conference on Electronic Publishing and Dissemination held in Dakar in collaboration with the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) and the Latin American Social Sciences Council (CLACSO) released the Dakar Declaration on OA in Africa and the Global South calling for making publicly funded research freely available to the public and establishing multi-stakeholder mechanisms for collaboration and cooperation to amplify and increase the voice and influence of research from Africa and the Global South. The Dakar Declaration also urges institutions and governments to develop OA policies and initiatives to promote open scholarship and knowledge production and dissemination and provide the enabling environment, infrastructure and capacity building required to support OA.*⁵⁷

In July 2025, the National Agenda for the Transformation of Higher Education, Research, and Innovation in Senegal (ANESRI), led by the Ministry of Higher Education and Research (MESRI), was held in Diamniadion and one of the key recommendations was the transformation of the National Centre for Scientific and Technical Documentation (CNDST-MESRI) into a true body for the promotion and support of Diamond OA journals.

Although Senegal does not yet have an explicit national policy dedicated to supporting Diamond OA publishing, several universities have developed institutional policies aimed at promoting OA and open science. While there is no specific legal framework governing OA or Diamond OA publishing to date, the regulatory environment within universities is evolving, notably with support for copyright reform, participation in discussions on transparency and access to information, and various recommendations calling for the creation of centralised national platforms for OA publishing.

⁵⁷ Dakar Declaration: <https://wiki.lib.sun.ac.za/images/5/50/Dakar-declaration-2016.pdf>

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Diamond OA journals are funded by their host institutions. Some journals are co-funded via African university consortia, for example, *Global Africa*, a pan-African interdisciplinary and multilingual journal. The primary financial support (56%) comes from the *French Development Agency*. The host institution - *Université Gaston Berger (UGB)* - contributes 12% of funding and provides human resources as well as the headquarters for *Global Africa*. *Institute for Research for Development (IRD)* contributes 11% and covers the editorial secretary position. Other members of the journal publishing consortium directly contribute 4% funding and provide their infrastructures and teams. The remaining funding relies predominantly on revenue generated by the online certification courses and a fundraising strategy.⁵⁸ Permanent consortium members and journal's co-managers are *Laboratory for the Analysis of Societies and Powers / Africa – Diasporas (LASPAD)* of UGB, Senegal; *IRD*, France; *The Laboratory for Studies and Research on Social Dynamics and Local Development (LASDEL)*, Niger; and *The International University of Rabat (UIR)*, Morocco. Other consortium partners support the journal as well: *the African Studies Association for Africa (ASAA)* in Ghana, *CODESRIA* in Senegal, the *National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies (INSEE)* in France, *Institute of African Worlds (IMAF)* in France, Cheikh Hamidou Kane Digital University (UNCHK)⁵⁹ in Senegal, the *University of Manouba (ULM)* in Tunisia, *The Conversation*, and the *Network of Science Journalists of French-speaking Africa (RJSAF)* from West Africa.⁶⁰ The financial viability of the *Global Africa* journal is based on a strategy of gradual empowerment of African editorial teams, founded on the transfer of skills, the internalisation of resources and the professionalisation of those involved in scientific publishing. This approach aims to reduce dependence on external funding, while consolidating sustainable local capacity. The recurring support of institutional partners such as UGB, AFD and IRD is an essential pillar of stability, guaranteeing the continuity of activities and long-term investment.

⁵⁸ Global Africa Presentation: <https://www.globalafricasciences.org/presentation>

⁵⁹ Cheikh Hamidou Kane Digital University (UNCHK): <https://www.unchk.sn/>

⁶⁰ Global Africa Partenariat: <https://www.globalafricasciences.org/parteneriat>

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

There are no incentives and rewards for Diamond OA publishing in Senegal. Recognition (for authors, editors and reviewers of Diamond OA journals) could be a major incentive and motivation, as it was discussed during the ANESRI.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

La Revue africaine de santé et de productions animales (RASPA) uses an overlay journal publishing model - an author deposits a preprint in an open archive (HAL) and then submits this preprint to *RASPA*; the journal's editorial committee examines the submission, forwards it to reviewers (for single blind review) and publishes using the Episciences platform, which offers a complete editorial workflow and a publication interface.

Some institutional repositories provide access to the full text of institutional journals (e.g. *Cheikh Anta Diop University in Dakar (UCAD) Bibliothèque Numérique*).

African Journals Online (AJOL) and Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) index *Global Africa* journal.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Top level institutional support is crucial for Diamond OA publishing, and it needs to be embedded in institutional structures. Four institutional examples below provide the current state of the arts.

At *Cheikh Anta Diop University in Dakar (UCAD)*, Diamond OA journals receive financial support from institutes, schools, and faculties in the form of annual research and publication grants awarded by Directorates and Deans. Presses Universitaires de Dakar (PUD) hosts and supports Diamond OA journals. There is a need for an institutional level policy though that would coordinate Diamond OA publishing at UCAD and pool all scattered resources into an institutional fund.

Ecole Inter-Etats des Sciences et Médecine Vétérinaires (EISMV) de Dakar funds *RASPA* from EISMV's operational budget and covers the journal's editorial work and office management costs, communication, including Internet connectivity, hardware and software.

Société Médicale d'Afrique Noire de Langue Française (SMANLF) funds *Dakar Médical* journal from the annual membership fees and an annual grant from the Dean of the *Faculty of Medicine, Pharmacy and Odonto-stomatology (FMPOS)* at *Cheikh Anta Diop University in Dakar*.

Groupe Interdisciplinaire de Recherche sur les Cultures et les Identités (GIRCI) also funds its journal *Revue Les Cahiers du GIRCI* with the membership fees.

The funding and sustainability strategies described above are common to other Senegalese Diamond OA journals. Improved institutional coordination, for example, between the Research and Innovation Department and the University Press, with the support of the Rectorate, will help to pool resources and create a sustainable support service for Diamond OA publishing.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Some Diamond OA journals, e.g. *Global Africa* pays journal staff: assistant editors, editorial secretary, communications manager, editorial production manager and webmaster and covers copyediting and translation costs (French, English, Arabic and Swahili).

Universities, particularly UCAD, employ personnel and training will help to strengthen the Diamond OA publishing teams at PUD and DISI (UCAD's IT and Information Systems Department). Some Diamond OA journal editors don't favour centralization and would like to have staff at their disposal. These personnel issues should be resolved at the institutional level by the rectorate and the relevant structures (Institutes, Schools, and Faculties).

Revue Africaine des Sciences de l'Antiquité SUNU XALAAT receives an annual contribution from the *UCAD Arts and Humanities Faculty* to cover the website hosting fee and to reward peer reviewers. However, the editorial team - the journal's editor, editorial secretaries and editorial board members - work on a voluntary basis. This is also the case for many Diamond OA journal editorial teams that work on a voluntary basis. Many of them have been trained in the job and do not have scholarly publishing qualifications. They are driven by a strong commitment to serve research and contribute to Africa's research and cultural impact.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

PUD and DISI provide all Diamond OA journals with a hosting platform based on Open Journal Systems. PUD also assigns DOIs to all UCAD journal articles and indexes journals in registries and databases. The current indexing challenges include non-compliance of journals with the standards set by indexing services databases, hence the importance of training.

RASPA collaborates with Episciences – a Diamond OA scientific publishing platform developed by the Centre for Direct Scientific Communication (CCSD) in France, a

CNRS/INRAE/Inria support and research unit (free of charge publishing, plagiarism checking and DOI assignment).

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Since November 2023, *Global Africa* has signed the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)⁶¹, which recognizes the need to improve the way research results are assessed to go beyond widely used metrics (e.g. Journal Impact Factor). As a DORA⁶² signatory, *Global Africa* is committed to fostering excellence and quality in research and ensuring that fair value is given to a wide variety of research outputs in the evaluation process and that researchers are assessed on their own merits.⁶³

Quality assurance is essential for mainstreaming Diamond OA publishing and ANAQ-Sup representatives (Autorité nationale d'Assurance Qualité de l'Enseignement supérieur, de la Recherche et de l'Innovation) participated in the ANESRI workshops on this topic.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

A strong political will is required, translated into strong legislative, financial, organizational, recruitment and training actions on Diamond OA publishing.

Recognition of Diamond OA publishing by Conseil Africain et Malgache pour l'Enseignement Supérieur (CAMES), for example, by creating a regional indexing database, would be very helpful as well.

At the national level, the MESRI's CNDST should be strengthened with technical, human, financial, and legal resources to enable it to:

- ✓ Create a national portal dedicated to Diamond OA.
- ✓ Make it mandatory for all Senegalese scientific journals to join this portal.
- ✓ Conduct regular monitoring.
- ✓ Fund and support Diamond OA publishing in Senegalese universities.
- ✓ Connect Senegal to global Diamond OA collaborative networks.

At the institutional level, PUD in collaboration with the UCAD Rectorate is ready to fully facilitate Diamond OA publishing for all scholarly journals. Annual journal

⁶¹ Declaration On Research Assessment (DORA) Signers:

https://sfdora.org/signers/?_organization_country=senegal

⁶² Declaration On Research Assesment (DORA): <https://sfdora.org/>

⁶³ <https://www.globalafricasciences.org/ethical-charter>

subsidies will be required as well as decentralized IT resources and training for PUD staff and journal managers. APC-charging journals are ready to flip to Diamond OA publishing when support is available.

TANZANIA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

In Tanzania, higher learning institutions, professional associations, government institutions and research institutions own and publish Diamond OA journals, for example, Institute of Accountancy Arusha, Mbeya University of Science and Technology, Muhimbili University of Health and Allied Sciences, Mzumbe University, Open University of Tanzania, Sokoine University of Agriculture, University of Dar es Salaam, University of Dodoma, The College of Surgeons of East, Central and Southern Africa and Western Indian Ocean Marine Science Association.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

There are no National Policies and Legal Frameworks yet that facilitate Diamond OA publishing. The Tanzania Commission for Science and Technology (COSTECH) - the principal advisory organ to the Government on all matters relating to scientific research, innovation and technology development and transfer - has a mandate to formulate policy on the development of science and technology and recommend its implementation by the Government; monitor and co-ordinate the activities relating to scientific research and technology development; acquire, store and disseminate scientific and technology information; and advise the government on allocation and utilization of research and innovation funds according to priorities,

⁶⁴ Some text is reused from COSTECH's draft "National Guidelines for Recognition and Promotion of Scientific Journals in Tanzania" and Kuchma, I., & Ševkušić, M. (2024). Landscape of no-fee Open Access publishing in Africa. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12792474>

regional and international co-operation in scientific research and transfer of technology, matters relating to the training and recruitment of research personnel, the initiation, formulation, and implementation of research policies and programmes and the establishment and maintenance of national scientific standards. COSTECH's draft "National Guidelines for Recognition and Promotion of Scientific Journals in Tanzania" introduced minimum criteria for journal publication to ensure credible and reputable publishing outlets to disseminate knowledge generated to a wider audience nationally and internationally.

COSTECH's National Guidelines draft also includes the following policy objectives for open science:

- ✓ Promote the development of effective institutional, national and regional open science policies and legal frameworks that are consistent with existing international and regional law and are in line with the Open Science definition, values, and principles as well as actions outlined by the UNESCO Recommendation.
- ✓ Recommend economic investment in open science and OA which will be consistent with their benefit to Tanzania and the East African region and African continent. Therefore, institutions and governments provide an enabling environment, infrastructure, and capacity building required to support OA.
- ✓ Promote higher education and academic publishing enabling environments through the committed provision of quality OA digital research materials.
- ✓ Emphasize recognition, respect, and acknowledgment of national, regional diversity of East African (and African) scientific journals, institutional repositories, and academic systems and, conversely, that researchers and corporations in the East African region should benefit from being able to access research.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Diamond OA journals are directly or indirectly supported financially by their host institution. For example, four Diamond OA journals are supported by the University of Dar es Salaam (UDSM), which provides funds for various activities including editorial work, typesetting, and prepress. UDSM sustains Diamond OA journals by providing a minimum amount of funds for specific activities. Currently, the burden of sustaining the journals is largely borne by the respective academic units.

COSTECH's draft National Guidelines mentions the following scholarly journals publishing weaknesses: lack of reliable ICT infrastructure to facilitate journal management operations; lack of specific budget for journal operations; many

journals are not institutionalised. Providing financial support through competitive mode for journal development is one of the aims of the National Guidelines in addition to establishing a data base of all journals published in Tanzania; instituting minimum standards for journals in line with international best practices; supporting indexing to increase visibility to the global scientific community and supporting capacity building of editorial teams.

The World Bank's Higher Education Economic Transformation (HEET) project provides an opportunity for enhancing ICT support for Diamond OA journals.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Universities provide incentives for various activities including editorial work, typesetting, prepress and technical meetings to discuss critical issues about the journal. The technical committees of the journals are also incentivized to conduct their technical meetings that are aimed at discussing some issues to improve the journal.

The Science, Technology and Innovation Division of the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology included in its financial year 2022/23 Annual Plan an activity of establishing an award system to best Tanzanian researchers who publish their research in the High Impact Journals. But this initiative doesn't intend to develop and promote Diamond OA journals in the country.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

African Journals Online (AJOL) indexes 23 Diamond OA journals and Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) - three Diamond OA journals.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Institutions provide overall governance and staff for Diamond OA journal as well as ICT facilities such as desktop computers, printers, the Internet network and working space. Diamond OA journals also receive legal and ICT services from the centralized legal and ICT departments. Four institutional use cases are described below.

Institute of Accountancy Arusha (IAA)

Diamond OA publishing aligns with the mission of the IAA to democratize knowledge dissemination and foster inclusive academic growth. Currently the institute (through the Faculty of Informatics) hosts *The Journal of Informatics*, which is a Diamond OA journal. The operational structure of this journal relies on internal infrastructure (servers and technical support), volunteer contributions from

academic and editorial staff, and institutional oversight. While this has enabled continuity, it poses challenges in areas requiring specialized input such as system upgrades, editorial turnaround time, and indexing compliance. A strategic decision has been made to allocate a portion of registration fees from IAA's annual academic conferences toward supporting the journal. This revenue will finance activities such as copyediting, peer-review management, training workshops, and publication software upgrades—while preserving the no-cost policy for authors.

Mzumbe University

Mzumbe University is the host institution for the *East African Journal of Applied Health Monitoring and Evaluation* and provides financial support through a limited budget to assist with the journal's operations. The allocated budget has been used to cover the costs for maintaining and updating the journal's website, including domain renewal and hosting services; pay for token professional copyediting and layout formatting to ensure high quality presentation of articles and support activities such as producing flyers to raise awareness and attract quality submissions. The University has also provided dedicated office space and essential utilities on campus for the Chief Editor, secretary, journal webmaster, and editorial assistants; university-managed servers, the journal management platform (Open Journal Systems), and regular IT support to ensure smooth and secure online operations; free access to plagiarism detection tools such as Turnitin, and other scholarly resources to support the peer review process and overall editorial activities; video conferencing facilities, supporting virtual engagement, outreach, and dissemination of journal content; legal and administrative support in the management of Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs), copyright agreements, and other legal documentation necessary for the effective operation and collaboration of the journal. The University has actively used its communication platforms, including the institutional website, social media channels, and newsletters, to promote the journal and its publications.

The journal Editorial Board has been appointed by the Deputy Vice Chancellor (Academic, Research, and Consultancy) on behalf of the Mzumbe University Council. The University has made the journal's sustainability a top priority and is currently exploring additional revenue streams for the journal, including the possibility of rehosting annual hybrid international conferences on health monitoring and evaluations. Mzumbe University is currently in the final stages of discussions with the Prime Minister's Office regarding the signing of an MoU to publish the conference proceedings of the Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning (MEL) Week 2025, that took place in September in Tanzania.

University of Dar es Salaam (UDSM)

“UDSM journals are managed in accordance with the UDSM institutional governing structure. Under this setup, the custodian of all UDSM journals is the office of the Deputy Vice Chancellor (DVC) - Research through the Directorate of Research and Publications (DRP), which oversees the establishment and operations of the University’s journals.”⁶⁵ DRP delegates funding to the Unit level. For example, The *Journal of The Geographical Association of Tanzania* (JGAT) is funded by the College of Social Sciences, and this funding covers editing, type setting and printing services.

Diamond OA journals at UDSM are hosted on a centralized system based on the open-source software Open Journal Systems maintained by the IT personnel from the University’s ICT department. The progress of the publishing portal is being reported in senate meetings on quarterly basis. UDSM’s Journal Policy and Guidelines (2024) require the UDSM to ensure journals are adequately funded and financially sustainable by setting aside funds for journal technological and infrastructural development, creating a conducive environment for the running of its journals and facilitating the creation of necessary conditions to make the UDSM journals financially sustainable.

The College of Surgeons of East, Central and Southern Africa (COSECSA)

COSECSA provides an annual approved budget for its *East and Central African Journal of Surgery* (ECAJS) journal, which in 2025 includes journal domain hosting fee, funding for the OA publishing platform and salary for journal support staff.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Although there are no dedicated institutional units for Diamond OA journals, publishing operations are usually the responsibility of the coordinators of research and publications at academic units.

No employees are assigned to work specifically for the journal as they also have other academic responsibilities such as teaching, research and consultancy. Most activities performed by journal staff, including the editor-in-chief, are voluntary and are regarded as part of their academic responsibilities. No direct payment is

⁶⁵ University of Dar es Salaam (UDSM):
https://www.udsm.ac.tz/sites/default/files/2025-02/20240806_093117_UNIT_16_CUSTOM_PAGE_%20Journal%20Policy%20and%20Guidelines-January2024.pdf

provided for the editors-in-chief and their associates. However, few become burdened.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

African Journal of Accounting and Social Sciences Studies (AJASSS) collaborate with the Open University of Tanzania (OUT) and *Pan-African Journal of Business Management*. This collaboration is grounded on the sharing of ideas on the review process and journal management.

ECAJS also collaborates with other journals, e.g. *The Surgeon journal*, *British Journal of Surgery*, *Surgery journal*, *Journal of Global Surgery*, *Diseases of the Colon & Rectum Journal*, *Canadian Journal of Surgery* and *British Journal of Surgery*.

Eastern and Southern African Journal of Agricultural Economics and Development collaborates with Mwalimu Nyerere University of Agriculture and Technology (Tanzania), University of Nairobi (Kenya), University of Burundi, University of Dodoma (Tanzania), Lilongwe University of Agriculture and Natural Resources (Malawi), Tanzania Agricultural Research Institute, Moshi Cooperatives University (Tanzania), Makerere University (Uganda) and Michigan State University involving staff from these universities as either editors or reviewers of manuscripts. Similarly, *Tanzania Journal of Agricultural Sciences* collaborates with Tanzania Agricultural Research Institute, Division of Agronomy, Indian Agricultural Research Institute (ICAR), Academy of Agriculture Science Urumqi (China), Makerere University (Uganda), Tanzania Dairy Board, Ministry of Livestock & Fisheries (Tanzania), Tanzania Food and Nutrition Commission, Open University of Tanzania and Commission for Science and Technology (COSTECH).

Tanzania Journal of Community Development is affiliated with Community Development Professional Association of Tanzania (CODEPATA) and Affirmative action on Gender Equality Network (AGEN) and collaborates with Tanzania Gender Networking Program, Participatory Ecological Land Use Management, International Exchange Alumni of the US Government, Women's Research and Development Project Association, and Sokoine University of Agriculture.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

The Harmonised Scheme of Service for Academic Staff in Public Universities and Constituent Colleges (2022) does not stipulate the nature and quality of journals to be considered for promotion and it's up to individual institutions to develop their own criteria for promotion purposes.

For example, all journals published by the UDSM are evaluated for quality every two years and they are ranked based on the adherence to a set of standards defined in the policy. The quality criteria include the peer-review process, indexing, the international character of editorial and advisory boards, timely publication of the journal, etc. OA-related criteria are taken into consideration to avoid being categorized as predatory journals, e.g. whether the publisher is a member of OASPA, or the journal is registered in DOAJ, a declaration of the journals' business model, etc.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Funding is needed to support the following activities:

- ✓ Providing incentives and training to the personnel of Diamond OA journals.
- ✓ Flipping journals charging publication fees and subscription-based journals to Diamond OA publishing.
- ✓ Supporting Diamond OA journals in Tanzania.

TOGO

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Diamond OA journals are supported by institutions and associations they belong to.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

There are no National Policies and Legal Frameworks that facilitate Diamond OA publishing in Togo.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Diamond OA journals are funded by institutions they belong to and these institutions do not always receive public funding.

Apart from institutional support, sources of income can include consultancy and service partnerships, project funding (provided by the European Union, the United Nations Development Programme, the Food and Agriculture Organization, the World Bank and the Swiss National Science Foundation) and membership fees from associations the journals belong to.

⁶⁶ Adapted from [Innocent Azilan](#) Universités de Toulon et de Lomé, WACREN (Togo) in Kuchma, I., & Ševkušić, M. (2024). Landscape of no-fee Open Access publishing in Africa. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12792474>

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

There are no incentives and rewards for Diamond OA publishing in Togo. As the management of the journal is not an administrative task at the university, it is not deducted from the statutory hours to be devoted to teaching and research.

Journal editing and publishing is not among the CAMES (Conseil Africain et Malgache pour l'Enseignement Supérieur) criteria for career promotion.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

To date, there are no national platforms or infrastructures for Diamond OA publishing in Togo.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Diamond OA journals in Togo are institutional. According to the editors of the two Diamond OA journals, the decision to opt for OA publishing at no cost to authors is motivated by a need to promote the publication culture. This challenges the almost systematic introduction of APCs (ranging from €50 to €80 depending on the journal) in OA journals in Togo. For some researchers these amounts are beyond the reach, and early career researchers (master's and doctoral students) are particularly affected, among other things they can make choices based on the APC amount rather than quality, e.g. choose journals with the lowest possible fees, which may have less rigorous evaluation process.

A notable example is Laboratoire de botanique et Ecologie Végétale, Université de Lomé, which supports *Revue Ecosystèmes et Paysages* by covering the costs of hosting and maintaining the website, covering connectivity costs and promotion activities - participation in scientific events. Lab members (PhD students, associate professors and lecturers) contribute their expertise and help run the journal. The Lomé University Press and the Research and Innovation Department provide advisory and administrative support.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Diamond OA journal editors have to mobilize their communities (from lecturers-researchers to PhD students) to help manage journals. They do not have "professional" teams employed to perform editorial tasks. Journals are most often created on the personal initiative of the lecturers with a view to disseminating and promoting research. Accordingly, the periodicity of a journal often depends on the availability of volunteers dedicated to getting involved in the publishing process.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

There are no notable collaborations between publishers and service providers on Diamond OA publishing.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

There are no Diamond OA journals specific quality assurance frameworks and strategies.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

The following policy and funding actions will help to overcome current obstacles and effectively mainstream Diamond OA publishing in Togo:

- ✓ Providing financial resources to Diamond OA journals.
- ✓ Ensuring technical expertise to support Diamond OA journal's editorial teams.
- ✓ Ensuring institutional support.
- ✓ Increasing the commitment of stakeholders and exploring sustainable economic models for Diamond OA publishing.
- ✓ Cooperation at local, national and international levels, pool resources and sharing good practices, providing training.
- ✓ Raising awareness of the benefits of Diamond OA publishing.

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Diamond OA journals are owned, funded and published by Universities (e.g. faculties at Islamic University in Uganda, Kampala International University, Makerere University, Uganda Christian University and Uganda Martyrs University), research organizations (e.g. National Agricultural Research Organization), not-for-profit organizations (e.g. African Field Epidemiology Network) and publishing companies (e.g. EcoScribe Publishers Company Limited). They see a strategic value of Diamond OA publishing for the country.

The Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST) launched a new open science policy⁶⁷ that includes measures to facilitate Diamond OA publishing in the country.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

UNCST regulates, monitors and evaluates all aspects of science, technology, and innovation (STI) in the country; translates STI policies into regulations and standards to guide the operations of the entire STI system; and provides continuing professional development to researchers and institutions. As a clearing house for research, UNCST reviews from 1,800 to 2,500 research projects annually.

UNCST adopted an open science policy in 2025 following an extensive and participatory stakeholder engagement process to ensure that the policy reflects the diverse voices and priorities of the national science and innovation ecosystem. The

⁶⁷ Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST) Open Science Policy:
<https://nru.uncst.go.ug/handle/123456789/11853>

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policy includes the following measures to facilitate Diamond OA publishing in the country:

- ✓ Develop and support open communication platforms and tools, including – among others open-source journal management systems and preprint platforms.
- ✓ Encourage researchers to publish in OA journals; promote OA publishing and ensure transparency in the peer review processes; promote the use of open licenses (e.g., Creative Commons) and enable the broad reuse of STI outputs.
- ✓ Collaborate for adequate investment in non-commercial open science infrastructures and services, including OA journals.
- ✓ Ensure grant applicants outline how they will incorporate open science into their projects, with specific plans for research data sharing, OA publishing, and collaborative research.
- ✓ Implement a system of incentives, such as recognition, awards, or grants, for STI practitioners and teams that significantly contribute to open science through the development, adoption and utilisation of open digital platforms and systems.
- ✓ Integrate open science in grants management systems and other research quality assurance mechanisms to ensure that all key stakeholders are aware of ongoing reforms within the global knowledge system to maintain these good practices within their own institutional systems.
- ✓ Introduce responsible research and researcher evaluation and assessment practices, which incentivise quality science, recognizing the diversity of research outputs, activities and missions.
- ✓ Facilitate the integration of open science principles into national STI policies, ensuring alignment with global standards and best practices.
- ✓ Establish national guidelines on open science practices, ensuring that all research funded or regulated by the government adheres to principles of openness, transparency, and inclusivity.
- ✓ Encourage academic and research institutes to draft and adopt their own open science policies.
- ✓ Implement capacity building programs aimed at training researchers, scientists, and policymakers on Open Science principles, research data management and OA publishing and work with universities and research institutions to integrate open science practices into higher education curricula, ensuring that future researchers are well-versed in OA publishing, research data sharing, and ethical research practices.

Openness, collaboration and inclusivity in science are central pillars of the UNCSST Strategic Plan (2025/2026 - 2029/2030), aligned with Uganda's Fourth National Development Plan.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Diamond OA journals are supported by institutional funds.

The *African Health Sciences journal* was also supported by the African Health Journals Partnership Project funded by the US National Institutes of Health (through the National Library of Medicine and the Fogarty International Centre) and facilitated by the Council of Science Editors.⁶⁸

Journal of Food Innovation, Nutrition, and Environmental Sciences (JFINES) welcomes “voluntary donations from authors and the general public to help maintain and improve the journal. Donations are not linked to any specific manuscript and do not influence peer review or publication decisions in any way.”⁶⁹ These donations support maintenance of digital publishing platform, ensure high publication standards, keep all content freely accessible and help assign DOIs for published articles and increase the visibility and impact of research.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Diamond OA journals provide a cost-effective solution for PhD students who are required to publish a paper and for researchers who are required to publish a paper every semester. But research assessment reform is needed to move away from overreliance on Journal Impact Factors and university rankings and to make local Diamond OA journals more accepted. Culture change is also needed to change the current perception that free means lower quality and showcase the quality of local Diamond OA journals.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Diamond OA journals collaborate with African Journals Online (AJOL), which hosts and publishes the online version of journals. The Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) indexes nine Diamond OA journals.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Institutional funds cover some administrative costs of Diamond OA journals as well as editing, typesetting and designing. Some journals cover personnel costs for

⁶⁸ <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ahs>

⁶⁹ <https://jfines.org/index.php/jfines/apc>

editorial team and associate editors, journal management systems, domain and website hosting costs, annual subscriptions for editorial tools and memberships to relevant professional bodies.

Universities provide OJS-based journal publishing platforms.

Two institutional examples below describe how and why institutional support is provided.

Kampala International University (KIU)

KIU publications unit is a part of the Directorate of Research Innovation, Consultancy and Extension (RICE) and RICE manager for Research and Consultancy oversees Diamond OA journals publishing.

KIU covers all the costs of its eight Diamond OA journals, and these journals publish two issues a year in alignment with the KIU mission. For example, The *Journal of Education*, the periodical of the College of Education, Open, Distance, and E-Learning, and The *KIU Journal of Health Sciences* align “with the mission of KIU and research roadmap on responding to societal needs of delivering an education guided by the principles and values of respect for society, economy, and environment.”⁷⁰ ⁷¹ The *Journal of Education* “acts as a medium for improving the quality and delivery of education through new and emerging learning technologies; innovative policy and development; digital technologies; traditional, local, and indigenous knowledge, particularly in the context of developing countries with limited resources.”⁷² Similarly, The *KIU Journal of Health Sciences* is “dedicated to promoting high quality research in the fields of medical, pharmaceutical and related health sciences. The journal acts as a medium of improving the quality of health care delivery and medical education, particularly in the context of developing countries with limited resources.”⁷³

Uganda Pentecostal University (UPU)

UPU supports two Diamond OA journals: The *Uganda Pentecostal University Journal of Sustainable Development* and *UPU Journal of Law and Legal Studies*. Funds collected from tuition fees go to sustaining the OJS platform and the journals. About eight volunteers support journal editing and publishing. Diamond OA journals

⁷⁰ <https://kjed.kiu.ac.ug/about-the-journal.php>

⁷¹ <https://kjhs.kiu.ac.ug/about-the-journal.php>

⁷² <https://kjed.kiu.ac.ug/about-the-journal.php>

⁷³ <https://kjhs.kiu.ac.ug/about-the-journal.php>

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ensure dissemination of local knowledge and provide access to trusted information.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Most journal editors are volunteers and finding enough time for editorial work is an issue. They also struggle with reviewers' delays and manuscripts requiring a lot of revisions - sending them back and force takes time and creates extra costs that the journal's unit hasn't budgeted for. Sometimes it could be a full-time unpaid job.

Editorial teams also face challenges with the journal management systems. A lot of journal management work remains non-automated hence limiting the efficiency and leading to large deployment of human labour.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Uganda Journal of Agricultural Science, published by the National Agricultural Research Organization, collaborates with Makerere University in designing and layout, copy editing and typesetting of the manuscripts. Server space is provided by a sister government institution.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Maintaining the quality of manuscripts and published articles and ensuring continued publication of Diamond OA journals are among the current quality assurance challenges.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

- ✓ Increase annual budget for Diamond OA journals from the Government of Uganda and development partners.
- ✓ Create an institutional editorial system with budgets that will support Diamond OA publishing at all levels and change the current approach where Diamond OA journals are sustained from overheads.
- ✓ Encourage collaborations and partnerships: build a community and create a platform for sharing experiences and success stories among local and international experts, provide infrastructure support and build capacities in running Diamond OA journals.
- ✓ Compensate editorial staff for their work on Diamond OA journals.
- ✓ Scale up Diamond OA publishing and create efficiencies.
- ✓ Raise awareness on the quality of Diamond OA publishing.
- ✓ Embed Diamond OA publishing in national and institutional policies.

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- ✓ Ensure institutional coordination and funding for coordinating Diamond OA publishing initiatives.
- ✓ Reallocate funds for APC-based publications to Diamond OA publishing initiatives. When the quality is ensured and there is efficient support, this could help researchers struggling to publish in APC-charging journals that might be of not so good quality.

The following stakeholders could support Diamond OA publishing:

- ✓ Libraries as Diamond OA journal publishers and also promoters of Diamond OA journals on their campuses.
- ✓ Consortium of Uganda University Libraries as an umbrella organization for libraries.
- ✓ RENU - Research and Education Network for Uganda for infrastructure support.
- ✓ UCST for policy and funding.

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Image 3: Word cloud based on European country case studies content. Source: Own creation.

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European country case studies are built upon the findings of the DIAMAS project, particularly the *National overviews on sustaining institutional publishing in Europe* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683953>, and the *Institutional publishing in the ERA: Full country reports* <https://zenodo.org/records/10026207>.

The comparative analysis of 15 European country case studies highlights a developing Diamond Open Access (OA) scholarly publishing landscape that is gaining momentum. It is characterised by strong OA policy frameworks, established infrastructures, and growing national and international coordination mechanisms. Across the region, there are consistent institutional and national open access and open science policies. They are supported in many cases by legal frameworks, some dedicated funding streams for OA (though not usually targeted at Diamond OA), and quality assurance systems. These elements collectively provide a promising regulatory and financial foundation for sustaining Diamond OA. However, when it comes to Diamond OA specifically, these policies are still very much underdeveloped and are not uniform across the region, leaving still much work to be done.

Despite growing Diamond OA momentum in Europe, several challenges persist. In Europe, a sustainable Diamond Open Access (OA) ecosystem requires stronger policy commitments specifically directed at Diamond OA, incentivising researchers to choose Diamond routes and more stable public funding by governments, funders, and research organisations.

Concerns about commercial influence and research assessment systems that undervalue community-driven publishing reveal deeper structural barriers. Future policies must move beyond APC-based models, promote rights retention, and ensure that Diamond OA is fully recognised in evaluation, career progression, and institutional strategies, so that researchers can more easily prioritise Diamond venues, contribute editorially to nonprofit outlets, and help sustain or create such channels. Although editorial incentives exist, they remain uneven across countries, with limited recognition for this labour thus weakening community-based publishing. Europe is well positioned to address these issues by aligning with international research assessment reform initiatives such as CoARA, helping researchers make better and more affordable choices about where and how they publish.

A shift in funding is needed away from commercial publishing and APC/BPC-based models toward community-led, non-profit Diamond OA. Libraries and research institutions need to reinvest savings from big deals and capped APC spending into collective funding schemes and Diamond OA infrastructures. This can be

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strengthened by reallocating APC budgets and supplementing them with ministry support, foundations, memberships, and other shared models.

Sustaining and growing Diamond OA depends on coordinated funding mechanisms, reinvestment strategies, and robust infrastructure provision. More governmental bodies, research funders, and research organisations need to fund Diamond OA through national funds, consortia models, donations, and baseline grants to support infrastructure, alongside national capacity building through capacity centres, coordinated advocacy, and shared national and international initiatives to improve visibility and support bibliodiversity. To track policy and funding impact, Europe needs monitoring systems to better understand costs, staffing commitments, uptake, and quality. By pooling resources, enhancing training, strengthening rights management, and promoting digital sovereignty—while addressing infrastructure gaps and fragmented coordination—governments, funders, institutions, learned societies, libraries all have essential roles to improve the Diamond OA policy and funding ecosystem. Collectively they can secure a more resilient, equitable, and diverse Diamond OA ecosystem

Furthermore, a coordinated advocacy effort is needed to position nonprofit Diamond OA publishing as a public good and to build political, institutional, and researcher support for it. Raising awareness of the model, improving transparency about publishing choices, and increasing trust and visibility—through indexing and landscape mapping—are key to shifting current research publishing habits.

At the grassroots level of the Diamond OA publishers and their editors, there is already a lot of collaboration in Europe. National working groups and networks can unite stakeholders to drive cultural change, strengthen bibliodiversity, and provide shared platforms for coordination, capacity-building, and policy alignment.

Progress in Europe is hindered by workforce gaps in digital publishing, metadata, and platform administration. Shared services and common infrastructures for editorial workflows, hosting, discovery, and preservation are widely needed. Improved national coordination can transform fragmented efforts into coherent strategies through emerging national capacity centres, which are rapidly gaining momentum across Europe. Together, the above actions will support the structural and cultural change required for Diamond OA to become the publishing channel of choice in Europe.

Taken together, the findings reveal a European scholarly communication system that is relatively well structured, internationally well connected, but rather sparsely resourced in comparison to commercial publishing, and marked by coordination

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gaps, uneven capacity, lack of recognition, and dependencies that challenge the full realisation and visibility of Diamond OA. Strengthening shared infrastructures, expanding professional development, harmonising national strategies, and aligning research assessment with open publishing values will be essential steps for consolidating a sustainable, equitable, and community-owned publishing ecosystem across Europe.

CROATIA

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1. Landscape of non-profit scholarly publishing and Diamond OA

Croatian journals are almost exclusively Open Access and most follow the Diamond OA model. This is largely due to a strong bottom-up effort since the early 2000s to build OA infrastructure and promote OA principles. Many journals transitioned directly from print to Diamond OA, without attempting to introduce subscriptions for the online version. At the same time, print editions (and subscriptions to them) persist (Bosman et al. 2024, 4–52; Agnoloni et al. 2024, 78–122; Stojanovski and Mofardin 2023).

The majority of scholarly journals published in Croatia are in the Social Sciences and Arts and Humanities (SSH), with significantly fewer in STEM fields, as STEM researchers more often publish in international journals indexed in major citation databases. On the other hand, SSH researchers remain largely oriented towards local journals, which play a cultural role by supporting the national language and identity⁷⁴.

The development of Croatian journal publishing has largely been shaped by collaboration driven by the Ministry of Science, Education and Youth as the main funder and HRČAK Portal of Croatian Scientific and Professional Journals⁷⁵ as the key service.

While there are no nationwide projects in Open Access book publishing, several institutions have recently launched OA book publishing platforms (Morka and Gatti 2021; Melinščak Zlodi 2023).

⁷⁴ Taşkın, Zehra, Iva Melinščak Zlodi, Mikael Laakso, Didier Torny, Sona Arasteh, Margo Bargheer, Tabea Klaus, et al. 2024. “D5.2 National Overviews on Sustaining Institutional Publishing in Europe,” <https://zenodo.org/records/11383941>

⁷⁵ HRČAK Portal of Croatian Scientific and Professional Journals: <https://hrcak.srce.hr/>

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The progress of OA and open science (OS) in Croatia has been achieved primarily through a bottom-up approach, where the main actors were individual institutions (and their libraries), groups of institutions gathered around a project or initiative, groups of professionals with a common interest, or the national representatives of European infrastructures⁷⁶.

The main actors in OS and OA publishing in Croatia include:

- ✓ Research performing organisations - early implementers of institutional open repositories, OA policies or OA presses: Ruđer Bošković Institute, University of Zagreb Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Zagreb Medical School, University of Rijeka, University of Zadar, etc.
- ✓ Croatian representatives of the OS-related European infrastructures (CROSSDA, Dariah-HR, OpenAIRE NOAD, OPERAS national node, RDA node, EOSC representatives);
- ✓ University of Zagreb Computing Centre - Srce, as the central IT support institution for open infrastructures like the Hrčak journal portal and DABAR (Digital Academic Archives and Repositories)⁷⁷, e-infrastructure that facilitates the establishment and maintenance of a large number of reliable and interoperable institutional and thematic digital repositories and archives;
- ✓ Governance bodies of open infrastructures (Hrčak Council and Dabar Steering Board);
- ✓ Croatian Association for Scholarly Communication ZNAK (CROASC)⁷⁸, which promotes scholarly communication based on free, open, publicly funded, and accessible science by supporting editors and organising activities that advance scholarly publishing in Croatia.

In 2021, the Initiative for a Croatian Open Science Cloud was established (with representatives from 21 organisations, including the representatives of the Ministry of Science, Education and Youth and the Croatian Science Foundation), with the aim to coordinate the activities related to Open Science in Croatia and develop open research infrastructures to support it, but primarily to define the national open science plan (“Politika otvorene znanosti u Hrvatskoj – Otvorena znanost u Hrvatskoj” 2025).

⁷⁶ Taşkın, Zehra, Iva Melinščak Zlodi, Mikael Laakso, Didier Torny, Sona Arasteh, Margo Bargheer, Tabea Klaus, et al. 2024. “D5.2 National Overviews on Sustaining Institutional Publishing in Europe,” <https://zenodo.org/records/11383941>

⁷⁷ Digital Academic Archives and Repositories: [Digital Academic Archives and Repositories](https://www.dabar.hr/)

⁷⁸ Croatian Association for Scholarly Communication ZNAK (CROASC): <https://www.znak.hr/index.php/en/>

In 2025, steps are being taken towards establishing the National Diamond Capacity Centre.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

Major actors that define and/or influence policies in Croatia's research sector include:

- ✓ Ministry of Science, Education and Youth.
- ✓ Croatian Science Foundation.
- ✓ National Council for Science, Higher Education and Technological Development.
- ✓ Croatian Rectors Council.
- ✓ Croatian Agency for Science and Higher Education.

Except for the Croatian Agency for Science and Higher Education, none of them has a detailed and clearly defined OS or OA policy.

The Croatian Open Science Plan ("Hrvatski Plan Za Otvorenu Znanost" 2025), adopted in 2025, addresses OA publishing in very general terms and merely encourages authors to publish their research in OA publications licensed under open licenses where neither authors nor readers are required to pay fees for publishing or accessing the work.

Higher education institutions and research organisations in Croatia retain significant autonomy in implementing research policies. As a result, the implementation of open science will largely depend on local strategies, leadership support, and the development of infrastructure and capacities. While most institutional policies are limited to defining obligations for researchers and do not address institutional publishing, the Open Science Policy of the University of Zagreb supports Diamond OA for journals, books, and conference proceedings and encourages voluntary author contributions or sales of alternative formats to ensure sustainability. It also mandates Creative Commons licenses (preferably CC BY) and the use of persistent identifiers, namely DOIs. Some institutional OS policies seek to secure the Diamond OA status of their journals (e.g. University of Zagreb Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology).

It is noteworthy that infrastructure-related policies, or rather terms of use, have played an important role in promoting OA publishing in Croatia: the inclusion

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criteria of the central national journal infrastructure (Hrčak) require journals to be OA and to have an OA statement.

Research assessment policies have also shaped the OA publishing landscape in Croatia. As the indexation in major citation databases is highly relevant to both journal evaluation and research assessment, Croatian journals are striving to get indexed in these databases to ensure sustainable submission rates.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

The central repository (Dabar) and journal publishing (Hrčak) infrastructures are funded by the Ministry of Science, Education and Youth. Along with supporting Dabar and Hrčak, the Ministry also funds the Crossref membership fees, annual DOI registrations, and similarity check subscriptions for Croatian journals through the Croatian DOI Office (DOI-HR)⁷⁹, managed by the National and University Library in Zagreb. Croatian publishers may join Crossref through the Office under different cooperation models.

Prior to the adoption of the *Law on Higher Education and Scientific Activity (2022)* and the *Regulation on the Programme Financing of Public Universities and Public Scientific Institutes* in the Republic of Croatia (2023), journals received direct subsidies through regular annual calls by the Ministry of Science, Education and Youth. Funding was granted as long as journals met specific quality and impact criteria and were accessible in Open Access via the national platform Hrčak. Open licenses, rights retention, or data availability statements were not required at the time. Between 170 and 190 scholarly journals benefited from these subsidies (Taşkın et al. 2024, 34-35).

The relationship between the editorial and publishing community and the Ministry was largely one-directional: journals were required to comply with the Ministry's criteria to secure funding. This system had two key positive outcomes. First, it provided a relatively stable, though sometimes limited, source of public funding that supported the sustainability of publishing operations. Second, as OA was a condition for funding, the vast majority of Croatian journals embraced OA as their preferred publishing model.

After the adoption of the new regulations, direct subsidies to journals were discontinued. Instead, funding for journals published by research performing organisations (RPOs) is now incorporated into the overall funding allocated to these institutions. The new system requires different planning approaches and is

⁷⁹ Croatian DOI Office (DOI-HR): <https://nsk.hr/nakladnici/hrvatski-ured-za-doi/>

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particularly challenging for journals that previously received substantial public funding through public calls and institutions publishing multiple journals.

The publishing activities of learned societies are supported through dedicated subsidy calls that cover their broader activities. Institutions that do not fall into the category of RPOs or learned societies, such as the Croatian Academy of Arts and Sciences, which publish a substantial number of journals, are no longer eligible for any public subsidies for publishing (Taşkın et al. 2024, 30–46).

Scholarly book publishing relies on a diverse range of funding sources. The Ministry of Science and Education continues to provide subsidies for completed and peer-reviewed books through annual calls, though this responsibility is expected to shift to RPOs. Public support may also come from the Ministry of Culture, while additional funding is often secured through sponsors or project-based resources. Scholarly books are sometimes published in collaboration with commercial publishers, and in this case, it is usually difficult to ensure OA.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

There are no formal financial or non-financial rewards (e.g., career or award-based incentives) for involvement in Diamond OA publishing.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

The central infrastructure for Open Access journal publishing in Croatia is the HRČAK Portal of Croatian Scientific and Professional Journals⁸⁰, established in 2006 and offered free of charge to local journals (Stojanovski, Petrak, and Macan 2009). It was created as a community-led initiative by the Croatian Information Society and its OA working group, with technical development by the University of Zagreb Computing Centre (Srce), which continues to maintain and support the platform. HRČAK has provided many print-only journals with an affordable way to move online and adopt OA. Today, all journals (556 titles in June 2025, 420 of which are active)⁸¹ on the platform are OA. The platform has an Advisory Board composed of journal editors, library professionals, and a representative of the Ministry of Science and Education.⁸²

University of Zagreb Computing Centre - Srce is also providing central national platforms based on Open Journals Systems⁸³ (86 journals are hosted in June 2025)

⁸⁰ HRČAK Portal of Croatian Scientific and Professional Journals: <https://hrcak.srce.hr/>

⁸¹ HRČAK: https://hrcak.srce.hr/popis_casopisa/abecedno

⁸² HRČAK: <https://hrcak.srce.hr/en/savjet-hrcka>

⁸³ National platforms based on Open Journals Systems: <https://hrcak.srce.hr/ojs/>

and Open Monograph Press⁸⁴ (for conference proceedings). However, many journals continue to use their own custom-made websites or independent OJS installations or rely on commercial hosting services. Due to this, it is not uncommon for Croatian journals to be available on multiple platforms (e.g. on Hrčak and on an institutional platform or an independent website).

Three institutional presses have established their own Open Access book platforms based on PKP's OMP software: MorePress⁸⁵ at the University of Zadar (122 titles), FF Open Press⁸⁶ at the University of Zagreb Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences (166 titles) and FFOS e-naklada⁸⁷ at the University of Osijek (42 titles).⁸⁸ OMP is used only for content display, while the submission and peer review procedures are managed manually outside the platforms and the organisational units managing them, partly due to OMP's limitations. Book publishing still faces many technical challenges. For example, the stable OMP versions used do not support landing pages for book chapters.

The national network of repositories, DABAR (Digital Academic Archives and Repositories), comprising 185 repositories, also plays a role in Diamond OA book publishing. It was initiated by five institutions, which form the governing body, while Srce is responsible for IT development. Some institutions publish their Open Access books through repositories rather than dedicated publishing platforms. The University of Zagreb Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences also deposits all books in the institutional repository to ensure better visibility

The infrastructures mentioned above (Hrčak, Hrčak-OJS, Hrčak-OMP, Dabar) are publicly funded, publicly governed, and available free of charge to institutions and journal publishers.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Croatian scholarly journals are typically published by public and not-for-profit organisations – including academic institutions (10 public and four private universities, as well as 13 public and 18 private colleges), public research institutes (25) (“Politika otvorene znanosti u Hrvatskoj – Otvorena znanost u Hrvatskoj” 2025), learned societies, and other public bodies. Only a small number of publishers are

⁸⁴ Open Monograph Press: <https://hrcak.srce.hr/omp/>

⁸⁵ MorePress: https://morepress.unizd.hr/index_en.php

⁸⁶ FF Open Press: <https://openbooks.ffzg.unizg.hr/>

⁸⁷ FFOS e-naklada: <https://naklada.ffos.hr/knjige/>

⁸⁸ [MorePress](#) is managed by a dedicated publishing office, while [FF Open Press](#) is managed by the library.

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professional private companies, usually small or medium-sized enterprises. There are no large commercial journal publishers in Croatia. However, some institutional publishers collaborate with major international companies to publish their journals.

OA books in Croatia are predominantly published by non-commercial entities such as universities, scholarly societies, and research institutes. In 2023, Croatian scholarly institutions launched an Initiative to support a sustainable and future-oriented system for scholarly book publishing. The signatories (University of Zagreb Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences; University of Zadar, University of Rijeka; The Miroslav Krleža Institute of Lexicography; The Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences of the Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek) have committed to ensuring visibility, OA, and international quality standards in publishing. The Initiative's goals include creating a community of practice, developing shared open infrastructure for OA and preservation, securing financial support for sustainable publishing, and providing professional and technological assistance ("Croatian Initiative for Open Scholarly Books" 2023).

Workforce and Capacity Development

Editorial services are provided mainly on a voluntary or in-kind basis, while production and IT services are largely outsourced. Even in organisations with dedicated publishing staff, challenges remain, including understaffing, shortages of qualified personnel, and difficulties with staff retention.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Collaboration among Croatian journal editors has traditionally been strong, primarily organised through an association of editors. Croatian Association for Scholarly Communication ZNAK (CROASC)⁸⁹ is involved in discussions about journal evaluation criteria and it collaborates with the National and University Library to support journal indexation in major international databases and works with Srce to improve publishing workflows within the national infrastructure. It also fosters the sharing of best practices through meetings and webinars.

There are also cases of sharing locally developed tools – for instance, a custom-built submission system created for one journal is now used by others for a small fee.

⁸⁹ Croatian Association for Scholarly Communication ZNAK (CROASC):
<https://www.znak.hr/index.php/en/>

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

While the Croatian Open Science Plan does not explicitly address support for Diamond OA publishing, it places significant emphasis on the sustainability and development of centralised, non-profit infrastructure for scholarly publishing, such as Hrčak. This type of coordinated, open, and interoperable platform, supported through national policies and institutions like Srce, can play a crucial role in advancing the adoption of the Diamond Open Access standard and promoting best practices in scholarly publishing.

This national infrastructure has long worked hand-in-hand with a system of public funding to support Diamond OA journals in Croatia. While the changing of the funding system could lead to disruptions in the publishing system (e.g. moves towards commercial publishing and introducing APCs), the Diamond model will probably remain dominant, as it is very important for small scholarly communities, especially for journals that publish in the national language or focus on topics important for the country. The change in funding could also have some positive effects, such as encouraging institutions to take better care of their journals.

Literature data and information collected through conversations with relevant actors underline the need for public policies and funding models that encourage or mandate OA and support the adoption of international standards.

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ESTONIA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Estonia has a relatively high number of Diamond OA journals, particularly within universities and research institutions. Most are hosted on institutional platforms, such as the OJS platform operated by the University of Tartu (UT) Library. Despite this active landscape, there is no national strategy or dedicated policy for Diamond OA publishing. Most initiatives are bottom-up and depend on internal resources and voluntary work. Collaboration between institutions (e.g., UT, Tallinn University, Estonian Academy of Sciences) is growing, but national coordination remains lacking.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

Estonia does not currently have a national policy or legal framework specifically focused on Diamond OA publishing. However, Open Science is briefly referenced in national-level documents such as the *Estonian Research and Development, Innovation and Entrepreneurship Strategy*, and institutions are expected to promote OA in general. Currently, Diamond OA publishing is not clearly distinguished from other OA models. This makes it more challenging to plan and support it in a focused manner. If Diamond OA were more clearly included in future Open Science policies or funding plans, it would provide better direction and support for those involved⁹⁰.

⁹⁰ Estonian Research and Development, Innovation and Entrepreneurship Strategy: https://www.hm.ee/sites/default/files/documents/2022-10/taie_arengukava_kinnitatud_15.07.2021_211109a_en_final.pdf

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

There is currently no centralised or long-term funding mechanism dedicated to supporting Diamond OA journals in Estonia. Most journals operate with limited financial support from universities (including libraries and presses), or through project-based funding. The situation is more complicated in the case of monographs. Funding streams are the same; however, in the case of monographs, OA publishing does not receive special funding.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Currently, there are no formal incentives or reward systems in place that encourage researchers to publish in Diamond OA journals or serve as editors or reviewers. While universities value OA in principle, evaluation criteria still prioritise journals with high impact factors or strong international indexing, which may not include many local Diamond OA journals.

Providing funding support or grants specifically for Diamond OA journal development or improvement could be beneficial, in conjunction with offering editorial training and technical support as part of national or institutional services. Encouraging publication in Diamond OA through open science mandates would also incentivise researchers to publish in Diamond OA venues.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Estonia has made good progress in technical infrastructure for Diamond OA. The University of Tartu Library, for instance, operates an OJS platform that hosts 25 scholarly journals (including all publications of the UT Press), with more than 12,000 published articles. This infrastructure is mostly operated institutionally, not nationally.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Within institutions, various institutes support publishing their own journals; however, the funding streams are not sustainable and are provided based on availability.

The University of Tartu Library, for example, offers technical support, platform hosting, and metadata management for several journals. However, the support is often fragmented and depends on internal resource availability.

There is a need for

- ✓ Institutional policies that formally support Diamond OA publishing and

- ✓ Dedicated staff or service units within libraries to manage and develop publishing services.

UT Press is offering OAPEN and DOAB support on demand. UT is also offering DOI registration services (via DataCite and Crossref).

Currently, a cross-institutional cooperation is being discussed for sustainability and innovation (including Tallinn University and the Estonian Academy of Sciences).

Workforce and Capacity Development

Diamond OA (like all other publishing) relies heavily on a dedicated and skilled workforce — editors, reviewers, copyeditors, and technical staff. In Estonia, many of these roles are filled by academics on a voluntary basis or by library staff without additional compensation.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

UT Press and the library are collaborating on publishing, with the library providing OJS infrastructure for all UT Press publications. Additionally, the UT Press maintains a separate collection in the UT institutional repository, ADA. UT Press is also publishing UT PhD Dissertations in a separate collection in the ADA repository.

International networking and collaboration also have a positive impact. For example, three Estonian institutions – UT, Tallinn University and Estonian Academy of Sciences are members of the Association of European University Presses (AEUP). Collaboration encompasses knowledge and best practice sharing, event planning, and advocacy, among other activities.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Quality assurance practices vary widely. While many journals follow peer review standards, there is no unified national framework or guidelines to support quality in Diamond OA publishing.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

To strengthen Diamond OA publishing in Estonia, future efforts should focus on:

- ✓ Setting up a national coordination mechanism or support structure.
- ✓ Integrating Diamond OA publishing into national Open Science policy.
- ✓ Creating a national and/or institutional funding mechanism or shared service model to support Diamond OA publishing with editorial services, metadata

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curation, and platform development. Including non-APC-based publishing as an eligible activity in grant funding schemes.

- ✓ Recognising Diamond OA publishing in research evaluation. Embedding Diamond OA publishing in the performance evaluation frameworks of institutions and individuals.
- ✓ Providing long-term shared infrastructure and editorial services support, especially for platforms like OJS and tools for workflow automation and quality assurance.
- ✓ Encouraging researcher and editorial participation.
- ✓ Strengthening collaboration between institutions and international initiatives on Diamond OA infrastructure, metadata, and metrics to improve interoperability and visibility.

Practical steps could include:

- ✓ Mapping the current Diamond OA landscape in Estonia (journals, platforms, hosts, disciplines).
- ✓ Establishing a national working group on Diamond OA publishing to bring together key stakeholders (universities, libraries, Research Council).
- ✓ Providing shared services for publishing support through libraries or consortia.
- ✓ Developing quality guidelines and sustainability criteria for Diamond OA journals.

Leadership could come from the Estonian Research Council, in collaboration with university libraries, the Estonian Academy of Sciences, and higher educational institutions.

Each stakeholder has a key role to play:

- ✓ Libraries can provide shared platforms, metadata curation, and infrastructure (e.g., hosting OJS journals).
- ✓ Universities and research institutions can ensure editorial support, staff time, and incentives for publishing in Diamond OA journals.
- ✓ Agencies and Ministries can establish supportive policies and strategic funding.

At the international level, Estonia should aim to participate in collaborative infrastructure projects, such as the European Diamond Capacity Hub or international OJS communities. International networking and collaboration (like AEUP) can advance Diamond OA publishing in Estonia.

FINLAND

Author⁹¹: Mikael Laakso

1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

A thorough study of the peer-reviewed journal landscape in Finland is provided by Linna et al. (2020). The study found that of the 336 peer-reviewed journals identified, 53% were publishing immediate OA, with a further 6% as delayed OA, and 2% of journals offering a hybrid OA option. Diamond OA is the dominant model of OA publishing among journals, with the study identifying only seven journals in the country that charge an APC. This distinctive characteristic of scholarly publishing in Finland is largely due to learned societies publishing around 70% of all publication channels (journals, book series, conference series), and dominantly so in the fields of humanities and social sciences, with commercial publishers only publishing under 3% of Finnish journals and books (Late et al., 2020). Compared to the development in many other European countries, there has not been any significant move towards involving commercial publishers in the activities of scholarly societies; rather, these functions are often managed within the institution itself. From an international perspective, the Finnish landscape of learned societies is highly coordinated with a robust national umbrella organisation, the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV). This furthers the common interests and practices of learned societies in many ways. TSV not only gives the community of learned societies a strong, unified voice when it comes to policymaking, but it also delivers centralised technical services and distributes public funding to publishing learned societies.

⁹¹ This is an updated and modified text from Taşkın, Z., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Laakso, M., Torný, D., Arasteh, S., Bargheer, M., Klaus, T., Schima, J., Agnoloni, T., Peruginelli, G., Davidson, A., Franczak, M., Coslado Bernabé, M. A., de Pablo Llorente, V., Dobson, H., & Heyman, J. (2024). D5.2 National overviews on sustaining institutional publishing in Europe. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683953>

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Based on a scan of journal start years for journals included in Ulrichsweb, a handful of Finnish journals are over 100 years old, with an average age of slightly over 20 years. While Late et al. (2020) found that learned societies are the main publishers of journals, commercial publishers and university presses are most prevalent when it comes to book publishing. Finland has contributed to the trend of internationally oriented OA university presses, with the two largest universities in the country operating such functions: Helsinki University Press and Tampere University Press.

The national journal platform journal.fi⁹² is the key OA infrastructure. Its development took place between 2015-2016 via the Kotilava Project (kotilava.fi, 2016), a joint effort by TSV and the National Library of Finland to support Finnish scholarly journals in their transition to immediate Open Access. The two main goals of the Kotilava Project, as outlined in a 2014 report *Finnish Scientific Journals and Open Publishing: A Study of Possible Funding Models* (in Finnish), were 1) to develop an OJS platform for editing and publishing OA journals, and 2) to create a new consortium-based funding model for Finnish OA journals. While the project resulted in the launch of the [Journal.fi](http://journal.fi) platform, a sustainable collective OA funding model has not been established despite continuous effort. There have been other attempts at coordinating collective funding models targeted to Finnish OA journals since then; however, no such attempts have resulted in consensus among stakeholders so that they could be put into practice.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

The highest governmental body responsible for overseeing the higher education sector in the country, the Ministry of Education and Culture, distributes funding to higher education institutions from the government's budget based on a performance-based funding model. The current funding model for Finnish higher education institutions incentivises Open Access research publications (journal articles as well as books), providing institutions with 20% extra funding for each peer-reviewed publication that is OA (including gold, hybrid, and green).

Open science has been a tangible part of science policy in Finland over the last decade, and Finland has a distinctively open and participatory approach to formulating and updating official science policy documents. From 2014 to 2017, the Ministry of Education and Culture ran a programme called the "Open Science and Research Initiative", which promoted Finnish open science in extensive

⁹² Finnish Scholarly Journals Online Platform : <http://journal.fi>

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cooperation between ministries, universities, research institutes and research funders. Finland has had a dedicated staffing for national-level coordination of open science since 2019, funded by the Ministry of Education and Culture and having its secretariat at TSV. This connects the activities closer to supporting functions operated by TSV, such as managing the national publication platforms journal.fi and edition.fi, as well as managing the public funding programme for Finnish non-profit journals. Here, a steering group exists under which working groups are open to anyone in the scholarly community, and draft documents are prepared openly. Frequent open consultations gather feedback broadly before documents are finalised. In 2019, a national policy and executive plan on OA to scholarly publications was published (Open Science Coordination in Finland, Federation of Finnish Learned Societies 2019) as part of the first work done within this coordination. This national policy on Open Access publishing has been in place since 2020, calling for full Open Access to journal articles. This policy has impacted the environment for scholarly publishers active in the country, as all universities are committed to it and strive to ensure as high a share of Open Access publications as possible.

For several years, there have been ongoing discussions about whether and how secondary publishing rights could enable universal self-archiving rights for Finnish authors. The most formal of these was a report commissioned by the Ministry of Education and Culture in 2017, which concluded that the current legislation does not enable such rights but that, through amendments, these rights could be achieved (Mansala, 2017). [1]^[ML2] Recently Finnish universities have been exploring options to implement rights retention to cover all outputs of their faculty and staff (blogs.helsinki.fi 2025), and it looks likely that some practical policies will be rolled out in 2026.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Concerning funding directed at journals, Finland has a relatively unique public funding system for supporting non-profit peer reviewed journal publishing. It is one of the most inclusive in Europe (Laakso & Multas, 2023). Any peer-reviewed journal can apply for a public funding subsidy that is distributed by TSV. In addition to this governmental funding, which provides some basic income in case of deficit, there have long been both formal and informal negotiations for developing a new funding model particularly suited to the circumstances of Diamond OA journals where there might be very little other income to support publication activities. Any Finnish peer-reviewed non-profit journals can apply for publicly funded subsidy distributed by TSV, but the funding principles are not fully aligned with the principles of Diamond

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OA publishing since the funding requires that the journal also has other monetary income. This is hard to generate if subscription fees and APCs are off the table. The public subsidy funding model does not allow for any financial buffers as it only covers deficits, many journals operate on thin margins and could face serious difficulties if public subsidies were ever reduced or interrupted or stopped.

The Finnish Association for Scholarly Publishing is the primary interest organisation for scholarly publishers in Finland, representing approximately 150 member organisations that are all involved in academic publishing. Through funds collected from national copyright agreements with the public and higher education sectors, the association supports development projects of publishers in the country through competitive funding rounds. In the last three years, they have also issued grants that scholarly publishers can use for any purpose they see fit to support their activities (given to any eligible application, of approximately a couple of thousand euros per grant) A current and future challenge for the continued existence of this financial support for publishers is that the collective copyright fees that are generated to be distributed by the Finnish Association for Scholarly Publishing onwards to publishers stems only from materials that the member organisations publish that is not Creative Commons licensed. With the growth in popularity among publishers to apply CC-licenses other income streams would be needed to compensate for this reduction

The primary sources of income for many Diamond OA journals in Finland stem from a combination of the TSV subsidy and the annual grant from the Finnish Association for Scholarly Publishing.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

During the last three years, the Ministry of Education and Culture has allocated a couple of thousands of euros extra for each Diamond OA journal in extra funding that can be applied for to cover deficits. It is unclear as to how long this practice will continue. Aside from this sporadic funding, there have been no direct financial incentives for journals in Finland to pursue Diamond OA publishing, yet many continue to do so nonetheless.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

The national journal platform based on OJS has been hosted by TSV at Journal.fi since 2015 (Pölonen, Syrjämäki et al., 2021). In 2023, 140 journals were published on the platform. It is possible for any peer-reviewed journal published in Finland to use the platform, but the journal has to be at least delayed OA to be eligible, thus incentivising journals to adopt that level of openness at a minimum. The platform is

free for TSV member societies, and a nominal fee is charged from other publishers. There is also a similar service for the publication of OA books based on OMP, Edition.fi, which launched in 2020 and currently has 16 publishers providing content on the platform.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Zacharewicz et al. (2019) provides a review of the presence and composition of such schemes in Europe, where Finland's model was also included and compared to other similar models. The performance-based allocation model has included a component that takes into account the quantity and quality of individual publications and their Open Access status (as based on the publication outlets placement in the national publication classification scheme managed by the national Publication Forum (Julkaisufoorumi), thus creating (at least on the institutional level, incentives to publish as much as possible in as highly ranked publication channels as possible, and making sure that the full-texts are available OA through some mechanism.

Workforce and Capacity Development

This is currently very distributed among the Diamond OA publishers in Finland, where the main centrality is provided by the journal.fi⁹³ technical platform, but where most publishers and journals take care of all other publishing-related activities in-house through internal means which are often volunteer or in-kind based. There are interest and demand for service providers that could provide assistance with copyediting and managing the technical aspects of the publication process, but so far there is no actor with substantial presence in this space.

Journal.fi and edition.fi have both managed to become established as the de-facto national platforms for OA journals and books respectively, which ensures a certain level of minimum technical implementation among the majority of scholarly publishing outlets in Finland. A further challenge is for publishers who use the platforms to leverage their functionalities to their full extent (e.g. XML publishing, comprehensive use of persistent identifiers, open references deposit) and for that it would be useful if there would be more collaboration and service providers to assist with these steps.

⁹³ Finnish Scholarly Journals Online Platform : <http://journal.fi>

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Publication Forum is a classification of publication channels created by the Finnish scientific community used since 2015 to support the quality assessment of academic research, inspired by the Norwegian Register for Scientific Journals. The evaluation of individual publication channels, both international and domestic, is performed by 23 discipline-specific Expert Panels composed of some 300 distinguished Finnish or Finland-based scholars who place publication channels into one of four levels for which the two highest ones have limited quotas within each discipline-specific category (1 = basic level, 2 = leading level, 3 = highest level, 0 = publication channels that don't meet the criteria for level 1). The ranking of publication channels is integrated into the funding model of universities, so that publications made at the higher levels significantly increase the amount of funding the institution receives per publication compared to 0 and 1 level publications.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Creating a national journal funding model that would align the principles of Diamond OA has been a long-standing topic, where there have been different initiatives ongoing for close to 10 years without reaching a model that would satisfy all central stakeholders. A consortium of Finnish journals was being built up in 2016 with an associated funding model (kotilava.fi, 2016), however, in the final stages of preparations the negotiations for its adoption were abandoned. After some years of silence following the collapse of this model, in 2022 a working-group associated with the National Open Science Coordination published a document titled “Proposals for New Supplementary Funding Models for Domestic Scientific Periodicals to Enable Immediate Openness: Final Report of the Working Group Appointed by the National Steering Group for Open Science and Research” which presented different alternative models for achieving higher OA for domestic journals (in Finnish). Based on this review of alternative models that could be considered by the scholarly community in Finland, in 2023 a working-group under TSV published a “Proposal for the Funding of Open Domestic Scientific Journals” (in Finnish) that was a refinement of the consortium model presented earlier in 2016 as part of the Kotilava Project. Negotiations around refining the proposal and what an actual model that everyone could agree with are still ongoing at the moment. One challenge with a consortium model that weights billing to consortia members based on publication activity is the low number of universities overall in Finland. Even within that group, the volume of publications produced is heavily skewed towards a few big institutions, creating a substantial change in costs for them

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(compared to the subscription-based models) unless substantial supplementary funding for the model is added by other actors. How research funders should get financially involved in funding models like this has also been a question mark, with no accepted solution so far.

Concerning the situation of OA support and requirements of Finnish research funders, the situation is highly supportive of OA in general, but not in any way specifically for facilitating the sustainability of Diamond OA publishing. The Research Council of Finland is a member of cOAlition S and thus has well-defined requirements for how grantees should make their research outputs available Open Access. The second-largest funder, Kone Foundation, recommends making works available OA and does allow for costs of OA publishing (excluding hybrid OA journals) to be included in project budgets. The rest of the private foundations funding research do commonly not have Open Access requirements but do allow for costs of OA to be included in the project budgets similarly to Kone Foundation.

Finland has an overall strong common direction for furthering open science and OA as an integral part of it. The country has a vibrant environment of institutional publishers, which are dominantly scholarly societies publishing a single journal each. These publishers are already to a large degree functioning on the principles of Diamond OA publishing, where an enabling success factor is the centralised technical services and public funding support distribution provided by the umbrella organisation TSV. The current level of public funding available to institutional publishers is relatively low, yet many publishers are entirely reliant on it as their main source of income, and there have been years of work and negotiation between stakeholders to develop a supplementary funding model, however, that work has not yet garnered tangible results.

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FRANCE

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

France boasts a rich and influential history in academic publishing, notably as the birthplace of the first scientific journal, *Le Journal des Sçavans* (1665). Over the 19th and 20th centuries, a highly fragmented publishing scene emerged, with thousands of journals but without dominant commercial or university press publishers as in other countries. This fragmentation had long-term consequences: STEM publishing experienced consolidation and acquisitions, with houses like Masson (medical journals) absorbed by Elsevier (2005) and EDP Sciences acquired by China Science Publishing and Media (2019). By contrast, the humanities and social sciences (HSS) retained a dispersed publishing landscape.

The digital era transformed this system. In HSS, two major platforms now dominate: OpenEdition Journals (established as Revues.org in 1999, renamed 2017) which follows a Diamond model, and Cairn.info (founded 2005), operating primarily on subscriptions with partial free access. Both expanded into books in the 2010s, partnering with university presses (OpenEdition) or private publishers (Cairn). Alongside them, Persée (2004) digitises and disseminates back catalogues (now over one million documents), while STEM disciplines benefit from infrastructures like the Centre Mersenne (maths, computer science) and Épisciences (overlay journals). Newer initiatives such as Peer Community In/Peer Community Journal showcase open peer review in Diamond form. Increasingly, universities have launched incubators and publishing services (e.g., Bordeaux's Open U, Paris-Cité's OPUS), federated by the REPERES network.

⁹⁴ This is an updated and modified text from Taşkın, Z., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Laakso, M., Torný, D., Arasteh, S., Bargheer, M., Klaus, T., Schima, J., Agnoloni, T., Peruginelli, G., Davidson, A., Franczak, Coslado Bernabé, M.A., de Pablo Llorente, V., Dobson, H., & Heyman, J. (2024). D5.2 National overviews on sustaining institutional publishing in Europe. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683953>

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A distinctive feature is France's reliance on HTML/XML publishing infrastructures rather than OJS, giving platforms strong control over workflows and metadata. As a result, international commercial publishers play only a minor role in domestic journal publishing, though they remain dominant in subscriptions. France spends around €90m annually on subscriptions and €30m on APCs, managed mainly through Couperin, the national library consortium. Until recently, transformative “publish and read” deals were rare, but in 2024 Elsevier signed a national licence, followed by agreements with Wiley, Springer Nature, and Cambridge.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

French open-access policy rests on a set of national laws, plans, and institutional practices that collectively support Diamond OA and nonprofit infrastructures. The Digital Republic Act of 2016 guaranteed authors the right to self-archive their work regardless of publisher contracts, setting maximum embargoes of six months for STEM fields and twelve months for HSS for publicly funded research. The two National Plans for Open Science, covering 2018–2021 and 2021–2024, committed the country to achieving full open access by 2030. These plans emphasised the development of Diamond OA and public infrastructures, created dedicated governance mechanisms such as the Committee for Open Science (CoSO), and promoted APC-free publishing models. The Research Programming Law of 2020 integrated open science into the formal missions of research institutions, justifying sustained investment in national infrastructures like HAL and Recherche Data Gouv and aligning incentives with Diamond publishing routes. Most universities and research organisations encourage or require deposit in HAL and favour open-access outputs in their internal assessment processes, contributing to the high level of participation; CNRS researchers alone deposit around 95 percent of their roughly twenty thousand annual publications.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Funding and sustainability strategies further reinforce this environment. The National Open Science Fund (FNSO) issues regular calls that support Diamond journals, book series, and shared infrastructures, including international initiatives such as SciPost. These programmes finance editorial upgrades, professionalisation, multilingual features, accessibility improvements, and core community-governed platforms such as identifiers, metadata services, and indexes. CNRS and universities complement these resources with direct subsidies, staff time, and technical infrastructure for services such as HAL/CCSD, OpenEdition, Persée, the Centre Mersenne, and Épisciences. Additional co-funding comes from regional bodies, research organisations, and library consortia like Couperin, which also supports OpenEdition through its freemium model. Hybrid platform-level revenue models, for instance OpenEdition's freemium access to PDFs and EPUBs combined with free HTML access, ensure that the Diamond principle of no author-side fees remains intact while securing financial stability. International open-science services also receive support through collective contributions via Couperin and SCOSS.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Incentive and recognition mechanisms consolidate these policies. The national funder ANR monitors compliance with its open-access requirements through an Open Science Barometer and recognises deposits in HAL. It also contributes to FNSO calls that favour Diamond publishing. Reform of research assessment practices has aligned France with the CoARA principles, reducing reliance on journal prestige metrics and placing stronger emphasis on openness and quality. This shift has significantly improved the standing of scholar-led and Diamond journals. Monitoring tools such as the French Open Science Barometer (BSO) track progress at national scale; open-access rates rose from 38 percent in 2018 to roughly 67 percent in 2024, with HAL accounting for about half of all openly available publications.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

A network of infrastructures underpins this system. HAL provides preservation, dissemination, and integration with ORCID, DOIs, and institutional workflows at no cost to authors. OpenEdition offers end-to-end publishing services for journals and books with strong multilingual and preservation capacities. Persée secures access to backfiles, while Épisciences supports overlay journals based on repositories such as HAL, arXiv, and Zenodo. The Centre Mersenne supports scholar-led STEM

journals by offering professional services within a Diamond model. Mir@bel aggregates and standardises journal information, making policy compliance and discovery easier. Recherche Data Gouv constitutes the national infrastructure for open research data, linking article-based workflows with datasets and code.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Institutions play a significant role in governance and operations. University presses and editorial incubators manage journal hosting, workflows, and training at campus level. Libraries operate many of the underlying services, including DOI registration, copy editing, accessibility review, and the administration of publishing platforms. Research organisations such as CNRS, universities, INRAE, and Inria help to fund and operate key national infrastructures and provide engineering and editorial staff. The Ministry has also brought together an alliance of 99 public scientific publishers—including university presses and research-organisation imprints—that collectively produce around 1,800 books and 430 journals each year with a workforce of 650 full-time equivalents.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Capacity development is another crucial component of the French model. Most Diamond journals function through a combination of academic volunteers and small professional teams working on management, production, and platform engineering. FNSO calls directly address the need for professionalisation and skill-building. Competence networks such as CoSO task forces, OPERAS working groups, and Recherche Data Gouv centres disseminate training on workflows, metadata standards, accessibility, and multilingualism. Assessment reform has begun to acknowledge editorial and infrastructure contributions in academic careers, and institutions are formalising new roles in research data management, scholarly communication, and publishing engineering.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Collaboration between publishers and service providers is facilitated by shared national platforms that avoid duplication and achieve economies of scale. Interconnections between systems, such as overlays between HAL and Épisciences or metadata exchange between Mir@bel and Open Policy Finder, further strengthen the ecosystem. These infrastructures integrate seamlessly with ORCID, DOAJ, DOAB, Crossref, and DataCite, while participation in OPERAS links French initiatives to European efforts such as DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA. Library consortia, particularly Couperin, contribute predictable support to platform sustainability while preserving zero author-side charges.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Quality assurance is reinforced by community-driven peer review, transparent editorial policies, and the spread of open-peer-review models such as those used by Peer Community In. Discoverability is supported by inclusion in indexes such as DOAJ and DOAB and by systematic use of persistent identifiers. Editorial ethics and standards follow COPE guidance, emphasise accessibility and localisation, and rely on machine-readable metadata. National evaluation bodies, including HCERES, have incorporated open-science criteria into assessments of research units and programmes, strengthening compliance.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Several future measures could further consolidate France's Diamond OA ecosystem. Stable, baseline funding for national infrastructures such as HAL, OpenEdition, Persée, the Centre Mersenne, and Épisciences would anchor long-term planning. Regional editorial hubs could offer shared services such as XML production, accessibility auditing, and copy editing for smaller journals. Academic evaluation processes could more fully recognise editorial labour by valuing reviewing and editing activities and by expanding training and certification opportunities. Technical quality could be enhanced by broader adoption of JATS/XML, open citations, and open peer-review systems. Financial reinvestment strategies could redirect savings from constrained APC and hybrid-journal expenditure into Diamond infrastructures and further expand collective library funding models. Internationalisation efforts might support multilingual metadata, translation services, and deeper cooperation through OPERAS and European projects like DIAMAS, CRAFT-OA, and ALMASI. Strengthening connections between publications, datasets, and code via Recherche Data Gouv would improve reproducibility and open workflows. Finally, monitoring tools such as the Open Science Monitor could be expanded to track Diamond-specific indicators including staffing levels, costs, quality measures, and accessibility standards.

Future measures could strengthen France's Diamond OA landscape:

- ✓ Stabilise funding: Provide baseline grants for national infrastructures (HAL, OpenEdition, Persée, Mersenne, Épisciences).
- ✓ Editorial hubs: Regional centres offering shared services (XML, accessibility, copy-editing) for small journals.
- ✓ Recognition of editorial labour: Include reviewing/editing in academic assessments; develop training and certification.

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- ✓ Technical quality: Incentivise adoption of JATS/XML, open citations, and open peer review.
- ✓ Reinvestment strategies: Redirect savings from capped APC/hybrid spending into Diamond infrastructures; expand library collective models.
- ✓ Internationalisation: Support multilingual metadata, translation, and European cooperation via OPERAS Research Infrastructure, and dedicated EU projects such as DIAMAS, CRAFT-OA and ALMASI.
- ✓ Integration of data/code: Link publications to datasets in Recherche Data Gouv and code repositories.
- ✓ Monitoring: Expand the Open Science Monitor to track Diamond-specific indicators (staffing, costs, quality, accessibility).

Conclusion

The French system combines historical fragmentation with strong public policy and infrastructure, making Diamond OA central to national open science strategy. While underfunded relative to commercial subscriptions, its collaborative platforms, institutional support, and clear policy direction provide a robust base for future growth.

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Image 4: Higher Education in Germany Statistics. Source: Federal Statistical Office of Germany.

⁹⁵ This is an updated and modified text from Taşkın, Z., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Laakso, M., Torny, D., Arasteh, S., Bargheer, M., Klaus, T., Schima, J., Agnoloni, T., Peruginelli, G., Davidson, A., Franczak, M., Coslado Bernabé M.A., de Pablo Llorente, V., Dobson, H., & Heyman, J. (2024). D5.2 National overviews on sustaining institutional publishing in Europe. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683953>. This update covers significant policy changes initiated by the German parliament elected in 2025 as well as some updates in publication numbers. Germany's federal structure means there are only a few organisations with national scope that can effectively support top-down initiatives. Because this makes it challenging to promote Diamond OA on a large scale, this overview puts an emphasis on identifying opportunities for positive intervention.

Background Information on the organisational level

Notably, Germany (along with the UK, and the Netherlands) stands out within Europe for its high numbers and relative shares of large publisher journals, especially from the commercial sector. Springer Nature has registered offices for some of its company branches in Germany, De Gruyter and CH.Beck are other large German publishers. DEAL and transformative agreements have been the main drivers for the significant growth of OA output in the last years. Funding initiatives dedicated to scholarly publishing continue to have a monetary focus on the transformation to OA.

Currently, 13.8% (7343) of 53,210 academic journals considered in the German Open Access Monitor⁹⁶ operate in the Diamond OA business model (Gold: 33.6%; Closed/Hybrid 36%; Transformation Contract 16.6%). In the last five years (1/1/2019 - 9/13/2023), 2.3% (17,639) of 766,911 journal articles were published in Diamond OA (OA monitor). Drilled down to the German situation, the actual numbers show the following picture. The period of 2021 to 2025 shows 803,772 articles⁹⁷ and an Open Access ratio of 67,5%, including all variants of OA. The Diamond OA ratio is 3.1%, meaning 24,917 articles over the observed period, resulting in an average of 445 German Diamond OA articles per month. The actual number of German Diamond OA journals is currently being assessed, especially since previous landscaping activities couldn't use the definitions for Diamond OA journals developed in the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA project, i.e. the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) and the operational six criteria for Diamond OA journals. The number is estimated between 298 (DOAG) and 350 (preliminary count from the launch phase of the Diamond Discovery Hub).

Most likely, the disciplinary distribution of Diamond OA journals continues to follow the one identified in the DOAG panel that revealed a substantial number of Diamond OA journals in the social sciences and humanities, and limited adoption in other fields: more than 70% of the Diamond OA journals were either assigned to the social sciences or the humanities. Natural sciences contributed 13% of Diamond OA journals, while the numbers in Engineering & Technology, Medical Sciences, and Agricultural Sciences were negligible.

To measure the quantitative impact of Diamond OA, the number of journals needs to be complemented by taking into account the size of its publisher and the number of published articles per journal. Stephen and Stahlschmidt 2022 proposed a

⁹⁶ German Open Access Monitor: <https://open-access-monitor.de/>

⁹⁷ German articles defined as articles with authors from German ROPs or in German journals.

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definition of small and very small publisher, a) very small publishers producing one journal per year and not more than 102 articles per year, b) small publishers producing two to five journals per year and not more than 240 articles per year across all journals and c) rather small publishers producing six to ten journals per year and not more than 240 articles per year across all journals. With this definition, most German Diamond OA journals belong to the sector of small publishers a-c.

A majority of nearly 58% in the DOAG panel were published by a research institution, which includes universities but also the large variety of non-university research institutions in Germany. Due to the stricter Diamond OA criteria developed in DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA, the actual number of Diamond OA journals from commercial publishing houses will be significantly lower than in the DOAG panel, bringing up the ratio from the institutional and academic sector.

For text-oriented disciplines such as the humanities, parts of social sciences and peripheral communities in the natural sciences, small and medium-sized book publishers with a high reputation in their specialist areas continue to play an important role. Authors, editors and their presses often have cautious or critical attitudes towards OA, content creators also still lag behind due to research assessments cultures, publishers often due to the required technical investment risks or scale-dependent deficits when setting up new workflows of content production and dissemination.

In contrast to scientific journals, print editions of books continue to be important despite generally declining sales figures and are also desired by authors. This wouldn't necessarily be an obstacle to introducing Diamond OA for books. However, OA for books in general is not yet as formalised, standardised and acknowledged as journal article publishing, making it even more challenging for OA book publishers to develop sustainable Diamond OA models. Exceptions are nevertheless there. Language Science Press⁹⁸ has established a crowdfunding model that allows the press to offer book publishing without mandatory author-facing charges.

⁹⁸ Language Science Press launched in 2013 as a born-digital scholar-led Open Access publisher in linguistics and operates with a platinum/Diamond OA business model. <https://langsci-press.org/forAuthors>

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

Formulated in reaction to the experiences of the national-socialist regime, Germany's constitution, called "Grundgesetz", puts specific emphasis on the freedom of research⁹⁹ and teaching. Any policy or legal framework attempting to drive scientists into a specific publishing behaviour – such as having to publish OA or trying to incentivise Diamond OA – is measured against the binding article 5 GG. Therefore, German policies tend to either regulate publishing decisions through funding rules (exercised by the DFG or the respective science ministries on the federal and state level) or through employment contracts and institutional codes of conduct. Until now, there is no national strategy or policy in place that could serve as a national guardrail encouraging German states, research organisations or scientific institutions to align their policies nationally. While the previous federal ministry BMBF¹⁰⁰ supported a joint strategy of the federal and state governments. It stated, "Publicly funded scientific findings should, in principle, be freely accessible. The increasing commercialisation of publicly funded scientific publications must therefore be specifically countered. The Federal Government and the Länder recognise the diversity of the scientific publishing system in Germany and acknowledge the important role played by small and medium-sized scientific publishers". The current federal ministry BMFT¹⁰¹ has given no indication that it will continue this course on scientific publishing. The coalition agreement¹⁰² for the 21st legislative period in Germany of CDU, CSU and SPD does not mention open science, citizen science, OA or scientific publishing in any of its political goals. It is therefore unlikely that the given situation will change in the coming years.

While the German states¹⁰³ have strong policies and funding schemes in place that promote OA, Diamond OA has only started to emerge as a desired pathway for more

⁹⁹ Article 5,3 of the Grundgesetz states (3) Art and science, research and teaching are free. Freedom of teaching does not release anyone from loyalty to the Constitution.

¹⁰⁰ Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung, was in place during the coalition of SPD, Bündnis 90/Die Grünen (Green Party) and FDP. Bündnis90/Die Grünen supports Open Access and formulates in their manifesto of principles Chapter 3, (159) "Free, adequately publicly funded research must also be open to society. That is why transparency is needed about how research is financed and which projects and topics are being pursued. The aim of research funding is to gain knowledge. Government-funded research results must be made accessible to society in the spirit of open science."

¹⁰¹ Bundesministerium für Forschung, Technologie und Raumfahrt

¹⁰² <https://www.koalitionsvertrag2025.de/>

¹⁰³ See the Open Access Länderatlas <https://oabb.pubpub.org/oa-atlas> for more details. Examples for practical support and strong OA policies are Baden-Württemberg or Lower Saxony. Lower

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open content and a self-organised publishing system for science and its researchers. The given OA policies of the state have the potential to be used for leveraging Diamond OA and strengthening an institutionally organised Diamond OA publishing system.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Research organisations in Germany are free to use their funds for all models of OA. While the majority of funds to enable OA publications are tied up in transformative agreements and APC payments towards commercial publishers, research organisations fund Diamond OA, nevertheless. For Diamond OA journals, crowdfunding and pledging initiatives are available. Examples are the KOALA¹⁰⁴ consortium program, for which journals can apply in a limited number of the pledging rounds organised by specialised information centres such as the FID - educational research and educational science - with “Diamond Open Access for journals via Crowdfunding”¹⁰⁵ in a BMFTR joint-venture project. These projects open pathways for libraries, as Diamond OA funding can become a routine for German research libraries. However, all pledging and crowdfunding to support Diamond OA requires that content providers, such as journals and publishers, are aware of these options, can become eligible and that potential supporters learn about the funding opportunities and have available funds. The Diamond Funding Navigator¹⁰⁶, a new TIB service, helps tackle these issues by simplifying the financing of Diamond OA.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

As of now, all incentives and rewards for Diamond OA publishing in Germany are rooted in self-organised and voluntary codes of conduct of RPOs or research organisations or within scientific communities embracing open science anyway. Thus, dedicated Diamond OA activities will have – for the time being – to take regional and local or disciplinary- and community-specific frameworks into

Saxony has initiated dedicated activities to strengthen Diamond OA, for example via the recently launched two phase project “NiedersachsenPUBLISHING” <https://www.nds-bibliotheksbeirat.de/niedersachsenpublishing/>

¹⁰⁴ “The KOALA funding model provides fair and sustainable funding for quality-assured APC-free Open Access publications (“Diamond Open Access”). It reduces financial barriers for authors and thus facilitates participation in OA publications.” <https://www.tib.eu/en/services/koala>

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.fachportal-paedagogik.de/en/literatur/produkte/fachinformationsdienst/Diamond-open-access-zeitschriften-durch-crowdfunding.html>

¹⁰⁶ <https://oa.tib.eu/Diamondfunding> “The Diamond Funding Navigator, now available as a beta version, compiles information on offers for the consortial financing of Diamond Open Access publications worldwide. This helps improve the visibility of these offers and makes it easier for academic institutions to decide which offerings they would like to support.”

consideration to develop successful bottom-up activities in place. Top-down approaches will usually require that decision makers are already convinced of open science and Diamond OA as the right way to go.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

A growing number of RPOs and research libraries run publishing services. The working group of university presses and institutional publishing services, called AG Universitätsverlage¹⁰⁷ has 33 members. There are 17 members offering journal publishing in their portfolio, in total resulting in 108 Diamond OA journals¹⁰⁸ of those, currently 50 are listed in DOAJ. Also, several of the specialised information services (so called FID) offer journal platforms for Diamond OA or dedicated backup solutions¹⁰⁹ for scholar-led journals. Acceptance for these platforms varies among disciplines and communities and usually depends on the standing of institutions within the scientific communities served.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

The fact that several of the mentioned university presses and institutional publishing services operate for one or more decades shows that their institutions have been investing in long-term solutions for self-organised OA journals without author-facing charges, long before the term “Diamond OA” emerged. The successful operation of institutional publishing services has contributed to a positive momentum for Diamond OA, on the institutional level and among decision-making bodies in Germany. The current program of the national OA Days 2025 lists several sessions, workshops and individual talks and posters on the topic¹¹⁰ of Diamond OA, namely around financing Diamond OA, tools and technologies, as well as specific use cases. The strategy of the alliance of science organisations mentioned earlier lists four pathways to bring the academic publishing system forward:

1. Evaluating and shaping developments in the dynamic field of academic publishing
 - a. Identification of new types of technical tools for scientific publishing, their evaluation regarding the sovereignty and openness of science and,

¹⁰⁷ AG Universitätsverlage: https://ag-univerlage.de/?page_id=2514

¹⁰⁸ See Krüger, O. et al (2025) for a detailed overview.

¹⁰⁹ For example, the periodical archive on The Stacks, the repository of the Library for Anglo-American Culture and History: <https://thestacks.libaac.de/communities/a1c3ae9d-db9a-4ce9-b013-9b3576d67287>

¹¹⁰ OA Days 2025 individual talks and posters on the Diamond OA topic: <https://www.conftool.org/oat2025/index.php?page=browseSessions&search>

- if necessary, derivation of necessary measures to be taken by the Alliance.
2. Preparation of further negotiations (in particular DEAL)
 - a. Development of criteria for the effectiveness and target dimensions of future DEAL contracts based on the analysis of current DEAL contracts.
 3. Establishment of scholar-led OA infrastructures
 - a. Identification and evaluation of models for joint or distributed financing of permanent, professional, quality-assured publication infrastructures at scientific institutions.
 4. Further measures to promote the OA transformation
 - a. Active lobbying for a reduction in VAT on scientific publishing from 19% to 7%.
 - b. Development and establishment of standards for standardised and efficient publication and cost monitoring at scientific institutions.

Bullet points 3 and 4 require that institutions are willing and able to put measures in place and – even more important – take their communities along to create change on the research assessment level, especially around acknowledgement, reward and incentive. Bullet points 1 and 2 refer to institutional publication funds. The oa.atlas displaying Open Access services¹¹¹ at German RPOs, lists 396 institutions that have journal publication funds and 179 that have monograph publication funds.

Workforce and Capacity Development

The mentioned Alliance report states “... the OA publishing sector, which is not-for-profit and predominantly publicly funded, has become increasingly important in terms of science policy, partly as a result of decisions by the Council of the European Union (2022 and 2023), while in most cases there is a lack of robust or permanent funding options and appropriate recognition of the services provided in the context of the development and provision of these infrastructures.” Until now, decisions on the institutional level to invest personal resources in institutional publishing services and promote Diamond OA publishing offers continue to be voluntary. Budget constraints and budget cuts at German HE institutions hit the publishing services hard. Several members of the AG Universitätsverlage find themselves – sometimes even repeatedly – in the position of having to justify the existence of their publishing services vis-à-vis changing leaders in their institutions or to engage their authors and editors to prove that the offered publishing services

¹¹¹ OA Atlas Open Access Services: <https://open-access.network/services/oaatlas>

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are needed and worth funding. This is unfortunate, especially since these institutional publishing services would be able to immediately enable Diamond OA book publishing for their authors and editors and partially are doing so already.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

So far there are no national backbone infrastructure services for institutional publishing in place that German RPOs can easily use, either due to fiscal obstacles to collaborate across German states or due to the limited disciplinary mandates that the existing central service units such as the specialised libraries or FIDs have. Collaboration exists but is usually organised among players that can build on existing agreements or joint networks. The BMFTR-funded project¹¹² “Diamond Thinking” is a positive example of such a collaboration.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Diamond OA publishing has taken place in several German university presses, in scholar-led journals¹¹³ or as institutional offerings for decades by now. These publishing services adhere to existing standards of quality assurance strategies, expressed, for instance by their uptake in registries such as DOAJ, DOAB, EZB or the Diamond Discovery Hub. Quality concerns around Diamond OA in Germany are often a result of the general preoccupation with legacy publishing and its perceived dominance in research assessment, despite the widely acknowledged observation that the commercialisation of scientific communication is threatening the trust in and integrity of science. On the other hand, concerns often are uttered out of a lack of understanding that scholarly-led and institutional publishing channels aim to live up to the same standards as other scientific publishing services. The fact that several German university libraries offer low threshold journal platforms or repositories for periodicals without quality assurance strategies except for mandatory affiliation to the institution or being within a specific subject scope is sometimes confused with a general lack of quality assurance for institutional publishing.

German institutional publishers engage significantly with existing quality assurance strategies, expressed by their attendance at webinars, talks, workshops and

¹¹² The project Diamond Thinking seeks to establish relevant, high-quality scientific journals for all important disciplines at KIT or to transfer existing commercial journals into the scientific sphere (“flipping”). The aim is to highlight the advantages of reclaiming distribution channels for scientific content for scientific communities. <https://www.bibliothek.kit.edu/Diamond-thinking.php>

¹¹³ The Forum Qualitative Social Research started in 1999 as an APC-free scholar-led and scholar-run journal and has by now turned into the largest international Open Access journal for qualitative methods in social sciences. <https://www.qualitative-research.net/index.php/fqs>

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conferences. The DOAS is widely known, and several German publishing services and journals have assessed the quality of their services with the provided tools.¹¹⁴ The quality standards for OA books that the AG Universitätsverlage is currently preparing for its third iteration are used as a benchmark and in some cases as a requirement¹¹⁵ for funding Open Access books.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Next to the ongoing engagement of Diamond OA practitioners and activists in Germany, two initiatives are worth mentioning as innovative ideas, regardless of whether they can be realised or not. One is the Diamond OA levy that Bernhard Mittermaier¹¹⁶ proposes. He suggests that all consortia taking part in transformative OA agreements should generally commit to a fixed percentage surcharge on individual participation costs and transfer this additional money to a Germany-wide pool for the financing of Diamond OA structures. The main intention behind this proposal is that it raises a substantial amount of reliably calculable funds with the help of established structures and financing channels. Mittermaier acknowledges that there are legal and tax issues, as well as the need to implement adequate governance decision-making structures for the use of funds. Another example is the Leopoldina Academy for Natural Sciences in Germany, which in April 2025 issued a discussion paper on the future of society journals. Accordingly, the authors recommend establishing what is known as a Diamond OA model. The running and the funding of journals that follow this model remain in the hands of expert scientific organisations or institutions that receive a budget for the purpose. This budget allows them to contract service providers in competitive procedures to fulfil certain publication components. Running a journal under the proposed funding system would be based on an application submitted by a scientific society, an academy, or a public institution with a scientific or infrastructural mission. The authors of the paper argue that the evaluation of such applications should follow the criteria

¹¹⁴ Several events bear witness to the engagement of German publishing services with the DOAS: A DOAS-A-THON for the German-speaking community with almost 90 participants was held on the 9th of April 2025, similarly the 2025 meeting of the AG Universitätsverlage has discussed DOAS and its self-assessment tool.

¹¹⁵ See page 12 of the document “Guidelines and Supplementary Instructions – Open Access Publication Funding [03/25]” by Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft:
<https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/167600/12-21-en.pdf>

¹¹⁶ Bernhard Mittermaier is library director at Forschungszentrum Jülich and also in charge of the OA monitor. He is active in library consortia and belongs to the DEAL negotiation group. See his abstract for the OAT25:
https://www.conftool.org/oat2025/index.php?page=browseSessions&form_session=111

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established by those research or funding organisations that also organise the evaluation of research funding. For the next stage in implementing the proposed funding process, the discussion paper specifically recommends involving representatives from scientific societies that publish scientific journals, in order to better estimate the required budget and how to shape the application procedure. A national pilot project should be launched to test the new procedure. The experts also suggest initiating an international working group to establish supranational co-financing.

Conclusions

Despite the stated challenges for Diamond OA in Germany, the German Diamond OA communities have achieved a lot without strong national policies and infrastructures over the last decades. This has added to their resilience and their embeddedness in local circumstances. Without the activation energy of concerted top-down policies, they relied on collaboration with open science-prone and Diamond OA-embracing local research communities, resulting in bottom-up growth. It would nevertheless be beneficial for the organic and sustainable growth of Diamond OA if a few challenges were tackled among high-level decision makers.

Those are:

- ✓ Substantial support (eased and concerted regulations, consulting capacities, framework agreements) on fiscal and legal topics to enable cross-institutional collaboration, especially for those institutions seated in different German states and reliable working conditions for institutions willing to take over national responsibilities in Diamond OA
- ✓ More collaboration among university leads and research institution leads to perceive institutional publishing services as state-of-the-art research infrastructures that each RPO should have in place, e.g. via a service portfolio of what would be the minimum equipment for any RPO, what should be available for certain disciplines, and what would be an ideal situation?
- ✓ Certain backbone infrastructure services on a national level, such as DOI services, OJS- and OMP platforms, with a white-label approach for institutional branding and orphan capacities for scholar-led publishing activities
- ✓ Recommendations on how higher education legislation in the German states can and should embrace Open Access and institutional publishing.

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Building on national policies and international recommendations, the Government of Ireland's *National Action Plan for Open Research 2022–2030*[1] aims to implement a sustainable and inclusive course for achieving 100% Open Access to Irish scholarly publications resulting from publicly funded research by 2030. The implementation of the National Action Plan for Open Research is overseen by the National Open Research Forum (NORF). In 2022, in support of the national ambitions for Open Access, NORF funded the 2-year PublishOA.ie [2] project to evaluate the feasibility of an all-Ireland digital publishing platform for Diamond OA journals and monographs.

The PublishOA project¹¹⁷ was co-led by the Royal Irish Academy and Trinity College Dublin Long Room Hub, with a consortium that included 10 partners and 8 affiliate organisations, including the UN SDG Academy, the Irish Humanities Alliance, the Moore Institute, and Publishing Ireland. The institutional project partners contributing to the project included the Institute of Art Design & Technology, Munster Technological University, Southeast Technological University, Technological University Dublin, Technological University of the Shannon, Trinity College Dublin, University of Galway, University of Limerick, and the Dublin Institute of Advanced Studies. The international Advisory Board included representatives from the European DIAMAS, CRAFT-OA, and PALOMERA projects, the Federation of Finnish Learned Journals, Openjournals.nl¹¹⁸, ITHAKA/JSTOR, and the Directory of Open Access Journals.

¹¹⁷ PublishOA project: <https://publishoa-ie.moodlecloud.com/>

¹¹⁸ Open Journals Netherlands: <http://openjournals.nl>

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In June 2023, the PublishOA project launched a *Directory of Irish Publishers* [3] based on a national survey, existing datasets, and desk research, which was subsequently followed up by contacting Irish publishers to verify details. The *Directory of Irish Publishers* is an all-island map of the Irish publishing landscape, listing over 180 active book and journal publishers.

In May 2024, the project published guidelines for publishers [4] and authors [5] with information, advice, and practical steps to comply with national and international standards for Open Access publishing, providing a step-by-step guide to key areas including platforms and technology, copyright and licensing, peer review, digital preservation, and funding models and requirements. Other outputs of the project include the *Publish OA: Communication and Dissemination Plan* [6] and *Publish OA Report: Comparison of Open Access Publishing Platform Software* (the basis of the technical specification of the proposed National Pilot Platform).[7] The PublishOA *Landscape Report* and *Technical Report* will be launched in June 2025. The *Landscape Report* makes the following recommendations:

1. Provide a staff member to create a robust network to support publishers to transition to OA by providing knowledge, training, practical support, and access to grants.
2. Allow publishers who are already publishing Diamond books and journals to work together now, using the Diamond infrastructure OJS/OMP.
3. Establish a grant system to directly fund publishers to publish OA, including book and journal publication costs and training and networking opportunities.
4. Provide an option for a portal to bring Irish published work together, irrespective of publication location, as much Irish-interest work is published by a variety of publishers in Ireland and abroad.
5. The *Directory of Irish Publishers* and the *Directory of Open Access Journals* published by the project provides the opportunity to build a network of publishers

PublishOA released a searchable *Directory of Irish Diamond Open Access Journals*¹¹⁹ [8] in February 2025. At the same time, an initial study on the number and sources of Irish Open Access monographs proved inconclusive due to difficulties in identifying OA books on a geographical basis but estimated a relatively low number of Diamond OA books published in Ireland to date.

¹¹⁹ Directory of Irish Diamond Open Access Journals: [https://publishoa-
ie.moodlecloud.com/course/section.php?id=58](https://publishoa-ie.moodlecloud.com/course/section.php?id=58)

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The Directory of Irish Diamond Open Access Journals shows that the current Open Access journal publishing environment in Ireland is quite heterogeneous in terms of its resourcing and infrastructural supports. A few institutions support a ‘stable’ of journals, often via their libraries, in support of their scholarly communication and Open Access objectives. Other journals are individually housed in university departments (for example) and are person-dependent and/or at risk from associated factors. Learned society journals are individually hosted or supported by a university or other institution.

The Directory of Irish Diamond Open Access Journals lists 55 Diamond OA journal titles currently being published in Ireland, 40% of which are indexed in the DOAJ. 32 (58%) of the 55 journals are hosted by university libraries.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

The National Action Plan for Open Research 2022–2030 strongly supports nonprofit scholarly publishing and Diamond OA: *"In line with the principle of biblio-diversity, we strongly encourage and support local and disciplinary publishing practices, society and academic-led publishing initiatives, non-profit Open Access publishers, and OA models in which journals or publishers do not charge fees to either authors or readers (also known as Diamond OA)."*

The National Plan also contains an Action A4.3.1, the aim of which is to *"Conduct a feasibility study and pilot with a view to establishing a publicly-owned, centralised national platform for Diamond OA publication of journals and books. This action will be aimed at supporting OA models for Irish-based academic journals and publishers."* This action was carried out by the above-mentioned PublishOA.ie project.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

A number of other NORF-funded projects are relevant to the PublishOA project in particular, and to Diamond OA publishing in Ireland generally. SCOIR (Secondary rights, Copyright, Open access, Institutional policies, and Rights retention)¹²⁰, led by Trinity College Dublin and Technological University Dublin, is exploring the adoption of secondary rights legislation in Ireland and creating an OA policy

¹²⁰ Secondary rights, Copyright, Open access, Institutional policies, and Rights retention (SCOIR): <https://scoir.moodlecloud.com/course/view.php?id=14#sectionid-89-title>

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framework¹²¹ aligned with the Irish policy landscape. SCOIR's draft legislation, the 'Research Outputs and Open Access Bill, 2025'¹²², requires publicly funded research outputs to be deposited in institutional repositories, a requirement that Diamond OA publishers can plan to deliver as a service to authors and their institutions.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

SCOIR'S OA policy framework lists 'access to Diamond OA journals' amongst the services institutions can provide to their researchers in support of Open Access.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

The National Open Access Repository Project¹²³, led by the University of Galway with fourteen institutional and organisational partners, aimed to strengthen and coordinate Ireland's network of Open Access repositories to facilitate interoperability via standard operating procedures, guidelines, and services. Direct deposit of Irish Diamond OA publications and provision of standardised publication metadata by Irish Diamond OA publishers to institutional repositories are examples of desirable publisher services.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

ABOARD¹²⁴, led by University College Cork, is examining the embedding of system-level incentives for open research practices. ENGAGED¹²⁵, led by Trinity College Dublin and Dublin City University, is building a national roadmap to shape public involvement in open research in Ireland. The TROPIC project (TRaining for OPEN research in an Irish Context)¹²⁶, led by Maynooth University, aims to develop and pilot a national open research training programme to upskill researchers in the fundamentals of open research practices. Finally, *Building a Culture of Open Research for Irish Health and Social Care Practitioner Researchers*¹²⁷, led by the

¹²¹ OA Policy Framework:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1IY_zj8mG2_rhTVG3lqWMtzklbcECGCza5NNPJRWHKfY/edit?pli=1&tab=t.0#heading=h.u6tg4ewehls0

¹²² Research Outputs and Open Access Bill, 2025:

<https://scoir.moodlecloud.com/mod/resource/view.php?id=120>

¹²³ National OA Repository Project: <https://www.universityofgalway.ie/openrepositories/>

¹²⁴ ABOARD: <https://www.universityofgalway.ie/openrepositories/>

¹²⁵ ENGAGED: <https://www.tcd.ie/civicengagement/engaged/>

¹²⁶ TRaining for OPEN research in an Irish Context (TROPIC Project): <https://osf.io/chxgd/>

¹²⁷ Building a Culture of Open Research for Irish Health and Social Care Practitioner Researchers:

<https://hselibrary.ie/open-health-research/>

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Health Service Executive and Trinity College Dublin, has a key objective of establishing a Diamond OA peer-reviewed medical journal.

Workforce and Capacity Development

The most prominent Irish community initiative for Diamond OA is the Irish Open Access Publishers (IOAP) (Buggle, 2025) [9]. The IOAP [10] was established in 2021 as a national community of practice to advance Diamond OA in Ireland. Its aim is *“to unite and strengthen communication and knowledge sharing among a diverse range of Diamond Open Access publishers in Ireland, engaging a wide variety of stakeholders including library publishers, institutional publishers, academics, students, librarians, national and international Open Access agencies, policymakers, and funders”* (Irish Open Access Publishers, n.d.). Among other initiatives, IOAP promotes Diamond OA journals by organising the IOAP Diamond OA Publishing Awards.[11]

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

The Library Publishing Group¹²⁸ of the Library Association of Ireland (LAI) was established in 2019 to promote and support library publishing activities in Ireland. The group is a strategic affiliate of the IFLA Library Publishing Special Interest Group¹²⁹ and the Library Publishing Coalition¹³⁰. The LAI Library Publishing Group organises regular training and advocacy events.

The national platform envisaged by the PublishOA project will facilitate Diamond OA publishing, in combination with institutional support coordinated by IOAP. The Open Book Collective [12] and the Irish Research electronic Library [13] are organisations aiming to work with Diamond OA publishers in Ireland and facilitate connections between publishers and supporting libraries. Various institutions are involved in Diamond OA publishing with library support, including Trinity College Dublin (TCD), Technological University Dublin, Maynooth University, University College Cork.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

The PublishOA Technical Report contains a number of recommendations on the pilot National Diamond Open Access Platform:

¹²⁸ The Library Publishing Group: <https://www.libraryassociation.ie/library-publishing-group/>

¹²⁹ IFLA Library Publishing Special Interest Group: <https://www.ifla.org/units/library-publishing/>

¹³⁰ Library Publishing Coalition: <https://librarypublishing.org/>

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- ✓ The Pilot Platform will be established as a prototype, demonstrator and forerunner of a fully featured and resourced National Diamond Open Access Publishing Platform.
- ✓ The Pilot Platform will be developed using the same principles, standards, and infrastructure as would be expected of a National Diamond Open Access Publishing Platform and as outlined in the forthcoming PublishOA Technical Report.
- ✓ The Pilot Platform will engage and seek alignment, technically and otherwise, with other initiatives in support of the National Open Research Action Plan and in pursuit of the national goal of achieving 100% Open Access to Irish publicly funded research by 2030. This includes the SCOIR project on Secondary Publishing, Copyright, Open Access, IP and Rights Retention. It also includes support for the outcomes and recommendations of the “Advancing Repositories” project.
- ✓ The Pilot Platform will aim to enable all participating journals to achieve the DOAS standard and to maximise their visibility, discoverability and impact.
- ✓ The Pilot Platform will include a Discovery Interface to showcase all Irish Diamond Open Access Journals regardless of their platform or location.
- ✓ The Pilot Platform will be developed for the same community and using the same governance and partnership model as would be expected of a National Diamond Open Access Publishing Platform.
- ✓ The Pilot Platform is not just a technical development. It will be built on the same Diamond Engagement model as would be expected of a fully realised National Diamond Open Access Publishing Platform. The following chart illustrates the Diamond Engagement model with its interconnected facets of Partnership, Principles, Standards, Community, Structure and Infrastructure.

The Diamond Engagement model is designed to support sustainability and scalability and will provide the scaffolding to support the Pilot Platform’s ultimate transition into a fully realised National Diamond Open Access Publishing Platform.

Image 5: National Diamond OA Publishing Platform. Source: PublishOA Technical Report, pp.42-43

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing.

The proposed all-Ireland Diamond OA publishing platform, combined with the *Directory of Diamond OA journals*, provides an excellent basis to benchmark the quality and sustainability of these journals, including alignment with the Diamond OA Standard. The Diamond OA landscape would also benefit from sustainable funding for IOAP. It is also important to develop coordinated initiatives at the institutional level to recognise and reward Diamond OA publishing.

In March 2025, NORF issued a funding call that specifically targeted “the sustainability and growth of open research networks established under the 2022 Open Research Fund, aimed at ensuring long-term impact and resilience in Ireland’s open research ecosystem” (NORF 2025 Open Research Fund Call - Royal Irish Academy)¹³¹. PublishOA is one of the eligible projects, and an application has been submitted. A key focus of the PublishOA application is on developing a network and sustainable Diamond OA publishing partnership to support bibliodiversity in Ireland. This call covers a 12-month period commencing later in 2025.

A number of the aforementioned NORF-funded projects are due to issue reports and recommendations within the next 12 months. It is too soon to report on concrete strategies when this key work is ongoing. It is clear, however, that the

¹³¹ NORF 2025 Open Research Fund Call - Royal Irish Academy: <https://www.ria.ie/2025/03/28/norf-2025-open-research-fund-call/#:~:text=The%20NORF%202025%20Open%20Research%20Fund%20is%20a,Fund.%20Find%20out%20more%20about%20the%20application%20process.>

vision of *the National Action Plan for Open Research* and NORF are in alignment, with a focus on network building and sustainability.

References

National Action Plan for Open Research. 2022-2030: <https://norf.ie/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/National-Action-Plan-for-Open-Research-webversion.pdf>

Publish OA Ireland: <https://publishoa-ie.moodlecloud.com>

Directory of Irish publishers - Database: <https://zenodo.org/records/8047015>

Open Access publishing guidelines for publishers: Open Access publishing guidelines for publishers: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11235895>

Open Access publishing guidelines for authors: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236652>

Publish OA: Communication and Dissemination Plan (Deliverable 5): <https://zenodo.org/records/10593989>

FIGURE 2 in Systematics and taxonomy of *Pipistrellus kuhlii* (Kuhl, 1817) in Central Europe and the Balkans: <https://zenodo.org/records/843176>

Directory of Irish Diamond Open Access Journals [database]: <https://publishoa-ie.moodlecloud.com/mod/data/view.php?id=121>

Building a National Community of Practice for Diamond Open Access: <https://katinamagazine.org/content/article/open-knowledge/2025/building-a-community-of-practice-Diamond-open-access>

Diamond OA Journals in Ireland: <https://sites.google.com/view/irish-open-access-publishers/irish-oa-publishers>

Advancing Diamond Open Access Publishing in Ireland: The Role and Impact of the Irish Open Access Publishers (IOAP): https://illustriadt.figshare.com/articles/journal_contribution/Advancing_Diamond_Open_Access_Publishing_in_Ireland_The_Role_and_Impact_of_the_Irish_Open_Access_Publishers_IOAP_/28566566?file=52896893

Irish Open Access Publishers: <https://ioap.ie>

IOAP Awards 2024: <https://ioap.ie/ioap-awards-2024/>

Open Book Collective: <https://openbookcollective.org>

Irish Research e-Library: <https://irel.ie/about-irel/>

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Scientific publishing in Italy is marked by a fragmented yet substantial editorial system. The market is dominated by a few major international publishers that account for a great majority of scientific articles. These publishers often operate through national branches or partnerships with local publishers, particularly in STEM and economics, where international influence is stronger. Disciplines within the social sciences and humanities (SSH) — law, literature, and the arts — tend to rely on local and national publishers prioritising Italian culture and language.

Italy is transitioning towards Open Access (OA) publishing: hybrid OA models coexist with traditional paywalls. The country has numerous publishers and several hundred journals indexed in DOAJ, most of them following the Diamond OA model. Institutional and disciplinary repositories are widespread, with over a hundred listed in OpenDOAR and around half as many in re3data.

Transformative agreements are reshaping the landscape by enabling immediate OA publication. Elsevier, Springer Nature, and Wiley lead in OA publications under these agreements. The Conference of Italian University Rectors (CRUI), through the CARE Group, plays a pivotal role in negotiating and overseeing the great majority of national transformative agreements.

¹³² This is an updated and modified text from Taşkın, Z., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Laakso, M., Torný, D., Arasteh, S., Bargheer, M., Klaus, T., Schima, J., Agnoloni, T., Peruginelli, G., Davidson, A., Franczak, M., Coslado Bernabé M.A., de Pablo Llorente, V., Dobson, H., & Heyman, J. (2024). D5.2 National overviews on sustaining institutional publishing in Europe. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683953>

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Despite the growth of OA, Italy faces substantial challenges: absence of dedicated OA funding schemes, lack of unified tools for data and publication collection, inadequate reform of research evaluation policies that continue to rely on traditional bibliometrics, insufficient awareness of copyright and author rights, and the absence of secondary publishing rights. Efforts by ANVUR to broaden research evaluation frameworks have met with obstacles, reflecting a gap between Italy's OA progress and broader European initiatives. Nonetheless, movements such as OA2020 and Plan S, along with grassroots efforts from organisations like the Italian Association for the Advancement of Open Science (AISA), continue to promote systemic reform.

Overall, Italy presents a clear asymmetry between large commercial publishers and non-profit initiatives, along with an excessive influence of bibliometrics on policy. Universities act largely independently, with fragmented and uncoordinated policies, while university presses lack systemic support and recognition. Political awareness of publication costs and alternative models remains limited, and little attention is given to distortions created by a market dominated by commercial actors. A more comprehensive understanding requires detailed analysis of how universities manage their presses and journals, and how such fragmentation affects the national landscape. Greater scrutiny should also be directed towards the predominance of costly transformative contracts, often regarded as successes despite their financial burden.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

Italy's research system encompasses nearly 100 higher education institutions, including a great majority that are state universities, a smaller group of recognised non-state universities, and several online institutions. It also includes around 20 research organisations under ministerial supervision.

The country launched its National Plan for Open Science (PNSA) in 2022 through Ministerial Decree No. 268, aligning with the National Research Programme (NRP) 2021–2027. The PNSA sets objectives for implementing open science, encompassing OA publishing, data sharing, and reform of research assessment. In 2023, the Ministry of Universities and Research (MUR) established a working group to guide implementation, although no reports, guidelines, or data have yet been published.

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Italy's OA framework builds upon Law 112/2013, requiring OA for publications funded with at least half public funds, though embargoes of up to two years are permitted and compliance is not monitored. The 2022 PRIN call also mandates green OA for peer-reviewed outputs from publicly funded projects, again without systematic verification or sanctions.

Private foundations such as Telethon and Cariplo promote OA through funding schemes that either require or encourage it, with varying licensing and archiving conditions. Nonetheless, challenges persist, including uncertainty over acceptable deposit versions, embargo policies, and limited legal enforcement.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Italy employs a national performance-based funding model in which around one fifth of institutional research funding is performance-related. This is distributed mainly according to general evaluation outcomes, research output from new or promoted staff, and teaching quality.

The Valutazione della Qualità della Ricerca (VQR), coordinated by ANVUR, plays a central role in assessing research and determines eligibility for schemes such as the “Departments of Excellence” programme. However, OA publication is not a criterion within this evaluation.

Although the PNSA calls for systematic monitoring, no national OA funding scheme or structural budget exists to support Diamond OA publishing. Institutional subsidies from parent organisations remain the most stable form of support, while project-based funding and sales revenues provide additional but inconsistent contributions. APCs are used to a limited extent, while public or external funds remain sporadic. In-kind support from institutions — facilities, staff time, and IT infrastructure — remains essential.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

OA and Diamond OA outputs are not recognised in Italy's main assessment procedures — the VQR and the Abilitazione Scientifica Nazionale (ASN). Both rely on a mix of bibliometrics, peer review, and informed peer review. Bibliometrics are widely used in STEM and to a lesser extent in economics and statistics, focusing primarily on citation counts and Journal Impact Factor (JIF). This reliance on journal-level metrics reinforces the “publish or perish” culture and dependence on commercial publishing.

In SSH disciplines, bibliometrics are not used, and publication lists or qualitative assessments prevail. Yet, even here, OA publication offers no direct advantage for

career progression or funding. Inclusion of OA criteria in ASN and VQR processes is seen as crucial for shifting assessment practices towards open science alignment.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Italy's OA ecosystem relies heavily on institutional repositories, most of which operate through IRIS (developed by Cineca). These integrate bibliometric data from sources such as Scopus and Web of Science.

Several universities and institutions manage OA publishing platforms for journals and monographs:

- ✓ Riviste UNIMI and Libri UNIMI (University of Milan)¹³³
- ✓ ROSA (Sapienza University of Rome)¹³⁴
- ✓ AlmaDL Journals (University of Bologna)¹³⁵
- ✓ SIRIO@UniTO (University of Turin)¹³⁶
- ✓ PubLISS (Istituto Superiore di Sanità Institutional Repository)¹³⁷

Most platforms use OJS and Open Monograph Press (OMP). However, there is no national Diamond OA platform or structured funding instrument. Initiatives remain fragmented and depend on institutional budgets or participation in European networks such as OPERAS and OBC.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

At least half of research-performing organisations (RPOs) have adopted institutional open science policies, primarily addressing publications. These cover definitions, deposit procedures, repository use, accessibility, preservation, and

¹³³ Riviste UNIMI and Libri UNIMI (University of Milan): <https://www.unimi.it/en/library-services/digital-library/riviste-unimi-and-libri-unimi>

¹³⁴ ROSA (Sapienza University of Rome): <https://rosa.uniroma1.it/>

¹³⁵ AlmaDL Journals (University of Bologna): <https://www.almadljournals.unibo.it/>

¹³⁶ SIRIO@UniTO (University of Turin): <https://www.sirio.unito.it/>

¹³⁷ PubLISS (ISS institutional repository): <https://publ.iss.it/>

monitoring. The ISS¹³⁸ and the CNR approved OA policies in 2022 and issued a Roadmap for Open Science in 2023¹³⁹.

Institutional support is, more than nothing, departmental. Universities tend to act independently, without coordination or central guidance. The University Presses Consortium (UPI), representing nearly twenty members, plays a coordinating role, although not exclusively for OA.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Italian institutional publishing systems suffer from limited staffing and overreliance on volunteers. Many publishers and services providers depend on in-kind support from parent institutions, with staff providing editorial and technical services as part of their institutional roles. Professional development opportunities in OA publishing, editorial management, and copyright remain scarce. Training and technical assistance are occasionally offered through cooperative groups such as CoPER's Open Science working group but lack a national strategy.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Most publishers rely on external service providers for technical and editorial functions. Editorial and production services are often offered in-kind or outsourced, while IT and hosting are frequently externalised. Communication, training, and administrative support are less commonly provided by third parties.

Common open-source platforms such as OJS help reduce costs and promote standardisation. Collaboration among academic publishers could enhance economies of scale, shared resources, and professionalisation, although systematic mechanisms are not yet in place.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

The Italian academic community maintains a National Peer Review Register of reviewers, though it has not yet reached its potential. Quality assurance in Diamond OA remains decentralised and relies largely on voluntary peer review by academic staff.

¹³⁸ OA Policy. Italy (ISS):

<https://www.iss.it/documents/20126/8788315/policy+ISS+pubblicazioni+e+dati+WEB.pdf/128e93ae-f4bd-0929-d48d-301f97efce80?t=1686557890727>

¹³⁹ Roadmap for OS. Italy (CNR): https://sibi.cnr.it/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Roadmap_Scienza_Aperta.pdf

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A collaborative Open Science Observatory, established by a group of universities and research centres, monitors open science activities across eight EU-aligned pillars. It offers a virtual research environment for institutional self-assessment yet lacks stable national funding and formal integration with ANVUR processes.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

To strengthen Diamond OA and nonprofit scholarly publishing in Italy, policy and funding measures should prioritise long-term structural support, coordinated infrastructures, and integration into assessment systems.

1. The establishment of a national fund for OA and Diamond publishing would provide stable resources for university presses and institutional publishers, reducing dependence on short-term project funding or commercial models. Reallocation of APC expenditures towards collective, non-profit initiatives could be considered in the medium term, complemented by ministry funding, private foundations, membership schemes, and crowdfunding.
2. OA outputs must be recognised in research evaluation systems. Incorporating OA criteria into ASN and VQR frameworks would create real incentives for researchers to publish in Diamond OA venues. Recognition in career progression, coupled with competitive institutional funding linked to OA results, could promote cultural and systemic change.
3. Developing shared and interoperable infrastructures at the national level would ensure sustainability and efficiency. Coordinated technical frameworks could provide publishing, metadata, and preservation services for all institutions.
4. Capacity-building measures are required. Dedicated training programmes for editors, librarians, and researchers should enhance skills in OA management, copyright, and quality assurance.

Finally, a coordinated advocacy strategy should raise political and institutional awareness of the societal value of nonprofit scholarly publishing. Stakeholders — including ANVUR, MUR, universities, libraries, and academic associations — must collaborate to frame scientific publishing as a public good. Policy actions should promote transparency, collective governance, and sustainable funding, aligning Italy's system with European open science objectives.

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Compared to other European countries, the Netherlands has a high number of students and significant higher education costs, all above the European median. Regarding the number of full-time faculty, total costs, and researchers in R&D, the Netherlands is also above the European average. This sector also has more researchers than the European average, which means it has a significant publishing output year on year (Eurostat 2024; UNL, Onderzoeksoutput).

Key national bodies and associations have open science strategies and goals in place as part of an integrated approach to Open Science nationwide. The Universities of the Netherlands (UNL)¹⁴⁰, Dutch University Libraries and National Library consortium (UKB)¹⁴¹ negotiate with publishers on OA contracts. The UNL manages the open science strategy for Dutch universities, coordinated by a body of representatives from all universities called the Chiefs of Open Science (COS).

Strong advocacy networks have supported the Dutch transition to Open Science, and a rich tradition of collaboration between institutions, funders, and policymakers has existed since 2017. More recently, collaborative networks such as the Netherlands University Presses (NUPs) and the collaborative development of national open infrastructures are key to advancing Diamond OA in the Netherlands. A new Diamond OA coordinator has been helping coordinate efforts on Diamond OA since 2024. The current national OA work plan also features Diamond OA and institutional publishing.

¹⁴⁰ Universities of the Netherlands (UNL): <https://www.universiteitenvannederland.nl/en>

¹⁴¹ Dutch University Libraries and National Library consortium (UKB): <https://ukb.nl/en/>

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The 2022 National Programme Open Science (NPOS) report *Strengthening Support for Diamond Open Access in the Netherlands*¹⁴² made recommendations that resulted in the formation of a Dutch National Expertise Centre for Diamond OA. Several initiatives promoting Diamond OA as part of the Dutch efforts to achieve 100% Open Access by 2030 have government and institutional support. This saw the initiation of the Capacity Building for Diamond OA Infrastructures Project. The Capacity Building for Diamond OA Infrastructures Project is developing a shared technical infrastructure nationwide.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

The Netherlands aims for 100% of scholarly journal articles from researchers at publicly funded knowledge institutions to be published immediately under an open licence by 2030. It also seeks to make OS the norm for academic research by 2031. To measure progress on these goals, the government monitors the overall percentage of OA uptake (per route: Gold, Hybrid, Green). Publication data on DOIs, publishers, contracts and institutions has been collected and warehoused since 2018. As of 2024, the level of Diamond OA is also tracked and mentioned explicitly, alongside other types of OA publications.

The Netherlands notably has a robust policy environment for OA and open science. All Dutch universities have OA policies. The Netherlands also has a secondary publishing rights policy called Taverne.

A Dutch National Open Science programme (NPOS) was active between 2017 and 2022, and 2023 saw the launch of Open Science NL (OSNL)¹⁴³. In 2022, Parliament agreed to the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science funding the Open Science NL initiative until 2031 with 20m EUR annually.

Recommendations by the National Programme Open Science (NPOS) in 2022 resulted in a Dutch National Expertise Centre for Diamond Open Access. This Centre was planned in 2024 and launched in early 2025 as a Community of Practice that promotes knowledge exchange and collaboration across the academic community, offering training, workshops, and discipline-specific toolkits. The Centre is part of a broader programme funded by the UNL and launched by the UKB.

¹⁴² Strengthening Support for Diamond Open Access in the Netherlands:

<https://zenodo.org/records/14185141>

¹⁴³ Open Science NL (OSNL): <https://www.openscience.nl/en>

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Research funding is provided at the national level by the Dutch Research Council (NWO) and, for health research, ZonMW. Many Dutch researchers also apply for international funding from the European Commission. Both Dutch public funding bodies require grantees to publish scholarly outputs resulting from funded research in OA.

In 2023, following the NPOS Ambition Document 2030, the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science allotted significant annual funding for ten years until 2031. The Open Science NL initiative is embedded in the NWO. The initiative addresses four pillars of Open Science, including Open Scholarly Communication (with OA), FAIR data, Open Research Software and Societal Engagement/Citizen Science. With a government change in 2024, we saw the initial annual sum of 20m EUR halved due to political change. The Open Science Infrastructure Programme received 17.5m EUR for one round in 2024/2025 (OSNL, 2023). The NWO, as a funding council, also helps kick-start OS projects. In addition, grant funding is available from the NWO for supporting projects designed to implement and stimulate open science practices (for example, the Open Science Fund) and for the publication of OA books (Open Access Books call) as well as the call for proposals to support the flipping of journals to Diamond OA.

Despite funder support for OA, no national budget for Diamond OA has yet been set (Jansen & Sondervan, 2023), even though the earlier NPOS strategy aimed to maintain the “harmonised multi-route approach (Green, Diamond, as well as Gold Open Access)” to scholarly publishing (NPOS, 2022). However, the current OSNL plan recognises “a renewed interest” in Diamond OA (OSNL, 2023). 300K EUR of the Ministry funds has also been allocated to enable and strengthen institutional open publishing from 2025, and this can focus on building Diamond OA capacity.

Many universities fund Diamond OA independently; some have set up Diamond OA funds. While institutional parent organisations provide subsidies and time-limited grants, the funding models of Dutch OA publishers and service providers vary significantly, and many rely more on in-kind and non-monetary support.

Many but not all universities fund Diamond OA publishing independently of national funding bodies. For example, the University of Amsterdam (UvA) pioneered a Diamond fund, annually offering a Diamond Open Access Fund to fund Diamond initiatives by both publishers of works by UvA researchers and UvA authors of works external to the UvA, but this 4-year programme came to an end in 2024. The Erasmus University of Rotterdam’s Open Access Fund has two streams dedicated

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to covering BPCs for OA books and initiatives related to Diamond OA journals. Similar funds for this purpose have been depleted in recent years, indicating issues with the sustainability of this approach.

There is also a project by the UKB Working Group Open Access that creates a national consortium designed to pool funding for OA infrastructures underlying the publishing system and is a first step towards a national collaboration for providing finances, infrastructure, professional support, expertise centres, and monitoring for success for Diamond OA institutional publishing (Jansen & Sondervan, 2023).

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Research assessment in the Netherlands is undergoing a significant transformation. Comparative studies have shown that institutional funding outweighs project-based funding for Dutch researchers (Zacharewicz et al., 2019). Thanks to collaborative, systemic reform efforts since 2019, Open Science outputs have become important for recruitment and promotion. These reforms — spearheaded by UNL, KNAW, NWO, ZonMw, and others — are grounded in the principle that research careers are diverse and that quality must outweigh quantity.

Following the 2019 position paper “Room for everyone’s talent,” eighteen higher education institutions launched a joint change management plan and revamped the Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP) for 2021–2027. This update foregrounds narrative CVs and Open Science practices, promoting qualitative, context-aware evaluations.

The 2023 Roadmap reiterates the need to abandon prestige metrics like Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and the h-index (Recognition & Rewards, 2023). However, Jansen and Sondervan (2023) show that the JIF continues to shape funding and publishing incentives, reinforcing the dominance of English-language, commercial journals and privileging Gold over Diamond OA, benefiting publishers through higher APCs. This means that publication by the Gold OA route in large commercial journals can have author preference over smaller Diamond OA journals.

Alongside collective action toward research assessment reform, financial incentives are now in place to embed Open Science into institutional policies on rewards and recognition. In 2024, OSNL issued a call to give institutions access to €50K project funding to develop plans to align hiring, promotion, and funding criteria with the Dutch Recognition & Rewards programme, which calls for openness and reproducibility to be recognised as key indicators of research quality (Recognition & Rewards, 2019; OSNL, 2023). A further €150K will support a national project manager in coordinating this transition. This shift aligns with the CoARA Agreement

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on Research Assessment, signed by major Dutch institutions in 2022, and follows national recommendations to improve recognition of Open Science practices (CoARA, 2022; NPOS, 2022). Since CoARA launched, the Netherlands launched a National Chapter of the Coalition on Advancing Research Assessment, or CoARA, that seeks better alignment of CoARA with Dutch developments such as Recognition & Rewards and the Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP).

Small incremental steps are being made to incentivise publication using the Diamond OA route. One such step is the creation of infrastructure that will increase the appeal of Diamond OA. To work on developing a shared technical infrastructure nationwide, the programme *Strengthening Diamond Open Access in the Netherlands* has developed an expertise centre that provides information, workshops, and training.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

OSNL's priorities include growing national capacity for open science and building robust infrastructure. The Netherlands already has a strong infrastructure for OA publishing, but support for Diamond OA still lags behind other countries (Jansen & Sondervan, 2023).

Thus far, significant progress on infrastructure has already been made. Fifteen years ago, Amsterdam University Press was the only university press in the country.

The Netherlands University Presses (NUPs) consortium is now collaborating on Diamond OA infrastructure: developing shared catalogues, a potential national book platform, and projects around peer review, metadata, open textbooks, marketing and sustainable business models. It has recently received 300k from OSNL to strengthen and empower the network. Collaboration with the expertise centre and Thoth are central to the project. This grant aims to strengthen that network, build on expertise, share knowledge, reduce costs (including costs on editorial services), and reduce inefficiencies. At present, Openjournals.nl¹⁴⁴ is the core infrastructure for Diamond OA publishing in the Netherlands, and collaborations such as these are gradually working towards creating a single technical platform for the country.

Openjournals.nl is a nationally funded platform for Diamond OA journals, mainly in the social sciences and humanities. Initially supported by NWO, it is funded by the OSNL until 2028. Financial support has also come from some universities in the Netherlands and Belgium, and participating journals (Association of universities in

¹⁴⁴ Open Journals Netherlands Platform: <http://openjournals.nl>

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the Netherlands (now UNL), 2023; Jansen & Sondervan, 2023). For €2000/year, it offers complete hosting and services via open-source OJS software, mainly for the social sciences and humanities. There is also a need for a broader infrastructure that supports journals, books, protocols, and preprints (Bosman et al., 2021; Jansen & Sondervan, 2023). Another platform is Publinova, which is focused on publishing outputs from the Universities of Applied Sciences.

The NPOS Ambition Document 2030 aimed to establish a national open digital infrastructure by 2027. Since 2024, the UNL has led efforts to create a federated network of Dutch institutional repositories, a central warehouse for open metadata, and a national platform to make OA research more visible and accessible. Just as national funding may be available to these infrastructures for OA publishing, institutional publishers lobby for funds from research funding organisations such as the NWO and their institutions (Jansen & Sondervan, 2023).

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Open Access policy in the Netherlands is well developed at institutional and research funder levels. The UNL and UKB negotiate with publishers on OA contracts. The UNL also manages the open science strategy for Dutch universities, coordinated by a body of representatives from all universities called the Chiefs of Open Science (COS). The Chiefs of Open Science have initiated the programme Strengthening Diamond OA in the Netherlands (2024 - 2026) to bring together university presses, Open Access officers, editorial boards, metadata experts, and others to advance non-profit publishing on a national level. The programme's output has met with positive feedback. Institutions fund Higher education academic libraries, and these are nationally connected. Some Dutch institutional publishers and service providers depend heavily on their parent organisations for subsidies and time-limited grants. There is significant variation in the funding models available (Bosman & Kramer, 2024), and some universities fund Diamond OA (see above). For example, many rely on in-kind and non-monetary support from parent organisations and volunteers (Bosman & Kramer, 2024).

The new Diamond OA Expertise Centre is taking advocacy strides with its seven newly appointed ambassadors, who come from different academic institutions and are at different stages of their careers, from PhD candidates to professors.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Some university presses work with dedicated staff, IT staff and OA officers who dedicate part of their working time to the press. Many Dutch institutional presses rely on in-kind and non-monetary support from parent organisations and volunteers (Bosman & Kramer, 2024).

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Several examples of successful collaborations between publishers and service providers have been documented in the Netherlands. Three important ones are described below.

The *How to flip your journal: A guide to more equitable publishing with Diamond Open Access* guidance published in early 2025 has been downloaded over 1.5k times as of June 2025. It was an activity of the UKB working group on Open Access. This promises to support many journal editors in the Netherlands and beyond who want to transition their journal to a Diamond OA publication model.

Collaboration between institutional publishers, libraries, and funding organisations is an opportunity to gain efficiency in the institutional publishing landscape for books and journals (OSNL, 2023). One of the funding calls of Open Science NL is even aimed at the NUPs, which strive to share the costs of developing services and infrastructures for Diamond OA. The NUPs and Openjournals.nl are also partners in the Capacity Building for Infrastructures project. The project will build on these platforms to establish a high-quality and flexible national publication infrastructure that will serve all Dutch university presses, research institutes, and other research organisations that wish to develop and publish their own articles, journals and (text)books.

Another activity of the Expertise Centre is to produce lists of Diamond OA journal and book publishers active in the Netherlands. The new 2025 Ryzhova and Siviero *Diamond Open Access Book Publishers List*¹⁴⁵ is a sound basis for collaboration between Diamond publishers and their service providers. It contains Dutch and European publishers that do not charge BPCs and are open to authors regardless of institutional affiliation. The list for journals is forthcoming.

¹⁴⁵ Ryzhova and Siviero Diamond Open Access Book Publishers List:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15697832>

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

As of 2025, the Dutch Diamond Expertise Centre will design an evaluation process to track both quantitative and qualitative progress in Diamond OA in the Netherlands. This will build on a baseline assessment of Dutch Diamond OA journals, Dutch-authored publications in Diamond OA journals, and books or book chapters by Dutch researchers published with Diamond OA publishers. The journal list will help evaluate quality and analyse journals against DOAS. The Expertise Centre will then develop materials and organise workshops.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Support for Diamond OA already exists among Dutch institutions and in several ongoing national programmes. However, there are still challenges for adopting and sustaining Diamond OA that institutional and national strategies need to address. A system change is not yet around the corner. First and foremost, actions such as reallocating funds for APCs to Diamond OA publishing will not be taken unless they are incentivised by strategy or policy, such as if research institutions state that they aim to support non-profits.

There is potentially strong motivation at all levels to make Diamond OA mainstream in the Netherlands because it offers researchers and institutions a publishing pathway that will better ensure digital sovereignty. The Netherlands is increasingly interested in digital sovereignty: from researchers concerned about exploiting content to big tech to policymakers, i.e., in controlling, governing, and retaining more autonomy over its research outputs and systems. This is also an opportunity to pursue the Diamond OA route.

Institutional support for Diamond OA is often library-led, with university presses offering Diamond OA publishing through libraries. Some academic libraries (at Leiden University and Utrecht University) are developing publication strategies for faculties that will help guide them on how to spend their budgets for OA publishing. It would be welcome if research institutions also stated they wanted to sustain non-profit publishing.

The Chiefs of Open Science, a body of representatives who meet monthly and liaise between the national and institutional levels, could lead national initiatives to make Diamond OA mainstream in the future. A multifaceted and co-ordinated approach is key in a country where transformational action on OS happens simultaneously at many levels. A coordinated approach must involve UNL, institutional libraries, NWO, Medical Centres (NFU), Universities of Applied Science, and OSNL and begin

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by lining up policy, incentives, funding, support and efficient practices. At present, UKB is working on a strategy for OA where Diamond OA will have a bigger part. Likewise, NWO is considering how it can develop more sustainable funding, since it already has a dedicated OS infrastructure budget for the mid- to long term. Other potential sources of funding to support Diamond OA could come from university-based trusts and foundations in the area of their remits or from actions such as consortial funding allocation for journals or scholarly societies flipping their journals.

Change in making Diamond OA mainstream must be at least partly led bottom-up since researchers must also convince policymakers of this potential change. More engagement with them will boost change. Academic community participation in the transition to Diamond OA is key and will only be unlocked when Diamond adoption is better incentivised. Even researchers who are willing to publish Diamond OA often cannot do so because they are bound by the traditional structures of recognition and rewards that favour publications by commercial publishers. This is especially true for ECRs, who, depending on discipline, are often not empowered enough to take the risk of publishing Diamond OA if the publication or press is less prestigious. The 2025 Dutch Diamond Ambassadors programme will help encourage researchers to adopt the Diamond model and create awareness about publishing choices: one is currently organising a conference on Diamond.

Creating conditions that make Diamond publications more attractive to researchers is important. One way of achieving this is to continue existing initiatives that seek to change the system of professional recognition and rewards for researchers so that choosing to publish Diamond OA will be better rewarded. In research assessment and hiring and promotion practices, one suggestion that could better incentivise Diamond is to have researchers omit the journal title when listing their publications on new job applications. Funders might use their influence by asking researchers not to review for commercial publishers thereby moving the attention away from certain venues and taking a broader view on publishing.

Attracting certain communities such as learned societies to flip to OA and adopt Diamond OA platforms such as ORE and Octopus would also be important. Identifying other (potential) key players can also accelerate this process, as the success of the Dutch Ambassadors programme has shown. Learned societies that publish may also have an important leadership role to play, but the level of their influence and their potential interest in Diamond OA are still not well enough known in the Netherlands (Late et al. 2024; Pampel et al. 2020; Late et al. 2019).

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Other recommendations include improving the quality and findability of Diamond OA publications, encouraging research organisations to fund Diamond OA and establishing a shared national platform that would make Diamond OA publications more visible and impactful. Sharing services for Diamond OA helps stakeholders achieve efficiency, which makes it possible to enhance quality and extend those services. These measures would go hand in hand with efforts to increase researcher awareness of Diamond OA and thereby empower researchers to choose the Diamond route from a range of available publishing options. In short, not only would such efforts help make Diamond OA more mainstream in the Netherlands, they would also increase digital sovereignty.

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

In Norway, scholarly publishing had up until the 1950s mostly been done by institutions directly. Since then, the national publishing environment started to change gradually with publishing duties being handled through a new company called Universitetsforlaget, owned by the major universities and the students' welfare unions. This publisher grew within Norway, and even within Sweden, to become "...the foremost scholarly publisher in Norway" (Bosman, Kramer, Stojanovski et al., 2024, p. 37). The event that substantially shaped the current national publishing environment happened in the late 1990s, when the company was sold off in parts due to financial challenges. The journals with international scope were transferred to Taylor & Francis and a national commercial publisher took over the Universitetsforlaget imprint and the Nordic language journals and book publishing that focus on the social sciences and humanities. The current Universitetsforlaget has a strong position in the national publishing landscape, where journals are either subscription-based or Diamond OA, with only one APC-based journal (Bosman, Kramer, Stojanovski et al., 2024, p. 37). The publisher has used and continues to use the name of Scandinavian University Press for journal publishing. Another larger national publisher in Norway is Cappelen Damm Akademisk, which publishes both Diamond OA and APC-based journals (Bosman, Kramer, Stojanovski et al., 2024, p. 37).

¹⁴⁶ This is an updated and modified text from Taşkın, Z., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Laakso, M., Torný, D., Arasteh, S., Bargheer, M., Klaus, T., Schima, J., Agnoloni, T., Peruginelli, G., Davidson, A., Franczak, M., Coslado Bernabé M.A., de Pablo Llorente, V., Dobson, H., & Heyman, J. (2024). D5.2 National overviews on sustaining institutional publishing in Europe. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683953>

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Based on a recent bibliometric scan of Ulrichsweb there are 213 active peer-reviewed journals in Norway (journals count 213 in Ulrichsweb) (Taşkın, Melinščak Zlodi, Laakso et al 2024). Checking DOAJ data, we can see that 125 Norwegian journals are listed, with the vast majority not having any fees required for publishing, suggesting that the majority of journals in the country are OA and adhering to a Diamond model of publishing. In 2008 the number of Norwegian journals was 13, so the growth has been substantial since then (Frantsvåg, 2008). The current large share of OA journals listed in DOAJ is likely a consequence of university libraries (e.g. UiB, NTNU, UiT, UiO, OsloMet) setting up institutional publishing services during 2011-2015. Providing these services shepherded journals towards good publishing and OA practices, with journals receiving practical support for e.g. funding of DOIs and applying to be included in DOAJ. National science policy has strengthened and formalised these initiatives as part of a national OA policy that has been in place since 2017 (Ministry of Education and Research, 2017).

Norway has comprehensive data visualisations available for OA monitoring available on the national webpages for information on open science. (<https://www.openscience.no/oa-barometer/nasjonal-oversikt>). Figure 1 presents the development of OA by access type in terms of where authors with Norwegian affiliations are publishing their articles, where Diamond OA has remained a small and relatively stagnant category while the share of hybrid OA, particularly through transformative agreements, has increased substantially.

Figure 1 - Share of article output by authors affiliated with Norwegian institutions, split by access type, where Diamond OA articles are the bottom category. Source: <https://www.openscience.no/oa-barometer/nasjonal-oversikt>

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

In an article from 2008, Frantsovåg (2008) provides a useful historical snapshot of the early days of OA publishing developments in Norway. Frantsovåg's (2008) description of the landscape shows that Norway has engaged in national-level formal collaborative projects promoting OA to research publications for over 20 years, most notably through a project called NORA (Norwegian Open Research Archives), which was started between the universities of Oslo, Bergen, Trondheim and Tromsø (Frantsovåg, 2008). Through NORA, universities were able to establish and standardise their repositories, and over time establish institutional policies to also facilitate deposit of self-archived journal articles. NORA also provided some initial funding for universities to establish journal publication services based on OJS (Frantsovåg, 2008). Since 2011, the work of coordinating repository activities on the national level has been handled through Cristin, which is a service operated by Sikt (described in detail later in this section).

The historical overview of OA in Norway is continued by Wenaas & Gulbrandsen (2022) in a longitudinal analysis of how Norwegian universities have responded to national policy developments for OA during the timespan of 2009–2021. Based on the review of 182 policy documents, strategy documents and annual reports of universities the authors conclude that “When considering the profile of the institutional policies and the explicit referrals to national policies, we find there is a great deal of homogeneity between Norwegian universities, and they are mostly aligned with national policy. [...] All universities show commitment to Open Access, and several can be described as proactive as they tie it to different types of local incentives.” Overall, it can be argued that Norway has been among the earliest movers when it comes to OA, and that the movement has been strong and consistent across the country and across both domestic outlets (Norwegian journals) as well for all research outputs authored by Norwegian authors (International journals).

Norway's first national Open Access policy was issued by the Ministry of Education and Research (2017). The policy contained the following summarising paragraph, which conveys the main message:

“The goal of the government is to make all publicly funded Norwegian research articles openly available by 2024. Norway shall be a driving force for all publicly financed research articles to be made openly available at the time of publishing. Research institutions, research funders and the

wider research community must all play a part in order to reach this goal of full Open Access. The research community in particular is expected to play a vital role in promoting Open Access through their national and international networks, and to convert important journals within their subject areas from closed subscription-based journals to Open Access titles.”

The policy also calls for more diverse research assessment, citing DORA, and the removal of reliance on journal impact factors for assessment tasks.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Until 2017, the national research funder, The Research Council of Norway (RCN) (Forskningsrådet) was a notable journal funding source for Norwegian journals. RCN used to have yearly application processes for providing baseline journal funding for journals in the social sciences and humanities, which provided support to around 40 journals annually (Wenaas, 2021). Since 2017 a requirement was introduced that all funded journals must be OA without an APC, making it a funding scheme exclusive to supporting Diamond OA journals. In conjunction with this OA requirement a journal funding consortium has been coordinated by Unit (the Norwegian Directorate for ICT and Joint Services in Higher Education & Research) running in its first phase from 2018 to 2021, acting under the name of NÅHST (Norskspråklege opne tidsskrift innanfor humaniora og samfunnsvitskap). This new model pooled money from NRC (~55%), The Ministry of Education and research (~40%), and most universities and university colleges in Norway (~5%). Based on the experiences from that first pilot three-year funding round, the following three-year period from 2021 onwards covered funding of 28 journals, for which an evaluation report is available as (Wikstrøm, Røeggen, Weisteen Bjerde, 2023). The most recent application round was organised in 2023 for the funding period of 2024-2026¹⁴⁷ where some of the central requirements include that journal must be included in DOAJ (or with submitted application provided as appendix) and the national publication channel listing, and they need to have around at least half of their content in Norwegian, with editors being tightly connected to the Norwegian higher education sector (NÅHST, 2024). The NÅHST model emphasises scholarly quality in its selection of journals to be funded, where the research community is involved in selecting the journals who received funding (The National Board of Scholarly Publishing are responsible for organising that component). The NÅHST-

¹⁴⁷ Norwegian-language OpenJournals in the Humanities and Social Sciences (SSH):
<https://www.openscience.no/oa-i-norge/nahst>

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model is a unique example of how substantial funding for Diamond OA journals can be organised through a central model, where no other Nordic countries have anything similar in place. There has recently been talks about potentially expanding the model to also include journals outside of the social sciences and humanities but no official decisions in this regard have been made as of August 2025.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

For journals to be eligible for applying to be part of the NÅHST-model they need to be published as Diamond OA. In other regards there are no direct incentives and rewards that would direct specifically for Diamond OA for journals or publishers.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Norway does not have a national journal portal that would provide common hosting and act as an access point for journals in the country, rather there has mainly been a tradition of universities in the country setting up their own OJS-based journal portals (Björk, 2019). For example, the University of Oslo hosts over 30 journals on their FRITT portal¹⁴⁸. UiT currently publishes 14 scholarly series and around a dozen grey material series on their Septentrio service.¹⁴⁹ The Norwegian University of Science and Technology¹⁵⁰ and the University of Bergen¹⁵¹ host over 10 journals. A summary of the organisation of the technical environment is also provided by Bosman, Kramer, Stojanovski et al. (2024). In 2021 a report by a national committee recommended a national publishing service should be created to centralise the technical publishing environment for institutional Diamond OA publications, however, at the time work on such a service was not initiated (Kolstrup, Aspaas, Hansen et al., 2021). For publishing data sets, based at UiT is used by nearly all institutions in Norway.¹⁵²

Workforce and Capacity Development

From the Norwegian responses to the DIAMAS-survey most reported strong institutional support particularly concerning IT services and human resources support (Bosman, Kramer, & Stojanovski et al 2024). This can be interpreted to be

¹⁴⁸ FRITT portal: <https://journals.uio.no/>

¹⁴⁹ UiT: <https://septentrio.uit.no/>

¹⁵⁰ The Norwegian University of Science and Technology: <https://www.ntnu.no/ojs/>

¹⁵¹ University of Bergen: <https://boap.uib.no/>

¹⁵² DataverseNO: <https://dataverse.no/>

related to the strong integration that many Norwegian Diamond OA journals have to universities where such services are often robust.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

From our queries we could not observe any strong patterns of cross-organisational collaboration, most of the activity seems to be happening on the level of individual institutions. However, such institutions can be quite comprehensive in the scope of coverage (e.g. the FRITT portal that hosts over 30 journals) which is quite a unique trait to specifically the Norwegian Diamond OA environment.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

The performance-based university funding allocation model has included a small component that takes into account the quantity and quality of individual publications (as based on the publication outlets placement in the national publication classification scheme managed by The National Board of Scholarly Publishing (Det nasjonale publiseringsutvalget) (Sivertsen, 2018). While WoS/Scopus metrics are not formally part of the national classification scheme, such information can be used as background for the panels that ultimately decide on the national classifications for the journals. Starting from 2025 use of the publication indicator as part of the performance-based funding model for universities from 2025 (but this continues for hospitals and research institutes) has been abandoned, in conjunction with other research-based performance indicators, in favor of placing more focus on education and degree indicators as the basis for university funding.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

As the timeframe from the 2017 Open Access policy issued by the ministry pointed to 2024 being the end year of the policy, work to create an updated policy was started in 2023. As part of the government's long-term plan 2023-2032 for research and higher education, the task of supporting higher education institutions to develop a new policy beyond 2024 was given to HK-dir, The Research Council of Norway, and Sikt (openscience.no, n.d.). The working group that was formed involved the three research sectors in Norway (The University sector, the research hospitals and the research institutions) and in December 2023 the final report was published (Forskningsrådet, 2024). The 60-page report is not a policy but provides a comprehensive snapshot of the current status. It also outlines recommended tasks for the research sector for promoting Open Access as part of the scholarly publishing system in Norway.

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Of the key Forskningsrådet (2024) recommendations that are of relevance in particular to the Norwegian institutional publishers are the following for each stakeholder group (not all recommendations translated, translations made freely, since they are only available in Norwegian):

✓ Government

- Update the national targets and policy for Open Access to scholarly articles
- Finance and build essential infrastructure for Open Access publishing
- Further develop the national registry of scholarly publication channels, making relevant and good Diamond journals visible
- Develop the NÅHST journal funding scheme to respond to current circumstances. Evaluate possibility to expand beyond SSH disciplines and consider how to support high quality Open Access international journals with an anchoring to Norway
- Develop a funding model to support immediate Open Access to academic books

✓ Funders

- Contribute to funding costs of Open Access and related infrastructure
- Act as driver for developing alternative publication channels, for example Diamond publication channels

✓ Research performing institutions

- Maintain an overview of the institution's costs related to publishing activities
- Enable faculty and research community members to take on editorial responsibilities in high quality Open Access publication channels and peer review within their own areas of expertise
- Enable faculty and research community members to establish new or further develop Open Access publication channels
- Support the development of Diamond OA in line with the Action Plan for Diamond Open Access by establishing a capacity centre for Diamond publishing

✓ Researchers

- To select high-quality publication channels and services that provide immediate Open Access to all research outputs
- Encourage or contribute to the development of good and Open Access discipline-specific publication channels that are of high-quality and provide transparency to costs

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- Researchers who take on editorial responsibilities or participate in editorial work for journals should
 - Reflect on the ownership of the journal
 - Evaluate the editorial independence of the journal in relation to the publisher
 - Evaluate if the journal has a pricing policy that is sensible in relation to incurred costs
 - Select Diamond OA publishing if good alternatives for this are available within the discipline
 - Select a publication channel that asks for a sensible APC if good alternatives are available in the discipline

In the report, all stakeholders are also recommended to further national work on strengthening rights management and rights retention of authors and their institutions. Overall, there are several key recommendations here that are about strengthening Diamond OA publishing. If these recommendations are adopted into practice and future policies, there should be positive development for the circumstances of institutional publishing in Norway. Since the publication of these recommendations in 2024 it has been up to the government to potentially take them into account and shape new official policies around them, however, as of August 2025 there has not yet been any action.

Some stakeholders in Norway have been looking into a population of highly-regarded community-owned Norwegian journals that are currently not Diamond OA and are published by commercial publishers. 10-15 such titles have been identified for potential flipping, but such cases pose challenges in turning Diamond OA without extra funding since they cannot be operated on a purely volunteer-based basis.

There has been interest shown from Norwegian universities in contributing to forming a Nordic Capacity Centre for Diamond OA. Discussion around this topic and the logistics involved have been discussed openly and in closed forums throughout 2025 but nothing more than a placeholder website has emerged as of August 2025 (<https://nordicDiamondoa.org/>).

Starting from January 2023, Universitetsforlaget have implemented a straightforward rights retention policy for its journals which is in line with the rights retention OA policies of large Norwegian universities, enabling authors to freely distribute the accepted manuscript under a CC-BY 4.0 licence (khrono.no, 2023). Due to the lack of a comprehensive Diamond OA funding model for all journals in the country, approaches like this enable funding streams to the journals through

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subscriptions while also enabling immediate liberally licensed OA availability through repositories.

A holistic new research assessment framework has been developed in Norway, going by the name of NOR-CAM. Through the work of the working group led by the Norwegian Rectors Conference, Universities Norway (UHR), six driving principles have been proposed to be at the centre of the new assessment framework (UHR, 2022).

- ✓ “Measure quality and excellence through a better balance between quantitative and qualitative goals
- ✓ Recognise several competencies as merits, but not in all areas at the same time or by each employee
- ✓ Assess all results, activities and competencies in the light of Open Science principles
- ✓ Practice transparency in the assessment and visibility of what should be recognised as merit
- ✓ Promote gender balance and diversity
- ✓ Assist in the concrete practice of job vacancy announcements and assessment processes locally”

The full report linked to from UHR (2022) provides more background context as well as describes how this toolbox of flexible assessment principles is positioned to the many concurrent international developments along the same lines (e.g. DORA, CoARA). Overall, one can deem this development to be a positive for the growth of OA and acknowledgement of editorial work in addition to just publication output.

Norway was one of the early movers when it comes to actions to further OA in the country, and that momentum and leading position has remained over time. There is strong collective action among stakeholders nationally to coordinate the circumstances for OA publishing, both nationally and through international publishers. Institutional publishing is dominantly handled by Universities and University Presses, with some also by scholarly societies. Most of such journals are already Diamond OA, with only a small minority being APC-based or limited to subscription-based access. There is a unique funding mechanism in Norway that provides funding to a select set of high-quality Diamond OA journals within the social sciences and humanities, something which is not present in any other country. Based on the recent national science policy documents, the future looks bright for developing more financial and technical support for Diamond OA journals active in the country.

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

The nonprofit scholarly publishing landscape in Poland, as in many countries, includes academic institutions, government agencies, libraries, publishers, and professional associations. National OA recommendations, funder mandates and institutional OA and open science policies drive nonprofit scholarly publishing activities. According to the Report on the State of Open Science in Poland 2023,¹⁵⁴ 84% of scientific journals in Poland are OA. Over 60% of institutional publishing entities operate under the Diamond OA model.¹⁵⁵ Many learned societies in Poland publish Diamond OA journals.¹⁵⁶

¹⁵³ This is an updated and modified text from Taşkın, Z., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Laakso, M., Torny, D., Arasteh, S., Bargheer, M., Klaus, T., Schima, J., Agnoloni, T., Peruginelli, G., Davidson, A., Franczak, M., Coslado Bernabé M.A., de Pablo Llorente, V., Dobson, H., & Heyman, J. (2024). D5.2 National overviews on sustaining institutional publishing in Europe. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683953>

¹⁵⁴ Open Science in Poland 2023: <https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/analizy/analiza-stanu-otwartej-nauki-w-Polsce>

¹⁵⁵ Agnoloni, T., Bargheer, M., Bosman, J., Caliman Fontes, Lorena, L., de Pablo Llorente, V., Franczak, M., Frantsvåg, J. E., Klaus, T., Kramer, B., Manista, F., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Pellin, E., Peruginelli, G., Rooryck, J., Schima, J., Stojanovski, J., Stone, G., Wnuk, M., Angelaki, M., ... Ševkušić, M. (2024). Institutional publishing in the ERA: Complete country reports. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10473495>

¹⁵⁶ Kansy, A. (2017). Czasopisma towarzystw naukowych w Polsce - raport z badań, Rocznik Bibliologiczno-Prasoznawczy 2017(20), 43-57. <https://depot.ceon.pl/handle/123456789/14567>

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

In 2015, the Ministry of Science and Higher Education (MNiSW) adopted recommendations¹⁵⁷ to support OA to scientific publications and research data, aligning with broader European and global movements towards open science. These recommendations include:

- ✓ Development and adoption of institutional OA policies by universities, research institutes and institutes of the Polish Academy of Sciences (PAN), as well as by the National Science Centre (NCN) and the National Centre for Research and Development (NCBR), which will define the principles of publishing research results in OA (mainly concerning articles in peer-reviewed journals, but also e.g. peer-reviewed conference proceedings, possibly research data).
- ✓ Appointment of OA officers by heads of research units and universities.
- ✓ Transition of scientific journals to OA models.
- ✓ Making dissertations available in open repositories.
- ✓ Monitoring and reporting to the Ministry of Science and Higher Education on progress in the implementation of OA, including systematic analysis of the number of publications produced in a given scientific unit or university to determine the proportion of publications in OA in relation to all publications.
- ✓ Organising OA training for all researchers and PhD students.

In 2018, The Law on Higher Education and Science¹⁵⁸ mandated OA for articles in journals funded through the "Support for Scientific Journals" programme. This law created a legal framework for the implementation of open science in Poland and updated the method of evaluating the quality of scientific activity by including open science as a criterion for evaluating the impact of scientific activity on society and the economy.

Research Funding Agencies: NCN, Polish National Agency for Academic Exchange (NAWA) and NCBR support OA by requiring funded projects to provide OA to

¹⁵⁷ Ministry of Science and Higher Education (MNiSW) recommendations:

https://www.gov.pl/documents/1068557/1069061/20180413_Kierunki_rozwoju_OD_wersja_ostateczna.pdf

¹⁵⁸ Law on Higher Education and Science:

<https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=WDU20180001668>

publications and research data. Both the MNiSW and the NCN recommend the use of CC BY licences for publicly funded publications.

Over 50 Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) adopted OA policies (e.g. Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań; Institute of Literary Research, Institute of Slavic Studies and Institute of Legal Studies of PAN; Jagiellonian University; Jan Długosz University of Humanities and Sciences in Częstochowa; Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce; The Polish Medical Platform that includes the Institute of Medicine in Łódź, Medical University of Białystok, Medical University of Gdańsk, Medical University of Lublin, Medical University of Silesia in Katowice, Medical University of Wrocław, Pomeranian Medical University in Szczecin, and Warsaw Medical University; University of Gdańsk; University of Silesia; and Warsaw School of Economics), and over 30 HEIs have been developing their OA and open science policies.

The majority of university libraries operate based on the university's OA policy, but some have also introduced their own OA policies (e.g. University Library of the University of Warmia and Mazury, POL-on The Integrated System of Information on Science and Higher Education, and the National Library).

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

According to the data presented in the report on Polish science¹⁵⁹ from 2022, nonprofit scholarly publishing is mainly funded by the institution's base funding and there are additional programmes for journals, such as 'Development of scientific journals' launched by the MNiSW in 2021.

According to the Polish report in the Institutional publishing in the ERA¹⁶⁰, nonprofit scholarly publishers mostly rely on fixed and permanent subsidies from their parent organisation, which they consider stable or very stable. Some receive permanent public government funding and others - public time limited grants or subsidies, all of them from outside of their organisations. However, many consider this kind of funding unstable or neither stable nor unstable. Most nonprofit scholarly publishers heavily rely on in-kind support: facilities and premises, general IT services, human

¹⁵⁹ Science in Poland Report: <https://radon.nauka.gov.pl/analizy/nauka-w-Polsce-2022>

¹⁶⁰ Agnoloni, T., Bargheer, M., Bosman, J., Caliman Fontes, Lorena, L., de Pablo Llorente, V., Franczak, M., Frantsvåg, J. E., Klaus, T., Kramer, B., Manista, F., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Pellin, E., Peruginelli, G., Rooryck, J., Schima, J., Stojanovski, J., Stone, G., Wnuk, M., Angelaki, M., ... Ševkušić, M. (2024). Institutional publishing in the ERA: Complete country reports. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10473495>

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resource management, general financial and legal services, salaries of permanent staff, salaries of temporary staff and service specific IT services.

Public funding, despite its relative stability, is criticised by some respondents as forcing collaboration with partners who are not necessarily the most desirable. The respondents declared that “public procurement as the main selection factor defines the price, which causes two main risks - extending the procedure for acquiring people to cooperate, and a small possibility of relying on proven, reliable concealers, editors, deposits or entities that perform other services (printing, IT service, etc.)”.

Institutional publishers face difficulties in sustaining their Diamond OA journals.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

There are no incentives and rewards for Diamond OA publishing in Poland. Research funding is based on assessments of research outputs through quantitative bibliometrics and journals with high impact factors are prioritised in the national evaluation. The largest number of points is assigned to publications in foreign journals, e.g. “Nature”.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

The Polish node of the OPERAS research infrastructure was launched in June 2021 at the

Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IBL PAN) with the mission to advance open scholarly communication in the humanities and social sciences. In December 2024, OPERAS-PL became a consortium of nine academic and research institutions and strongly supports the Diamond OA publishing model.

OPERAS-PL released the Open Humanities Manifesto, signed by over 200 individuals and over 15 organisations, calling for systemic support for open science in Poland and stronger support of nonprofit platforms, science policy reform, and sustainable funding for Diamond OA publishers, especially in the humanities and social sciences, where OA remains underfunded. One of the key objectives of the OPERAS-PL Consortium is to develop community-driven publishing services for journals practicing or transitioning to the Diamond model – combining technical coordination with expert support across partner institutions.

To support the Polish Diamond OA community, the Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling at the University of Warsaw (ICM UW) plays a key role in the development of the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH) within the CRAFT-OA project. As a major contributor to this European infrastructure, ICM’s

involvement significantly boosts Poland's capacity in Diamond OA and positions it as a vital partner in the planned Diamond Capacity Centre – Poland (DCC-PL). ICM UW also maintains Biblioteka Nauki¹⁶¹, which ensures OA to journals and books.

OPEN - the Repository of Open Scientific Publications¹⁶² enables Polish researchers from all fields to openly share their articles, books, conference materials, reports, doctoral theses, and other scientific texts.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Many universities in Poland have their own Diamond OA publishing arms and journals. Various professional associations and scientific societies in Poland also publish their Diamond OA journals and books. Two examples below outline Diamond OA publishing operations of the university press and research institute publishing house.

Adam Mickiewicz University (AMU) Press

AMU Press operates a Policy on Open Access to scientific publications and research data of employees and doctoral students of Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań¹⁶³ introduced by Order No. 47/2020/2021¹⁶⁴ of the Rector of AMU of 8 January 2021. Authors may indicate the OA publication model when submitting their publishing proposal to the press and the press recommends OA publishing. AMU Press publishes Diamond OA journals and books.

The Publishing House of IBL PAN

IBL PAN employs a business model that combines traditional academic publishing with modern OA funding strategies. A key element of this model is the diversification of revenue sources, including the sale of print publications, licensing fees, grants, and external funding. With support from research programmes and institutional resources, IBL PAN promotes the Diamond OA model. IBL PAN journals and selected monograph series are also made available in the freemium model on the OpenEdition Journals¹⁶⁵ and OpenEdition Books¹⁶⁶ platforms. As part of the Science

¹⁶¹ Biblioteka Nauki: <https://bibliotekanauki.pl/>

¹⁶² Open Scientific Publications: <https://open.icm.edu.pl/home>

¹⁶³ Policy on Open Access to scientific publications and research data of employees and doctoral students of Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań:
https://bip.amu.edu.pl/_data/assets/pdf_file/0028/178480/ZR-47-2020-2021-Zal.1.pdf

¹⁶⁴ Order No. 47/2020/2021: https://bip.amu.edu.pl/_data/assets/pdf_file/0034/178477/ZR-47-2020-2021.pdf

¹⁶⁵ OpenEdition Journals: <https://journals.openedition.org/>

¹⁶⁶ OpenEdition Books: <https://books.openedition.org/iblpnan/>

for Society program, OPERAS-PL – led by IBL PAN – partnered with OpenEdition to publish over 80 humanities monographs in Diamond OA. This collaboration exemplifies IBL PAN’s commitment to the Diamond OA publishing model and sustainable, non-profit dissemination of scholarly work.

Workforce and Capacity Development

N/A

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Hosted by IBL PAN, the SCIROs project deepens OPERAS-PL’s efforts by supporting collective publishing and sustainable funding models in collaboration with OpenEdition — building on past successes and integrating Diamond OA into institutional strategies. OPERAS-PL aims to connect researchers, institutions, publishers, librarians, service providers and policymakers to

foster knowledge exchange and drive innovation for the Polish SSH community. As part of the SCIROs project, IBL PAN advances this mission through workshops and experience-sharing with academic institutions across Europe.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

The evaluation of scientific journals is conducted by the MNiSW. The Ministry prepares and updates a list of scientific journals and a list of scholarly publishers that are recognized for their scholarly value. This list categorises journals into various disciplines and assigns points to them based on their perceived scientific merit and international standing. However, the assessment criteria are not fully transparent, so many controversies arise each time the lists are updated. Journals and publishers are awarded points on a scale that reflects their impact and importance in the scientific community. The point system is designed to distinguish between journals based on criteria such as impact factor, international collaboration, and editorial standards. Higher points are given to journals with more stringent peer-review processes, wider international reach, and significant impact in their fields.

The points awarded to journals are used to assess the scientific output of researchers and institutions. Publishing in higher-ranked journals, as determined by this point system, can lead to greater recognition, funding opportunities, and career advancement for scholars.

The list of journals and their point assignments are regularly reviewed and updated to reflect changes in the scientific landscape, ensuring that the evaluation system

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remains current and accurately represents the quality and impact of scholarly publications.

This evaluation system encourages Polish researchers to aim for publication in high-ranked journals, thereby fostering higher standards of research and international collaboration. However, it has also sparked discussions regarding its impact on research priorities and the pressure it places on academics to publish in highly ranked journals.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

- ✓ Develop a comprehensive OA and open science policy that includes Diamond OA publishing.
- ✓ Discuss sustainable funding for Diamond OA publishing.

PORTUGAL

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Since the early 2010s, Portugal has developed a robust ecosystem for nonprofit scholarly publishing and Diamond OA. Key elements include institutional publishing initiatives, national repositories, and a growing network of support services for journals and books.

At the national level, the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) and its digital services unit (FCCN) have played a central role by establishing and maintaining the RCAAP platform (Open Access Scientific Repositories of Portugal) and services like SARC (Scientific Journals Hosting Service). These initiatives ensure the long-term preservation, visibility, and management of scientific outputs, while supporting best practices in Open Access.

Several university presses and institutional platforms have contributed significantly to the Diamond OA landscape: Coimbra University Press, UMinho Editora, Proa (University of Aveiro), Edições P.PORTO (Polytechnic Institute of Porto), Revistas Científicas da Universidade Católica Portuguesa, and PRELO (NOVA University FCSH). These entities provide infrastructure and technical support for publishing Diamond OA journals and books.

The development of interoperability standards, persistent identifiers (DOIs via DataCite), and author identifiers (ORCID) has strengthened the national ecosystem, facilitating metadata propagation and visibility of publications both nationally and internationally. Collaborative efforts such as PUBin and participation in initiatives like the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) further consolidate Portugal's position in nonprofit scholarly publishing.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

In March 2016, the Council of Ministers approved Resolution No. 21/2016, establishing an Interministerial Group tasked with drafting the National Open Science Policy (PNCA). This group developed a strategic plan coordinated by the Ministry of Science, Technology and Higher Education (MCTES)¹⁶⁷.

In May 2014, FCT introduced its first mandatory OA policy for funded projects, aligned with European Commission recommendations. Two documents were published: "Policy on Open Access to Scientific Publications Resulting from R&D Projects Funded by FCT" and "Policy on the Availability of Data and Other Outputs from R&D Projects Funded by FCT" (both 5 May 2014). The latter remains in force, supported by a data management infrastructure¹⁶⁸.

On 7 February 2025, FCT launched a fully updated version aligned with Plan S, covering journal articles, books, chapters, monographs, and theses. The policy introduces a mandatory rights retention strategy: both the Version of Record (VoR) and the accepted manuscript must be made available under a CC BY licence (or similar), without embargo periods, through Gold, Green, or Transformative routes¹⁶⁹.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Alignment with Plan S requires immediate access via Gold, Green, or Transformative routes, with default rights retention. FCT's policy allows APC/BPC costs to be eligible for funding, although no specific funding line for Diamond OA currently exists.

In 2025, FCT financially subsidised:

- ✓ European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH)
- ✓ Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
- ✓ Peer Community In (PCI)

¹⁶⁷ Ciencia Aberta: <https://www.ciencia-aberta.pt/en>;
<https://www.uc.pt/en/openscience/about/policies/portugal/>

¹⁶⁸ Polen: <https://polen.fccn.pt/>

¹⁶⁹ Policy on open access to scientific publications resulting from research funded by the FCT:
<https://www.fct.pt/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Politica-Acesso-Aberto-FCT.pdf>
<https://www.fct.pt/sobre/estudos-e-planeamento-estrategico/politicas-de-ciencia-aberta/acesso-aberto-a-publicacoes-cientificas/>

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Indirect support through FCT and institutional efforts contributes to sustainability. Funds currently allocated to APC-based publishing could gradually be redirected toward Diamond initiatives, as APC models mainly benefit commercial publishers.

Existence

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

FCT endorses the “Action Plan for Diamond Open Access” (Science Europe, 2022).

Some of the incentives are:

- ✓ Conferences and training series: “Arquivos do Saber”, “Jornadas FCCN”, PUB IN.
- ✓ Annual PUB IN meetings (last in March 2025) for knowledge sharing, workshops, and best practice exchange.
- ✓ Call for thematic working groups to modernize the publishing ecosystem.
- ✓ Co-organization of the 16th CONFOA conference (2025) focusing on OA and Open Research Data, Open Science, and information management.

Portuguese institutions participate in CoARA to promote Diamond OA journals in evaluation systems, moving away from journal impact factor dependence. Incentives for recognition of Diamond journals in assessments strengthen adoption.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Since 2008, FCT/FCCN – the digital services unit of the Foundation for Science and Technology – has operated the Open Access Scientific Repositories of Portugal¹⁷⁰, bringing together institutional repositories to ensure long-term preservation and visibility of scientific outputs. RCAAP Portal is an aggregator portal that gathers the descriptions (metadata) of documents deposited in the various resources available in its directory. Whenever possible, it collects the full text to improve search results but does not store any documents. In search results, the title of a document on the RCAAP portal always links to its content in the repository or journal where the document is deposited.

SARC – Scientific Journals Hosting Service¹⁷¹ was created in 2011 to develop the online publication of scientific journals in Portugal, facilitating the management of scientific journals and supporting best practices. The service is based on the OJS –

¹⁷⁰ Open Access Scientific Repositories of Portugal (RCAAP): [RCAAP platform](#)

¹⁷¹ Scientific Journals Hosting Service (SARC): <https://revistas.rcaap.pt/>

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Open Journal System publication and management platform. It started with 10 journals and has now (2025) 44. Applications are accepted periodically. The basic criteria are it must be a scientific journal, published by a Portuguese entity, and available in Open Access. This service is free and includes the provision of software and some essential services such as: OJS hosting and updates, 1 GB of disk space, service monitoring, backups, own domain, security certificate, graphic template adaptation, ORCID plugin configuration, DOI assignment, integration into the RCAAP portal, user support.

Services such as SARC, which uses OJS, are examples of shared infrastructures that directly support the Diamond OA model. Globally, Diamond journals could gain greater impact and visibility through robust search platforms such as OpenAIRE or OpenAlex, though further development of advanced search mechanisms is still needed.

SciELO Portugal¹⁷² contributes to this visibility by providing a curated environment for the dissemination of peer-reviewed Portuguese scientific journals published in Open Access. Managed by FCT/FCCN in collaboration with the University of Minho, it functions as a national indexing and dissemination platform that applies established criteria for quality, interoperability, and editorial consistency. Since its reorganisation under FCT in 2021, SciELO Portugal has aligned its processes with international standards supporting the discoverability, credibility, and long-term accessibility of the journals it includes. It complements services such as SARC and PUBin, reinforcing the national infrastructure available to Diamond OA journals.

Since 2019, RCAAP (Open Access Scientific Repositories of Portugal), through FCCN/FCT, has created the Persistent Identifier Assignment Service via DataCite. This service allows institutions in Portugal to assign DOI persistent identifiers, free of charge, to their publications. Its objectives are to make national scientific output more visible and citable, and to promote the use of high-quality metadata across systems, enabling interoperability between CiênciaVita, ORCID, institutional repositories, and the RCAAP Portal. This initiative aligns with the “DOAS: The Diamond OA Standard” requirement that publishers register article identifiers with registration agencies immediately upon publication.

PUBin¹⁷³ is an initiative launched in 2020 that aims to support scientific publishing in Portugal. This platform offers support services for the publication of national Diamond journals. Some of their goals are: to promote the integrated management

¹⁷² SciELO Portugal: <https://scielo.pt/scielo.php?lng=es>

¹⁷³ PUBin Platform: <https://www.pubin.pt/sobre/>

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of the presence of national scientific journals in Open Access in national and international directories and indexing platforms; to create an ecosystem for managing these journals in order to simplify, integrate and make coherent the current offer of platforms for managing the editorial life cycle (submission, review, publication) of national scientific journals; modernise editorial lifecycle management platforms in order to embrace Open Science concepts, such as open peer review or open annotations, enable new paradigms of citizen engagement and the use of internationally recognised formats and protocols; promote the digital preservation of digital objects from scientific journals. SARC became one of the services provided within PUBin, alongside others such as JATS-XML support, digital preservation support, or training.

Interoperability is enhanced through OAI-PMH aggregation, DOI assignment via DataCite, and ORCID adoption, enabling metadata propagation across systems such as CiênciaVita, institutional repositories, and RCAAP. A self-assessment tool for journal quality standards is in development.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Institutions provide publishing infrastructure and coordination:

- ✓ Coimbra University Press – Diamond OA books and journals since 2013.
- ✓ UMinho Editora – Diamond OA University Press.
- ✓ Proa – Univ. Aveiro Open Access journals platform.
- ✓ Edições P.PORTO – Polytechnic Institute of Porto Publisher.
- ✓ Revistas Científicas da Universidade Católica Portuguesa – UC journals portal.
- ✓ PRELO – NOVA Univ. FCSH Journals and Books Platform.

Universidade Católica Portuguesa supports Diamond OA journals through its libraries, offering technical support, sharing best practices, and providing platforms such as OpenBooks¹⁷⁴ and the scientific journals portal¹⁷⁵.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

FCT has established the next agreements and collaborations to strengthen Diamond OA:

- ✓ National cooperation with Redalyc (December 2024) for visibility, training, and editorial management.

¹⁷⁴ Open Books: <https://openbooks.ucp.pt/>

¹⁷⁵ Scientific Journals PT: <https://revistas.ucp.pt/>

- ✓ PUBin as the national hub for EDCH.
- ✓ Shared infrastructure support via RCAAP, SARC, PUBin, and institutional presses.
- ✓ Collaboration includes training, digital preservation support, and advanced tool usage.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Quality is being promoted through:

- ✓ Training workshops and conferences.
- ✓ Self-assessment tools for Diamond journals (in development).
- ✓ Adoption of international standards for metadata, DOIs, and ORCID identifiers.
- ✓ Alignment with COARA and reform of research assessment systems to value Diamond OA outputs over impact-factor-based evaluation.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Several policy and funding actions have been put in place to support and advance Diamond OA publishing, including:

- ✓ FCT policies aligned with Plan S mandates immediate OA and rights retention
- ✓ Financial support to EDCH, DOAJ, and PCI
- ✓ National cooperation agreements (Redalyc, FCT, University of Minho)
- ✓ Infrastructural support via RCAAP, SARC, and PUBin
- ✓ Conferences, training, and thematic working groups to promote adoption and sustainability
- ✓ Encouragement of evaluation reforms to favor Diamond OA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Scholarly publishing in Serbia is primarily driven by universities (nine public and five private), research institutes (78), learned societies, and small not-for-profit organisations founded and run by scholars. It is estimated that more than 400 scholarly journals are published in Serbia, which is a relatively large number considering the size of the research community (over 17,000 researchers, according to official data). Almost all are free-to-read, about two-thirds of have explicit OA policies, and the vast majority do not charge publication fees. While subscriptions to print editions are still present, there have hardly been any scholarly journals that charge for access to their online versions. This is largely possible thanks to the system of national subsidies for journals, institutional financial and in-kind support, and volunteer work of editors, editorial board members and reviewers (Agnoloni et al. 2024).

Scholarly publishing in Serbia is still transitioning from print to digital, which is particularly evident in academic book publishing, where digital formats are regarded as secondary to printed books. Open access to digital versions of books is typically delayed and enabled through institutional websites with limited interoperability and, recently, through repositories (Ševkušić et al. 2017).

The actors who have played a significant role in the development of OA publishing in Serbia include:

- ✓ Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation as the main policy maker and funder;
- ✓ Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), many of which publish OA journals and books, and promote OA;

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- ✓ Serbian Library Consortium for Coordinated Acquisition (KoBSON), which maintains the doiSerbia journal platform, provides training and support to editors and publishers, and coordinates the newly established National Diamond OA Capacity Centre;
- ✓ Academic libraries, which support OA publishing through infrastructure, expertise, and services;
- ✓ Team for Open Science in Serbia (TONuS), a task force established by the Ministry to draft the national OS policy and oversee its implementation;
- ✓ Serbian OpenAIRE National Open Access Desk (NOAD), which has played a key role in developing the national repository network and promoting best practices in scholarly publishing.

In 2025, the National Diamond OA Capacity Centre was established. The Centre will support Diamond OA publishers, foster cohesion among fragmented initiatives and promote alignment with the Diamond Open Access Standard.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

A major policy maker and funder in the area of OA publishing in Serbia is the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation. It holds significant potential to shape the landscape of OA scholarly publishing through regulations guiding journal evaluation, criteria for the allocation of annual subsidies, and the implementation of the national open science policy. However, this potential is not consistently leveraged to advance OA.

Serbia adopted its first open science policy in 2018, mandating OA for all publications resulting from publicly funded research, including journals, books and conference proceedings, either through Open Access publishing venues or repositories. However, attempts to align the requirements for publishing subsidies with the policy's provisions and recognised best practices (e.g. mandatory Open Access statements and the use of Creative Commons (CC) licences) were unsuccessful.

Most institutional policies did not explicitly address institutional publishing, but some institutions included OA-related provisions in their publishing regulations (e.g. the OA status of institutional journals, the use of CC licences, provisions governing co-publishing arrangements with commercial book publishers to ensure that Open Access to books could be achieved via repositories).

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In December 2024, an updated policy — Open Science Platform 2.0¹⁷⁶ — was adopted. In addition to encouraging researchers to prioritise Diamond OA venues whenever possible, the policy explicitly endorses the Diamond OA model and stipulates that public subsidies may be awarded only to Diamond OA journals. Journals, monographs, and conference proceedings that receive public funding are required to enable immediate OA and comply with open licensing provisions. Following the adoption of the policy, these conditions were integrated into national calls for subsidies.

Regulations guiding journal assessment public subsidies for publishing have recently led to important shifts in scholarly publishing. Journals and conference proceedings increasingly adopt persistent identifiers, as the Ministry requires DOIs for all publications and ORCID iDs for authors affiliated with Serbian institutions. Consequently, more conference proceedings are being made available in OA as the commonly used platforms (doiFil, UBKG, Zenodo offer OA as the default option.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Scholarly publishing is largely sustained through a combination of public subsidies and institutional financial and in-kind (providing office space, IT infrastructure, technical services, or administrative assistance) support. Thanks to this, many journals work with an approved annual budget, which tends to be modest. Publishing operations are generally not expected to generate profit. Collective funding models and author contributions are rare.

Public subsidies for scholarly publishing in Serbia are provided by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation through annual calls that cover journals, monographs, and conferences. The number of supported journals and the allocated amounts have been steadily increasing over the past ten years. In 2023, the Ministry allocated more than 700,000 EUR to support 216 journals.¹⁷⁷ According to the financial plan, more than 900,000 EUR will be allocated to journal subsidies in 2025.¹⁷⁸ However, until the 2024 call, even print-only and APC-based journals were eligible for support.

¹⁷⁶ Open Science Platform 2.0: https://nitra.gov.rs/images/nauka/TONuS-Platforma_2.0-Final-eng.pdf

¹⁷⁷ Public subsidies for scholarly publishing: https://nitra.gov.rs/images/nauka/dokumenta/Izvestaj%20o%20stanu%20u%20nauci_2023.pdf

¹⁷⁸ Public subsidies for scholarly publishing: <https://nitra.gov.rs/images/ministarstvo/dokumenta/budzet-ministarstva/Finansijski%20plan%20za%202025.pdf>

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The subsidy system is insufficiently transparent, as neither the lists of funded publications, nor the amounts awarded to individual publications are publicly available. The funding system tends to favour long-established journals with higher rankings in the national research assessment system, where particular value is placed on journal impact factors and inclusion in databases such as Web of Science and Scopus. At the same time, new journals are at a disadvantage because they often need to gain international recognition before they can get national funding.

Platforms rely on different funding sources. doiSerbia is funded by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation. Most institutional publishing platforms rely on institutional in-kind or financial resources, while those offering services beyond their parent institutions usually charge affordable fees to external users (e.g. doiFil, UBKG). However, the income generated is not always reinvested in the platforms' further development. The business model of the privately owned platform Serbian Citation Index (SCIndeks) is based on tiered service packages offered for affordable fees.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

There are no formal financial or non-financial rewards (e.g. career or award-based incentives) for Diamond OA publishing. However, editorial work is taken into account in research assessment and promotion procedures.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Infrastructure for scholarly publishing in Serbia is highly fragmented, with many individual journal websites and several platforms offering varying quality of service.

The first online platform in Serbia to host multiple OA journals was doiSerbia¹⁷⁹, launched in 2005 with funding from EIFL. The goal was to provide an online presence for prominent Serbian journals. The national library consortium team, based at the National Library of Serbia, created landing pages and assigned DOIs to journal articles free of charge, on the condition that publishers made their content openly accessible (Kosanović 2012). After the project had ended, the ministry responsible for science continued to support the platform, which now hosts over 55 active journals. However, doiSerbia ceased expanding in 2011, mainly due to limited human resources.

doiSerbia does not support editorial or publishing workflows. Journals manage those processes separately - either manually or using other platforms - and interact

¹⁷⁹ Online platform in Serbia for OA journals: <https://doiserbia.nb.rs/>

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with doiSerbia only at the stage of assigning a DOI to an accepted manuscript or final PDF. The doiSerbia model has inspired the creation of other custom-built DOI-assignment platforms in Serbia, such as doiFil¹⁸⁰, managed by the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Philology, and DOI UBKG¹⁸¹, managed by the University of Kragujevac Library.

There are no nationwide aggregators or publishing platforms in Serbia. Until 2015, the Serbian Citation Index (SCIndeks)¹⁸², developed by the non-profit organisation Centre for Evaluation in Education and Science (CEON/CEES) through public funding and international projects, served as a national citation index and a tool for journal assessment, along with enabling journals to display their content at the abstract level or in full text. This custom-made platform built on proprietary software combined features that were available to all journals free of charge and those offered for a fee.¹⁸³ In 2015, the role and business model of SCIndeks changed after support from the ministry responsible for science had been discontinued. The platform currently hosts more than 200 active journals, the vast majority of which are Diamond OA (Ševkušić et al. 2020).

This shift resulted in significant content loss, as CEON/CEES could no longer host all journals previously available on the platform. The Ministry did not offer a new infrastructure and many journals struggled to reestablish their online presence for a long time, leading to the emergence of independent journal websites based on popular free and open source content management systems (e.g. Wordpress) and adoption of OJS-based platforms, as well as to content duplication across platforms - e.g. a single journal may display content via doiSerbia (offering free DOIs), SCIndeks (a paid service), and a standalone website. This practice, which is often seen by journals as a safeguard against content loss and vendor lock-in, highlights a widespread lack of understanding of digital publishing standards and best practices.

Common issues that limit the functionality of journal websites include outdated website software, fragmented setups where OJS is used only for submissions while content is hosted elsewhere, and the continued manual handling of submissions and peer review despite using OJS.

¹⁸⁰ Faculty of Philology, University of Belgrade: <https://doi.fil.bg.ac.rs/>

¹⁸¹ University of Kragujevac Library: <https://doi.ub.kg.ac.rs/>

¹⁸² Serbian Citation Index (SCIndeks): <https://scindeks.ceon.rs/>

¹⁸³ For example, in 2011, Open Journal Systems was integrated into it to enable editorial and publishing workflows and this feature was offered to journals on a Software-as-a-Service basis, for a fee (Ševkušić et al. 2020).

Only a small number of Serbian journals use services provided by commercial international publishers. The primary motivation for such partnerships is the expectation that collaboration will lead to faster inclusion in major citation indexes. However, this rarely happens, which is why the trend has never gained significant traction and is now even declining. Given the substantial costs of these services, some journals have been forced to introduce Article Processing Charges (APCs) to cover expenses.

The infrastructure for online book publishing is virtually non-existent. There are only a few isolated platforms based on Open Monograph Press (e.g. Anthroserbiabooks¹⁸⁴, managed by the Department of Ethnology and Anthropology at the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Philosophy and Open Monographs Press¹⁸⁵ by the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering). In recent years, repositories have played a significant role in enabling Open Access to scholarly books.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Research performing organisations (RPOs) are the primary publishers, often relying on public subsidies to cover the costs of typesetting, printing and publishing platforms. Institutional support for scholarly publishing can take various forms. In some cases, institutions establish and fund dedicated publishing units with paid staff and infrastructure (e.g. University of Niš) to support all or most of their affiliated journals. In other cases, institutions provide financial support by covering the cost of external publishing services on behalf of individual journals. Most institutions provide in-kind support (especially office space, IT infrastructure, human resources management). Institutional libraries provide various types of support to publishing operations (e.g. PID management, copyediting, reference checking, etc.) but the scope of this support remains vague, while this work is usually insufficiently recognised and often unrewarded. Libraries are rarely responsible for the management of publishing platforms (a notable exception is the University of Kragujevac Library), most likely due to understaffing and limited IT resources.

Strictly speaking, there are no university presses in Serbia. This is partly due to the highly decentralized structure of Serbian universities, where faculties and institutes function as fully independent legal entities. While some universities do have publishing departments, only the University of Niš operates a university-level OJS-

¹⁸⁴ Anthroserbiabooks: <https://www.anthroserbiabooks.org/index.php/asb>

¹⁸⁵ Open Monographs Press: <https://ebooks.sf.bg.ac.rs/index.php/1>

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based journal publishing platform, and the University of Kragujevac Library maintains a platform for assigning DOIs.

Very often, institutional publishing departments are responsible primarily for monographs and textbooks, while academic journals are typically managed independently by editors, sometimes without any formal involvement from the publishing department. Moreover, institutional publishing departments are generally focused on overseeing printed editions rather than digital publishing.

Major national institutions, such as the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts and Matica Srpska, have active publishing departments and produce a significant number of publications. Although their outputs are available through their websites and institutional repositories, they have not developed dedicated online publishing platforms.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Institutional Diamond OA publishing in Serbia faces a serious lack of human resources. Long-term employment restrictions in the public sector have made it impossible to hire qualified staff. Editors usually work on a volunteer basis, and editorial assistants or other staff are often not paid. IT support is another major challenge, since it is difficult to find experts familiar with OJS or OMP. In some cases, editors themselves manage the installation and setup of the system. Finding peer reviewers outside the publishing institution is also not easy. Services such as copyediting, translation, and typesetting are often outsourced, but they are sometimes carried out by librarians or research support staff on a volunteer basis.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

The high level of infrastructural fragmentation in Serbian scholarly publishing is both a consequence of limited collaboration among publishers and a barrier to further cooperation. Even journals published by the same institution often rely on different service providers and have completely different website setups. Collaboration among major public platforms such as doiSerbia, doiFil, and UBKG has so far been limited mainly to exchanging information on best practices. To address this gap, KoBSON and the EIFL OA Programme Country Coordinator have acted as the key hub for information exchange, support, and training, helping journals deal with technical challenges and adopt more consistent publishing practices.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

A performance-based model is used to allocate journal subsidies, taking into account the journal's ranking in the national evaluation system and the number of articles published. In Serbia, journals are evaluated annually according to the Rulebook on the Categorization and Ranking of Scientific Journals.¹⁸⁶ An annex to the rulebook lists the formal requirements a journal must meet to be evaluated. Although efforts have been made to align these requirements with those of the DOAJ, full alignment has not yet been achieved. Some progress has been made, such as introducing a requirement for journals to have transparent editorial policies. The quality assessment mainly relies on bibliometric indicators, especially Web of Science metrics and data from the national bibliometric report.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

While Serbia's first national Open Science policy, Open Science Platform, adopted in 2018, did not explicitly address Diamond OA, the revised policy adopted in December 2024 – Open Science Platform 2.0 – introduces a stronger commitment to this model. It recommends that researchers publish in Diamond OA journals whenever possible.

To further mainstream Diamond OA, the 2024 policy requires that all publicly funded journals align with Diamond OA principles. The Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation actively supports this model by offering public subsidies exclusively to Diamond OA journals. In the latest call for subsidies, launched in December 2024, applicants were required to provide proof of their Diamond OA status as a condition for funding. The policy has faced resistance from several APC-based journals, and the final outcome of its implementation remains uncertain.

To ensure effective policy implementation, national regulations on scholarly publishing, journal evaluation, and public subsidies should be aligned with the Diamond Open Access Standard, accompanied by clear guidelines and training.

¹⁸⁶ Categorization and Ranking of Scientific Journals: <https://pravno-informacioni-sistem.rs/eli/rep/sgrs/ministarstva/pravilnik/2024/80/4/reg>

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Spain is a decentralised state with a National Government and 17 Autonomous Communities (CCAA). The Spanish Science, Technology, and Innovation System (SECTI) is institutionally and administratively distributed across both levels. While most R&D funding and evaluation agencies operate under the national government, universities are primarily governed by regional authorities (their publishing departments are drivers of scientific and academic dissemination in the country).

This structure, while allowing local autonomy, often results in institutions feeling isolated and lacking coordination. This underlines the need for clear national and European-level guidance to support Diamond OA publishing. Additionally, the regional authority over universities contributes to disparities in institutional commitment, resources, and strategic focus regarding Diamond OA.

The main instruments reflecting national research and innovation policy are:

- ✓ The Spanish Strategy for Science, Technology and Innovation (EECTI) 2021–2027: Designed to maximise coordination between national and regional planning, and to align Spanish R&D policy with the European Union’s Horizon Europe framework.

¹⁸⁷ This is an updated and modified text from Taşkın, Z., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Laakso, M., Torný, D., Arasteh, S., Bargheer, M., Klaus, T., Schima, J., Agnoloni, T., Peruginelli, G., Davidson, A., Franczak, M., Coslado Bernabé M.A., de Pablo Llorente, V., Dobson, H., & Heyman, J. (2024). D5.2 National overviews on sustaining institutional publishing in Europe. Zenodo.

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- ✓ The State Plan for Scientific and Technological Research and Innovation (PEICTI): A government initiative that sets out priorities and actions to promote scientific excellence, foster public–private collaboration, address societal challenges, and enhance knowledge transfer between academia and society.
- ✓ The Organic Law of Universities. Organic Law 2/2023, of 22 March, on the University System: The current legislation governing universities in Spain. It was published in the Official State Gazette (BOE) on 23 March 2023 and entered into force on 12 April 2023.

Although these legal frameworks exist, current legislation and administrative processes often limit practical implementation—particularly in areas such as human resources and funding execution—hindering the development of Diamond OA.

Public universities—governed primarily by regional authorities—play a leading role in scholarly publishing, with institutional publishing services acting as key players in the dissemination of academic knowledge. The Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), along with other Public Research Bodies (OPs), further contributes to the country’s strong research output. All these institutions have begun to incorporate and implement institutional Open Access policies into their statutes, involving their libraries, publishing services, outreach units, and other departments.

According to DOAJ, Spain hosts 1,004 Diamond Open Access journals, illustrating the scale and consolidation of fully OA scholarly publishing. Altogether, the eight FECYT assessments have evaluated nearly 1,200 journals, of which, in 2024, 627 (52.25%) were FECYT-certified¹⁸⁸. In the 2025 assessment, 752 journals were evaluated, and 624 of them met the six criteria required by the Diamond Discovery Hub, underscoring the solid alignment between Spanish scholarly publishing and emerging standards for high-quality Diamond OA practices.

The non-profit Diamond OA ecosystem in Spain is supported by several national initiatives. The Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT), under the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities (MICIU), operates infrastructures such as the national OA repository harvester, RECOLECTA, and the platform for managing and publishing scientific journals, RECYT. These infrastructures are based on free and open-source software, which serves as a fundamental pillar of

¹⁸⁸ Coslado Bernabé, M.A., et al. "Open science indicator compliance by Spanish scientific journals" *Journal of Data and Information Science*, vol. 10, no. 4, Chinese Academy of Sciences, National Science Library, 2025, pp. 219-242. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jdis-2025-0042>

their development. Additionally, the biennial FECYT Journal Quality Seal promotes high editorial standards among national journals.

A national call managed by FECYT for the promotion of Open Science exemplifies governmental support not only for infrastructure development but also for the broader implementation of Open Science practices at the national level. This funding initiative has supported numerous institutional projects aimed at strengthening repositories, CRIS systems, and open publishing platforms, thereby facilitating the integration of Open Science across the research ecosystem.

The Union of Spanish University Publishers (UNE)¹⁸⁹ has developed a well-structured infrastructure with its scientific journals' portal, which serves as an essential tool for researchers looking to publish in Spanish open-access journals. This portal, created by UNE, brings together a wide variety of publications from universities and research centres, offering a robust platform to enhance the visibility and impact of academic research. The journals included in the portal cover various fields of knowledge, such as history, philosophy, art, philology, linguistics, social sciences, and education.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

Spain's legislative and strategic framework supports Diamond OA in alignment with European Open Science goals. Both the Science, Technology and Innovation Law (Art. 37.2) and the Organic Law on the University System (LOSU, 2023) establish mandates for publicly funded research to be openly accessible. Researchers are required to deposit publications and research data into open repositories, creating legal support for non-commercial, open dissemination models. Additionally, regional governments (for example, Madrid, Catalonia, Asturias) reinforce these mandates with localised OA policies.

Despite this legal support, practical challenges such as rigid hiring laws, limited human resources, and administrative complexity prevent full implementation.

The National Open Science Strategy (ENCA) promotes open, transparent, and socially impactful scholarly communication, creating a policy ecosystem to facilitate Diamond OA. FECYT coordinates the actions of this strategy, and within its framework, several committees have been established, including one at the

¹⁸⁹ Union of Spanish University Publishers (UNE): <https://www.une.es/>

governmental level and another at the technical level, to guide and oversee its implementation.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Although there is no exclusive funding for Diamond OA, multiple national initiatives indirectly support its growth. The María de Guzmán Call, managed by FECYT, is a key funding mechanism that has distributed funding through successive calls to support repository development, CRIS systems, and open publishing platforms.

The lack of dedicated funding for Diamond OA is a major barrier. There are existing and helpful initiatives that are not enough to cover essential costs such as human resources, training, and editorial needs.

Despite this support, sustainability challenges persist—particularly in maintaining consistent staffing, technical upgrades, and editorial services at institutional publishing services.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Spain's academic assessment systems recognize Open Access publishing. The ANECA incorporates Open Access into research and career evaluations, considering repository deposits and open availability as new merit criteria. Diamond OA publishing still lacks recognition in reward structures compared to Gold OA. However, there is growing awareness of the need to reward nonprofit publishing that emphasises multilingualism, editorial autonomy, and regional relevance.

In this context, the CSIC has recently introduced an indicator for “Membership on Editorial Boards,” which will be considered in the allocation of productivity based on objective compliance. Although its weight is still small compared to other indicators, it represents a first step toward internal recognition of such contributions.

Recognition is still limited: standardized rewards are needed for Diamond OA activities to be truly valued within academic careers.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

The Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT) plays a crucial role in supporting the infrastructure for Diamond OA publishing at the national level. FECYT acts as a national node and strengthens its work as a provider of public services for the Diamond academic publishing system. This includes the

development of an ecosystem based on accessible, interoperable, and open scientific information.

Additionally, FECYT carries out activities and services to support the Spanish editorial community, including:

- ✓ The ARCE service, supporting the professionalization of Spanish scientific journals.
- ✓ The biennial call for the evaluation of scientific journals.
- ✓ The open scientific publishing platform RECYT.
- ✓ The annual evaluation of academic monograph collections in collaboration with ANECA and UNE.

These shared infrastructures are essential, but professionalisation and stable human resources remain as gaps: some tasks are still voluntary.

In addition to FECYT's services, there is a range of infrastructures, repositories, and collaboration networks at the institutional, national, and European levels that serve as a strong complement to the Diamond OA ecosystem.¹⁹⁰ These services include:

- ✓ DIGITAL.CSIC¹⁹¹: The institutional repository of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). It operates as a multidisciplinary OA archive and also provides dedicated publishing services for Diamond journals through its *Diamante en verde* program. This service offers repository hosting, permanent storage, DOI assignment, curation and preparation for external indexing, digital preservation, and even an optional open peer-review module. This one is a practical example of “Repository-as-Publisher” that ensures sustainability, community control and barrier-free access.
- ✓ UB Dipòsit Digital¹⁹²: The institutional repository of the Universitat de Barcelona (UB). It provides OA to a wide range of teaching, research and institutional outputs, including articles, theses, books, book chapters and research data. The UB Dipòsit is supported by the UB's CRAI services, which offer guidance on publishing, copyright, OA and repository use. Materials deposited are also harvested by cooperative repositories such as RECERCAT, ensuring wider dissemination.

¹⁹⁰ Universitat de Barcelona. (2024). *Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA*. Dipòsit Digital de la Universitat de Barcelona.

<https://diposit.ub.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams/e4d7a39e-c43d-468c-a595-f53859892619/content>

¹⁹¹ DIGITAL. CSIC. <https://digital.csic.es/>

¹⁹² UB Dipòsit Digital. <https://diposit.ub.edu/home>

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- ✓ **European Initiatives:** Projects such as DIAMAS¹⁹³ and the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH)¹⁹⁴ that work to map, coordinate, and improve the efficiency, quality, and sustainability of Diamond publishing services. These initiatives promote the development of quality standards, including the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS)¹⁹⁵, the creation of learning pathways, and the generation of self-assessment guides and tools, as well as shared funding frameworks. Spain participates in these efforts through FECYT, contributing to the harmonization and enhancement of Diamond OA publishing practices.
- ✓ **Spanish Institutional Repositories:** Various institutional repositories of Spanish universities (e.g., RiuNet — UPV¹⁹⁶, Biblos-e Archivo (UAM Institutional Repository)¹⁹⁷, GREDOS (USAL Documentary Repository)¹⁹⁸, Archivo Digital UPM¹⁹⁹, etc.) host OA academic outputs such as articles, theses, and research data. They contribute to the visibility, preservation, and accessibility of knowledge, providing a foundation for, or complementing, Diamond publishing.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Universities and research-performing organizations are central to Spain's Diamond OA ecosystem. Many maintain in-house publishing services, often run by libraries and their own IT staff, in collaboration with academic editors and reviewers. These services operate on non-APC models and are often embedded in larger open science strategies.

University consortia like Consorcio Madroño (Madrid) and CSUC (Catalonia) have developed shared platforms and services, such as Pagoda for Data Management Plans and shared repositories. These efforts help lower costs and foster sustainability through collaboration.

However, institutional commitment is uneven, needing quality seals, formal recognition, and dedicated funding to make these services sustainable and valued.

¹⁹³ DIAMAS: <https://diamasproject.eu/>

¹⁹⁴ European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH): <https://diamas.org/>

¹⁹⁵ Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS): <https://zenodo.org/records/15128179>

¹⁹⁶ RiuNet - UPV: <https://riunet.upv.es/home>

¹⁹⁷ Biblos-e Archivo (UAM Institutional Repository): <https://repositorio.uam.es/home>

¹⁹⁸ GREDOS (USAL Documentary Repository): <https://gredos.usal.es/>

¹⁹⁹ Archivo Digital UPM: <https://oa.upm.es/>

Workforce and Capacity Development

Sustaining Diamond OA publishing depends on dedicated professionals as editors, technical staff, and repository and publishing platform managers, who often operate without formal recognition or stable contracts. Much of this work is performed on a voluntary basis, harming the long-term viability of the system.

The current volunteer-based workforce threatens system sustainability. Training programs are a step forward, but long-term professionalisation requires funding, stable contracts, and career recognition.

Collaboration between Publishers and Service Providers

Collaboration is a cornerstone of Spain's Diamond OA infrastructure. Institutions, consortia, and national bodies like CRUE, URICI-CSIC, and FECYT have established shared platforms and services to support Open Access publishing.

Shared infrastructures like RECYT and RECOLECTA, combined with national coordination by FECYT, exemplify Spain's collective approach as it reduces duplication and promotes resource use across the scholarly publishing ecosystem.

This collaboration should also extend to policy development, funding mechanisms, and reward systems to ensure long-term impact.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Spain has a robust quality assurance framework for scholarly journals, led by the FECYT Scientific Journals Assessment System. Since 2008, FECYT has awarded its Quality Seal to hundreds of journals, many under Diamond OA models.

The evaluation combines quantitative metrics (e.g., editorial policies, citation data) with expert panel reviews. This process enhances journal credibility, improves indexing opportunities, and supports journal inclusion in international databases.

Universities also conduct internal quality reviews, especially for journals managed by university presses. However, smaller and emerging journals still face barriers to meeting these standards without compromising editorial independence or regional diversity.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Spain has a strong public infrastructure and a policy framework for Open Access publishing. The country needs to fully support and scale up Diamond OA publishing.

Concrete and actionable policies—not just high-level strategies—are needed. It is recommended to establish coordinated national funding, formal recognition of editorial work, and specific incentives for staff and researchers.

The following policy and funding strategies could help embed Diamond OA as a model of scholarly communication:

- ✓ The creation of specific policies and financial instruments, but also the recognition of institutional and community-led publishing initiatives as integral parts of the national research system.
- ✓ The role of OPIs and universities could also be expanded. These institutions already contribute significantly to Spain's scientific output and host numerous journals and repositories. With appropriate support and funding, they could further develop, and initiate publishing programs aligned with the Diamond OA model.
- ✓ Mechanisms led by CRUE, CSIC, or FECYT could be reinforced to improve and enable shared infrastructures, training opportunities, and technical services.

Policy harmonisation could provide coherence and legal clarity, ensuring that Diamond OA is referenced in national regulations and university policies. This would support formal recognition of institutional publishing services and help define funding eligibility criteria, enabling their professionalisation and expansion.

FECYT has developed various policies and funding actions to consolidate Diamond OA publishing at the national level. These actions include:

- ✓ Financial support providing direct or indirect funding through public funds, donations, or other sources of income to enable free access for both authors and readers, ideally covering all costs.
- ✓ Sustainability plan, with a strategy to ensure the economic viability of the Diamond OA business model in the medium term. This includes a clear vision of available funding sources and other external and internal resources aligned with future cost expectations for maintenance and development.
- ✓ Funding calls to increase compliance, implementation, scope, and awareness of national and international quality and interoperability standards for institutional repositories. This includes the creation and

updating of data repositories, improving data quality and interoperability with other infrastructures, and training and capacity building in data management.

- ✓ Dissemination and training through continuous training and information materials, organising online courses on Open Science, institutional repositories, and research data for both researchers and repository management staff.

While these measures are valuable, they do not always cover staff costs or provide career recognition, creating a sustainability gap. A comprehensive approach should therefore include HR support, infrastructure maintenance, incentives, and institutional recognition.

A shared approach involving public administrations, research institutions, and service providers will be essential to consolidate the ecosystem. Long-term sustainability will require coordinated action across ministries, regional governments, and academic bodies, ensuring that Diamond OA becomes a viable and recognized part of Spain's research landscape.

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

The 2024 National Open Access Strategy²⁰⁰ includes objectives that relate directly to Diamond OA and an intention to introduce regulatory framework conditions that promote Open Access to all scholarly publications, introduce a secondary publishing right under Swiss law, and orientate contract legislation towards more affordability and sustainability in scholarly publishing.

Community efforts in Switzerland have focused on developing infrastructure that can support Diamond OA publishing, particularly by building networks and developing shared services, including a Swiss Community of Practice for OJS. The “Platinum Open Access Funding” (PLATO) project (2022-2025) has done much to provide insight into the Diamond OA ecosystem in Switzerland by publishing a landscape study (2023) and to mobilise the Swiss Diamond OA community, also through the first Swiss Diamond OA Conference and a Diamond OA Workshop Day in 2025.

Further network-building efforts are underway, with the one-year DOACH project working to become a national capacity hub for Swiss institutions and develop shared services. Diamond OA leadership comes from the institutions, where libraries host scholarly publishing platforms and work together by building up these networks and sharing services to make that infrastructure more robust. Furthermore, in 2025, swissuniversities (the umbrella organisation of the Swiss universities) approved a call to form a national Diamond OA consortium.

²⁰⁰ 2024 National Open Access Strategy:

https://www.swissuniversities.ch/fileadmin/swissuniversities/Dokumente/Hochschulpolitik/Open_Access/Swiss-National-Open-Access-Strategy-2024-en.pdf

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Past efforts to raise awareness of Diamond OA have resulted in some project-based funding from swissuniversities. While these funds are limited to the very short term (with the PLATO project ending in June 2025, the CoDOA and the DOACH projects ending in 2026), the premise of these projects is to better understand the landscape and potential for Diamond OA in Switzerland and to build collaborative infrastructure that could sustain Diamond OA nationally in the longer term.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

The Swiss OA community is increasingly convinced of focusing on alternative routes to OA, such as Diamond OA, including swissuniversities²⁰¹, the national rectors' conference and the voice of Swiss universities, which also promotes Diamond OA. This shows that Diamond OA awareness-raising efforts have started to take root. As key players, together with a wide range of actors from the Swiss community, including an association of editors and the six partner institutions, involved in the PLATO project fed into the revised 2024 National Open Access Strategy²⁰², which now includes objectives (5 & 6) that relate directly to Diamond OA. It clearly states its support for the model:

“Scholarly publications in Diamond OA are financially viable and a robust alternative for authors.” (swissuniversities, 2024)

It also stipulates measurable qualitative and quantitative indicators for Diamond OA, including the proportion of scholarly articles published in Diamond OA, the financial sustainability of Diamond OA publishing and researcher acceptance of Diamond OA publishing options. This focus on affordability, sustainability, and diversity is new since 2024 and reflects an approach to Diamond OA that both aims for equity and allows for compromise: the strategy supports Diamond OA while still working with commercial publishers for sustaining the publishing system, while at the same time not wishing to have too heavy systemic dependencies upon them.

Currently, there are no legal frameworks to facilitate Diamond OA. However, the 2024 National OA Strategy seeks to introduce regulatory framework conditions that promote OA for all scholarly publications. These conditions encompass broad institutional support for implementing the retention of authors' rights and

²⁰¹ swissuniversities: <https://www.swissuniversities.ch/?r=1>

²⁰² 2024 National Open Access Strategy:
https://www.swissuniversities.ch/fileadmin/swissuniversities/Dokumente/Hochschulpolitik/Open_Access/Swiss-National-Open-Access-Strategy-2024-en.pdf

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introducing a secondary publication right under Swiss law for publicly-funded scholarly publications. Now efforts are underway to change contract legislation (not copyright legislation) with an emphasis on improving the affordability and sustainability of scholarly publishing. Green OA is the primary focus rather than Diamond OA.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

At the national level, swissuniversities have historically had funding lines that support initiatives for Diamond OA, including one for alternative Open Access routes and another for a national Diamond consortium. From 2022-2025, the first Programme Open Science I funded the PLATO project that involved six partner institutions as part of the funding line for “alternative Open Access routes”. This covered nationwide actions, including a study on the national Diamond OA landscape, the first Swiss Diamond OA Conference, and a Diamond OA Workshop Day. One outcome of the conference acknowledged that there is insufficient funding for Diamond OA in Switzerland. Demand for funding is high, even as the funds needed for Diamond OA are significantly less than what is currently invested in big deals with commercial publishers. Sustaining publishing platforms is also essential for Diamond OA going forward.

Following on from that programme, the Programme Open Science II²⁰³ has made 13.65 million CHF/ 14.6 million Euros available for 2025–2026. Due to recent budget cuts, it will now only include one call: to develop a National Diamond OA Consortium, which was approved in June 2025. In 2025, a federal decision to reduce funds for swissuniversities has resulted in the budget for Open Science being divided between research data and Open Access, without funds being set aside specifically for Diamond OA. Journals, including Diamond OA ones, can indeed receive funding from the Swiss Academies for Humanities and Social Sciences (SAGW)²⁰⁴, if the scholarly society owning the journal, is a member.

Some academic libraries utilise their OA fund for Diamond if funds are not exhausted, also in the sense of funding recognised Diamond initiatives like OLH, but not on a journal level. The Universities of Lausanne²⁰⁵ and Lucerne²⁰⁶ also have a dedicated fund for Diamond OA journals. However, personnel, training, and

²⁰³ Programme Open Science II: <https://www.swissuniversities.ch/en/topics/open-science/open-science-programme/funded-projects>

²⁰⁴ Swiss Academies for Humanities and Social Sciences (SAGW): <https://www.sagw.ch/sagw/>

²⁰⁵ University of Lausanne: <https://www.unil.ch/news/en/1738333065563>

²⁰⁶ University of Lucerne: <https://www.zhbluzern.ch/english-pages/open-science/publishing-open-access/funding-open-access>

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licensing remain insufficiently covered. Diamond OA journals would need 20-30k CHF annually, or the equivalent of 20% FTE, to be more sustainably funded.

There is little – if any – funding for Diamond OA books in Switzerland, except insofar as publishing services are funded. Institutional support also comes in non-monetary form, as the institution may provide in-kind contributions, free hosting and other publishing services.

Some universities share services, namely hosting infrastructures: HOPE (UZH)²⁰⁷, BOP (Bern)²⁰⁸, eterna/emono (Basel)²⁰⁹, OAP (Geneva)²¹⁰, and SOAP2 (University of Fribourg)²¹¹. This contributes to some cost savings.

Investment in infrastructure for Diamond OA is important for Switzerland as this is often a way of providing support to Diamond for an institution's own researchers without competing with private enterprises. Efforts to create more national, non-commercial opportunities for funding Diamond OA are underway. Funded by swissuniversities and the partner institutions as part of the Open Science Programme II, the Creating a Sustainable Funding Scheme for Diamond Open Access through Institutional Collaboration in Switzerland (CoDOA-CH) Project (2025-2026)²¹² aims to create a consortial funding scheme for Diamond through collaboration. While CoDOA runs only for one year, this project aims to explore the possibility of building a national Diamond OA consortium that could collectively fund Diamond OA journals.

Switzerland has a National OA Monitor²¹³ and a Repository Monitor²¹⁴. Switzerland aspires to track the adoption of Diamond OA articles, which will feed into discussions on publishing strategies and sustaining them.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Awareness is growing for research assessment reform amongst Swiss institutions thanks to the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)²¹⁵ leadership.

²⁰⁷ HOPE (UZH): <https://www.hope.uzh.ch/>

²⁰⁸ BOP (Bern): <https://bop.unibe.ch/>

²⁰⁹ eterna/emono (Basel): <https://eterna.unibas.ch/>; <https://emono.unibas.ch/emono>

²¹⁰ OAP (Geneva): <https://www.unige.ch/biblio/en/openaccess/publish-a-journal/open-access-publications/>

²¹¹ SOAP2 (University of Fribourg): <https://www.soap2.ch/>

²¹² (CoDOA-CH) Project: <https://consortium.ch/codoa/?lang=en>

²¹³ National OA Monitor: <https://oamonitor.ch/de/>

²¹⁴ Repository Monitor: <https://oamonitor.ch/charts-data/repository-monitor/>

²¹⁵ Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA): <https://www.coara.org/>

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CoARA signatories who commit to change include both funders (swissuniversities, SNSF, and SAGW) and higher education institutions (Bern University of Applied Sciences, EPFL – Swiss Federal Technology Institute of Lausanne, ETH Zurich, Schwyz University of Teacher Education, Swiss Reproducibility Network, University of Fribourg, University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland, University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland (HES-SO), Zurich University of Applied Sciences, Zurich University of the Arts, Zurich University of Teacher Education). However, for implementation to occur, researchers are vital and involving them remains difficult and requires trailblazers in different academic disciplines to drive change in Diamond OA and reward that practice.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

An important finding of the PLATO project was that publishing/hosting platforms are essential for enabling Diamond OA, while there is still insufficient funding for them (Hahn et al., 2023). 2023 data shows that about 27% of all Diamond OA journals in Switzerland were hosted on an institutional platform. The PLATO landscape study found that shared infrastructures, such as institutional ones for Diamond OA, “play a significant role in sustaining and supporting journal operations and in creating opportunities, especially as small improvements on the level of technology can have a substantial impact on journal operations such as enhancing IT support, indexation, article metadata and citation standards” (Hahn et al., 2023). The PLATO study also points out that opportunities exist when sharing the costs of infrastructures since sharing can strengthen these systems, foster collaboration and uncover innovative business models.

Other vital Swiss infrastructure includes an OJS Community of Practice formed by the hosting platforms to share best practices and foster knowledge exchange and a National (DB) List of Diamond OA journals²¹⁶. The one-year DOACH project aims to become a national capacity hub for Swiss institutions and to develop shared services; this infrastructure is essential for sustaining Diamond OA nationally. DOACH plans to develop one platform or entry point to all Diamond OA platforms active in Switzerland, linking them all, and providing training, guidelines, best practices and information on rights. It will also provide instructional and information material for practitioners.

Some institutions share services, namely hosting infrastructures: UZH is the base for HOPE, the University of Bern for BOP, the University of Basel for eterna/emono, the University of Geneva for OAP, and the University of Fribourg for SOAP2, an OJS

²¹⁶ National (DB) List of Diamond OA journals: <https://zenodo.org/records/6992615#.ZAC90LTMi-Q>

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technical infrastructure which serves five member organisations without being a shared publication service.

Journals can also liaise with publishers to deliver publishing services, as seen in Zurich where a medium-sized publisher is entrusted with producing the final, peer-reviewed papers. In this collaboration, one version for printing and one online version of each article is published.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Institutions are essential in supporting Diamond OA since they employ editors, authors, researchers, and support staff, as well as providing hosting infrastructures. Research performing organisation libraries cater mainly to their institutional members, following the publishing needs of their own authors and research communities insofar as they require a diversity of publishing options. Institutional leadership can also be conservative as regards their attitudes towards less traditional paths for scholarly publishing, such as Diamond OA, its costs and how this relates to the library function as a collection steward. One way institutions can support Diamond OA publishing is by supporting professors who act on their prerogative to negotiate to get institutional funds to fund their Diamond OA journals.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Most Diamond OA journals depend heavily on in-kind support from their parent institutions, such as libraries or faculties, which provide services such as hosting, office space, or infrastructure. Editorial teams usually consist of only a handful of collaborators who undertake tasks voluntarily and without remuneration. For most, these responsibilities are neither part of their formal job description nor institutionally recognised. While professors cannot legally take on “overtime,” early-career researchers are typically subject to contracts that stipulate the distribution of time across teaching, research, and administration, sometimes with explicitly protected research time, leaving little room for voluntary editorial work.

The publishing process in these journals heavily relies on voluntary work, with only very few able to financially compensate editors, managers, or assistants. As one editor critically remarked, this model risks being exploitative. Nevertheless, many involved in Diamond OA emphasise their strong commitment to serving their research communities and advancing scholarship through this type of publishing. Scholars contribute in diverse roles, including editing, reviewing, copy editing, proofreading, typesetting, and marketing, while outsourcing is usually limited to technical tasks such as IT support or graphic design. However, reliance on

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volunteers restricts training opportunities and makes journals vulnerable to staff turnover.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Switzerland has no national quality assurance strategy for Diamond OA, but the CoDOA project resulting from the call from Programme Open Science II (2025-2028) will work in this area. In the absence of a national approach, the quality assurance strategies of DOAJ²¹⁷, the KOALA criteria²¹⁸ and SAGW (Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Science)²¹⁹ serve as orientation points.

Institutional hosting platforms provide some minimum quality criteria which they set for themselves and partly also support journals with indexation in DOAJ and Redalyc. One drawback is that in some cases, meeting set criteria can be slow when available financial resources are limited, so there is a risk that service providers and publishers may be delisted from DOAJ (or not accepted) before their quality criteria are in place.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

A structural and cultural change in how, where, and how much researchers publish is required for Diamond OA to become mainstream in Switzerland, both amongst researchers and within libraries. Trust in the model is key. Preconceived notions about Diamond OA, such as that it results in lower-quality publications without significant impact, still hold back researchers from pursuing the Diamond route, despite library awareness-raising efforts. Advocacy is still important to promote different formats. More information is needed on publishing models, and the consequences of choosing certain venues or models. Many are not aware of what is needed to change their publishing culture.

The transformation in academic publishing, and more particularly Diamond OA, will take time; also, co-ordinating it within the institution is a new process for many. The adoption of Diamond OA is further challenged by the lack of incentives for authors, especially as long as scholarly career advancement seems to depend on publishing in established journals, regardless of how open those journals are, what route to open they follow and the cost of publication. Also, it is essential to move away from the quantitative metrics that commercial publishers both generate and capitalise on, and towards new approaches to research assessment—for example,

²¹⁷ DOAJ: <https://doaj.org/apply/guide/>

²¹⁸ KOALA criteria: <https://www.tib.eu/en/services/koala/requirements>

²¹⁹ Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Science (SAGW): <https://www.sagw.ch/fr/assh/>

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recognising open science practices in academic recruitment. Redefining success for journals in terms of how they reach their communities, rather than in terms of metrics, could also help Diamond OA journals be better recognised going forward.

From the top down, deciding for such research assessment reform as well as formalising the necessary in-kind contributions for Diamond OA publishing and putting time dedicated to Diamond OA publishing in researchers' statements of duties are essential steps to embed institutional publishing. From the bottom up, researchers need to make better and more affordable choices in how, where, and how much they publish.

All stakeholders have a shared responsibility to effect cultural change towards Diamond OA. They need to collaborate and work together, also on national and international levels: researchers, funders, libraries and their management, and senior university management. For their part, researchers can lead efforts within their institutions to coordinate on advocacy campaigns and contribute to infrastructure development for Diamond OA, by coordinating more and creating links between libraries and OA teams and management and other groups such as digital humanities teams and digital science labs. Another key step for the academic community would be for them to stop reviewing and conducting editorial work for commercial publishers and instead doing this work for Diamond OA journals.

On a practical level, creating efficiencies and providing support to academics as publishers by providing templates, guidance on website management, and increasing the involvement of researchers in launching, flipping, or maintaining Diamond OA journals will help make the model more sustainable and relieve some of the current burdens. Communities of practice, which already lead on some Diamond OA actions in Switzerland, should promote more coordination between platforms and do more to promote those. Identifying whether infrastructure has the capacity to scale up to onboard more journals is important in order to have better conditions to convince more journals to flip to Diamond OA in the future.

However, Diamond OA sustainability is currently hanging in the balance in Switzerland. It is libraries that should take the lead in helping make Diamond OA more sustainable by providing or redistributing funds for Diamond OA. Both national and institutional funds are needed to help related infrastructure scale up. Faculties or institutes could also provide more monetary support.

However, more widespread action is needed to help sustain Diamond OA for it to become a viable alternative to big deal journals. On the one hand, funders such as

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The Swiss National Science Foundation need to reconsider paying APCs. On the other hand, university or library management need to reconsider their contracts with legacy publishers. University or library management should also consciously decide to reallocate funds from APC payments to support Diamond OA. The academic library needs to evaluate its big deal contracts with commercial publishers to identify whether these funds can partly be allocated to Diamond OA, whilst critically monitoring these deals and their value and acting upon that or by setting a percentage of read and publish spend to go towards Diamond OA. Although management has shown an interest in reducing the funds that go towards Transformative Agreements, the actual reallocation of funds has largely yet to happen. Setting up a consortial fund to pool resources for redistribution or pledging could also help make Diamond OA more financially sustainable. However, what is fundamental to this conversation is also for the library to consider the place of Diamond OA in its portfolio of assets and its (potential) role as a publisher.

Finally, more cooperation—not competition—on national and international levels will further support Diamond OA adoption in Switzerland and make it more sustainable. Just as more coordination is needed within institutions, institutional publishers and service providers can benefit from seeking cooperation across national borders. Having national and international platforms and other international infrastructure, as well as better coordination between infrastructure nationally for hosting and publishing, would enable wider adoption of Diamond OA and facilitate the diversity that is Diamond OA's strength.

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

The scholarly publishing landscape in the UK has become notably diverse over the last decade as new university presses as well as independent scholar-led publishers²²⁰ that offer Diamond OA publishing or related services have emerged on the scene. Academic institutions and their libraries are the most prevalent Diamond OA journal publishers. In response to these trends, the Open Institutional Publishing Association (OIPA) was established, aiming to serve as a community of practice for new OA university presses, library publishing initiatives, and departmental publishing ventures across the UK. However, the scholarly publishing market is still dominated by medium and large commercial publishers (with a notable presence of international commercial publishers), who are mainly focused on APC/BPC-based and Hybrid publishing. Whilst most Diamond OA centred initiatives and service providers have emerged over the last decade, it is still a minority model in the national landscape, and dedicated public funding for institutions publishing Diamond OA journals and books is needed to expand the reach and capacity of Diamond OA initiatives.²²¹

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

Despite the absence of dedicated public funding to support existing OA journals or books published by nonprofit organisations in the UK, efforts are being made to promote OA publishing. UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) has played a critical role in the country's

²²⁰ See e.g. Adema and Stone, 2017 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4420993>

²²¹ This is an updated and modified text from Taşkın, Z., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Laakso, M., Torny, D., Arasteh, S., Bargheer, M., Klaus, T., Schima, J., Agnoloni, T., Peruginelli, G., Davidson, A., Franczak, M., Coslado Bernabé, M.A., de Pablo Llorente, V., Dobson, H., & Heyman, J. (2024). D5.2 National overviews on sustaining institutional publishing in Europe. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683953>

transition via its block grants to institutions and OA policies. However, the lack of centralised national funding for Diamond OA remains as a gap in the national landscape with a negative impact on the sustainability and reach of nonprofit scholarly publishing.²²²

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Research funding for UK higher education institutions is allocated via two main funding mechanisms: project-specific grants and strategic institutional funding allocated based on research and knowledge exchange performance. National-level funding plays a crucial role in supporting scholarly journals. The absence of direct public financial support for non-commercial OA publishing in the UK raises sustainability concerns.²²³²²⁴

Wellcome and UKRI have updated their terms and conditions on OA block grants to make Diamond OA compliant, which is very helpful to Diamond OA publishing.

The Jisc Open Access Community Framework (OACF), launched in 2022, offers a centralised mechanism for Jisc member institutions to support not for profit publishers or initiatives based on the Diamond OA model. Jisc has invited mission-based and Diamond OA publishers to apply to participate in the OACF and, similar to the Lyris Open Access Community Investment Program (OACIP). Despite limited library budgets, many UK institutions recognise the importance of supporting Diamond OA and mission-driven initiatives, and are exploring ways to allocate funds accordingly.²²⁵

The Open Journals Collective (OJC) is a newly-launched international publishing collective launching library memberships scheme to raise investment for Diamond OA journals from January 2026 onwards (c. 320 journals in HSS and STEM).

The Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs (COPIM) project (2019-23) and its successor project Open Book Futures (2023-26), both co-funded by UKRI and Arcadia, explore collective approaches to OA book publishing, with an aim to establish collaboration and knowledge exchange among publishers and to ensure affordability, accessibility and long-term availability of Diamond OA books. One of the outcomes of COPIM has been the inception of the Open Book Collective (OBC), which

²²² Ibid

²²³ Ibid

²²⁴ Fathallah, J., & Deville, J. (2025). Report on librarians' barriers to participation in collective funding models for open access books. OBC Information Hub. Retrieved from <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/report-on-librarians-barrier-to-participation-in-collective-funding-models-for-open-access-books>

²²⁵ Ibid

now provides a collective library funding mechanism to Diamond OA publishers (or those seeking to move to a Diamond OA model) that meet the OBC membership criteria.²²⁶²²⁷

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

The Open Library of Humanities (OLH) is a nonprofit, Diamond OA publisher of humanities scholarship based at Birkbeck, University of London. OLH publishes 34 Diamond OA journals. The university provides support for the OLH, which includes legal, HR, accounting, and management support. OLH has two funding streams: library memberships and income from hosted publishing services via their open-source Janeway platform. OLH model is widely supported and recognised as contributing to sustainable, equitable OA publishing.

The University of Edinburgh Library launched Edinburgh Diamond in 2009 (then known as the Journal Hosting Service). Edinburgh Diamond is the publishing partner for Diamond OA books and journals led by their academics, professional staff and students. Only the main author/editor has to be based at the University of Edinburgh, publishing is globally otherwise. Staffing, technical costs, membership fees, ISBNs and DOI registration fees are met by the Library's core budget. Edinburgh Diamond is a Publisher Member of the newly launched OJC and so expects to start receiving funding from 2026 onwards. Edinburgh Diamond uses open-source software (currently Open Journals Systems (OJS) and Open Monograph Press (OMP) from the Public Knowledge Project) to host, publish and manage the workflow of their books and journals, LOCKSS and CLOCKSS for archiving and preservation, Crossref for DOI allocation and registration, Thoth Open Metadata for metadata and dissemination and Matomo for analytics.

The team who manages Edinburgh Diamond also manage a shared service called the SCURL (Scottish Confederation of University & Research Libraries) Open Hosting Shared Service. This is open to all members of SCURL across Scotland and exists to provide the technical infrastructure required to manage a Diamond OA publishing programme. This has enabled other institutional libraries and publishers to launch their own Diamond OA initiative, which they were unable to do before due to lack of internal technical resources. Ten out of 11 Diamond OA publishers/library publishing initiatives in Scotland are members of the SCURL Open Hosting Shared Service and there is also Aberdeen University Press.

Important infrastructures for OA monographs include Thoth Open Metadata and the Thoth Open Archiving Network (set up within COPIM and the follow-up Open Book

²²⁶ Ibid

²²⁷ See Joy, E. A. F., Adema, J., & COPIM. (2022). Open Book Collective: Our Organisational Model. Copim. <https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.13890eb3>

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Futures projects). Thoth Open Metadata is an independent non-profit service provider enabling publishers to create and manage high-quality, open metadata for books and chapters (including OA license, usage of PIDs and funder metadata of Diamond OA titles), and to facilitate wide dissemination, discovery, and long-term archiving of Diamond OA books and chapters. Its software is open source, tailor-made for Open Access book metadata, and the multiple output formats and specifications for more than a dozen platforms (incl. ONIX3, MARC, and KBART) are all CC0-licensed and available via the free-to-use self-service Thoth platform. And the Thoth Open Archiving Network supports small-to-medium-sized publishers with the archiving of their OA books via multiple repositories. Thoth Open Metadata receives collective funding from academic libraries via OBC to support the provision of its free self-service platform and open metadata exports. Paid-for added-value services built on the provision of open data (such as the dissemination of Diamond OA titles to aggregators on behalf of a publisher, the provision of usage statistics, and website and catalogue hosting) are also available.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

The proportion of university press titles in the UK is close to 15%, which may be due to the large university presses - Oxford University Press and Cambridge University Press - as well as several smaller presses based in UK universities, including Manchester, Edinburgh and Liverpool. Over the past decade, there has been a notable emergence of new university presses and scholar-led publishers in the UK, embracing the Diamond OA model from their inception: The University College London Press, the University of Huddersfield Press, the University of Westminster Press, the Birkbeck, and the University of London Press.²²⁸

Many institutional Diamond OA journals use library and/or book hosting services and/or are based within academic departments and some examples are described below.

Liverpool John Moores University (LJMU) provides a LJMU Open Journals Service, established in 2016, to support the publication of LJMU academic and student-led Diamond OA journals. The service is run by the Library, using OJS, and includes initial set up of journals and ongoing support for editorial teams. LJMU Open Journals Service is supported from the library budget.

Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh (RBGE) publishes two Diamond OA journals ("Edinburgh Journal of Botany" and "Sibbaldia") and have made their historical journal "Notes of the Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh" freely available via the same platform. The journal publishing programme is supported via core funding from the Scottish

²²⁸ Ibid

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Government which covers both the staffing and production costs. Charities fund outreach and marketing activities. In line with the Scottish Government's Open Data Strategy, RBGE is committed to making their research publications and associated data freely open and available for others to use and reuse.

Dundee Open Journals is a library-based hosting and publishing service for researchers, staff, and postgraduate students at the University of Dundee funded by a small institutional OA fund. As well as offering technical assistance with OJS and institutional archiving, the service supports the University of Dundee community, particularly PGRs and ECRs, with Diamond OA scholarly publishing and adopting open research best practices.

University of St Andrews provides a journal hosting service for 12 active Diamond OA journals. A Library OA fund supports OLH, as well as their own Diamond OA publishing. It has also been used for Jisc OACF which included some Diamond OA models but also is used for non-Diamond OA models. Team members are on multiple advisory boards for Diamond OA organisations (OJC, OIPA) and have contributed to studies through the DIAMAS project.

University of Warwick Press/Journals also currently hosts OJS for Diamond OA journals (and a few monographs) and provides technical infrastructure. Additionally, the team also maintains a central expertise within the open research space (data, repositories, etc.,) and has a strong representation within the institution's governance and committee structure for the same. Currently a subsidy model is used where the library hosts the platform and offers limited direct support. Individual departments fund/support/host staff actively running Diamond OA journals. Other options to more centrally support, develop and encourage Diamond OA publishing efforts are currently being explored.

University of Westminster Press (UWP) aspires to cover all costs of book publication internally, with their budget for a small number of new books (4-5) to be published Diamond OA. They are in receipt of grants and donations from Jisc and the OBC, and this money is put towards supporting additional publications. Additionally, UWP publishes six Diamond OA journals.

Workforce and Capacity Development

The staff of Diamond OA initiatives that participated in the consultation process for this county case study range from 0.4 to 12 FTEs.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Copim, Edinburgh Diamond, OBC, OJC, OIPA, OLH, SCURL and Thoth Open Metadata seek to foster collaboration within the UK as well as with international stakeholders such as OAPEN, PKP, and within the OPERAS network, share best practices, and collectively address common challenges faced by emerging players in the Diamond OA publishing ecosystem.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Research quality is measured in a periodic exercise known as the Research Excellence Framework (REF). The REF exercise takes place every seven years and its outcomes inform the allocation of approximately two billion GBP per year of public funding for research within universities. The next REF is planned for 2029. As part of the initial decisions on REF 2029, the UK funding bodies announced their intention to replace the environment element with People, culture and environment (a proposed 25% weighting) and to replace outputs with Contribution to knowledge and understanding (a proposed 50% weighting). Whilst the element will largely be based on assessment of research outputs, it signals a desire from funders to move further from the assessment of individual researchers and publication-based metrics to an expanded definition of research excellence. Whilst it is likely to still include an assessment of research outputs, it will also require evidence of broader contributions to the advancement of the discipline. This includes greater alignment with the objectives of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). Over 90 UK HEIs are signatories of the DORA or have made an equivalent commitment to research assessment.²²⁹

Diamond OA publishing initiatives maintain the latest software, which requires hosting fees and staff effort. Crossref membership demonstrates a commitment to standards as well. Otherwise, institutions have developed guides for e.g. GDPR adherence, and advice on accessibility, copyright and licensing, but there are no direct finance implications for these. Turnitin is often used as a centrally provided support service for originality checking and resourced by library funding.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

- ✓ A clear commitment to the Diamond OA publishing by funding and research oversight bodies. UK Funding bodies to advocate, invest, and recognise Diamond OA publishing as a viable pathway for impact in scholarly publishing. Government funding and policies geared towards supporting and sustainably growing Diamond OA for both journals and books and more collective advocacy.

²²⁹ Ibid

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- ✓ A shift towards measures of impact that are less reliant on commercial publishing models would also be helpful.
- ✓ Support for sustainability in terms of funding, pooling of resources and institutional commitment to continuing Diamond OA publishing support. A shift away from APC/BPC-based funding and transitional agreements towards stronger support of collective funding schemes such as the OBC and OJC. Redirecting a larger proportion of funding away from large commercial publishers and towards community-led, non-profit publishing initiatives would significantly strengthen Diamond OA in the UK.
- ✓ Support for community-led not-for-profit infrastructures to provide value-added services like copyediting, proofreading, hosting, high-quality metadata management, dissemination, and archiving of Diamond OA publications.
- ✓ Funding and expert training support for independent, scholar-led as well as institutional, library-based publishing services to professionalise services that can stand alongside those of commercial publishing, in the way of HTML, ePub and/or XML publishing and production. Support independent as well as library-based publishing services to offer typesetting for their hosted journals. Ongoing funding support to assist with maintaining and improving independent as well as library publishing infrastructure.
- ✓ Collective advocacy to have Diamond OA titles indexed more widely. A major issue for both Diamond OA journal and book communities is gaining sufficient visibility with different audiences, including authors, editors, and funders. Efforts towards more collective approaches in this direction to foster discoverability of publishers' valuable outputs will be crucial to maintaining community-led contributions to the wider sector.

LATIN AMERICA

Image 6: Word cloud based on Latin America country case studies content. Source: Own creation.

LATIN AMERICA

The comparative analysis of the 18 Latin American country case studies reveals a scholarly publishing ecosystem with substantial structural strengths but also recurrent and systemic challenges that impact the sustainability and future development of non-profit and Diamond OA publishing in the region. A prominent finding is the strong institutional foundation upon which many journals operate. Institutional policies, dedicated staff, and established national quality assurance systems consistently appear as the most significant assets across countries. These elements collectively reinforce a stable operational environment, embedding journal management and evaluation within formal academic structures.

Latin America also benefits from a rich and mature Open Access infrastructure, underpinned by the widespread adoption of OJS, present across all countries studied. Major regional platforms, including Latindex, Redalyc-AmeliCA, SciELO and DOAJ, continue to play a pivotal role in sustaining non-profit publishing, providing visibility, technological support, and internationally recognized quality standards. National policies and supportive legal frameworks further contribute to the consolidation of Open Access norms, reflecting a long-standing regional commitment to publicly funded and publicly controlled scholarly communication.

Despite these strengths, the region faces a series of persistent challenges that hinder the full professionalization and long-term consolidation of Diamond OA. The most frequent is a strong reliance on voluntary labour, particularly for editorial and technical tasks, which remains widespread and strains the capacity of journals to maintain quality and continuity. This is closely linked to insufficient professionalization, the lack of incentives and rewards, and limited funding streams, all of which undermine the stability and career recognition of editorial work. Regarding incentives, the Latin American Forum for Research Assessment (FOLEC)²³⁰ at the Latin American Council of Social Sciences (CLACSO)²³¹, has been since 2019 advocating for research assessment transformation aligned with the Diamond OA principles and with CoARA work.

Although some progress has been made, the adoption of PIDs is still uneven, reducing the interoperability and global visibility of many journals. Additional challenges, including occasional pressure in some countries to adopt APC-based models or to rely on commercial publishing solutions appear less widespread but nonetheless signal points of vulnerability in certain national systems. This is explained by persistent financial burdens to outsource the implementation of innovations in Diamond OA through third parties service providers as it is done in the European context though

²³⁰ <https://www.clacso.org/folec/>

²³¹ <https://www.clacso.org>

LATIN AMERICA

unattainable for many institutions in the Latin American region. Conversely, it is perceived that developing non-commercial collaborative and decentralized approaches would be more suitable and sustainable for developing regions.

Overall, the findings point to a region with a deep-rooted Open Access culture, strong institutional and regional infrastructures, and a longstanding preference for non-commercial, community-driven venues for knowledge sharing. To sustain and strengthen this model, however, coordinated actions are needed to reduce dependence on voluntary work, expand financial and institutional support, professionalize editorial roles, and accelerate the uptake of global scholarly communication standards. By addressing these challenges, Latin America is well positioned to reinforce its leadership around the globe in equitable, publicly controlled scholarly publishing and to further consolidate the Diamond OA model as a cornerstone of its academic ecosystem.

ARGENTINA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Argentina has a robust ecosystem of non-profit academic publishing, driven by national universities, public research organizations, and inter-institutional publishing networks. The country has active policies promoting Open Access (OA), supported by Law 26.899 of 2013, which establishes mandatory OA to publicly funded scientific production (Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, 2013).

The leadership of the Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET) and the national universities have been decisive. It has established initiatives such as the SciELO Argentina portal, coordinated by the Centro Argentino de Información Científica y Tecnológica (CAICYT-CONICET), which indexes more than 200 national OA journals, most of them under the Diamond model.

Argentina also actively participates in regional journal and Open Science networks such as Redalyc and LA Referencia, promoting the visibility of Latin American science, seeking to strengthen academic autonomy, and reduce dependence on commercial publishers.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

The Ley 26.899 de Repositorios Digitales Institucionales de Acceso Abierto (2013)²³² is the cornerstone of the Argentine OA system. This pioneering law in Latin America has served as the basis for many public institutions to implement non-commercial OA,

²³² Ley 26.899 de Repositorios Digitales Institucionales de Acceso Abierto (2013):
<https://repositoriosdigitales.mincyt.gob.ar/vufind/>

fostering infrastructure for this purpose Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación, 2013).

These aspects are considered in the Resolución 753/2016²³³ of the Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación Productiva (2016), which deals with the implementation and regulation of OA to scientific and technological production in Argentina, establishing guidelines for the management of institutional digital repositories supported with public funds, within the framework of Law 26,899 and the Sistema Nacional de Repositorios Digitales (Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación, 2022).

In addition, at the institutional level, institutions such as national universities, for example the Universidad de Buenos Aires (UBA), Universidad Nacional de La Plata (UNLP) and the Universidad Nacional de Córdoba (UNC), have adapted their internal regulations to comply with these regulations, generating their own technological infrastructures to strengthen their institutional journal portals, the vast majority in OA at no cost to readers and authors.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Funding for Diamond OA journals comes primarily from public funds. Both CONICET and the Argentinian universities allocate human and technical resources through their science and technology departments. However, these funds do not always include specific allocations for editing or digitization.

According to RESOL-2023-774-APN-MCT²³⁴, the Program for the Strengthening of Argentine Open Access Scientific Publications intended to support the publication and sustainability of Argentinian Diamond OA scientific journals that make up the Basic Nucleus of Scientific Journals of CAICYT-CONICET, contributing to the generation of new capacities and the technological and professional updating of the editorial teams that manage them. However, currently that financing is not available. Some universities, such as the UNLP, have created editorial support programs and training scholarships for editors, while others, such as the UNC, have entered into agreements with regional networks to share technological infrastructure (Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación, 2023).

Despite progress, challenges persist in professionalizing technical staff and covering costs associated with platform maintenance, translation, and digital preservation.

²³³ Resolución 753/2016 of the Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación Productiva (2016): <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/resoluci%C3%B3n-753-2016-267833/texto>

²³⁴ RESOL-2023-774-APN-MCT: <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/resoluci%C3%B3n-774-2023-392070/texto>

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

In Argentina, there are, at least, two distinctive circuits to assess research: one at universities and the other at scientific organizations like CONICET, and previous AGENCIA I+D+I and ex-MINCYT and different instrument involved to assess researchers and institutions: PROINCE/PRINUAR, CICyT at CONICET, Institutional Evaluation Program (PEI) of the Undersecretariat of Science and Technology (ex-MINCYT) and CONEAU. And that they developed different incentives with diverse scopes for OA. Publication in OA journals is beginning to be recognized as an academic merit. The Comisión Nacional de Evaluación y Acreditación Universitaria (CONEAU) y el Sistema Nacional de Docentes-Investigadores (SiDIUN) consider OA as a positive criterion in evaluations, although recognition is not yet uniform across disciplines. There have been three successive programs: 1) the Programa de Incentivos a Docentes Investigadores (PROINCE), which was later replaced by 2) the Sistema Nacional de Docentes Investigadores Universitarios (SIDIUN) that was never implemented, and 3) the Programa para la Investigación Universitaria Argentina - PRINUAR. In fact, the former PROINCE was replaced by PRINUAR that sought to institutionalize and strengthen university research careers in general, including its integration with teaching, outreach, and the arts, and that includes the SIDIUN.

CONICET (2023:4)²³⁵ highlighted that open publishing practices strengthen the visibility of national production and improve the assessment of scientific impact. In addition, In 2014, the National Council for Scientific and Technical Research (CONICET)²³⁶ approved a special resolution for the social sciences and humanities that equates journals indexed in the main circuit with those indexed in regional databases. However, university publishers advocate for an incentive system to value Diamond OA journals equitably with those published in commercial journals indexed in databases from Global North. According to what was expressed by the Advisory Committee on Open and Citizen Science in its document “Diagnóstico y lineamientos para una política de ciencia abierta en Argentina: In the regulations of the latest PROINCE categorization, there is no weighting or even mention of OA to publications and open data in the evaluation criteria. However, this has not been incorporated in the new Ministerial resolution that creates SIDIUN (Resolución 1216/2019): despite the fact that one of its main objectives is to expand the visibility of the results of the scientific production of universities, at no time does it refer to Law 26899 or to the weighting of OA (Authier et al., 2022: 73).

²³⁵ CONICET: <https://www.conicet.gov.ar/bases-para-la-categorizacion-de-publicaciones-periodicas-en-ciencias-sociales-y-humanidades/>

²³⁶ Ibid

On the other hand, the former AGENCIA I+D+i²³⁷ had also taken a position in favor of promoting non-profit open access publishing, whether in the form of institutional repositories (green route) or pure open access journals from academic publishers and scientific societies (diamond route).

This situation extends to PRINUAR, which only refers to widely recognized journals (preferably indexed) (Punto 3.1.b) (Ministerio de Educación, 2023).

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Argentina has a solid publishing infrastructure network. CAICYT-CONICET manages SciELO Argentina, and there is also the CONICET Digital Portal, which integrates interoperable national repositories and journals. At the university level, Open Journal System (OJS) systems operate in a network under the umbrella of the Red Sara Red Nacional de Portales de Revistas Científicas²³⁸, which coordinates best practices, training workshops, and dissemination of editorial standards. In this regard, the former Ministerio de Ciencia y Tecnología and current Secretariat of Innovation, Science, and Technology, (2022: 6) emphasizes that strengthening digital repositories and creating interoperable national platforms are pillars of the Argentine open science model.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

National universities are the heart of the Argentine model, some exemplary models such as the UBA have 279 journals. The UNLP has 106 journals²³⁹. The UNC²⁴⁰ has 109 journals, all of them using OJS. Universidad Tecnológica Nacional and the Universidad Nacional de Quilmes also maintain their own catalogues of journals of this nature and all of them use OJS.

On the other hand, in this specific aspect, CONICET provides technical advice and indexing programs through CAICYT, while the former MINCyT coordinates national guidelines for interoperability and regional visibility.

Workforce and Capacity Development

University and research editorial teams are essential. However, many of their members work *ad honorem* or are overworked. As a report by the Red de Editoriales de

²³⁷ AGENCIA I-D-i: <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/ciencia/agencia/la-agencia-idi/article-processing-charges-apc>

²³⁸ Red Sara Red Nacional de Portales de Revistas Científicas: <https://redsara.org/>

²³⁹ Portal de Revistas UNLP: <https://portalderevistas.unlp.edu.ar/>

²⁴⁰ UNC Portal de Revistas: <https://revistas.unc.edu.ar/>

Universidades Nacionales (REUN), editorial staff constitute the most vulnerable link in the scientific chain and, at the same time, the most indispensable.

Several universities have launched training and professional development programs in academic publishing, such as the Diploma in Scientific Publishing at UNLP, which seeks to strengthen the human sustainability of the system.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Interinstitutional cooperation is a distinctive feature of the Argentine system and the Latin American region. REUN, SciELO Argentina, Redalyc, and LA Referencia form a network of shared services that benefit non-commercial OA publishing by optimizing resources and standardizing processes. This collaborative effort has allowed national journals to be internationally recognized for their transparency and editorial quality.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Editorial quality is guaranteed through peer review systems, publication ethics policies, and CAICYT-CONICET certifications. SciELO Argentina applies international evaluation criteria and grants its own Seal of Editorial Quality, which contributes to the professionalization of the sector.

At the institutional level, several universities have implemented editorial quality committees and periodic reviews of their publication policies.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Diamond OA in Argentina has a solid political foundation but needs to increase funding and professionalize its publishing ecosystem. The following actions are recommended:

- ✓ Consolidate a permanent national fund for Diamond OA journals managed by MINCyT, currently the Secretariat of Innovation, Science, and Technology, and CONICET.
- ✓ Strengthen training programs in scientific editing and editorial management.
- ✓ Develop a national publishing certification system, in conjunction with SciELO and REUN.
- ✓ Promote South-South cooperation with other Latin American countries to share technological and digital preservation resources.
- ✓ These measures would allow Argentina to consolidate its position as a regional benchmark for non-profit academic publishing and inclusive open science.

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BRAZIL

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Brazil has become one of Latin America's leading examples in the promotion of Open Access and non-profit scholarly communication. Since the establishment of the Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (Ibict) in 1954 and the subsequent creation of the SciELO Brazil network in 1997, the country has built a solid infrastructure and a scholarly community deeply committed to open science (Packer et al., 2018; Amaro, Campos & Sena, 2025). These initiatives have fostered the expansion of the Diamond OA model.

In recent years, the country has undergone an institutional reconfiguration regarding Open Access policy. Organizations such as Ibict, the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES), and the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq) have coordinated efforts to strengthen scholarly communication, although tensions remain due to budgetary dependence and national research assessment policies (Trinca & Melo, 2024).

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

The Brazilian Open Access framework is supported by an interconnected network of public universities, funding agencies, and research centres. However, Brazil lacks a unified national Open Access policy. Instead, decentralized initiatives have emerged, led by institutions such as Ibict, which coordinates support services for journals—including Miguilim, Manuelzão, Diadorim, and the National Latindex Centre—aimed at promoting editorial best practices and technical training (Appel, 2025).

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

The Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES) has played a key role in consolidating non-profit scientific journals. Since 2023, the agency has allocated financial resources to the SciELO Brazil program to enhance the international visibility of national journals (CAPES, 2024b), although these funds are not exclusively designated for Diamond journals. Nevertheless, the agency itself acknowledges that the continuity of such support largely depends on the country's economic and political context (Trinca & Melo, 2024).

Likewise, university portals have served as platforms that connect editors, libraries, and research units, contributing to the sustainability of institutional infrastructures.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Brazil has a consolidated publishing ecosystem, characterized by the historical leadership of SciELO, the technological innovation of Ibict, and the academic support of public universities. Its technical infrastructure includes systems such as OJS, digital preservation services like LOCKSS, and the development of alternative open identifiers such as dARK, which is being created by Ibict to reduce the costs associated with commercial DOIs (Appel, 2025).

In addition, the CNPq–CAPES Editorial Program (2023) promotes the editing and publication of highly specialized scientific journals, many of which follow the Diamond OA model. These initiatives seek to ensure editorial independence and prioritize scientific quality over commercial interests (CNPq, 2023).

The strengthening of this model is also linked to regional cooperation through networks such as Redalyc and LA Referencia, which expand the visibility of Brazilian research output within the Latin American context. In this way, the country contributes to a form of scientific diplomacy grounded in collaboration, openness, and equity in the dissemination of knowledge (UNESCO, 2023).

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Brazilian institutions play a central role in sustaining Open Access. Ibict leads policies related to digital infrastructure and editor training, while CAPES and CNPq provide financial support and academic recognition. Public universities, in turn, manage repositories, journals, and integrated portals that operate according to interoperability and preservation standards (Appel, 2025).

Interinstitutional collaboration has made it possible to maintain a horizontal governance model in which technical and human resources are shared among entities. This

approach strengthens editorial autonomy in contrast to commercial models and reaffirms the State's commitment to public science.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Editorial and technical staff constitute the backbone of the Diamond OA model in Brazil. Most university journal teams are composed of faculty and researchers who devote part of their time—often voluntarily—to editorial management tasks. Although this work is frequently unpaid, it ensures the quality and continuity of publications (Trinca & Melo, 2024).

Institutions have begun to acknowledge the need to professionalize this workforce. In this direction, training programs in scientific editing, metadata management, interoperability, and editorial ethics have been implemented. Nevertheless, challenges remain regarding the lack of financial incentives and formal recognition mechanisms within academic evaluation systems (CAPES, 2024b).

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

The Brazilian Open Access model is distinguished by interinstitutional collaboration and the shared use of infrastructures. Initiatives such as SciELO, Diadorim, and AmeliCA represent successful examples of cooperation among editors, universities, and public agencies, in which indexing, DOI assignment, peer review, and digital preservation services are collectively coordinated (Redalyc, 2023).

These alliances make it possible to optimize resources, ensure interoperability, and preserve editorial independence. Likewise, some institutions are exploring shared service models—such as copyediting and XML tagging—that support journals with limited resources (Appel, 2025).

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Brazil has developed a robust system for ensuring editorial quality. SciELO Brazil applies rigorous selection and continuous evaluation criteria based on peer review, process transparency, and publishing ethics (Packer et al., 2018).

CAPES also establishes quality guidelines through its Qualis system, although this framework continues to privilege commercial impact indicators, creating tensions with the Diamond OA model. In response, a new evaluative culture is being promoted—one grounded in social relevance, methodological rigor, and the openness of scientific data (UNESCO, 2023). Moreover, it has been announced that the current Qualis system will be suspended and replaced by a model emphasizing the qualitative aspects of national

scientific output. The aim is to develop a metric more focused on the quality and impact of articles (CAPES, 2024a).

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Despite its progress, the Diamond OA model in Brazil faces structural, financial, and cultural challenges. Among the most significant are:

- ✓ The absence of a formal national policy ensuring sustainable and continuous funding.
- ✓ An excessive dependence on commercial impact indicators.
- ✓ A shortage of human and technical resources to keep platforms up to date.
- ✓ The limited recognition of editorial work within academic evaluation systems.

In response to these challenges, Ibict is promoting shared infrastructures, while CAPES and CNPq have proposed the creation of specific funds to strengthen editorial teams and improve technological interoperability (Trinca & Melo, 2024). Likewise, there are ongoing discussions about reforming scientific evaluation systems to value the quality and social relevance of publications beyond traditional metrics (CAPES, 2024b).

The Brazilian case demonstrates that the Diamond OA model is not only viable but essential for regional scientific sovereignty. The collaboration among Ibict, CAPES, CNPq, public universities, and other educational and research institutions has consolidated an ecosystem that prioritizes openness, collaboration, and epistemic justice.

The future of Brazilian Open Access depends on the consolidation of clear national and institutional policies, the continuous training of editorial teams, and the academic recognition of editorial work as an integral component of science. Brazil remains a regional benchmark, offering models of technical cooperation and infrastructure that can be replicated in other contexts.

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CHILE

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Chile has maintained a prominent position in Latin America for its commitment to scientific communication and the creation of sustainable infrastructures for public access to knowledge. Since the implementation of the SciELO scientific journal indexing platform in 1998 —one of the first regional Open Access portals— the country has established itself as a pioneer in the open dissemination of scientific knowledge (Prat, 2000; ANID, 2025a).

The early adoption of the SciELO scientific publishing methodology has allowed it to become the national quality standard for scientific journals. It has also contributed to improving editorial processes and strengthening the Diamond model that characterizes scientific communication in Latin America. Currently, SciELO is included in the Open Access Policy of the Agencia Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo (ANID) and in the calculation of the Aporte Fiscal Directo to universities²⁴¹. It is also a component of the Infraestructura Nacional de Acceso²⁴², a project led by ANID that proposes a new way to access, manage, and use knowledge generated with public funds, thereby strengthening the role of university libraries and reducing dependence on foreign publishing offers.

A distinctive feature of the Chilean system lies in the fact that the journal indexing platform, funding instruments, scientific production indicators, ISSN assignment, and Open Access mandates are all managed by a single public agency —the Agencia Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo (ANID). This centralized structure enables the unification of strategies, criteria, and guidelines, thereby accelerating the decision-making process.

²⁴¹ Aporte Fiscal Directo to universities: <https://dfi.mineduc.cl/instrumentos-de-financiamiento/asignacion-directa/aporte-fiscal-directo-afd/>

²⁴² Infraestructura Nacional de Acceso: <https://acceso-abierto.anid.cl/componentes/ina/>

The 2020 transformation²⁴³ of the Comisión Nacional de Investigación Científica y Tecnológica (CONICYT) into the Agencia Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo (ANID)²⁴⁴ strengthened and diversified the agency's mission. This change enabled the implementation of the national Open Access policy and the design of funding instruments for universities to establish and/or strengthen competencies in open science, promoting transparency, collaboration, and equity in the dissemination of knowledge.

In Chile, most universities that publish scientific journals do so under the Diamond model through OJS portals, repositories, and institutional arrangements that foster non-profit publishing.

The ecosystem is complemented by the recently launched Espacio Ciencia service, where ANID's repository and those of seven universities are harvested through interoperability mechanisms and shared metadata standards, with search results displayed in a single unified platform²⁴⁵.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

The Open Access Policy on Scientific Information and Research Data Funded with Public Resources of ANID, in force since 2022 for all instruments producing scientific results, is the main mechanism for promoting the openness, circulation, and reuse of knowledge (ANID, 2022).

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Funding for non-profit journals comes primarily from university institutional funds and competitive calls from ANID. The agency manages the only instrument in the country dedicated to financing scientific journals: the Fondo de Publicación de Revistas Científicas, created in 1988, which —starting with its 2024 call— only accepted institutional projects aimed at funding national Diamond journals, restricting eligibility to those scientific journals indexed by Scielo and the proprietary commercial databases of Clarivate and Elsevier (ANID, 2025b).

Additionally, the SciELO Chile indexing platform, which currently hosts 140 journals, has been administered by the Chilean State through ANID since its creation to maintain the international visibility of national journals. It has become an essential platform for the

²⁴³ Agencia Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo: <https://anid.cl/conoce-anid/historia/>

²⁴⁴ Ibid

²⁴⁵ Espacio Ciencia Platform: <https://www.espaciociencia.cl/>

professionalization of scientific publishing, providing a shared methodology and ensuring the sustainability of the ecosystem²⁴⁶.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Some universities that publish journals have incorporated incentives into their faculty evaluation systems that include scientific editing activities, thereby strengthening the professionalization process. However, the lack of formal recognition of editorial work — for instance, within the university accreditation criteria administered by the Comisión Nacional de Acreditación (CNA)²⁴⁷—remains a structural challenge in the country.

Another challenge is to recognize and reward Open Access publishing within the incentive schemes that universities provide to their authors —making a clear distinction between publishing in Open Access and paying to publish— as well as within the evaluation criteria for academic careers, which currently privilege publication in high-impact factor foreign journals. This contradiction is also reflected in several competitive funding programs administered by ANID.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Chile has a well-developed network of institutional portals managed with OJS, which are increasingly being integrated with persistent identifiers such as ORCID. In addition, universities, scientific societies, and research centres operate interoperable repositories under Creative Commons licenses, facilitating the regional circulation of knowledge.

In October 2025, ANID launched the Espacio Ciencia²⁴⁸ service, which allows information from eight repositories to be retrieved through a single access point, enhancing the visibility of national scientific output, as this service is harvested by LA Referencia and visible in OpenAire. This makes it a scalable service, as more institutions develop repositories that comply with the guidelines defined by ANID in 2024 through cooperative work with universities under the INA framework (ANID, 2024).

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Universities and ANID play a central role in consolidating the Diamond OA model. In fact, universities are the main publishers within the SciELO-Chile collection, followed by scientific societies.

²⁴⁶ SciELO: <http://www.scielo.cl>

²⁴⁷ Comisión Nacional de Acreditación (CNA): <https://www.cnachile.cl/Paginas/Inicio.aspx>

²⁴⁸ Espacio Ciencia Platform: <https://www.espaciociencia.cl/>

In 2022, within the Consorcio de Universidades Estatales (CUECH), the Chilean Network of Open Access Scientific Journals was established with the aim of coordinating and increasing the visibility of the scientific, technological, and social output of 15 of the 18 state universities, while also promoting Open Access to knowledge and strengthening publishing platforms. The Network holds regular meetings (CUECH, n.d.).

Another component is the competitive funding instrument known as InES Ciencia Abierta²⁴⁹, which began operating under ANID in 2021 and has awarded projects to 30 universities. With these resources, universities have been able to establish and/or strengthen their capacities in this area and promote open science practices, including publishing under the Diamond model through editorial training activities, courses on intellectual property rights and digital preservation, as well as the creation of communities of practice for academic editors (ANID, 2025c).

Workforce and Capacity Development

The sustainability of the model largely depends on specialized editorial teams, librarians, and IT technicians who work with limited resources. In most Chilean journals, editorial work is carried out on a voluntary basis or with partial support from universities, highlighting the need for the professionalization and formal recognition of these roles.

In the case of SciELO Chile, in 2024 ANID conducted a study to determine how “Diamond” the SciELO-Chile collection truly was. Of the 136 journals included in the study, 19 titles (14%) charged some form of author fee. These fees varied widely, ranging from USD 35 to USD 2,690. In most cases, the charges were justified by the additional processing time required for complex articles. Among the 19 journals that applied fees, 42% were published by a scientific or professional association. In terms of subject areas, 42% belonged to the biological sciences (ANID, 2024).

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Chile has participated since their inception in the regional networks Red SciELO, RedCLARA, and LA Referencia, which facilitate technical interoperability and the exchange of best practices among editors. In addition, SciELO Chile collaborates with other regional platforms to standardize metadata, impact indicators, and shared digital preservation services.

²⁴⁹ InES Ciencia Abierta: <https://anid.cl/concursos/concurso-ines-ciencia-abierta-2025/>

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Chilean journals indexed in SciELO Chile maintain peer review processes, DOI adoption, CC-BY licenses, and anti-plagiarism policies. Within ANID, the SciELO Chile Coordination Office keeps up to date both the formal and content-based indexing criteria that journals must meet to apply for inclusion through a web platform²⁵⁰. It also maintains a strong communication strategy on social media, provides ongoing training to editors both in person and online, and monitors compliance with these criteria for journals already included in the collection. These actions strengthen a community of practice aligned with international academic publishing standards, ensuring transparency and scientific integrity (ANID, 2025d).

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

In the future, coordinated policies among ANID, the Ministry of Science, the Ministry of Education, the National Accreditation Commission, and universities will be needed to ensure stable funding for Diamond OA journals. The proposed strategic actions include the following:

Encouraging inter-institutional cooperation among universities, libraries, and ministries to share platforms and reduce costs.

Reforming academic evaluation systems traditionally based on scientific productivity indicators such as the Impact Factor and others, to value Open Access and the social relevance of research in science, technology, knowledge, and innovation.

Reassessing the weighting of publications in SciELO Chile journals within the algorithm used to calculate the Aporte Fiscal Directo a las Universidades by the Consejo de Rectoras y Rectores de las Universidades Chilenas²⁵¹.

These measures would help strengthen the Diamond model as a structural component of Chile's national science policy.

The Chilean case demonstrates that the Diamond OA model has become an effective means of expressing universities' commitment to the professional editing of scientific journals, the academic reappropriation of the entire scientific communication cycle, and the democratization of knowledge. With a solid institutional foundation—represented by ANID and the universities—the country can consolidate a sustainable, equitable, and

²⁵⁰ Revistas Científicas Platform: <https://revistascientificas.informacioncientifica.cl/>

²⁵¹ Consejo de Rectoras y Rectores de las Universidades Chilenas: www.consejoderectores.cl

technologically robust publishing system based on a model that can be replicated, as it is supported by well-documented institutional frameworks.

However, its sustainability will depend on long-term funding policies, the professionalization of editorial teams, the inclusion of national Open Access journals in the evaluation criteria for individuals and research projects, and the revaluation of editorial work as a public and collaborative good.

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COLOMBIA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

In Colombia, the non-profit academic publishing ecosystem following the Diamond OA model is in a process of institutional and regulatory consolidation. This development is being led by public universities, supported by recent national policies framed within the context of Open Science (Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation [Minciencias], 2022).

According to current data, Colombian journals are reported as follows: 134 journals listed in Latindex (Catalog 2.0); 268 in RedAlyc; 173 in SciELO-Colombia; and, according to DOAJ, 446 journals, of which 441 do not charge APCs. Their Creative Commons license distribution is as follows: CC BY (88), CC BY-NC (62), CC BY-NC-ND (142), CC BY-NC-SA (132), CC BY-ND (4), and CC BY-SA (18) (Uribe, 2025).

The institutions with the greatest prominence in this field are public universities such as the University of Antioquia (UdeA), the National University of Colombia (UNAL), and the Francisco José de Caldas District University (UDFJC). These institutions have assumed a strategic role in the democratization of knowledge and in the creation of infrastructures that foster open academic production and dissemination through the Diamond OA model.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

At the national level, Colombia has a National Open Science Policy 2022–2031 (Minciencias, 2022), aimed at promoting Open Access and the democratization of knowledge. In accordance with this framework, several institutions have developed institutional policies that support the Diamond OA model. For instance, the University of Antioquia states that the institution is committed to “making publicly and freely available

the academic production created under a legal, regulatory, or contractual relationship with the institution” (University of Antioquia, 2018, para. 3). The National University of Colombia (UNAL) implements actions consistent with the National Open Science Policy (Minciencias, 2022) by strengthening its institutional infrastructures. These regulatory frameworks encourage the adoption of the Diamond OA model.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Public universities maintain this non-commercial Open Access publishing model, which is reflected at different levels through institutional sustainability strategies funded by state resources or by their own academic funds.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Although progress has been made, institutional incentives for publishing under the Diamond OA model still need to be strengthened. Universities acknowledge the importance of recognizing non-profit academic production within evaluation systems and of fostering greater editorial participation.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

National infrastructures such as the UdeA journal system, the UNAL repositories, and the role of UDFJC as a Latindex node strengthen the international visibility of non-profit publications. These platforms facilitate access to Colombian articles and contribute to the global Diamond OA ecosystem.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Some institutions like —UdeA, UNAL, and UDFJC—have established explicit policies that promote non-profit Open Access publishing. These policies include the creation of editorial units, the use and strengthening of the OJS, and interinstitutional cooperation.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Editorial, review, technical, and academic management constitute a fundamental pillar of the Diamond OA model. However, one of the main barriers identified is the limited recognition of these tasks within academic career systems, which hinders the sustained long-term commitment of editorial teams.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

There is observable inter-institutional collaboration among university libraries, publishing units, and national indexing platforms. These partnerships facilitate the shared use of editorial services, team training, and interoperability among journals.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Each university has implemented quality assurance mechanisms such as peer review, digital preservation policies, and the use of Creative Commons licenses. However, the formalization of specific national standards for Diamond OA journals is still lacking.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Although the Diamond OA model is gaining strength in Colombia, further progress is needed through specific policies and sustainable funding mechanisms. Priority strategic actions include the following:

- ✓ Establishing a national fund dedicated to non-profit academic publishing.
- ✓ Formally recognizing editorial, technical, and review work within academic evaluation systems.
- ✓ Creating regional alliances to share platforms and infrastructures that reduce operational costs.
- ✓ Integrating quality indicators other than traditional ones (such as quartiles and Journal Citation Reports) to more fairly assess Diamond OA journals.

Conclusions

The Colombian case demonstrates an institutional maturation process in the adoption of the Diamond OA model. Public universities have led the transition toward more collaborative and sustainable practices, although they still depend on state funding and the consolidation of long-term policies.

The coordination between national policies (Minciencias) and the institutional frameworks of UdeA, UNAL, and UDFJC represent both the main challenge and the key opportunity to establish a stable and competitive non-profit publishing system. Overall, Colombia is moving toward a more inclusive model of open science, grounded in cooperation between universities and the State to ensure access to knowledge as a common good.

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COSTA RICA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Costa Rica presents a scenario where public universities lead the practices of scientific publication without profit and under the principles of Open Access. This prominence arises, among others, because by government decree, public universities directly manage resources for research, which means that 83.2% of national research is produced by these institutions. This propitiates these universities as key actors to lead the transition towards open, inclusive, and sustainable models of scientific production (Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación, Tecnología y Telecomunicaciones, 2024: 46).

This orientation has normative support in the Declaratoria de Ciencia Abierta del Consejo Nacional de Rectores (CONARE, 2024), a document that affirms that the state university system must promote "Open Access and mandatory deposit of generated research" and in non-commercial Open Access (Consejo Nacional de Rectores, 2024: 2).

A key action for this policy was the creation of the Subcomisión de Ciencia Abierta del Consejo Nacional de Rectores, established in 2012, established with the goal of articulating regulations and defining instruments for open science among Costa Rican public universities (Córdoba, 2016), and extending throughout the country. This initiative has promoted hundreds of training sessions and infrastructure implementation for the strengthening of non-commercial Open Access in Costa Rica (Campos et al., 2023).

This framework has strengthened and allowed scientific journals to operate under principles of access and publishing without charging fees to authors or the reading public. However, persistent challenges exist, such as the shortage of human and technical resources and infrastructure, and the limited recognition of editorial work in internal academic evaluation systems.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

La Declaratoria de Ciencia Abierta del CONARE (2024) not only defines Open Access as a guiding principle but also encourages its members to generate alliances for the mandatory deposit of research results, directly promoting non-commercial Open Access.

On the other hand, the Plan Nacional de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación 2022-2027 of the MICITT recognizes the need to strengthen the science and technology system of Costa Rica and promote a knowledge society. In that document, it indicates that the scientific system should articulate resources and promote the social appropriation of knowledge, which opens space and stimulates Open Access and non-profit publication policies (Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación, Tecnología y Telecomunicaciones., 2021).

These two normative documents constitute the legal and strategic support for universities and public institutions when formalizing Open Access as part of their academic and research mission.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Costa Rican public universities contribute their institutional budgets and internal allocations. Universities assume costs of technological infrastructure, editing, and digital preservation as part of their academic work. However, the lack of funding obliges many tasks to be carried out as part of the academic work carried out in universities or as an additional burden on academics. Successful and consolidated models exist, such as those of the Universidad Nacional (UNA), where the university not only assumes all costs and even competitive funds, but also establishes that all its journals must be on the Diamond OA path (Mora-Campos et al. 2024).

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Some universities have made progress in recognizing publication in their journals as academic merit. For example, at UNA, they recognize the merit of scientific journals that do not charge APCs (as a sign of commitment to Open Access). At the Universidad de Costa Rica (UCR), changes have been promoted to equate the evaluation of articles in Diamond OA journals with those in journals that charge a publication fee. However, these incentives require a greater effort to formalize them.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Costa Rican universities use OJS to manage their journals and these platforms support each other through institutional networks. From CONARE, the coordination between institutions facilitates interoperability and the exchange of good practices. With the participation of Costa Rica in networks such as LATINDEX, SciELO and Redalyc, this has increased the visibility of its publications and improved its training and professionalization processes for editorial management.

However, the Declaratoria de Ciencia Abierta de CONARE (2024) identifies the need to improve technological infrastructure and guarantee technical support for the maintenance of interoperable repositories and platforms.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Public universities play a central role in supporting Open Access. Through their vice-rectories of research, publishing offices, and institutional libraries, they manage non-profit scientific journals, guarantee their operational sustainability, and promote their indexing in recognized databases. Some universities have their own competitive funding funds for journals using the Diamond OA model.

Other institutions have adopted internal scientific publishing regulations that promote the Diamond OA model, integrating it into their university research and extension policies.

Workforce and Capacity Development

The editorial staff constitutes the key element. The sustainability of the model depends on its professionalization, stability, and institutional recognition. In many cases, these functions fall on the academic staff as an institutional service, this as part of their working day or with a minimum discharge of their work, which limits the growth and editorial quality.

There are institutions that provide specific time allocations for editing journals that must constantly assess adjustments according to current needs and the demands of the scientific community.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Inter-institutional collaboration is a consolidated practice in Costa Rica. Editorial committees, libraries, technology offices, and vice-rectories coordinate efforts to share infrastructure, training, and services. This cooperation has been promoted by the Subcomisión de Ciencia Abierta (Campos, 2023).

Likewise, Costa Rican institutions take advantage of the initiatives of Latin American networks to access training, knowledge exchange, and greater international visibility.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Peer review, internal editorial processes, and the use of digital identifiers are institutionalized practices in many Costa Rican university journals. However, there is still no uniform national quality certification mechanism for Diamond OA journals that enhances them compared to commercial journals. It relies on international certification with Redalyc, LATINDEX or SciELO. Finally, at the institutional level, the Universidad de Costa Rica does have its own journal evaluation index (called UCRIndex) (Universidad de Costa Rica, 2025) and UNA evaluates the management of its journals with institutional criteria (Mora et al., 2024).

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

To consolidate the Diamond OA model in Costa Rica, it is recommended to:

- ✓ Formalize a national policy for non-profit publications that complements the CONARE Open Science declaration with specific support mechanisms.
- ✓ Establish a national competitive fund to finance non-profit university journals.
- ✓ Professionalize editorial teams through hiring, training, and institutional academic recognition.
- ✓ Modernize and secure the digital infrastructure of OJS platforms and implement them with security and interoperability standards.
- ✓ Promote the review of academic evaluation standards so that Diamond OA publications are valued on equal terms in promotion and incentive processes.
- ✓ Strengthen cooperation between universities, regional networks, and international organizations to share resources for training and good practices.
- ✓ Establish technical teams in national publishing houses for the discharge of technical work by editors (XML tagging, Diagramming, Translation, ...) and strengthen the time dedicated to editorial management.

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CUBA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Cuba has shown steady progress in Open Access, with coordinated efforts among the Ministry of Science, Technology, and Environment (CITMA), universities, and research centres. Although there is no specific national policy for the Diamond OA model, there is a clear trend toward the free dissemination of scientific knowledge as a principle of the national science system. According to CITMA (2023), science produced with public resources must serve society without any charges to authors or readers. Cuban journals are largely managed under a non-commercial Open Access model, sustained by the internal resources of their publishing institutions, primarily public universities.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

CITMA has made progress in developing a National System for the Certification of Scientific Journals, which establishes mandatory Open Access for electronic publications and periodic quality evaluations (CITMA, 2023). This mechanism represents a key step toward the institutionalization of the Diamond OA model.

Additionally, most journals explicitly state that publication is free for both authors and readers, reinforcing the idea of independence from commercial models. These policies are also rooted in Cuba's scientific culture, which has historically promoted academic collaboration and informational sovereignty (Casate, 2018).

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Although structural funding still needs to be strengthened, several institutional mechanisms have been identified. Universities support technological infrastructures with their own resources, and some journals receive basic university funding for hosting

OJS platforms or maintaining digital services (Martí Lahera et al., 2016). There is no specific national fund dedicated exclusively to Diamond journals; however, publishing entities can obtain financial support for improving quality processes and implementing new services through the National System of Science, Technology, and Innovation Programs and Projects. They may also request State budget allocations through the Annual Science, Technology, and Innovation Plan to cover publication and editing costs, which helps ensure their sustainability.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

In Cuba, institutional recognition of editorial, peer-review, and open-access publishing work still needs to be strengthened. Nevertheless, some journals collaborate with international networks, which provides indirect acknowledgment of their quality and openness. To consolidate the Diamond OA model, academic and career advancement systems must include editorial work as a recognized academic merit.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Technological infrastructures for journal preservation promote transparency and digital archiving (Martí Lahera et al., 2016). Many Cuban journals are indexed and operate under the Diamond OA model, enhancing their regional visibility. Moreover, Cuba's participation in the Global Summit on Diamond OA (held in Toluca, Mexico, in October 2023) demonstrates its engagement with global platforms that support the non-profit publishing model (CITMA, 2023).

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

In most Cuban institutions, there is evident commitment and support for the publication of Diamond OA journals, especially within universities and Entidades de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación. Public Cuban universities—such as Universidad de La Habana, Universidad Central “Marta Abreu”, and Universidad de Pinar del Río—serve as fundamental pillars of the Diamond OA model by providing editorial platforms, technical support, institutional Open Access policies, and hosting for non-profit journals (Martí Lahera et al., 2016). Among the main challenges faced by some institutions are the completion and training of technical teams, as well as access to data centre hosting services that ensure uninterrupted online availability of journal websites.

Workforce and Capacity Development

The human factor is key: editors, reviewers, information technicians, librarians, and repository managers make publication without charges possible. In Cuba, much of this work is carried out on a voluntary basis. To strengthen sustainability, it is necessary to

professionalize these roles, ensure institutional stability, and recognize their contribution within academic evaluation systems (Casate, 2018).

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

There are collaborations between universities and CITMA for the certification of journals and the strengthening of Open Access. Likewise, some journals use shared OJS platforms, common licensing standards, and interoperable metadata, which helps reduce costs and improve editorial quality.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Cuban journals explicitly declare their Diamond OA model and adopt policies for peer review, anti-plagiarism, Creative Commons licensing, and digital preservation. These practices reflect a quality assurance strategy that can be replicated by other national publications.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

To consolidate the Diamond model in Cuba, the following actions are proposed:

- ✓ Create a National Fund for Diamond OA Journals to ensure resources for infrastructure, digital hosting, and editorial training.
- ✓ Integrate editorial work, journal management, and Open Access into the criteria for academic evaluation and university promotion.
- ✓ Strengthen regional and international collaboration through networks such as AmeliCA, Redalyc, and SciELO, and promote broader integration of Cuba.
- ✓ Professionalize the editorial, technical, and library teams that support the model through continuous training and institutional stability.

Conclusions

Cuba is moving toward a united and sovereign Open Access model, grounded in the idea that science must serve the common good. Although it faces economic and technological limitations, its institutional structure and collaborative scientific culture provide a solid foundation for strengthening the Diamond OA model. The creation of explicit national policies, along with sustainable funding and recognition of editorial work, will enable Cuba to consolidate an open, inclusive, and sovereign scientific system.

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ECUADOR

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

The non-profit academic publishing ecosystem in Ecuador is structured around university networks, recent policies, and a growing Open Science movement. Diamond publishing is promoted primarily by public universities and civil society actors such as the Fundación Openlab Ecuador. Over the past decade, the country has made significant progress in institutionalizing Open Access and Open Science. The Secretaría de Educación Superior, Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación (SENESCYT) has led policies that promote knowledge as a public good and its dissemination without economic barriers (Silva-Garcés et al., 2025).

This approach has led to the creation of national and institutional repositories, the adoption of open editorial policies, and the consolidation of networks such as the Red de Investigación de Conocimiento, Software y Hardware Libre, which includes a Working Group on Open Science²⁵² registered with SENESCYT under N.º REG-RED-18-0009²⁵³. However, the Diamond OA model requires financial and editorial professionalization, as many journals rely on the voluntary work of faculty members and technical staff.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

Ecuador has strengthened the legal framework for Open Access, which is now established in the Constitution (2008), the Ley Orgánica de Educación Superior (2010), the Código Ingenios (2016), as well as the recent draft public policy on open science developed jointly by OpenlabEC and the State (2024), which is still pending approval.

²⁵² Working Group on Open Science: <https://comunidad.conocimientolibre.ec/assemblies/ciencia-abierta>

²⁵³ SENESCYT under N.º REG-RED-18-0009: <https://www.conocimientolibre.ec/>

These instruments mandate the deposit of theses and research results funded with public resources in open repositories, while also promoting free licenses and national and regional interoperability (Silva-Garcés et al., 2025). On the other hand, it is worth noting that the initial regulatory frameworks, such as the Ley Orgánica de Educación Superior (LOES)²⁵⁴—in its latest reform of 2025—and its supplementary provisions²⁵⁵, promoted the creation of digital repositories. Although these regulations do not explicitly refer to current open access repositories or interoperability principles, they lay the groundwork for developing infrastructure oriented toward Open Access. In this process, community-driven initiatives carry greater weight than regulatory mandates.

For their part, higher education institutions such as the Universidad Central del Ecuador (UCE), the Escuela Politécnica Nacional (EPN), and the Universidad Técnica Particular de Loja (UTPL) participate in national cooperation networks that promote platform interoperability and editorial professionalization.

FLACSO ANDES Ecuador, EPN, UTPL, and the Escuela Superior Politécnica del Litoral (ESPOL) have played an important role in the early stages of implementing open access infrastructures in Ecuador.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Ecuadorian universities form the core of the Diamond OA model. The Universidad Central del Ecuador (UCE), Escuela Politécnica Nacional (EPN), and Universidad Técnica Particular de Loja (UTPL) finance technological infrastructure (servers, DOI registration, Open Journal Systems support) with institutional resources, while also incorporating open academic publishing into their development plans.

SENESCYT, through public policy, plays a coordinating role by promoting regulations and competitive funding for editorial projects, as well as the standardization and development of capacities in editorial management.

Institutions such as SENESCYT, CEDIA, and universities manage key infrastructures (RED DE REPOSITORIOS DE ACCESO ABIERTO, SciELO-Ecuador). However, challenges remain due to the lack of permanent incentives and resources, as well as the absence of standardized editorial models with sustainable funding (Silva-Garcés et al., 2025).

²⁵⁴ Ley Orgánica de Educación Superior (LOES):

<https://procuraduria.utpl.edu.ec/sitios/documentos/NormativasPublicas/Ley%20Org%C3%A1nica%20de%20Educaci%C3%B3n%20Superior%202025.pdf>

²⁵⁵ Supplementary provisions of the LOES:

<https://atenea.epn.edu.ec/bitstream/25000/1000/1/LOES%20-%20207-02-2023.pdf>

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Evaluation, categorization, and accreditation policies still favour commercial models and international metrics, which hinders the institutional recognition of Diamond OA journals. While there are some financial compensation and acknowledgment of training hours (for example, at the Universidad de las Fuerzas Armadas ESPE and in Manabí), direct incentives for non-profit publishing and an Open Science culture remain marginal and not widely promoted (Silva-Garcés et al., 2025).

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Journal platforms use the Open Journal System (OJS) and are implemented directly by universities and research centres. Ecuador has developed advanced technological infrastructure for Open Access to facilitate interoperability; however, there is an urgent need to foster a stronger culture of Open Science and data integration, as well as to manage journals according to international standards (Bermúdez, 2011; Silva-Garcés et al., 2025).

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Key actors include higher education institutions; the Secretaría de Educación Superior, Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación (SENESCYT); the Corporación Ecuatoriana para el Desarrollo de la Investigación y la Academia (CEDIA); the Consejo de Educación Superior (CES); the Consejo de Aseguramiento de la Calidad de la Educación Superior (CACES); the Red Ecuatoriana de Revistas Científicas y Editores (RERCIE); OpenLab Ecuador; and various collaborative networks. Deans, rectors, and open science specialists are driving processes of cooperation and capacity building (Silva-Garcés et al., 2025). Likewise, there are editorial associations such as the Red de Editores y Revistas Científicas Ecuatorianas²⁵⁶, which promote coordination and the strengthening of the national publishing ecosystem.

Workforce and Capacity Development

The sustainability of the Ecuadorian Diamond OA model largely depends on the work of editorial teams within higher education institutions, who in many cases combine teaching and research responsibilities with the management of scientific journals. Likewise, the stability of Ecuadorian publications requires the institutionalization of these teams and the recognition of unpaid academic work; therefore, the formalization and financial compensation of these tasks are essential to ensure the continuity of the model. Without a cultural and professional shift toward collaborative and open

²⁵⁶ Red de Editores y Revistas Científicas Ecuatorianas: <https://rercie.ups.edu.ec/>

practices, no number of financial resources will be sufficient to achieve lasting transformation (Silva-Garcés et al., 2025).

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Ecuador has promoted editorial cooperation based on inter-institutional networks. SENESCYT, the Red de Conocimiento Libre, among others, fosters interoperability among platforms and shares technical infrastructure such as servers, persistent identifiers, and digital preservation systems. Likewise, universities collaborate with international organizations such as LA Referencia to increase the visibility of national research output and reduce costs through shared repositories (Silva-Garcés et al., 2025).

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

The Ecuadorian system incorporates editorial evaluation mechanisms through non-commercial indexes. Universities apply good practice guidelines, blind peer review, COPE standards, and open licenses. Editorial oversight is carried out by journal committees and university departments, although institutional support and stricter public quality assurance mechanisms are still lacking (Silva-Garcés et al., 2025). These actions aim to ensure academic integrity, transparency, and the traceability of scientific publishing processes.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

To strengthen the Diamond OA model, it is recommended to transform evaluation frameworks, invest in technical, human, and editorial infrastructure, consolidate public and private funding, safeguard academic independence, and promote institutional, national, and international partnerships. The consolidation and proper implementation of public policies will be key to ensuring long-term sustainability (Silva-Garcés et al., 2025).

Taken as a whole, the Ecuadorian Diamond OA model shows significant progress in infrastructure development and inter-institutional cooperation, particularly through OJS platforms maintained by universities and academic networks. However, challenges remain regarding the institutionalization of editorial work, training in open science, and the adoption of international standards. The sustainability of the model depends on coherent public policies, stable funding, and recognition of the human capital that sustains scientific journals. Ultimately, the coordination among universities, national networks, and international organizations strengthens an editorial ecosystem oriented toward more visible, rigorous, and equitable scientific communication.

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GUATEMALA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Guatemala is at a crucial juncture for rethinking and strengthening the ecosystem of nonprofit academic publishing, especially within the framework of Diamond OA. The Universidad de San Carlos de Guatemala (USAC), as the main and only public institution of higher education in the country, plays a fundamental role in promoting Open Access and the democratization of knowledge. Despite recent progress, the absence of robust institutional policies and formal mechanisms for funding and recognition of editorial work under Diamond OA schemes limits the consolidation of this model in the national context (Universidad de San Carlos de Guatemala, 2023).

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

Since 2023, USAC has had a new Research Policy that promotes the generation of knowledge, its dissemination, and Open Access as fundamental pillars (Universidad de San Carlos de Guatemala, 2023). This policy is based on principles of ethics, equity, sustainability, and social inclusion, and responds to the current demands of Guatemalan society in alignment with the national agenda on science, technology, and innovation. However, although the importance of nonprofit scholarly publishing is recognized, no specific regulations or dedicated funding lines have yet been developed to strengthen the Diamond OA model either institutionally or nationally.

The national legal framework, from the Constitution (Article 82), guarantees university autonomy and the promotion of research, and the Ley de Promoción del Desarrollo Científico y Tecnológico (Decree 63-91) encourages the generation and dissemination of new knowledge (Universidad de San Carlos de Guatemala, 2023). Nevertheless, implementing these principles into concrete actions that ensure editorial sustainability remains a challenge.

Institutional Role and Key Actors

The public university leads the landscape with dozens of journals and infrastructure for the Diamond OA model, alongside editorial teams and arbitration committees. The editorial independence of Diamond OA journals allows prioritizing scientific quality, social relevance, and academic sovereignty, although centralized coordination and professionalization of editorial work are still lacking.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

In Guatemala, editorial independence —especially under the Diamond OA model— represents an opportunity to prioritize social relevance, scientific quality, and sovereignty over the academic knowledge produced. Key actors in this process are the editorial ecosystems of higher education institutions' journals, whose collaboration is essential to articulate efforts and resources dedicated to nonprofit academic production. Regional academic alliances and potential public funds are also important, but there are still no formal mechanisms or dedicated financing for the Diamond OA model.

Furthermore, there is no formal and centralized structure for managing Diamond OA publishing, resulting in heterogeneous practices and difficulty in sustaining the model— an issue also reflected in other Latin American contexts.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

One of the main challenges identified is the precarious working conditions and lack of formal recognition of editorial work, as most editorial teams lack specific contracts and perform their duties without exclusive dedication or clear financial incentives. This situation leads to a lack of professionalization, demotivation, and a high risk of discontinuity in scientific publications (AmeliCA, 2021). Additionally, the lack of technological infrastructure and common platforms hinders efficient journal management and preservation (Marroquín, 2023).

The absence of sustainable funding mechanisms, along with the lack of clear regulations and guidelines, creates institutional fragmentation and prevents the consolidation of good practices associated with Diamond OA, such as interoperability and international visibility. These challenges can be mitigated by strengthening technical capacities and human resources through continuous training, professionalizing the editorial role, and promoting common institutional technological platforms, as demonstrated by regional collaborations such as Redalyc and AmeliCA.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Inter-institutional cooperation, regional indexing platforms, and national repositories are emerging yet promising pillars for improving the interoperability and visibility of Guatemalan journals. Developing unified technological infrastructure, shared platforms (such as OJS), and participation in international networks could strengthen the Diamond OA landscape: Redalyc and AmeliCA.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Universities and individual academic units independently promote the creation and management of journals. However, the lack of a central institutional editorial unit limits strategic planning and resource optimization. Institutional policies aligned with open science are needed to support editorial autonomy, technical development, and career recognition.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Editorial teams face limited recognition, precarious contractual conditions, and insufficient training opportunities. Transitioning to formal contracts, technical support, and professional career paths is key to retaining talent and ensuring rigorous editorial practices.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Current efforts remain fragmented, with pockets of collaboration among universities, science councils, and regional networks (Redalyc, AmeliCA, Latindex). Expanding these alliances and joint initiatives could reduce costs, enhance journal quality, and promote national and regional sustainability.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Updating and harmonizing editorial guidelines, peer review standards, and periodic evaluations of journal quality are necessary to meet international indexing requirements. Collaborative training and adoption of best practices support continuous improvement in editorial rigor.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Mainstream Diamond OA Publishing

To consolidate the Diamond OA model in Guatemala, it is a priority to:

- ✓ Promote academic and administrative recognition of editorial work, incorporating editorial management indicators into institutional evaluations and funding allocations.

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- ✓ Develop specific institutional and national policies for the Diamond OA model, aligned with open science, including funding lines and mechanisms for inter-institutional collaboration.
- ✓ Encourage the creation of interoperable institutional platforms and repositories, leveraging successful experiences in Latin America.
- ✓ Foster interuniversity consortia, alliances with regional networks, and international cooperation to share technical resources, infrastructure, and editorial training.
- ✓ Coordinate with SENACYT and higher education institutions to create common frameworks for support and sustainability.
- ✓ Strengthen the visibility and quality standards of Guatemalan journals.

Guatemala has made significant progress in recognizing the importance of research and Open Access but faces major challenges in consolidating the Diamond OA publishing model. The articulation of policies, funding, professionalization, and institutional collaboration will be essential for strengthening and sustaining the nonprofit editorial ecosystem.

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HONDURAS

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Nonprofit scholarly publishing and the Diamond Open Access (OA) model in Honduras are in the process of consolidation, driven mainly by higher education institutions. The platform that hosts most journals is the portal CAMJOL,²⁵⁷ which brings together journals from Honduras, El Salvador, and Nicaragua under standards of free access for both authors and readers. In Honduras, there are currently 62 journals, all following the Diamond model according to Latindex.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

At the institutional level, higher education institutions are the primary supporters of scientific journals operating under the Diamond OA model. Some of these institutions, such as UNAH, are working on open access regulations aligned with Diamond OA. Adherence to international initiatives such as AmeliCA and Redalyc expands legal and technical support. At the national level, there is still no specific policy for Diamond OA, but the academic community increasingly promotes open production as a public good.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Journal funding comes mostly from higher education institutions themselves. However, long-term sustainability requires strengthening financial incentives, technical capacities, and human resources dedicated exclusively to editorial work, as well as achieving recognition and appreciation within internal academic evaluation systems (Maradiaga, 2021).

²⁵⁷ https://cbues.org/sv/?page_id=1292

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Currently, there are incentives for faculty reclassification and financial rewards focused on publishing in indexed journals — including both open access and paywalled ones — without distinguishing the editorial model. For Diamond OA production, recognition is promoted through scholarships, awards, and career advancement when publications achieve international visibility and meet quality and open access criteria.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

The essential infrastructure is represented by journal portals implemented in OJS. Other initiatives such as Latindex, Redalyc, DOAJ, and AmeliCA provide training and technological transfer collaborations.

Institutional Roles and Support Mechanisms

Editors, university editorial offices, research departments or directorates, library systems, research institutes, and faculties actively participate in nonprofit scientific production, coordinated by deans, vice-chancellors, and rectors. External actors from the Latin American and regional Open Science networks also play a role.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Sustainable production under the Diamond model requires trained personnel, editors, managers, researchers, and an academic culture oriented toward open and collaborative practices. The most significant limitations are the lack of continuous training, insufficient advanced editorial education, and dependence on volunteer human resources (Maradiaga, 2021).

Collaboration between Publishers and Service Providers

Institutional and international collaboration relies on strengthening networks such as CAMJOL, which supports journals from several Central American countries, and partnerships with regional databases and repositories. Joint work with AmeliCA, Latindex, and Redalyc contributes to journal professionalization, global visibility, and better editorial practices (AmeliCA, 2024).

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Honduran Diamond journals use peer review, DOAJ, Latindex, Redalyc, and AmeliCA criteria, Creative Commons licenses, and periodicity and quality standards for international indexing. Editorial assurance depends on internal committees, regulations, and the continuous training of editorial teams (Universidad Nacional de Honduras, 2024).

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Mainstream Diamond OA Publishing

Honduras requires clear open access policies and sustainable funding, continuous training, equitable financial incentives for all personnel, and modernization of publishing platforms. Interinstitutional agreements and open networks can consolidate the model both locally and regionally.

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MEXICO

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

In Mexico, there has been a strong contribution to the advances in Open Access. There are hundreds of journals supported by universities, authors, professors, and researchers belonging to public institutions, mainly financed with public funds. In addition, Open Access is supported by platforms such as Latindex²⁵⁸ in 1995 at the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM) and which became a regional cooperation network from 1997; Biblat²⁵⁹, the portal launched in 2009 by the General Directorate of Libraries of the UNAM; Redalyc²⁶⁰ which was established in 2003 at the Autonomous University of the State of Mexico; and SciELO Mexico²⁶¹ developed by the General Directorate of Libraries and Digital Information Services of the UNAM in 2004.

The platforms are complemented by the use of repositories: currently 135 repositories operate in Mexico at 80 institutions, curating around one million items that mostly include open data deposits. There are also initiatives such as REMERI²⁶², LA Referencia²⁶³, and AmeliCA Open Data Repository²⁶⁴, which allow the publication, access, and reuse of publications, documents, and research data.

This model has historically been characterized as public, cooperative, non-profit and fundamentally community driven. Its main purpose is to democratize knowledge, promoting equity and accessibility for all. Furthermore, this model actively fosters bibliodiversity and facilitates focused research.

²⁵⁸ Latindex: <https://latindex.org/latindex/>

²⁵⁹ Biblat: <https://biblat.unam.mx/es/>

²⁶⁰ Redalyc: <https://www.redalyc.org/>

²⁶¹ SciELO Mexico: <https://scielo.org/es/>

²⁶² REMERI: <https://www.remeri.org.mx/app/index.html>

²⁶³ LA Referencia: <https://www.lareferencia.info/es/>

²⁶⁴ AmeliCA Open Data Repository: <https://commons.amelica.org/open-data/home>

Government initiatives seek to provide transparency to information and stimulate Open Access to science with the Open Access Law²⁶⁵ of 2014, the National Open Science Policy²⁶⁶ of 2017, the reform of the Political Constitution of the United Mexican States²⁶⁷ in 2019 and the General Law on Humanities, Sciences, Technologies and Innovation²⁶⁸ in 2023.

These initiatives have defined Open Access as an essential element of the human right to science and are progressively establishing a legal framework aimed at guaranteeing this fundamental right as the basis of the country's public policies.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

In 2014, a reform was carried out on various regulatory provisions in the Science and Technology Law, the General Education Law and the Organic Law of the National Council of Science and Technology, which configured the Open Access Law in Mexico.

In 2017, Mexico published its National Open Science Policy (CONACYT, 2017). This policy was directed at the National System of Science, Technology and Innovation and at all those who carry out academic, scientific, technological and innovative research, fully or partially funded with public resources or who have used public infrastructure.

Currently, Open Access in Mexico has an unprecedented regulatory framework and can be considered a global benchmark. In 2019, the Political Constitution of the United Mexican States was amended, and Article 3, Section V, the Right to Education, establishes that everyone has the right to enjoy the benefits of scientific development and technological innovation. The State will support scientific, humanistic, and technological research and innovation and will guarantee Open Access to the information derived from it. The General Law on Humanities, Sciences, Technologies, and Innovation, in its first title, establishes the human right to science as the foundation of public policies and defines Open Access as an element of the human right to science.

Recently, the Sectoral Program for Science, Humanities, Technology and Innovation 2025-2030 includes a Strategy aimed at disseminating the results of basic and applied

²⁶⁵ Open Access Law: <https://repositorionacionalcti.mx/docs/LCyT.pdf>

²⁶⁶ National Open Science Policy: https://secihti.mx/wp-content/uploads/transparencia/planes_programas_informes/libros_blanco/Ciencia_Abierta.pdf

²⁶⁷ Political Constitution of the United Mexican States: <https://www.constitucionpolitica.mx/versiones-antteriores/2019>

²⁶⁸ General Law on Humanities, Sciences, Technologies and Innovation: <https://www.diputados.gob.mx/LeyesBiblio/pdf/LGMHCTI.pdf>

research, through the design and implementation of the National System of Scientific and Humanistic Publications²⁶⁹.

Despite the current absence of an established national policy, such a policy is currently under development and promises significant impact and institutional implementation. As part of this effort, the SECIHTI—the governing body for Open Access policy in Mexico—has conducted a survey of Open Access journals to identify their characteristics, editorial policies, and sustainability challenges. Furthermore, to ensure the dissemination and outreach of knowledge, a Technical Advisory Group has been formed to establish and strengthen the future National System of Scientific and Humanistic Publications.

These actions together seek to guarantee that access to science is a human right, as well as to define the principles under which research should be carried out to seek social benefit, and the use of platforms and implementation of initiatives to ensure that access to state-funded scientific information is open and free.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Scientific journals are primarily supported through institutional public funding models (mainly managed by CONAHCYT) and, to a lesser extent, through alternative revenue streams.

Many journals are published by public universities, research centres, and scientific societies. These institutions contribute human resources, infrastructure, and budgets for editorial operations as part of their commitment to generating and disseminating knowledge. Editorial work is frequently carried out by faculty and researchers without additional compensation, as part of their academic responsibilities.

At the institutional level, several universities are providing concrete support for publications. At UNAM, the Subdirectorate of Academic Journals and Digital Publications is responsible for the distribution of resources and services. Similarly, the University of Guadalajara has maintained an annual program of university scientific journals²⁷⁰ since 2014. It offers various forms of support, encompassing assistance with hiring or retaining staff working on the journals and strengthening editorial activities, among other incentives.

²⁶⁹ National System of Scientific and Humanistic Publications:

https://www.dof.gob.mx/nota_detalle.php?codigo=5767978&fecha=17/09/2025#gsc.tab=0

²⁷⁰ University of Guadalajara. Annual program of university scientific journals:

<https://vicerrectoriaacademica.udg.mx/transferecia-tecnologica/convocatorias/revistas-cientificas>

Some journals are supported by cooperation with thematic networks, publishing consortia, or academic associations. This allows them to share resources and experiences, thereby reducing operating costs.

Overall, many Diamond OA projects lack fixed budgets and rely on extraordinary funding or international cooperation, which generates a lack of sustainability that prevents the permanent consolidation of some of their services and limits their long-term impact. This situation highlights the urgent need to establish financing models focused on strengthening these projects.

This is precisely where the development of regional and global Open Access infrastructures becomes essential for the stability and sustainability of the ecosystem. Especially because commercial models based on article processing charges (APCs) and transformative agreements—which threaten to re-enclose knowledge and exacerbate inequalities—are still emerging and hardly adopted in the Mexican context, having been virtually nonexistent just a few years ago.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

While limited strategies exist to promote Diamond OA through direct financial incentives, there are also strategies that operate through institutional recognition and academic evaluation as key mechanisms.

Mexico's National System of Researchers (SNII) establishes, among its considerations²⁷¹, the state's recognition of its responsibility to guarantee Open Access to research and innovation in science, the humanities, and technology. And in the evaluation criteria²⁷², one of the components considered is the contribution of Open Access research, such as publications in repositories, book chapters, and data.

In several Mexican public higher education institutions, evaluation systems have adopted indexing on non-commercial Open Access platforms (such as DOAJ, SciELO, Redalyc and Latindex) as formal criteria and a validated metric for awarding incentives and performance recognition.

These strategies provide significant validity and formal legitimacy to Diamond OA publishing, and while they are highly relevant and necessary incentives, there is still the need to strengthen infrastructure, professionalization, and funding.

²⁷¹ National System of Researchers (SNII) considerations: <https://secihti.mx/el-conacyt/sistema-nacional-de-investigadores>

²⁷² National System of Researchers (SNII) evaluation criteria: https://secihti.mx/wp-content/uploads/sni/marco_legal/criterios/Anexo_Parametros%20de_referencia_para_la_evaluacion_d_eL_SNII.pdf

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Universities have been developing institutional journal portals to increase the visibility and bring together all the academic journals published and maintained by their community. The most relevant is the UNAM journal portal, which implements Latindex criteria and allows users to retrieve journal articles from the OJS platform or any other system that allows the exchange of descriptive article data.

OJS in Mexico has established itself as a platform that optimizes the publication and management of nearly 500 academic journals. Its use, which stands out for its low cost or free availability, has facilitated the adoption of open publishing practices and by operating under international standards, Mexican journals increase their visibility and impact in the global scientific community.

The visibility and reuse of scientific production in Mexico is enhanced thanks to initiatives such as REMERI, LaReferencia and AmeliCA Open Data Repository, which facilitate the publication, access and reuse of publications, documents and research data.

The Mexican Network of Institutional Repositories (since 2012) collects and integrates the scientific, academic, and documentary output deposited in repositories for dissemination, visibility, and Open Access. This network integrates all institutional and thematic repositories of higher education institutions and public and private organizations and includes the portals of university journals that primarily promote non-profit academic publication.

The Centralized Open Science Repository (RECCA) of the SECIHTI is designed to streamline deposit and guarantee the preservation, security, and dissemination of research output in the Humanities, Sciences, Technologies, and Innovation (HCTI), RECCA aims to position itself as a key tool for promoting Open Access to scientific information for all social actors. A fundamental characteristic of RECCA is its capacity to foster interoperability with other digital repositories.

Initiatives such as Redalyc, SciELO Mexico, Latindex, and AmeliCA have been key in providing free technical support and visibility for scientific journals. These infrastructures offer services for quality assurance and indexing, visibility, and also provide editorial training and technological tools (such as content management systems, XML-JATS, and persistent identifiers).

Additionally, there are academic initiatives that seek to strengthen and implement open science in Mexico, such as the permanent seminars at UNAM that seek to professionalize and strengthen academic and scientific publishing work, and the Redalyc international congresses, in which editors are trained in the use of digital tools

and standards such as XML-JATS, in editorial quality, use of metrics, visibility and sustainability of journals, among others.

These Open Science infrastructures fundamentally address the existing inequalities in the dissemination of and access to scientific knowledge in the country.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Although most Mexican academic institutions have scientific journals that are largely Open Access, very few have an institutional Open Access policy (similar to that of UNAM).

UNAM has an Agreement establishing the General Guidelines for UNAM's Open Access policy, which states that the university, in fulfilment of its core activities, provides free and Open Access to academic content. The UAM has a significant body of scientific work published in non-commercial academic and scientific journals. These journals are part of a public goods ecosystem supported by universities under a non-profit model.

At the University of Guadalajara (UDG), the aim is to maintain the publication of Open Access journals of academic and scientific communication and dissemination, but not under a defined institutional policy scheme, although they recognize that all the research they work on as an institution must be at the service of society.

Although science has been constitutionally recognized as a human right, and Open Access is established as a right, institutional practices persist that contradict this principle by treating knowledge as a commodity. Mexican academic institutions have the opportunity to play a key role in consolidating the Diamond OA model. This is to reaffirm the duty of universities to respond to social needs, understanding knowledge as an essential public good for confronting the challenges of injustice, exclusion, and inequality.

Workforce and Capacity Development

The sustainability of the Diamond OA publishing model in Mexico rests fundamentally on the human factor, understood as an inseparable triad comprising technical staff, academic staff, and management/decision-makers, supported by institutional financial backing. Participation and coordination for Diamond OA is inherently interdepartmental, involving essential units such as academic libraries, university presses, graduate programs, and research, technology, dissemination & communication centres and coordination offices.

The editorial staff constitutes the operational core of the system. Editorial teams, frequently composed of faculty and researchers, assume essential technical, scientific, and administrative functions for the quality of the journals. Leadership and coordination

rest with both government authorities (science ministries) and institutional authorities, as well as the journal's director/editor-in-chief. Functions are distributed among academic departments (editorial officers), the management of the digital infrastructure (such as the UNAM's Academic Journals Division), institutional repositories, and printing facilities.

To strengthen this core, staff professionalization is critical. Training and development programs promoted by infrastructures such as Redalyc and AmeliCA, and by institutions like UNAM and CONAHCYT, among many others, have been fundamental in raising standards in peer review, metadata, and digital preservation technology. Ongoing training and development are necessary as both a cultural and operational solution, through the implementation of awareness programs and capacity building for Diamond OA and digital publishing management. Trained staff and trainers are required to carry out this mission.

However, the system faces challenges, and it is necessary to reaffirm the commitment and initiative of those responsible for academic and administrative departments. The workforce, despite its crucial role, does not always have the necessary structural support. It is vital that key stakeholders—such as universities, research centres, funding bodies, and science secretariats—assume their role in leading and coordinating institutional Open Access policies, as well as editorial and evaluation policies that formalize support for the model.

The effort should be directed towards formalizing and financing the triad of roles (technical, academic, managerial), ensuring interdepartmental articulation and counteracting institutional inertia through the continuous professionalization of editorial teams.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

The Mexican open science ecosystem is essentially based on collaboration for the sustainability of Diamond OA to share technological infrastructure, indexing services and online editing tools.

The cornerstone of this collaboration is open infrastructure, which is the fundamental vehicle for safeguarding, accessing, disseminating, and preserving an institution's academic output. This infrastructure fosters cooperation over competition by sharing technological infrastructure, indexing services, technical support, and online publishing tools free of charge.

It is worth highlighting the role played by journal portals, platforms and databases with the aim of providing visibility and bringing together the set of academic journals published and supported by their community and whose services benefit and complement the functionalities of scientific journals in this non-commercial system.

The region has several journal portals, platforms, directories and databases that provide a range of services to non-commercial scientific publications, including Latindex, Redalyc, SciELO, PKP and AmeliCA, among others.

The direct benefits of these services for publishers are increased visibility of their journals' content, improved search engine ranking, and enhanced prestige. Furthermore, the benefits of shared infrastructure and horizontal collaboration include reduced costs, enhanced quality control and professionalization, greater scalability, resilience, and digital preservation. Platforms like OJS and tools like Marcalyc are essential in this process, as they facilitate compliance with international standards for digital publishing management. Shared infrastructure, collaboration, and horizontal exchange are key to the model's success.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Diamond OA quality is ensured through three pillars: the professionalization of the editorial process, technical standardization, and an editorial approach based on academic and social relevance.

This editorial approach differs from a commercial one because decision-making is based solely on quality, assessing whether content contributes to the field of study and is socially relevant, not on generating revenue through APCs. Professionalization involves having established and stable editorial teams and formal recognition of the editorial process as a professional activity. Standardization is necessary in both technical solutions and processes to ensure platform interoperability through the use of international standards and open technologies.

In terms of good practices, Mexican journals employ rigorous peer-review systems, editorial transparency, and the use of persistent identifiers (DOI, ORCID). Initiatives such as Scielo, Redalyc and Latindex have demonstrated their effectiveness, quality, and implementation of recognized quality standards and criteria, contributing to increased visibility, interoperability, and quality of journals in the region. These practices have positioned Mexico as a regional benchmark in visibility, editorial ethics, and quality control in non-profit publications.

Finally, it is crucial that Diamond OA publications receive academic recognition in evaluation systems; without this, researchers lack incentives to publish in them, which weakens the established quality ecosystem.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

To strengthen the Diamond ecosystem, the following policy and financing actions are proposed:

- ✓ Consolidate a national policy for non-profit publishing (in conjunction with CONAHCYT), recognized and validated by all entities involved in the generation, evaluation, consumption and dissemination of knowledge.
- ✓ Creation of a Diamond OA policy at the institutional and national level, aligned with the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science and Manifestos and Declarations on Diamond OA.
- ✓ Implement Diamond OA institutional policies and establish mandatory regulations (binding institutional and national policies).
- ✓ It is essential to reform the Evaluation Criteria to recognize and value the Diamond OA publication, prioritizing its quality and social relevance over conventional productivity metrics such as the Impact Factor, the percentile/quartile of journals, and indexes such as WoS or Scopus.
- ✓ Measuring impact and visibility on social media and alternative metrics (Altmetrics)
- ✓ It is crucial to ensure sustainable public funding and regulations for the entire non-profit academic production ecosystem. The sustainability of non-commercial scientific journals published by Mexican institutions, along with institutional, thematic, or regional repositories, must be strengthened and integrated into structural budgets to guarantee their continued operation.
- ✓ The institution's total spending on Article Processing Charges (APCs) and/or Transformative Agreements should be audited to identify funds that can be strategically redirected toward investment in the Diamond OA publishing model. This includes the possibility of allocating a percentage of the budget that a faculty or research centre used to cover APCs to Diamond OA journals. Following initiatives such as the one proposed by UNAM, the proposal suggests cutting the resources currently allocated to APC payments for foreign journals.

- ✓ Promote the reallocation of public funds, for example, by converting library budgets from "content acquisition" to "support for publishing infrastructure" (UdeG).
- ✓ Seeking funding by submitting projects to national and international calls for proposals, as well as obtaining sponsorships from non-profit civil organizations or the private sector.
- ✓ It is proposed that a central body (such as a knowledge management office or an Open Access office) be created within the institutions. This body's main objective will be to implement the policy and coordinate all related efforts.
- ✓ Interoperable infrastructure must be strengthened and a shared national infrastructure developed for the academic ecosystem. This includes the implementation of open digital infrastructures for the storage, management, access, and preservation of scientific output, such as institutional repositories, CRIS (Current Research Information Systems), journal/book platforms, and open data management tools.
- ✓ It is essential to promote the professionalization of editorial processes and increase institutional editorial capacity, along with the adoption of relevant technical standards.
- ✓ Creation of awareness-raising, training, promotion, and incentive programs on the benefits of Open Science and publishing in Diamond OA, aimed at researchers, managers, and interested people.
- ✓ Recognition and active participation of the academic community should be encouraged, as they are the main actors and primary promoters among peers and students. This can be achieved through the promotion and training of new researchers, volunteering (such as the Wikimedia Projects model), and open collaboration at all levels.

In this way, México and developing countries could maintain autonomy and control over the generation and circulation of knowledge and sustain a non-profit scientific communication system aligned with the principles of equity, inclusion, and transparency. This would preserve their independence from the commercial publishing model, where their communities are often excluded or patronized.

However, obstacles still exist that threaten its sustainability and implementation. This model faces significant challenges in terms of the stability of its funding, the recognition of editorial work as an essential component of scientific activity, the implementation of

incentives and evaluation mechanisms that promote Diamond OA publishing, and the strengthening of the open infrastructures that support it.

Mexico has taken significant steps to promote and implement Diamond OA, which could give it a unique international leadership position. This potential lies specifically in its ability to consolidate and export the model, which has historically been strong in Latin America.

NICARAGUA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

In Nicaragua, the development of open science and the Diamond OA model is at a characterized level by isolated institutional efforts but with growing interest from public universities and research organizations. The Universidad Nacional Autónoma de Nicaragua (UNAN-Managua) has been a pioneer in promoting Open Access policies and institutional repositories, in line with UNESCO's (2021) recommendations on the openness of scientific knowledge.

The editorial independence of Diamond OA journals allows for greater freedom in selecting content relevant to the local academic community, free from the commercial pressures of private publishers. This perspective reflects an emerging trend toward the democratization of scientific knowledge in the Nicaraguan context, where institutions seek to balance academic production with social commitment and inclusion.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

In Nicaragua, Open Access initiatives are primarily developed within higher education institutions, in line with the principles of knowledge openness promoted by the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021). Several public universities have established institutional repositories and academic journal portals that operate under open licenses, contributing to the free dissemination of scientific knowledge.

These platforms are harvested by the Sistema de Información y Documentación Científica de Centroamérica (SIIDCA-CSUCA)²⁷³, which strengthens the regional visibility

²⁷³ Sistema de Información y Documentación Científica de Centroamérica (SIIDCA-CSUCA):
<https://catalogosiidca.csuca.org/>

of Nicaraguan academic output and facilitates the circulation of knowledge without economic or access barriers.

Although specific policies on Diamond OA publishing are still being articulated at the institutional level, the country has a solid foundation of interoperable academic infrastructure, favourable university regulatory frameworks, and a growing culture of Open Access promoted by universities and regional scientific cooperation networks. This scenario provides fertile ground for the future consolidation of national guidelines that will strengthen the sustainability and international projection of scientific journals under the Diamond model.

On the other hand, the absence of sustainable funding mechanisms and institutional recognition for editorial work, which limits the development of non-profit academic journals.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

The funding of Nicaraguan academic journals depends almost entirely on universities' internal resources, with occasional support from international cooperation. At present, there are no permanent national funds allocated to non-profit publications, resulting in dependence on annual institutional budgets.

Emerging strategies include the following:

- ✓ Integrating publication costs into university research and outreach budgets.
- ✓ Establishing national competitive funds for scientific journals.
- ✓ Fostering cooperation with regional networks such as Redalyc, Latindex, and AmeliCA to obtain technical support and international visibility.

These measures aim to ensure the sustainability of the Diamond OA model and reduce dependence on voluntary work.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

In Nicaragua, formal recognition of editorial and peer review work is limited. Editors and reviewers usually perform their duties on a voluntary basis, which affects the continuity of journals and the quality of editorial processes.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

In Nicaragua, public universities play a central role in strengthening the editorial and technological infrastructure that supports Diamond OA publishing. Several institutions—including the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de Nicaragua (UNAN-Managua), the Universidad Nacional de Ingeniería (UNI), the Universidad Nacional Agraria (UNA), and the Universidad de las Regiones Autónomas de la Costa Caribe

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Nicaragüense (URACCAN)—manage scientific journal portals based on Open Journal Systems, ensuring the free dissemination of knowledge and interoperability with international Open Access networks.

At the regional level, the country actively participates in the Sistema de Información y Documentación Científica de Centroamérica (SIIDCA-CSUCA), which integrates and harvests academic information resources from universities that are members of the Consejo Superior Universitario Centroamericano (CSUCA). This platform enhances the visibility, preservation, and regional circulation of Nicaraguan scientific publications, contributing to the consolidation of editorial practices aligned with the Diamond OA model.

Altogether, the coordination between institutional journal portals, university repositories, and the regional SIIDCA-CSUCA infrastructure forms a collaborative ecosystem that supports the technical sustainability and international projection of Open Access scholarly publishing in Nicaragua.

Regional cooperation with networks such as Latindex or Redalyc is essential to increase the visibility and sustainability of the Diamond model in Nicaragua.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

In Nicaragua, institutional involvement is a determining factor in supporting Diamond OA publishing through several mechanisms:

- ✓ The Secretaría Técnica de Educación Superior, Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación (SETEC), as the coordinating body of the university system, participates in defining research and innovation policies that include the circulation of scientific knowledge. For example, the presentation of the Política y Agenda Nacional de Investigación e Innovación del Sistema Educativo marked its institutional linkage with research management at all levels (Duarte, 2025).
- ✓ National public universities fulfil their institutional role through Open Access academic journal portals managed according to editorial criteria aligned with the Diamond OA model and through institutional repositories that enable the preservation, dissemination, and visibility of scientific output.
- ✓ Institutions establish editorial regulations and internal guidelines that reinforce the professionalization of editorial processes (manuscript management, peer review, open licenses), thereby strengthening the editorial infrastructure required for the Diamond OA model. For instance, the report *Situación actual de las revistas académicas nicaragüenses* identifies the need for institutional policies

on Open Access and the improvement of editorial technical equipment (García et al. 2010).

Overall, institutional coordination—from SETEC to public universities—creates a structured environment that supports the adoption of the Diamond OA model by ensuring that resources, regulations, and editorial structures are aligned with free access for authors and readers, open visibility, and quality assurance.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Editorial staff in Nicaragua play an essential role in sustaining the Diamond OA model, although they face precarious working conditions and limited institutionalization. The lack of incentives, formal recognition, and job stability has hindered the consolidation of a professional community of editors and reviewers, affecting the continuity and quality of editorial processes (García et al., 2010).

The sustainability of the Diamond OA model largely depends on the human capital within public universities: editorial teams, librarians, repository technicians, and support staff. In practice, this collective sustains key processes—management of OJS platforms, peer review, metadata normalization, and digital preservation—that enable publication without fees for authors or readers and ensure interoperability across systems.

In recent years, various initiatives have sought to strengthen the technical and editorial capacities of this workforce. On one hand, public universities such as UNAN-Managua have organized workshops for editors and technical staff focused on using XML-JATS markup tools and improving editorial workflows (UNAN-Managua, 2022). On the other, the CSUCA, through its PIRESC V program, includes explicit action lines for training the university community in repository management and open scientific publishing, encouraging the adoption of technical standards applicable to the Diamond OA model (CSUCA, 2023).

Together, these actions reflect a gradual process of professionalization and regional cooperation that strengthens the competencies of Nicaraguan editorial staff and lays the groundwork for consolidating a sustainable Open Access scientific publishing ecosystem.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Cooperation with international networks constitutes one of the most promising strategic pillars for strengthening Diamond OA in Nicaragua. The participation of public universities and their journals in platforms such as Redalyc, Latindex, and CLACSO has enabled the sharing of technical infrastructure, indexing methodologies, and editorial training services, promoting common standards of quality, visibility, and sustainability.

At the regional level, cooperation within SIIDCA-CSUCA expands these synergies by integrating university repositories and journals under a shared infrastructure for harvesting and digital preservation. This network of international and regional collaboration not only optimizes resources and processes but also consolidates an interconnected Latin American editorial community oriented toward the sustainability of open knowledge.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Nicaraguan scientific journals maintain consolidated quality assurance mechanisms aimed at ensuring academic integrity, process transparency, and international interoperability. Most apply double-blind peer review systems, have public editorial policies, and adhere to the principles of ethics and best practices defined by networks such as Latindex and Redalyc–AmeliCA.

In recent years, public universities have strengthened their internal editorial procedures by incorporating digital management tools (OJS), metadata standardization, and the assignment of persistent identifiers. This sustained effort has allowed for the standardization of publishing processes and increased the international visibility of Nicaraguan academic journals.

For its part, SETEC has proposed the establishment of a national editorial certification system, inspired by regional experiences—such as those of Cuba and Mexico—with the goal of integrating criteria of ethics, visibility, and regularity in journal evaluation. This initiative complements the institutional work of universities and reinforces the sustainability of the Diamond OA model in the country.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Priority actions to strengthen the Diamond model in Nicaragua include the following:

- ✓ Develop a National Open Access Policy led by SETEC and the Ministry of Education.
- ✓ Establish national competitive funds for non-profit journals.
- ✓ Provide continuous training for editorial teams in international standards.
- ✓ Promote regional partnerships with open science networks in the Caribbean and Latin America.
- ✓ Integrate academic recognition of editorial work into university evaluation systems.

The country is in a transitional phase—from the discourse on knowledge openness to its practical implementation within public universities. Nicaragua is moving toward a

culture of open science grounded in the values of collaboration, equity, and transparency. The initiatives of Nicaraguan universities and SETEC mark a crucial starting point. The future of Open Access in the country will depend on coordination between academic and governmental actors, continuous training of editorial staff, and the creation of sustainable funding mechanisms.

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PANAMA

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

In Panama, progress toward open science and the Diamond OA model has been closely linked to the leadership of public universities and the support of the Secretaría Nacional de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación (SENACYT). Since the early 2020s, both institutional and national policies have promoted knowledge openness, although challenges related to funding and sustainability persist. Panamá has 117 scientific journals according to LATINDEX.

The Universidad de Panamá (UP), the Universidad Tecnológica de Panamá (UTP), and the Universidad Autónoma de Chiriquí (UNACHI) constitute the main pillars of the national open academic publishing ecosystem. These institutions maintain an ongoing commitment to regional networks such as the Consejo Superior Universitario Centroamericano (CSUCA), and together they endorsed the CSUCA Open Science Declaration (CLACSO, 2021).

The independence of a Diamond journal allows university funds to be allocated directly to research rather than to the commercialization of knowledge, ensuring that results are accessible to everyone without restrictions. This principle guides institutional efforts toward a more inclusive, collaborative, and transparent science.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

At the regulatory level, Panama has an expanding institutional framework driven by the joint efforts of its three main public universities. In this context, the Universidad de Panamá (UP) adopted in 2023 its Institutional Policy on Open Science and Open Data, which promotes “compliance with the principles of Open Access and transparency in the management of scientific data” (Universidad de Panamá, 2023, p. 2). It has also endorsed international commitments such as the Budapest Open Access Initiative and the DORA Declaration on responsible research assessment.

For its part, the Universidad Tecnológica de Panamá (UTP) adopted a formal Open Access Policy for its scientific journals, approved by the Research, Graduate, and Extension Council (CIPE) in 2021. This policy aligns with international standards and promotes the free and immediate dissemination of scientific output (Murillo & Tejedor, 2021).

Finally, the Universidad Autónoma de Chiriquí (UNACHI) approved its Open Access Policy in 2021, which ensures that “all scientific production funded by the university or the State must be deposited in Open Access repositories” (Universidad Autónoma de Chiriquí, 2021, p. 1). Complementarily, the Reglamento Editorial de la UNACHI (Universidad Autónoma de Chiriquí, 2021) establishes technical guidelines for the management of journals under the Diamond OA model.

SENACYT has supported the editorial management of journals published by the universities that are part of the Consejo de Rectores de Panamá (CRP) through competitive funds granted under the Programa de Fortalecimiento de las Revistas Científicas, Phases I and II²⁷⁴. However, structural gaps persist: the country still lacks a sustained policy for non-profit journals, and editorial work largely depends on academic volunteerism.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

The funding of Panama’s editorial ecosystem comes mainly from university budgets, with partial support from SENACYT through competitive calls. However, the absence of permanent structural funds limits the sustainability of Diamond OA journals.

Among the institutional strategies, the following stand out:

- ✓ Integrating editorial costs into research and outreach budgets.
- ✓ Applying for funding from regional and multilateral sources (CSUCA, CLACSO).
- ✓ Encouraging collaborative work among universities through shared editorial networks.

The sustainability of the Diamond OA model requires national and international competitive funds, as well as partnerships with science and technology organizations.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

The Universidad de Panamá has incorporated journal markup and publication tasks into the Manual Descriptivo de Clases de Puestos under the responsibilities of library staff, allowing for salary recognition of editorial work (Universidad de Panamá, 2024). This formal acknowledgment represents a significant step forward in valuing editorial work

²⁷⁴ Programa de Fortalecimiento de las Revistas Científicas, Phases I and II: <https://umecit.edu.pa/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/memoria-programa-revista-2024-digital.pdf>

within the academic sphere. However, it remains necessary to develop national incentive systems that recognize scientific and editorial production as activities of academic merit.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

The UP has developed a robust system of academic and scientific journals managed by the Vicerrectoría de Investigación y Postgrado through the Oficina de Publicaciones Académicas y Científicas, in coordination with the Sistema de Bibliotecas de la Universidad de Panamá (SIBIUP). The institution also serves as a collection centre for the Red Latindex and coordinates the Red BIREME (BVS-Panamá). In collaboration with Redalyc²⁷⁵, it carries out journal markup in AmeliCA, both for its own publications and for those of other national institutions. It is also important to highlight the development of the national indexing system PANINDEX.

The journal system uses interoperable platforms based on OJS, assigns DOIs to all published articles at no cost to authors, and employs semantic analysis software designed to detect improper use of information, thereby strengthening the quality of editorial management (Universidad de Panamá, 2023).

The UTP sustains the Diamond OA model by providing the necessary digital infrastructure. It maintains a centralized Portal de Revistas Académicas for the management and dissemination of its publications and implements rigorous technical standards—such as DOI assignment and the use of the OAI-PMH protocol—that ensure traceability and international visibility, facilitating metadata harvesting by external indexes and repositories.

At the UNACHI, academic journals—mainly in the fields of natural sciences and education—have been incorporated into regional databases such as Latindex and Dialnet. In 2025, one of these journals was officially accepted into both indexes following an editorial training process led by the Vicerrectoría de Investigación y Posgrado (Guerra Blanco, personal communication, 2025).

These initiatives strengthen the regional visibility of Panamanian scientific knowledge and consolidate its integration into international networks.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Public universities, particularly the UP, UTP, and UNACHI, have taken the lead in implementing Open Access policies. These institutions provide infrastructure, technical training, and editorial support to their journal teams. SENACYT, in turn, coordinates efforts with the CSUCA to promote regional cooperation and the strengthening of open

²⁷⁵ Redalyc: <https://uphacialaluz.com/2020/08/14/redalyc-america-y-la-universidad-de-panama-avanzan-la-visibility-de-las-revistas-cientificas-del-pais/>

science. This joint work demonstrates the progressive coordination between academic and governmental actors in consolidating a sustainable ecosystem.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Editorial staff play an essential role, although most work under volunteer-based arrangements. The lack of job stability and specialized training limits the continuity of editorial projects. In response, universities have implemented training programs in OJS, XML markup, and digital preservation with the goal of professionalizing editorial teams. Likewise, the Vicerrectoría de Investigación y Postgrado of the UP offers a Postgraduate Program in Editorial Management of Scientific Journals, which helps strengthen the technical and academic competencies of the sector.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Regional collaboration has been fundamental. Panama actively participates in the CSUCA and in the Red de Revistas de Acceso Abierto de Panamá, spaces where technological infrastructures, editorial guidelines, and indexing processes are shared. These alliances strengthen cooperation among institutions and optimize the available human and financial resources.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Panamanian academic journals apply peer review processes and editorial transparency policies. They also use persistent identifiers (DOI, ORCID) and adopt digital preservation standards. However, it is still necessary to consolidate a national system for editorial quality certification to ensure the sustainability and international visibility of the Diamond model.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

To advance toward a consolidated non-profit publishing model, the following actions are proposed:

- ✓ Develop a National Policy on Open Scientific Publications coordinated by SENACYT and public universities.
- ✓ Establish a competitive public fund for Diamond OA journals.
- ✓ Promote regional partnerships with CSUCA, CLACSO, and UNESCO.
- ✓ Reform academic evaluation legislation to prioritize open publication.

At the level of higher education institutions, establish an Institutional Program of Recognition and Incentives —formal, periodic, and public— aimed at Editors, Editorial Committees, and Reviewers, to acknowledge their essential role in sustaining the quality of academic publications.

Panama has taken firm steps toward the institutionalization of Open Access, combining university policies, regional cooperation, and international commitments. However, the sustainability of the Diamond OA model depends on stronger state financial support and the consolidation of technical capacities within universities. Specifically, the experiences of the Universidad de Panamá, the Universidad Tecnológica de Panamá, and the Universidad Autónoma de Chiriquí demonstrate that editorial training, technological interoperability, and academic recognition of editorial work are essential factors for advancing toward a sustainable and equitable scientific ecosystem.

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PARAGUAY

Authors: Méndez, Andrea; Mora-Campos, Andrea; Sena Correa, Emilce; Víquez-Mora, Naomy.

1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

In Paraguay, the Diamond OA model is in a stage characterized by fragmented efforts and reliance on public support; however, the country lacks clear policies and specialized editorial training to fully promote the Diamond model. According to LATINDEX, Paraguay currently has 36 Diamond OA journals, and only one that charges APCs.

Diamond OA journals are sustained primarily by higher education institutions—for example, those published by the Universidad Nacional de Asunción (UNA), which has emerged as one of the most active institutions in promoting Open Access. These journals operate under open access principles, with no charges to authors or readers. However, they generally face significant limitations in financial sustainability and editorial training.

The Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología (CONACYT) has promoted calls for editorial strengthening and technical programs aimed at improving scientific quality, such as the Programa de Fortalecimiento de Revistas Científicas²⁷⁶ (CONACYT, 2024). Nevertheless, many of these initiatives are directed toward commercial indexed journals, leaving non-profit publications at a disadvantage. The absence of clear national policies deepens this inequality and hinders the sustainability of the Diamond Open Access model.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

Currently, Paraguay does not have a specific national policy for Diamond OA, although there are institutional provisions that promote knowledge openness.

²⁷⁶ Programa de Fortalecimiento de Revistas Científicas: <https://www.conacyt.gov.py/programa-fortalecimiento-revistas-cientificas-2024>

The Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología (CONACYT), through its *Programa de Fortalecimiento de Revistas Científicas*, promotes improvements in editorial quality, though funding tends to prioritize journals aimed at international indexation on commercial platforms (CONACYT, 2024).

Moreover, Law No. 828 on Universities recognizes the research and non-profit function of Paraguayan universities, creating a favourable —though not specific— legal framework for the Diamond OA model (Law No. 828 on Universities, Paraguay, 2014). The absence of a comprehensive policy leaves each institution responsible for managing its own resources, resulting in inequalities and challenges for the model's sustainability.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

The main financial challenge lies in the absence of specific funds for non-profit journals. Currently, funding comes primarily from university budgets or occasional projects supported by the Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología (CONACYT), without a long-term sustainable strategy.

The priority measures to ensure sustainability include the following:

- ✓ Establishing permanent national funds for scientific publishing.
- ✓ Integrating publication costs into institutional research budgets.
- ✓ Creating international partnerships with networks that support the Diamond OA model, such as Redalyc and CLACSO.

The lack of adequate technological infrastructure and the low institutional recognition of editorial work remain significant obstacles to the sustainability of the non-profit publishing model.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Academic recognition for editorial work remains limited. Merit and promotion processes for faculty do not explicitly consider scientific editing or journal management, which discourages academic participation. It is recommended to establish an incentive system that acknowledges editorial production as an academic activity with institutional value, alongside professional training and certification programs to strengthen the national Diamond OA ecosystem.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Institutional journal portals constitute the main infrastructure for the Diamond OA publishing model. However, technical and budgetary limitations hinder effective indexation and digital preservation.

CONACYT provides indirect support through funding and training programs, but there is still a lack of interoperable infrastructure connecting universities, institutions, and repositories — a gap that constrains regional cooperation.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

The key institutions are the Universidad Nacional de Asunción (UNA) and CONACYT. UNA leads the editorial and technological management of university journals, while CONACYT promotes scientific quality. However, the lack of funding policies and training programs limits the model's reach. Both entities must coordinate efforts to move toward a more comprehensive open science ecosystem in Paraguay.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Editorial staff work mostly on a voluntary basis, without formal compensation or recognition, which affects the continuity and quality of publications. Specialized training in platforms such as OJS and standards like XML-JATS are essential. Regional training programs supported by organizations such as CLACSO or UNESCO could strengthen these skills and reduce dependence on external services.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Interinstitutional collaboration is currently under development, with proposals to create a National Network of Scientific Journals in Paraguay aimed at sharing infrastructure and peer-review services. Integration into regional networks such as Latindex and Redalyc could enhance the visibility of Paraguayan journals and facilitate the exchange of best editorial practices.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Paraguayan journals apply peer review and follow basic ethical standards, although evaluation practices remain uneven. Therefore, some recommendations to strengthen quality include implementing national editorial guidelines and adopting international standards to enhance transparency and editorial rigor.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

To consolidate the non-profit open access model, the following actions are necessary:

- ✓ Develop a National Policy on Open Science and Diamond OA publishing led by CONACYT.
- ✓ Establish sustainable public funds for non-profit journals.
- ✓ Create editorial training and professional certification programs.

- ✓ Formally recognize editorial work in academic promotion and evaluation systems.
- ✓ Foster regional cooperation with Latin American and Caribbean academic networks.

Institutional commitment and coordination with regional scientific networks will be key for the future.

The Paraguayan case reflects a growing commitment to open knowledge, yet it still relies on isolated institutional initiatives and lacks structured, sustainable funding.

The UNA and CONACYT have made progress in promoting Open Access and enhancing scientific visibility; however, the Diamond OA model requires clear policies, stable financing, academic recognition, and sustained institutional cooperation.

Strengthening Paraguay's editorial ecosystem demands specialized training, technological development, and appropriate legal frameworks.

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PERU

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

According to Latindex data, Peru has 265 Open Access journals, 262 of which follow the Diamond OA model.

The Peruvian scientific and academic system is in a stage of consolidation regarding the adoption of the Diamond OA model. The institutions that are members of the Red Nacional de Repositorios Digitales de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación de Acceso Abierto (RENARE)²⁷⁷ are integrated through institutional repositories connected to the Repositorio Nacional Digital, known as Acceso Libre a la Información Científica para la Innovación (ALICIA)²⁷⁸.

The Consejo Nacional de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación (CONCYTEC) leads the national open science strategy, in which ALICIA serves as the official infrastructure for the preservation of and access to scientific knowledge, including scientific journals (CONCYTEC, 2020). This platform ensures that scientific output funded with public resources is openly accessible, in accordance with the principles of UNESCO and the Budapest Open Access Initiative.

CONCYTEC and the Superintendencia Nacional de Educación Superior Universitaria (SUNEDU) have implemented policies aimed at strengthening the visibility, transparency, and dissemination of national scientific knowledge through the institutional repositories of higher education institutions.

Through ALICIA, Peruvian scientific journals enhance their regional visibility. These publications must guarantee Open Access to their content by applying Creative

²⁷⁷ Red Nacional de Repositorios Digitales de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación de Acceso Abierto (RENARE): <https://conocimiento.concytec.gob.pe/termino/red-nacional-de-repositorios-digitales-de-ciencia-tecnologia-e-innovacion-de-acceso-abierto-renare/>

²⁷⁸ Acceso Libre a la Información Científica para la Innovación (ALICIA): <https://alicia.concytec.gob.pe/que-es-alicia/>

Commons licenses, incorporating digital identifiers, and being indexed in the Latindex system, in order to facilitate their harvesting by the Repositorio Nacional Digital.

Under the Ley N.º 30035, which regulates the “Repositorio Nacional Digital de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación de Acceso Abierto” (Gobierno del Perú, 2013) and its corresponding regulations, all institutions that are part of RENARE²⁷⁹ must establish Open Access policies to ensure the deposit of processed data, works, and monitoring statistics in their institutional repositories within no more than 60 calendar days after the submission of the final version, under institutional responsibility.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

The Peruvian legal framework supports the consolidation of open science. The Ley N.º 31250, “Ley del Sistema Nacional de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación (SINACTI),” together with its regulations approved in June 2024, promotes scientific openness and free access to research data (Gobierno del Perú, 2024). Likewise, the Política Nacional de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación al 2030 (CONCYTEC, 2022) reinforces the State’s commitment to the democratization of knowledge and the reduction of technological gaps. Taken together, this regulatory framework promotes the alignment of university policies with the national Open Access strategy, positioning ALICIA as a central component of the Peruvian scientific ecosystem.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

The funding of the Diamond OA model in Peru relies mainly on institutional resources and university research budgets. Despite its importance, there is still no national fund exclusively dedicated to non-profit journals. Emerging strategies include the following:

- ✓ Integrating editorial costs into university research budgets.
- ✓ Establishing national competitive funds for Diamond OA journals.
- ✓ Encouraging international cooperation with Latin American networks for the exchange of editorial and technical services.

CONCYTEC has led workshops on journal management, the use of OJS, and compliance with indexing standards to strengthen national editorial capacity through its participation in regional networks such as SciELO and Latindex.

²⁷⁹ RENARE: <https://conocimiento.concytec.gob.pe/termino/red-nacional-de-repositorios-digitales-de-ciencia-tecnologia-e-innovacion-de-acceso-abierto-renare/>

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Institutional recognition of editorial work is still incipient. Although some universities—such as the Universidad Nacional Mayor de San Marcos (UNMSM) and the Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú (PUCP)—include academic editing in their faculty evaluation criteria, this standard is not unified at the national level. The Ley de Acceso Abierto 30035 and Ley del SINACTI 31250 (Gobierno del Perú, 2013 and 2024) suggest redefining scientific evaluation mechanisms to acknowledge the merit of open publication and the social contribution of knowledge, thus fostering a cultural shift toward valuing Open Access.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

The Repositorio Nacional ALICIA constitutes the main national Open Access infrastructure and, since 2013, has gathered the scientific output of universities, research centres and institutes, as well as public entities. Its update in 2020 strengthened interoperability with international platforms and consolidated its role as the central archive of Peruvian scientific knowledge (CONCYTEC, 2020). Likewise, universities have developed repositories and journal portals that operate on OJS platforms and connect with regional databases such as Latindex, SciELO, and Redalyc, which has expanded the global visibility of knowledge produced in the country.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Peruvian universities have assumed a leading role in the implementation of the Diamond OA model. Likewise, university research offices and libraries play key roles in digital preservation and the technical training of staff.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Human capital is a determining factor for the sustainability of Open Access in Peru. Despite significant progress, gaps remain in technical training related to editing, digital curation, and metadata management. CONCYTEC has addressed this limitation through workshops and training sessions across the country, although staff turnover and the lack of salary incentives continue to pose major challenges. Therefore, the professional strengthening of editorial personnel requires university policies that formally recognize their work within promotion and academic stability systems.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Partnerships between universities and public institutions have been fundamental to the expansion of the Diamond OA model. Collaboration among CONCYTEC, SUNEDU, and major public universities has enabled the creation of technical support networks and the adoption of interoperable systems. Likewise, cooperation with international

organizations such as UNESCO and CLACSO has fostered knowledge transfer and the dissemination of editorial best practices across the region.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Peruvian Open Access journals apply peer review mechanisms, open licenses, and ethical policies inspired by standards such as COPE and DOAJ. Likewise, the strengthening of editorial boards and the adoption of digital preservation tools (LOCKSS, PKP Preservation Network) help ensure the quality, transparency, and continuity of publications.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

To consolidate the Diamond ecosystem in Peru, the following actions are recommended:

- ✓ Establish a permanent national fund for non-profit journals.
- ✓ Integrate the recognition of editorial work into academic evaluation systems.
- ✓ Promote continuous technical editorial training.
- ✓ Establish strategic regional alliances for technological cooperation and shared visibility.

The Peruvian case demonstrates a strong institutional commitment to the development of the Diamond OA model. The leadership of CONCYTEC and the active role of universities reflect an ecosystem evolving toward equity and scientific collaboration. However, the lack of sustained funding, the technological gap, and cultural challenges continue to hinder its full consolidation. Therefore, building an inclusive open science environment will depend on interinstitutional coordination, the professionalization of editorial staff, and the formal recognition of Open Access as a national policy for scientific development.

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PUERTO RICO

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1. Landscape of Diamond OA and Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing

Puerto Rico presents a particular context for nonprofit scholarly publishing and the Diamond OA model, influenced both by its political status and internal university dynamics. The institution that has led this topic has been the Universidad de Puerto Rico (UPR), a public university that has developed infrastructure to facilitate Open Access, mainly aimed at ensuring the preservation and visibility of local research.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

The country has no regulations specifically directed toward Diamond OA, although at the institutional level, the public university has policies that promote Open Access.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

The financial and operational environment of nonprofit publishing in Puerto Rico faces significant challenges due to chronic budget cuts, lack of institutional incentives, and limitations in human and technological resources. The sustainability of journals depends on efficient fund management, trained human resources, and technological integration among university campuses. Consolidating platforms to implement Open Access is essential for the long-term viability of the Diamond OA model.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Currently, there are no formal institutional incentives directed toward Diamond OA publishing. Institutional Open Access policies are general and lack specific mechanisms of recognition or motivation for those who participate in the nonprofit model, which affects the motivation of researchers and editorial committees.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

The fragmentation of technological infrastructures and the dispersion of editorial policies limit the comprehensive development of the Diamond OA model. It is a priority to centralize and modernize editorial resources and journal management systems, facilitating both access and the preservation and dissemination of scientific knowledge produced in the various campuses.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Key actors sustaining the Diamond OA model include academic editors, university libraries, researchers, and academic authorities (institutional decision-makers). Libraries play an important role by facilitating access, preservation, and building bridges between journals and the university community. Faculty and researchers contribute content, while authorities provide political and, to a lesser extent, financial support.

Workforce and Capacity Development

Specialized human resources are essential to ensure the quality and continuity of nonprofit publishing. Without a stable and trained editorial and technical team, the operation, visibility, and credibility of Diamond journals are threatened. The current model largely depends on the voluntary work of faculty and librarians, which poses a challenge for sustainability.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Collaboration among departments, libraries, and administrative units is recognized as essential to strengthen the Diamond model. Inter-campus coordination and effective articulation can enhance the dissemination and collective impact of academic production.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Currently, quality assurance processes are managed by editorial committees and academic peer review, although more formal institutional frameworks for evaluating and recognizing editorial quality still need to be developed—similar to national or international seals existing in other contexts. Evaluation through indexes such as LATINDEX, Redalyc, SciELO, and DOAJ is also important.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

Strengthening the Diamond OA model in Puerto Rico requires more specific institutional and possibly national policies, supported by concrete funding. It is critical to consolidate infrastructure, train and recognize key actors, and encourage active participation in the editorial and research fields. Collaboration with networks in the Caribbean and Latin America can help transfer good practices (Universidad de Puerto Rico, 2023).

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EL SALVADOR

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1. Landscape of Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing and Diamond OA

El Salvador has shown steady progress in adopting Open Access (OA) policies and strengthening its scientific communication ecosystem. However, the development of the Diamond OA publishing model is still in an early stage in terms of national and institutional policies, even though the country already has journals operating under this model.

The main initiatives for the openness and dissemination of knowledge in El Salvador are led by key public institutions such as the Ministerio de Educación, Ciencia y Tecnología (MINEDUCYT) and the Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología (CONACYT).

In this context, both public and private universities manage their own institutional repositories. However, the Consorcio de Bibliotecas Universitarias de El Salvador (CBUES) promoted the creation of the Repositorio Digital de Ciencia y Cultura de El Salvador (REDICCES), established with a dual strategic purpose: to host the scientific and cultural output of institutions that do not yet have their own repositories, and to serve as a starting point for harvesting content from existing institutional repositories through the national harvester ACCES, in order to centralize the country's academic production.

This principle has inspired academic institutions to create repositories, journal portals, and editorial training programs. Nevertheless, financial sustainability, limited technological infrastructure, and the low professionalization of editorial teams remain key obstacles to consolidating a robust and sustainable national Open Science system.

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

The absence of a unified legal framework ensuring continuous funding limits the expansion of the Diamond OA model. According to the ‘Informe sobre el Estado de la Ciencia en El Salvador’ (CONACYT and MINEDUCYT, 2024), academic publishing largely depends on voluntary efforts and limited institutional funding within higher education institutions.

In addition to other government-led initiatives, the Dirección Nacional de Educación Superior (DNES) of the Ministerio de Educación, Ciencia y Tecnología (MINEDUCYT) has also played a key role. In a coordinated effort, MINEDUCYT launched in 2023 the country’s first Portal de Revistas Académicas y Científicas de El Salvador²⁸⁰. This project aims to support open access to the scientific output of Salvadoran universities and to promote shared technical resources to strengthen transparency and digital preservation efforts.

On the other hand, a successful example is that of the Universidad de El Salvador (UES), which enacted in 2022 its Política de Investigación, Ciencia y Tecnología e Innovación²⁸¹. This policy develops the institutional framework for the application, publication, dissemination, and transfer of research results, aiming to bring research outcomes into the spheres of teaching and society through the creation of structures such as Open Access scientific journals. In doing so, it seeks to ensure their digital preservation, visibility, and impact at both the national and international levels (Universidad de El Salvador, 2022, p. 27).

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Salvadoran universities rely primarily on internal resources and international cooperation, such as funding from the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) and the Consejo Superior Universitario Centroamericano (CSUCA). Consequently, the following emerging strategies stand out:

- ✓ Allocating fixed budget lines for scientific journals within the annual university expenditure.

²⁸⁰ Portal de Revistas Académicas y Científicas de El Salvador: <https://consultas.mined.gob.sv/revistas/>

²⁸¹ Política de Investigación, Ciencia y Tecnología e Innovación: <https://sic.ues.edu.sv/politica-investigacion>

- ✓ Strengthening interuniversity consortia to share human and technical resources, such as the Red Exlibris, a network that brings together publishers from 23 higher education institutions.
- ✓ Developing regional projects with the support of multilateral organizations.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

The Salvadoran system still lacks formal incentives specifically aimed at editing and publishing in Diamond OA journals. However, the Universidad de El Salvador (UES) and the Universidad Tecnológica de El Salvador (UTEC) have begun to recognize editorial work and peer review as relevant academic activities within faculty reports. In particular, UTEC, as the national partner of Latindex, has promoted capacity-building and training processes for editors, contributing to the consolidation of editorial quality standards. Likewise, the *Plan de Fortalecimiento Académico UES 2023–2027* has incorporated initiatives aimed at the institutional recognition of editorial functions.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Salvadoran universities have their own portals for Diamond OA academic journals, managed by libraries or Vice-Rectorates for Research. In this regard, they have sought to interoperate with networks such as UTEC, Latindex, Redalyc, and CSUCA to strengthen international visibility.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), led by UTEC and UES, are transitioning toward a non-profit publishing ecosystem through their Vice-Rectorates for Research and Academic Journal Systems, which centralize technical support, DOI acquisition, editor training, and quality evaluation processes. All these efforts have resulted in the creation of the Red de Editores de Revistas de la Universidad de El Salvador (Rodríguez, 2025).

Likewise, the DNES and CONACYT act as coordinating bodies between universities and international agencies, as they offer calls for strengthening and editorial certification. These institutions constitute the pillars of the Salvadoran Diamond OA model.

Workforce and Capacity Development

The human component is critical. In most Salvadoran universities, editorial teams work on a voluntary basis or with additional academic workloads. The Red de Editoriales Académicas de El Salvador (ExLibris El Salvador) emphasizes the importance of collaboration and coordination to strengthen editorial capacities, provide training in editorial management, analyze indexing platforms, and improve the quality and visibility of Salvadoran academic publications (Meyer, 2025).

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

El Salvador maintains sustained involvement in regional cooperation initiatives, for example with Latindex and AmeliCA, and later through progress made with Redalyc, which promotes the shared use of technological infrastructure, editorial training, and international dissemination. At the national level, the creation of the Portal de Revistas Académicas/Científicas de El Salvador²⁸² is under discussion—an interinstitutional platform that would integrate OJS and academic repositories. This collaborative approach would make it possible to optimize resources and standardize good practices in editorial management.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Salvadoran academic journals apply double-blind peer review processes, originality assessments, and the mandatory use of DOI and ORCID identifiers. CONACYT plans to establish a national certification system for scientific journals that incorporates criteria related to editorial ethics, publication frequency, and visibility in open databases (CONACYT, 2023). These strategies aim to raise the country's quality and competitiveness standards in relation to international systems.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

To move toward full integration of the Diamond model, the following actions are considered priorities:

- ✓ Develop a National Policy on Open Scientific Publications coordinated by the DNES, CONACYT, and higher education institutions.
- ✓ Establish a public fund to support Diamond OA journals through annual calls for proposals.
- ✓ Integrate editorial training into postgraduate research programs.
- ✓ Promote international partnerships with Latindex, AmeliCA, Redalyc, and DOAJ to enhance regional interoperability.

El Salvador is moving toward an Open Science model that prioritizes equity and collaboration; although it faces structural limitations, its universities have laid the foundations for a sustainable open access ecosystem. Strengthening editorial professionalization, developing specific national policies, and granting academic

²⁸² Portal de Revistas Académicas/Científicas de El Salvador: <https://consultas.mined.gob.sv/revistas/>

recognition to non-profit editorial work will be the key pillars for consolidating the Diamond OA model in the coming years.

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VENEZUELA

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1. Landscape of Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing and Diamond OA

Venezuela faces significant challenges in nonprofit scholarly publishing, due to political, economic, and structural factors. Although there are ministerial resolutions promoting Open Access (Gobierno Bolivariano de Venezuela, 2022; Ministerio del Poder Popular para Ciencia y Tecnología Observatorio Nacional de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación Caracas, Venezuela, 2023), the institutional reality shows low adoption of specific Diamond OA policies and limited editorial management within universities and research centres. Initiatives arise mainly from the will of researchers and editorial teams who value academic independence and the non-intervention of external economic interests in the publication process (Martínez-Guerrero & García Romero, 2018).

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

There are initiatives at the government level to implement regulations on Open Science (Gobierno Bolivariano de Venezuela, 2022), but none are exclusive to the Diamond OA model. Some universities and research centres publish research results freely and openly through Open Access platforms, ensuring data transparency and accessibility.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

Publishing in national and open journals lacks concrete incentives and is less valued in the evaluation of scientific personnel, with preference given to high-impact private journals (Martínez-Guerrero & García Romero, 2018).

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

In Venezuela, there are still no systematic policies promoting publication in Diamond OA journals or recognition within academic evaluation systems, except for individual efforts by researchers and university presses.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Open access infrastructures, such as interinstitutional collaboration networks, are essential for the sustainability of nonprofit scholarly production in Venezuela. However, it is necessary to strengthen national open journals and database platforms that serve as technical and visibility support for scientific work.

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Governments, editorial funds, foundations, university rectors, research directors, and entities responsible for public policy play a vital role in coordinating and leading the nonprofit model.

Workforce and Capacity Development

The success of the Diamond OA model depends on the availability of editorial teams, platforms, and qualified human resources to carry out publication and scientific dissemination processes. There remains a need to improve training, stabilize personnel, and secure funding for their functions, especially in postgraduate, teaching, and research areas.

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Building networks and interinstitutional alliances facilitates the creation of shared platforms, dissemination of the model, and generation of best practices for the development of open scholarly publishing. Additionally, fostering collaborations at the national and regional levels is fundamental for the sustainability of the system.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Editorial quality assurance is linked to collaborative processes between researchers and organizing committees, as well as institutional and international certifications. Editorial freedom and scientific autonomy have been the main values associated with the Diamond OA journal model in Venezuela.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

To consolidate the model, it is necessary to design and implement strong institutional and governmental policies, increase budgets for university scientific journals, create shared infrastructures, and review scientific evaluation systems to value both national production and open publishing.

The Venezuelan case reflects a stage of discursive-to-operative transition in the field of Open Science.

VENEZUELA

There are solid conceptual foundations and growing institutional awareness, but implementation faces structural and financial shortcomings that hinder the advancement of the Diamond OA model.

To achieve real consolidation, it will be essential to:

- ✓ Link political discourse with concrete executive actions.
- ✓ Ensure sustainable funding and technological infrastructure.
- ✓ Recognize and professionalize academic editorial work

URUGUAY

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1. Landscape of Nonprofit Scholarly Publishing and Diamond OA

In Uruguay, academic publications are mainly managed by university institutions, professional associations, and public organizations, in which nonprofit and community-managed Open Access models play a predominating role. The Agencia Nacional de Investigación e Innovación (ANII) actively promotes open access and open science principles through institutional mandates, digital repositories, and capacity-building projects. On the other hand, there is the Asociación Uruguaya de Revistas Académicas (AURA), an association that brings together journals with the purpose of providing training and building community among journal editors to solve problems collectively. It is also the DOI agency in Uruguay.

In Uruguay, there is no national policy that is exclusively dedicated to the Diamond OA model, and the publishing ecosystem faces challenges in institutional coordination, visibility, and prestige compared to large commercial publishers (Aguirre-Liguera et al., 2022).

Most national academic journals in Uruguay are managed under nonprofit principles, following the Latin American tradition of understanding knowledge as a public good and Open Access as a common resource. The existence of technological infrastructure for Open Science and initiatives such as the Sistema Nacional de Repositorios Digitales en Acceso Abierto stand out, demonstrating the national commitment to knowledge openness, although there are still no specific legislative or policy frameworks for the Diamond model. ANII has funded specific institutional strengthening projects, consolidating independent initiatives (Prieto, 2022).

2. Policy and Systemic Enablers

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

Uruguay currently does not have an explicit national policy for the Diamond OA model. Open Access mandates are implemented by ANII through the “green route” deposit requirement for project results it funds, seeking to ensure that generated knowledge is available to society regardless of medium, although this only partially covers nonprofit academic publishing. Recommendations and institutional regulations vary among organizations, and Open Access and repository guidelines depend on each entity’s initiative (Agencia Nacional de Investigación e Innovación, 2022).

On the other hand, Uruguay has a solid legal framework to guarantee free access to research results funded with public resources. Ley N.º 18.381 sobre Derecho de Acceso a la Información Pública (2008) establishes that access to public information is free of charge (Gobierno Oriental de Uruguay, 2008). Likewise, ANII requires that beneficiaries of its funding programs deposit their research results in institutional or national repositories. In its Open Access regulation, the agency emphasizes that it “promotes open access to national scientific-technological production as a strategy to strengthen the national science and technology system, its links with society and the productive sector” (Agencia Nacional de Investigación e Innovación, n.d., p. 1).

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

The Agency has supported small capacity-building projects in publishing, but there is no structured or specific funding for Diamond OA journals. Sustainability depends on institutional and international cooperation, as isolated efforts risk fragmentation, low periodicity, and limited academic impact. Strengthening infrastructure, professionalizing editorial teams, and consolidating journals at the regional level are priorities to increase competitiveness and quality (Aguirre-Liguera et al., 2022).

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

Recognition of editorial work and incentives for publishing in Diamond OA journals are applied unevenly and to a limited extent. Including these activities in researcher and institutional evaluation and categorization systems would strengthen commitment and editorial professionalization, but robust systems and inter-entity cooperation are still needed to consolidate these benefits (Prieto, 2022). Additionally, strengthening incentive policies in Diamond journals could increase researcher participation in national journals and reduce dependence on international commercial publications. Another example is that, in recent years, higher education institutions have begun requiring their researchers to publish in journals included in DOAJ.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

Uruguayan journals benefit from regional indexing platforms (DOAJ, SciELO, LATINDEX, Redalyc), digital repositories, and the collaborative work of AURA, which improves visibility and interoperability. However, the fragmentation of low-visibility journals persists, calling for strategic action to consolidate journals from different disciplines under interinstitutional support, in order to allow them to compete in prestige with large commercial groups (Aura, 2025).

Institutional Roles and Mechanisms

Institutions such as ANII, universities, and scientific societies are fundamental in managing, funding, and promoting nonprofit academic publishing. This enables editorial independence that allows the selection of relevant topics, but institutional dependence can create biases or endogamy, making professionalization, interinstitutional support, and the consolidation of clear editorial policies essential. A special mention goes to the Universidad de la República, which serves 86% of the country's university students and is responsible for 80% of national scientific production. Therefore, it plays a significant role within the Secretaría Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología (SNCT).

Workforce and Capacity Development

Editorial sustainability requires the participation of professional scientific and technical editors, supported by continuous training and institutional resources. Recognition in evaluation systems and access to training are essential to maintain quality and commitment to the open access model (Aguirre-Liguera et al., 2022).

Collaboration between Support Publishers and Service Providers

Uruguay maintains active collaboration with regional Open Science networks.

The Portal Timbó is linked to international projects such as LA Referencia, RedalyC, and CLACSO. These synergies have fostered the exchange of good editorial practices and the development of technical interoperability standards.

Cooperation with neighbouring countries (Argentina, Brazil, and Chile) also represents a strategic avenue for sharing human resources, technological infrastructure, and digital preservation services. In this sense, international and regional cooperation is seen as essential to counteract the dispersion and low visibility of Diamond OA journals, allowing the sharing of resources, infrastructures, and expertise to compete more effectively with large commercial publishers (Aura, 2025).

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Consolidating prestigious academic journals and fostering their scientific rigor requires investment in editorial training, robust peer review, and the implementation of cross-institutional quality standards, thereby raising the impact and reputation of national scientific production. Uruguayan scientific journals apply indexing processes in DOAJ, LATINDEX, SciELO, Redalyc, and Amelica.

3. Policy and Funding Actions to Advance Diamond OA Publishing

The recommended strategies are:

- ✓ Develop gradual funding schemes, reallocating resources from APC-based publications and promoting the consolidation of Diamond OA journals with quality and sustainability.
- ✓ Integrate the Diamond OA model into institutional and national evaluation systems, recognizing the editorial role and open production.
- ✓ Encourage international and interinstitutional cooperation, allowing Uruguayan Diamond OA journals to compete in visibility and prestige.
- ✓ Increase editorial professionalization and the expansion of interoperable digital repositories.
- ✓ Recognize editorial contributions in the evaluation of researchers and institutional teams, ensuring continuity and quality.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

The comparative analysis of the Diamond OA publishing ecosystems in Africa, Europe, and Latin America reveals that the model shares a common definition and normative principles across the three world regions. However, its practical implementation reflects distinct historical backgrounds, political frameworks, sustainability strategies, and levels of institutional involvement. These differences not only explain the varying degrees of model consolidation in each region but also influence the strategies needed for its future strengthening.

In Africa, the report highlights increasing dynamism and institutional commitment in some countries, along with structural challenges related to funding, technical capacities, and academic recognition. The challenges faced by the Diamond OA model are proportional to the difficulties in building robust public science, technology, and innovation systems in most countries. The fact that the academic publishing debate is occurring concurrently with the creation and strengthening of these systems can be seen as a strategic opportunity. In Europe, recent political momentum in favour of Diamond OA has generated a solid narrative framework, but significant gaps remain in funding, coordination, and alignment of national policies. The strong linguistic diversity and varying degrees of penetration of the private scholarly publishing market across countries make it difficult to align common starting points for decision making and to design common technical solutions to be implemented. In Latin America, a long-standing tradition of non-profit academic publishing supported by cooperative infrastructures and a strong regional identity surrounding Diamond OA stands out. This is explained by a strong linguistic identity and significant involvement from the research community, independent of policy. However, this historical strength coexists with increasing financial pressures and the need to renew and professionalize infrastructures and teams.

1. ANALYSIS BY POLICY AND SYSTEMIC ENABLERS

National Policies and Legal Frameworks

The comparative analysis reveals significant heterogeneity on the existence, maturity, and scope of explicitly supporting Diamond OA publishing public policies. While some countries have developed relatively advanced normative frameworks that include national open access policies, open science strategies, or mandates for publishing publicly funded research results, in many other contexts the Diamond model remains implicit, fragmented, or entirely absent from political agendas. Even when Open Access policies exist, they are not always accompanied by specific funding instruments,

incentives, or governance mechanisms to sustain non-commercial publishing infrastructures and practices. The analysis shows that the development of Diamond OA is deeply conditioned by how Open Science, research, and higher education policies explicitly recognize or ignore this model.

In Africa, there is a significant lack of legal and political frameworks for Open Science in general, and for Diamond OA in particular. When such frameworks exist, they tend to be general and declarative, rarely distinguishing between commercial and non-commercial scholarly publishing business models. Thus, Diamond OA benefits indirectly from open access policies and knowledge sovereignty initiatives, even though it lacks specific regulatory recognition. This results in a weak enabling environment, where the model legitimacy depends more on institutional action than on clear national mandates.

In Europe, many countries have explicit Open Science policies and increasing references to the Diamond OA model in strategic documents, national plans, and high-level statements. However, this is not always translated into binding legal instruments. Diamond OA often appears as a desirable but non-prioritized option because it coexists with policies that still incentivise researchers to be editors and authors in commercial APC based publishing venues. A normative fragmentation between countries limits ecosystem coherence.

In Latin America, Diamond OA is more deeply institutionalized, though with varying degrees of formalization. In several countries, the Diamond model is implicit in strategies, laws, and institutional policies despite not being explicitly defined as such. This historical normalization has allowed its expansion but has also generated a certain normative invisibility, making it harder to defend against pressures to shift toward commercial solutions.

Funding and Sustainability Strategies

There is a widespread absence of structural and stable funding for Diamond publishing. With a few exceptions, most of the countries analysed rely on institutional grants, specific projects, volunteer work, and, in many cases, informal support from libraries or technical units. This situation creates a risk of systemic vulnerability that directly impacts editorial continuity, process quality, and the capacity for medium and long-term planning. The lack of specific budgetary allocations is one of the main bottlenecks for consolidating the model across the three world regions, albeit with notable variations.

In Africa, funding for Diamond OA publishing is scarce and depends on limited institutional budgets and international projects, showing a high structural vulnerability. The policies analysed recognize the need for financial support but rarely establish stable budgetary streams. Sustainability strategies rely on sharing resources like

infrastructures, open-source software platforms, and regional cooperation mechanisms.

In Europe, while there is greater financial capacity, resource allocation is highly uneven. The bulk of public money for publishing goes to transformative agreements and to APCs payments, while Diamond OA receives marginal funding. The analysis shows a massive joint need to rebalance public investment and to create structural funds for Diamond infrastructures and services, either national or consortium based.

In Latin America, public funding has been key to the strong development of this model, though it remains insufficient and precarious. Diamond platforms and journals are supported by university budgets, national agencies, and regional cooperation, but lack long-term financial guarantees.

Incentives and Recognition Mechanisms

The analysis reveals a structural misalignment between Diamond OA and academic incentive systems across the three world regions.

In Africa, incentives for publishing or editing in Diamond OA venues are scarce or non-existent. Research assessment frameworks prioritize international commercial databases indexed journals, discouraging the strengthening of local journals even when they perform strategic functions for national development.

In Europe, although discourse on responsible research assessment has advanced further, practical changes have been slow. Editorial work and publication in Diamond OA still receive limited recognition in academic careers and funding processes, thus diminishing the impact of policies supporting this model.

In Latin America, although publication in Diamond OA is strong, it needs further reinforcement in its legitimacy within merit-based research assessment systems, where the concept of quality is at risk of becoming a commercial good.

Infrastructures and Platforms Supporting Diamond OA

The report highlights the strategic role of shared digital infrastructures as one of the main assets of the Diamond OA ecosystem. National and regional platforms, journal portals, editorial management systems, and common services like persistent identifiers, digital preservation, and indexing act as true enablers of the model because they reduce costs, standardize processes, and improve visibility and editorial quality. However, the development, interoperability, and sustainability of these infrastructures are highly uneven.

In Africa, continental and national platforms constitute the pillars of the ecosystem, but they face significant technical and financial limitations. Interoperability and the

alignment with international technical and quality standards remain their main challenges.

In Europe, there is a more robust and diversified infrastructure, but it is highly fragmented and often dependent on national policies or specific projects. The linguistic diversity in Europe and the existence of national policies articulated through these supporting platforms and infrastructures in most countries, prevent the establishment of consolidated, shared services with stable funding.

In Latin America, grassroots cooperative regional infrastructures are a distinctive feature and a structural strength. This is due to a strong linguistic community in which the common use of Spanish and Portuguese promotes the development and deployment of common solutions for the research community, beyond national borders. However, these infrastructures need greater political and financial backing to ensure their sustainability.

Institutional Roles and Support Mechanisms

Research institutions, mainly public universities, research centres, academic libraries, and, to a lesser extent, national agencies, constitute the fundamental operational pillar of the Diamond OA model in all three regions. However, the degree of formalization, coordination, and institutional capacity to sustain Diamond OA publishing varies significantly.

In Africa, higher education institutions are the main, and often the only, support for Diamond OA. Editorial, technical, and management functions are carried out by academic units and university libraries, even though these responsibilities are not clearly institutionalized and are not accompanied by specific resources. This leads to fragmented support mechanisms that depend on the goodwill of specific academic teams. The absence of clear national and institutional policies reinforces this decentralized approach, creating inequalities between institutions and limiting the scalability of the model.

In Europe, institutional roles are more defined, especially in universities with their own publishing services. However, support for Diamond OA often coexists with significant financial commitments to commercial models, thus diluting its strategic centrality. Many institutions support the model as part of their public mission but do not fully integrate it into their research, internationalization, or research assessment strategies.

In Latin America, public universities play a structural role in Diamond OA publishing and act simultaneously as publishers, funders, and guarantors of transnational infrastructures. This grassroots model has allowed extensive coverage but has also

created strong dependence on limited institutional budgets, making them vulnerable to political and budgetary changes.

Workforce and Capacity Development

The human resources dimension emerges as one of the most critical and transversal factors for the sustainability of Diamond OA. In all three world regions, the model heavily relies on unpaid or insufficiently recognized academic work. Staff performing editorial and review tasks, as well as technical teams, take on significant workloads without formal recognition, clear incentives, or integration of these functions into formal academic career paths. This situation negatively affects the stability of editorial teams, the quality of review and editing processes, and the ability to adapt to international standards. Moreover, the absence of incentive systems for both editing and publishing in Diamond OA venues reinforces researchers' preference for commercial routes, associated with greater prestige in scientific assessment frameworks.

In Africa, there is a significant shortage of specialized personnel. Editorial, technical, and management functions fall to faculty members who lack specific training and allocated time for editorial work, and who often lack the necessary digital and editorial skills, significantly hindering adherence to international standards and the use of advanced technical infrastructures.

In Europe, while there is a greater availability of qualified personnel, professionalization is concentrated in specific institutions or initiatives. Many of these depend on temporary funding, which hinders the consolidation of stable teams. Additionally, editorial work continues to have limited recognition in academic careers, which discourages long-term involvement.

In Latin America, academic commitment has historically been a key asset, but also a source of precariousness. Work overload, lack of formal recognition, and the absence of specific career paths for scientific editing threaten the continuity of the model.

Collaboration between Publishers and Service Providers

Collaboration appears as a structural condition of Diamond OA, especially in contexts with limited resources.

In Africa, cooperation between publishers, libraries, national platforms, and regional networks is a structural necessity and is essential for the Diamond OA model. The analysis highlights the role of shared infrastructures in reducing costs, improving quality, and ensuring visibility. However, these collaborations are usually informal and depend on external projects, limiting their stability.

In Europe, advanced networks and consortia exist, but with uneven coordination. Collaboration between publishers, libraries, and technical providers is more common but often fragmented by country, discipline, or institution. The analysis shows a need to consolidate cooperative models at the national and European level, with a clear governance model and stable funding streams. The European Diamond Capacity Hub was recently established to undertake that work.

In Latin America, cooperation is a grass-rooted historical and constitutive practice of the Diamond ecosystem. Regional networks, shared platforms, and common standards have enabled the regional ecosystem to be highly interoperable. However, many of these collaborations lack formal institutional recognition and sufficient financial support, which jeopardizes their sustainability.

Quality Assurance and National Infrastructures

Another significant finding of this study is the persistent tension between research assessment frameworks and Diamond OA principles. In many countries, research assessment criteria still incentivise publication in commercial venues with higher indexing rates in international commercial databases, failing to adequately recognize the scientific, social, and strategic value of Diamond OA journals, particularly those with national or regional scope. This misalignment between open science policies, editorial practices, and assessment systems constitutes a key obstacle to strengthening the model.

In Africa, quality mechanisms are in highly unequal stages of development and not formalised. National and regional platforms play a central role in ensuring technical standards, but limitations persist in the uptake of persistent identifiers, use Creative Commons licences and other international standards.

In Europe, there are more formal quality assurance frameworks, but they are not always aligned with the specificities of Diamond OA. In most cases, applied criteria replicate the logic and values of commercial publishing, generating disincentives for Diamond OA publishing.

In Latin America, quality assurance systems are relatively consolidated and have contributed to the model's legitimacy. However, they face external pressures to adopt international metrics and standards that do not always reflect the region's linguistic and disciplinary diversity.

2. REGIONAL ANALYSIS

Africa: Early Institutionalization and the Need for Structural Funding

In Africa, Diamond OA is developing in a context shaped by profound structural inequalities, but also by growing dynamism and a strong orientation toward regional cooperation. Unlike Europe and Latin America, where the open access debate is embedded in relatively consolidated scientific systems, in many African countries the emergence of the Diamond OA model converges with broader processes of building and strengthening publicly funded science, technology, and innovation systems, developing scientific capacities, and reinforcing institutions.

The report shows that, in Africa, the development of Diamond OA relies significantly on shared infrastructures at national and continental levels, such as journal platforms. These infrastructures play a critical role in compensating for the lack of individual institutional resources and in providing basic publishing, indexing, and visibility services. However, their sustainability is constrained by the scarcity of structural funding, dependence on external donors, and the shortage of specialized technical staff.

A distinctive feature of the African context is the centrality of volunteer work and enthusiasm of editorial teams. Although this situation is not unique to the region, its impact is particularly pronounced due to the limited availability of human and financial resources. This is compounded by the low integration of Diamond OA publishing into academic evaluation systems, which reduces incentives to publish in and edit local journals. Nevertheless, the report also highlights growing political and community commitment to Open Access, as well as the emergence of national and regional initiatives that could lay the foundations for more robust development of the model.

In summary, Africa presents a clear and coherent action agenda, but one that remains in a phase of institutional construction. The main challenge is not the legitimacy of Diamond OA, but rather the capacity of countries and institutions to sustain it in a structural and autonomous manner.

Europe: Strategic Alignment, but Operational Fragmentation

In Europe, the situation is markedly different. In recent years, Diamond OA has become an explicit object of public policy, driven by the European Union's narrative, Open Science strategies, and specific action plans. Diamond OA is understood as an essential pillar of an equitable, transparent, and non-commercial publishing system and is explicitly linked to debates on digital sovereignty, responsible research evaluation, and bibliodiversity. Unlike Latin America, where the model has emerged from long-standing grassroots institutional practices, in Europe Diamond OA has been primarily top down built, through regulatory frameworks, policy recommendations, and supranationally

funded projects. This has generated a strong narrative consensus around the need for a more equitable and transparent academic publishing system but has not yet fully translated into stable national structures for funding and governance.

The European region is characterized by a high internal heterogeneity. Some countries have well-developed national infrastructures, consolidated platforms, and relatively solid institutional support mechanisms, while others display fragmented ecosystems that are highly dependent on temporary projects. A distinctive feature of Europe is the need to partially redirect spending on APCs toward collective funding models, national consortia, and dedicated competitive funds for Diamond publications, alongside the strong tension between political support for Diamond OA and the persistence of academic assessment frameworks and incentive systems deeply rooted in commercial logics and metrics that privilege commercial publishing. This misalignment creates a structural paradox: the Diamond OA model is promoted as desirable at the policy level but is de facto penalized in the professional trajectories of editors and researchers.

Furthermore, the European ecosystem shows a high dependence on project-based funding, both at national and European levels. While such projects have enabled significant progress in standards, interoperability, and cooperation, their temporary nature raises questions about the long-term sustainability of the infrastructures and services developed. In this sense, Europe is in a transitional phase: it benefits from a favourable policy framework and advanced technical capacities but still needs to resolve how to institutionalize and structurally fund Diamond publishing.

Overall, Europe is in a phase of strategic consolidation, in which Diamond OA enjoys political and technical legitimacy but requires firmer budgetary decisions and greater integration into national funding and evaluation policies in order to realize its full transformative potential.

Latin America: Historical Consolidation and Sustainability Tensions

In Latin America, Diamond OA is not an emerging model, but rather the predominant and structural form of academic publishing in the region. Historically, it was a grassroots movement that is now fully culturally legitimized. Unlike other regions, non-profit academic publishing did not arise as a recent response to the crisis of commercial models, but as a long-established practice, closely linked to public universities, national science and technology systems, and a conception of science as a public good. A distinctive feature of Latin American approaches is the centrality of shared regional infrastructures. Cooperative platforms and systems are conceived as regional public goods. This has contributed to building a shared regional identity around bibliodiversity, multilingualism, and open knowledge circulation.

However, this structural strength coexists with significant tensions. Protecting the model from the commodification of scholarly communication remains a challenge. In many Latin American countries, the Diamond model is sustained by limited public budgets that are highly vulnerable to political and economic changes. Funding is often implicit, fragmented, and dependent on the stability of public higher education institutions. Moreover, although the model enjoys symbolic legitimacy, significant challenges persist in terms of editorial professionalization, technological renewal, and alignment with research assessment frameworks that, in some contexts, continue to privilege indicators and international commercial databases that favour commercial publishing venues. Thus, Latin America displays a Diamond OA ecosystem that is robust in principles and practices, but structurally fragile in the face of external pressures and insufficient sustained investment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Overall, this report confirms that Diamond OA is neither a marginal nor a transitional model, but a critical infrastructure for the future of scholarly communication. Its consolidation requires political will, sustained investment, and strong alignment between policies, incentives, and practices. The challenge is not technical or conceptual, but fundamentally structural and political. Addressing it will strengthen science as a global public good and ensure that knowledge produced with public funds serves society.

Based on this diagnosis, the report underscores the need to move toward coordinated, long-term strategies. This first requires the development of explicit public policies that recognize the value of the Diamond OA model and integrate it coherently into open science, innovation, and education strategies. These policies must be accompanied by clear regulatory frameworks, inclusive governance mechanisms, and measurable objectives.

Second, it is essential to establish dedicated, stable, and predictable funding mechanisms, targeting both infrastructures and editorial work. The partial reallocation of resources currently devoted to commercial venues, including APC based open access, emerges as a strategic pathway to strengthening sustainable Diamond OA ecosystems. Cooperative, consortium, and multi-level funding appears particularly promising in resource-constrained contexts.

Third, the report highlights the urgency of professionalizing non-profit academic publishing through investment in training, and the formal recognition of editorial and peer review functions. Integrating these tasks into academic career paths and institutional assessment framework is a necessary condition to ensure quality and continuity for the model.

The strengthening of shared, interoperable infrastructures aligned with international standards is also identified as a central strategic axis. Regional and interregional cooperation, the development of common services, and the adoption of persistent identifiers and quality editorial practices are key elements for increasing the visibility, trust, and impact of Diamond OA publishing.

Finally, the report emphasizes the importance of fostering international partnerships and spaces for political dialogue between regions. The diversity of contexts analysed demonstrates that there is no single model of success, but rather a shared set of principles and adaptable solutions. Initiatives such as interregional forums, common standards, and cooperative platforms are essential tools for advancing toward a truly equitable, sustainable, and academically governed global ecosystem of scholarly publishing.

FINAL CONCLUSIONS

The comparative analysis of the 45 national studies clearly shows that the Diamond OA model has developed more solidly and persistently in countries where non-English national languages have a strong tradition in scholarly communication and limited representation in the international commercial scholarly publishing mainstream. In these contexts, Diamond OA has emerged not as a marginal alternative, but as a structural response to the historical exclusion of non-English languages from dominant scholarly publishing systems, heavily controlled by large commercial publishers. The limited presence of national journals in international commercial databases, combined with economic, linguistic, and cultural barriers, has encouraged universities, scholarly societies, and public bodies to develop their own non-profit publishing infrastructures, aimed at ensuring the circulation of knowledge in local languages and addressing research agendas relevant to national and regional contexts. In these countries, scholarly publishing fulfils a social and academic function closely linked to public policies, university systems, and institutional missions. It has fostered the legitimacy of the Diamond OA model as a public good rather than a market service. Moreover, the absence of a strong national commercial publishing industry has reduced competition from APC-based models, allowing no-fee open access to consolidate as a cultural norm and dominant practice, particularly in the Social Sciences and Humanities, as well as in applied disciplines with strong territorial roots. This phenomenon is consistently observed across large parts of Latin America, many African countries, and several non-Anglophone European contexts, where Diamond OA has been key to sustaining bibliodiversity, multilingualism, and academic autonomy. By contrast, in countries with consolidated commercial publishing markets and high integration into international publication flows, the Diamond OA model has faced greater difficulties in expanding, often remaining confined to specific niches or dependent on compensatory policies. In sum, the strength of Diamond OA in non-English-speaking countries is not accidental, but the result of a structural convergence between language, academic sovereignty, and the absence of viable commercial alternatives, which has made this model the primary means of ensuring the production, legitimation, and dissemination of scientific knowledge outside the hegemonic circuits of the global scholarly publishing market.

Despite the diversity of histories, capacities, and priorities, the three regions analysed share common challenges with respect to Diamond OA. Africa needs to build institutional and budgetary capacity; Europe must translate its normative leadership into coherent financial commitments; and Latin America must consolidate and protect an existing model against external pressures. Across all national contexts analysed, the evidence shows that the Diamond OA model will not be able to guarantee equity,

sustainability, and bibliodiversity without explicit public policies and stable funding streams.

Responses to these challenges must build on the specific trajectories of each world region, be adapted to their contexts, and avoid one-size-fits-all approaches. Recognizing and respecting this diversity is a necessary condition for global strengthening. Only through context-sensitive policies, differentiated funding mechanisms, and sustained interregional cooperation will it be possible to consolidate a scholarly publishing ecosystem truly equitable, sustainable, and aligned with science as a global public good.

ALMASI will continue these discussions in the new Diamond OA Policy Forum of international, national, and local policymakers and funders in Africa, Europe and Latin America with the aim to share, discuss and develop policy recommendations and funding mechanisms that work in various contexts to support more equitable, diverse, and community-led scholarly publishing internationally.

TECHNICAL ANNEX. Guiding Questions for Focus Groups and Interviews

Feedback on the Country case studies:

- ✓ Do you think that the information in the case study covers your country well?
- ✓ Are there any aspects that haven't been covered properly?
- ✓ What extra information would help give a fuller picture?

Landscape of nonprofit scholarly publishing and Diamond OA:

(1) What policy or funding actions already help to support and grow the Diamond model in your country/institution?

- ✓ Are there any existing initiatives that go in this direction?

(2) Let's look more closely at the difficulties and obstacles:

- ✓ What are the main challenges for adopting or sustaining the Diamond OA model?
- ✓ What solutions / resources could help address them? (Structural, economic, cultural, or technical)

(3) Does the institution support Diamond OA journals?

- ✓ Which institutional units are involved in Diamond OA publishing and who coordinates them?

(4) What practical steps would help make the Diamond OA model more sustainable?

- ✓ Who should lead or coordinate these actions?
- ✓ What role could the academic community play?

(5) When thinking about strategic, policy, and funding actions:

- ✓ What kinds of policy or strategic actions are needed to help strengthen the Diamond model?
- ✓ If there is a policy or strategy for Diamond, does it come with dedicated funding?

(6) Looking at financial support:

- ✓ Do you think it's possible to reallocate funds from APC-based publications to Diamond initiatives in the short and/or in the long term, and if so, how?
- ✓ What additional/alternative ways of funding could be used to support Diamond?

(7) What is the role of the stakeholders (institutions, agencies, libraries...) for pooling or cooperating on a national or international scale?

(8) How could shared infrastructures advance Diamond OA publishing in your country and/or globally?

(9) What incentives could help publishers, researchers, and universities increase the adoption of the diamond model?

- ✓ How could these incentives be implemented in the institutions and in the country?